

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH
AND MODELLING

D3.8 Final case study reports and comparative report

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Executive Summary

The COVINFORM project aims to conduct a comparative analysis across case studies to evaluate COVID-19 impacts on vulnerable communities in Europe. This final report summarizes findings from the conceptualization within a syndemic and socio-ecological systems framework to characterize and assess resilience in those communities and systems, and in-depth analysis of field data based in 9 countries case studies.

Thus, this deliverable presents an exhaustive analysis of the experiences of various vulnerable groups during the COVID-19 pandemic across European contexts. Utilizing complex systems and intersectionality approaches, it synthesizes findings across multiple domains—such as governance responses, public health measures, and community engagement—and their impact on targeted populations like healthcare workers, migrants, and minorities.

Key Findings:

- **Mental Health:** Almost universally, mental health was adversely affected. Healthcare workers faced stress and burnout, while migrants and minorities suffered from social isolation and discrimination.
- **Economic Precarity:** Many groups, especially those in gig economy jobs, faced economic hardships, including income loss and housing issues.
- **Digital Divide:** Inequalities in access to digital information and resources were highlighted, affecting especially migrants and minority groups.
- **Communication and Trust:** The study found varying levels of trust in governmental institutions and communication effectiveness across different countries and communities.
- **Timeline of Impact:** Initial lockdowns caused maximum disruption, but later phases also revealed persistent issues like ongoing mental health challenges and economic instability.

Methodological Insights:

The COREQ analysis shows that most studies relied on small qualitative samples, and thematic coding was used to analyse the data. Despite inconsistencies in reporting, the methodology was generally rigorous.

Recommendations:

- Targeted mental health services for frontline workers and minorities.
- Interventions to bridge the digital divide.
- Social protection schemes covering gig economy and informal workers.
- Culturally appropriate public health messaging.
- Improved housing policies.

Conclusions:

The results emphasize the importance of understanding the interconnectedness of various vulnerabilities to better prepare for future crises. It argues for targeted interventions across multiple dimensions—mental health, economics, digital access, and housing—to ensure a more effective and equitable response to future pandemics. All the case studies showed forms of resilience and that

inequalities preceded the pandemic. Thus, besides the specific adaptation of a pandemic framework (for example, developing tailor made risk communications), what is more important is implementing measures during 'normal' times.

This is the only way that a pandemic does not become a syndemic.

In conclusion, the COVINFORM case studies provide invaluable, context-specific insights into pandemic impacts on diverse vulnerable populations. By revealing complex systems dynamics and intersecting vulnerabilities, they strengthen preparedness for future shocks and crises. The findings reinforce the scientific value of systems and intersectionality approaches while also informing more ethical, effective policy responses.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
SES	Socio-Ecological System
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
DGS	General Health Directorate
ENSP	National School of Public Health
LTCF	Long-term care facility
MSSS	Ministry of Solidarity and Social Security
SNS	National Health Service
SS / ISS, I.P.	Social Security
HCW	Health Care Workers
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estadística (National Statistics Bureau)
NHS	National Health Service
PHW	Public Health Wales
FSW	Fonds Soziales Wien
HAH	Hannah-Arendt-House
PEH	People experiencing homelessness
CSO	Civil Society Organization
IFEMA	Exhibition site – during the pandemic it was turned into a mobile hospital
PEMAM	City Council's Municipal Emergency Territorial Plan

1. Introduction and Case Studies Methodology

The COVINFORM project aims to conduct a comparative analysis across case studies to evaluate COVID-19 impacts on vulnerable communities in Europe. This final report summarizes findings from two phases of research. Phase 1 involved conceptualization within a syndemic and socio-ecological systems framework to characterize and assess resilience of relevant systems. Phase 2 entailed primary data collection through interviews and field work for in-depth analysis.

The overarching research questions guiding the project were: 1) How did COVID-19 impacts accumulate and interact to affect vulnerable groups? 2) What factors mitigated or enhanced impacts? 3) What commonalities and differences emerge across cases?

Conceptualization: Syndemic Approach & Socio-Ecological Systems Framework

The conceptual frameworks grounding this research were complex systems theory (Hynes, Lees & Muller, 2020), a syndemic approach (Singer, 2009), intersectionality theory (Cho, Crenshaw & McCall, 2013; Giritli-Nygren & Olofsson, 2014), and the socio-ecological systems (SES) framework (McGinnis & Ostrom, 2014).

The socio-ecological systems framework (McGinnis & Ostrom, 2014; Ostrom, 2007) (see Figure 1) guided examination of COVID-19 impacts on community systems. This approach recognizes complex linkages and feedback loops between entities like governments, organizations, and social groups. Disruptions like COVID-19 permeate through these systems unevenly. Vulnerable populations often experience cascading economic, social, environmental, institutional, and health harms as pandemic impacts ripple through fragile systems.

Figure 1. The SES framework (McGinnis & Ostrom, 2014).

The utilization of the SES framework applied to COVID-19 research was carried out, simultaneously and independently, by both the COVINFORM project and the team of Ling and colleagues (2020, 2021). Ling et al. (2021) provide a clear instance of employing the SES framework across various countries (Figure 2); their objective was to comprehend how COVID-19 cases manifested in different countries due to variations in relevant factors. Their analyses aimed not only to grasp this evolving situation but

also to understand how the adaptability of systems is affected by alterations in national or local factors. This involves investigating how different outcomes beyond COVID-19, such as varying levels of underemployment, heightened risk perception, and more, stem from the strategies of stakeholders, resource availability, governance, and interactions in response to the crisis.

Figure 2. The SES framework in the Covid-19 context (Ling et al., 2021).

While Ling et al. (2021) applied the SES framework at a higher level of abstraction (i.e., at the level of Asia-Pacific countries), we aim to apply it to smaller and more specific systems, at a lower level of abstraction, which would allow us to conduct a more detailed analysis.

Furthermore, just like other health issues previously examined in the literature (e.g., HIV), COVID-19 can be considered a syndemic (Courtin & Vineis, 2021; McGowan & Bambra, 2022). Syndemic theory (Singer, 2009) suggests that multiple health and social problems interact in ways that are multiplicative, leading to worse outcomes than those that would occur if each problem was considered in isolation. While the contamination spread during a pandemic can easily spread in a more indiscriminate way, in a syndemic, the pandemic and overall situation are influenced by multiple other factors, both in the disease propagation and in its consequences. In this sense, similarly to what happened during the HIV pandemic, the COVID-19 pandemic also has differentiated and heightened effects along several lines of social and economic vulnerability, which classifies it as a syndemic. In other words, the unequal nature of the pandemic has resulted from a syndemic of COVID-19 and endemic inequalities in chronic disease burden, exacerbating existent health inequalities and resulting in higher mortality rates among those more socially disadvantaged (McGowan & Bambra, 2022). In light of this, our aim is not only to test the Syndemic Theory in a more contextualized way, but also to be more precise in designing the COVID-19 syndemic context predicted by the theory, by studying how

specific minority populations have experienced disproportionate disruption from the COVID-19 pandemic.

This way, the integration of the SES framework with the Syndemic Theory – the strategy adopted by this project for the case studies – allows for a more detailed analysis of the syndemic context through a more precise depiction of the systems and its relevant variables.

The present report

This report summarizes Phase 1 system characterization and Phase 2 analysis for each case study.

In Phase 1, relevant populations and their systems were delineated and described by partners for each case study, identifying key variables and indicators (see D3.4: *Phase 1 case study reports and comparative report*). The goal was to understand vulnerability and protective factors shaping COVID-19 impacts. Resilience was conceptualized as the balance between cumulative and synergic vulnerability and protective factors. The SES frameworks guided system characterization and resilience assessment in this phase to analyse interaction effects and understand syndemic factors.

Phase 2 – the main focus of the present report – involved primary data collection to explore experiences of target groups. The frameworks guided analysis of how vulnerabilities accumulated and interacted synergistically to produce COVID-19 impacts over the pandemic timeline. Comparative analysis identified commonalities and differences across cases. Cross-case analysis synthesizes key factors influencing COVID-19 impacts on vulnerable communities across contexts. Findings aim to inform policies and interventions to mitigate syndemic impacts of future crises.

Mixed methods were utilized, including quantitative data analysis, document analysis, and qualitative interviews. The COREQ guidelines were followed to ensure rigorous qualitative methods. The use of COREQ (Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research) (Tong, Sainsbury & Craig, 2007) guidelines ensured rigor and transparency in their study design, data collection, and analysis. Research performers began by developing a research question and inclusion and exclusion criteria to identify the specific minority populations that would be included in the study. They then used a criterion-based purposeful sampling strategy to select a diverse sample of participants that represented different minority populations.

The teams then used multiple methods of data collection, including interviews, observations, and document analysis, to gather data from different sources. They also used a standardized data collection protocol to ensure consistency in the data collected across different interviewers. They then transcribed and translated the data, and used thematic analysis to identify the themes, patterns, and relationships that emerged from the data.

The findings of the studies revealed that minority populations experienced disproportionate disruption from the COVID-19 pandemic, including poor access to healthcare, job loss, and increased stress and anxiety. These findings supported the theory of syndemics, as the results demonstrated how multiple health and social problems interacted in ways that were additive or multiplicative, leading to worse outcomes than would occur if each problem were considered in isolation.

2. COVINFORM Case Studies: Phase 2

Section 2 presents the case study country reports conducted in Phase 2 of the COVINFORM project. These case studies utilize complex systems approach and intersectionality framework to examine the impacts of COVID-19 on vulnerable populations in select European countries. Each case study focuses on specific groups made vulnerable by the pandemic, including healthcare workers, migrants, ethnic minorities, and economically disadvantaged communities.

The case studies were conducted in Austria, Belgium, England, Germany/Sweden, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, and Wales. Both qualitative and quantitative methods were utilized, with most case studies employing interviews as the primary data source. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with relevant stakeholders, including representatives from vulnerable groups, government officials, healthcare workers, and community leaders. The sample sizes ranged from 7 to 31 interviews across the case studies. Detailed information about the interview methodology and samples for each case study is provided in completed COREQ checklists. Some case studies supplemented interviews with surveys or analysis of secondary data sources.

The case studies highlight the multifaceted impacts of COVID-19 on physical, mental, social, and economic wellbeing. Key themes include heightened stress, anxiety, and burnout among healthcare workers; struggles with social isolation, loneliness, and deteriorating mental health among minority groups; digital divides exacerbating inequalities; loss of income and precarity due to pandemic restrictions; inadequate housing conditions increasing contagion risks; and complex dynamics of trust and mistrust towards government messaging.

The Austrian case study focused on women in socially assisted housing who were formerly homeless, examining their lived experiences during the pandemic. Interviews with residents and staff revealed increased alcohol consumption and psychological crises, underscoring the mental health toll. However, the housing facilities mitigated negative health and financial consequences.

- The **Belgian case study** explored the mental health impacts on migrants in Antwerp, uncovering social isolation, health concerns, and economic factors as key drivers. Interviews found local organizations played a vital role in providing mental health support and culturally competent care.
- The **English case study** adopted a systems theory approach to investigate communication practices within minority "hard-to-reach" communities. Situating government communication practices within the daily experiences of minority communities, this case study aimed to identify the ways isolated social groups have engaged with the pandemic news. This way, the case study provides an in-depth understanding of COVID-19 communication, its constitutive processes, and the actors involved. Interviews highlighted reliance on community networks and in-group communication to share pandemic information.
- The **German/Swedish case study** examined information-seeking behaviours related to protective measures among ethnic minorities in Mannheim and Gothenburg. Interviews found high trust in government authorities, with some exposure to misinformation.
- The **Greek case study** focused on law enforcement interactions with minority groups during COVID-19, as well as the implications of implemented measures, mechanisms and impact they

subsequently had on social interaction, trust and perception. Therefore, it identifies several areas for improving communication, trust-building, and inclusive pandemic response.

- The **Italian case study** surveyed healthcare workers to assess pandemic impacts on wellbeing, revealing increased stress, burnout, and family distress. It emphasized the need for targeted mental health support.
- The **Spanish case study** explored experiences of Latin American and Moroccan migrants in Madrid, documenting economic precarity, housing vulnerabilities, deteriorating mental health, and imperfect government communication.
- The **Portuguese case study** focuses on resilience of 2 types of long-term elderly care facilities, their residents, and their workers. It revealed that information put out by the government, health authorities and media were not adapted to the elderly, which contributed to more fear and confusion. Additionally, the excessive dissemination of the number of cases and deaths created more anxiety, panic and fear, not only for the elderly, but also the staff. This hindered response and care for high-risk individuals.
- Finally, the **Welsh case study** adopted an intersectional lens to examine vulnerabilities of migrant nurses from Africa working in Welsh hospitals. It revealed structural disadvantages, territorialized virus controls, and racial biases negatively impacting this group.

In conclusion, the Phase 2 case studies provide in-depth insights into the diverse experiences of marginalized groups during COVID-19 in selected European contexts. They highlight opportunities for more inclusive, ethical pandemic governance and targeted support for vulnerable populations in future health crises. The methodological approaches demonstrate the value of complex systems and intersectionality perspectives for understanding syndemic impacts.

2.1 Austria, SYNYO

Supporting vulnerable groups during COVID-19: the role of a socially assisted housing institution for homeless women in mitigating the risks of COVID-19

2.1.1 Introduction

This case study investigates the lived experiences of women, who live in socially assisted apartments designed for people who were affected by homelessness, during the COVID-19 pandemic. More specifically, the women of this study were formally homeless. They now permanently live in socially assisted apartments located within the infrastructure of the so-called Hannah Arendt House. This institution is run by one of the big players of the Austrian social economy that is particularly active within the provision of health care and social services. The Fonds Soziales Wien (FSW), an enterprise that delivers social services for the City of Vienna and that is also financed by the City of Vienna, subsidizes these apartments. The inhabitants only pay a small amount of rent. Beside the apartment the inhabitants also receive assistance in various areas of everyday life, in particular health care and financial issues as well as other bureaucratic matters.

Homelessness goes hand in hand with poverty, social exclusion as well as often multiple health vulnerabilities including substance abuse disorder (Amnesty International, 2022). For women, poverty and homelessness also often goes hand in hand with experiences of domestic violence and/or divorce (Amnesty International, 2022). Thus, homelessness is often preceded by loss of family structure and

financial assets. In this study we aim to understand how women who were affected by homelessness experience the COVID-19 pandemic while living in permanent and assisted housing.

The house opened in March 2010 and it provides overall 122 socially assisted small apartments. The house is financed by FSW. There are two levels reserved only for women that provide 34 small apartments. All inhabitants are in some form affected by homelessness. However, people living in the house come from various backgrounds and walks of life. Some are of refugee backgrounds, some struggle with severe and untreated mental illness and/or addiction, some are victims of domestic abuse and so on.

Our research team first got in touch with the management of the housing while conducting interviews with women of low socioeconomic status for the COVINFORM project. We quickly developed a good relationship with the organisation. They helped us with the recruitment of the women which made the process of interviewing smoother for us. The management of the HAH seemed to care about the inhabitants which made working with them a positive experience. Through the interviews we conducted for the Resident Interviews, we anticipated interesting insights, particularly around trust and compliance. We asked the management of HAH to build on the findings we already got through the Resident Interviews. They immediately agreed.

In this study we use an intersectional lens to investigate vulnerability. Intersectional approaches acknowledge and emphasise that multiple social structures and processes intersect and produce identities as well as social locations (Anthias 2012, p. 106). Further, they highlight the particular experiences that arise through the intersection of multiple categories of difference. These categories of differences often create vulnerabilities. These can be social vulnerabilities but also financial and health vulnerabilities as social vulnerabilities often led to the latter.

Kimberle Crenshaw's (1991) article *Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics and Violence Against Women of Colour* is one of the most seminal texts for the formation of intersectional theory. In her article, Crenshaw raises issues on the interaction of race and gender in the case of violence against Women of Colour (1991, p. 1296) and argues that categories of difference such as race and gender, but also others, are mutually constitutive and cannot be thought of as additive (also see Yuval-Davis 2006). By this Crenshaw means that the experience of people who are affected by multiple forms of oppression is not adequately understood if it is simply framed as the experience of racism and sexism. Gender and race intersect with each other and create a specific form of racism, a gendered racism that cannot be understood by framing them as two separate phenomena a person is simultaneously experiencing (see Adler 2022). In this case study we would like to understand the particular experiences of women and financial precarity/class which led to homelessness. We aim to understand what are the consequences of these intersecting categories of differences to formulate insights that could be of help during future (health) crises.

Vulnerability can be defined as "the conditions determined by physical, social, economic, and environmental factors or processes, which increase the susceptibility of [an individual or] a community to the impact of hazards" (UN/ISDR, Geneva 2004; cited in United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction 2005). In its current use in public discourse, however, vulnerability remains a blurry concept that is often not clearly specified (Daniel 2010). We understand vulnerability as relational, following Habermas (2003), who argues that it is our intersubjectivity that makes us first, human and second, vulnerable. This also means that vulnerability can be mitigated through organisations such as the Hannah Arendt House (see Habermas 2003).

Figure 3. SYNO, Austria – SES framework.

Context: Homelessness in Vienna and State of the Art

Homelessness can briefly be understood “as a state or condition of lacking a stable, secure and adequate housing” (Amnesty International, 2022). In Austria there are almost 19.500 people who can be considered homeless (*Österreich - Wohnungslose 2021*, n.d.), whereas a large majority (58,2 %) resides in Austria’s capital, Vienna, and most of them are male (69 %) (Statistik Austria, 2022). No data could be found on the migration background of those homeless, however, in order to rightfully register as homeless to receive government subsidies and access to aid, people must have previously been registered in Austria (Amnesty International, 2022). Therefore, the number of people being affected by homelessness could be far higher than estimated by official statistics. The official statistics do not account for the so-called “hidden homeless”, those sleeping rough or women in women’s shelters (Amnesty International, 2022; Eberhardt et al., 2023). Hidden homelessness, according to the Canadian Observatory on Homelessness (COH), “describes people who stay with friends, family, or even strangers. They are typically not paying rent, their duration of stay is unsustainable in the long term, and they do not have the means to secure their own permanent housing in the future.” (Gaetz et al., 2012)

The reasons for homelessness are multifaceted and can range from unemployment and insufficient financial resources (40 %), to divorce (29 %), issues with mental disorders (23 %) or bodily illnesses (25 %) (Fonds Soziales Wien, 2020). In regard to **homeless women**, it has been found that there exists a strong correlation between gender-based violence and their homelessness, either from their own families or partners. Other factors that lead to homelessness are substance abuse, mental disorders, a negative life-changing experience or having worked as an unregistered care worker and not being of Austrian origin (Eberhardt et al., 2023). Furthermore, women face greater difficulties as Austria does not provide enough emergency beds, temporary housing facilities or other forms of aid specifically directed towards them, as their needs often differ from those of men (Amnesty International, 2022; Eberhardt et al., 2023). Plus, women, it is assumed, experience hidden homelessness more often, as they succeed to find shelter at friends, family or partners for a certain period of time and thus are underrepresented in official statistics (Amnesty International, 2022). Hence, they represent a particularly vulnerable group.

Literature on how permanent housing facilities mitigated the vulnerabilities of formerly PEH in the Austrian case was scarce, as most studies were conducted in other European countries (Germany, France), the USA or Canada. Plus, rather than focussing on permanent housing facilities generally, they analysed what effect the transitioning of temporary housing facilities into permanent ones during the pandemic had had on PEH (Carnemolla & Skinner, 2021). Although it has already been well-established that permanent housing facilities have a positive effect on the well-being as well as physical and mental health of the inhabitants (Carnemolla & Skinner, 2021; Onapa et al., 2021), a recent systematic review found that this also especially held true during the Covid-19 pandemic (Baral et al., 2021).

In regard to these positive effects a major facilitator for PEH to overcome barriers has been found to be trust (Lupprich & Meyer, 2020; Schiffler et al., 2022; Reid, n.d.). Social workers stated that formerly PEH benefited greatly from receiving permanent shelter as they were more open towards and engaged more in advisory services (Lupprich & Meyer, 2020). This **good, trustful, relationship** between the women and the staff could also be found in our interviews. Generally, PEH drew support from the **shelters** as they **provided stability, health aid and a better protection from the virus** (Crouzet et al., 2022; Padgett et al., 2022) but stronger feelings of **isolation, mental strains and a lower general well-**

being were also found (Bammer-Tasch, 2022; Liedauer & Buchner, 2021). **Homeless youth** especially had difficulties dealing with contact restrictions and the closing of community activities as these led to the loss of friendships or social contacts in general, plus dealt with negative feelings ranging from boredom to loneliness (Roy et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, despite benefiting from the accommodation PEH had to cope with the negative effects elicited through the pandemic, and viewed it as a potential health risk, thus causing them to abide by the **protective measures of handwashing and/or social distancing** similar to the normal population (Allaria et al., 2021; Henwood et al., 2020). This also shows in regard to the **vaccination acceptability**, which proved to be positive (Knight et al., 2022). Furthermore, PEH abided measures in order **to return to ordinary life** and because they felt a **civic obligation** (Knight et al., 2022). PEH also reported a higher stress level due to information overload (Crouzet et al., 2022). However, it also showed that Covid-19 posed only one risk from the many PEH are confronted with (Allaria et al., 2021). Similarly, they also **feared infection, isolation**, having limited access to physical and mental health services and some resorted to **negative coping strategies such as drug consumption** (Nyamathi et al., 2022).

Negative aspects that were mentioned in the studies were mainly directed towards other PEH. For example, inhabitants of a permanent shelter criticised **other inhabitants for their drug and alcohol use/consumption** (Lupprich & Meyer, 2020).

As **women** rather experience hidden homelessness, they are often overlooked (Amnesty International, 2022; Eberhardt et al., 2021) – also in scientific literature. However, they represent an especially vulnerable group who often have experienced domestic violence (DV), severe mental disorders – like substance abuse disorders – that Covid-19 has amplified (Reid, n.d.). In 2020 the Austrian helpline for women witnessed 71 % more calls in just March to June compared to the previous year (neunerhaus, n.d.a). One former victim of DV describes the immense happiness she felt when receiving the confirmation for her own apartment: "I thought it was raining gold from the sky!" (neunerhaus, n.d.a), while another describes it as an immense freedom: "Only there could I enjoy my freedom. I cannot describe this happiness of being free." (neunerhaus, n.d.b) Permanent housing therefore greatly stabilizes the lives of former DV.

2.1.2 Purpose and Research Questions

As mentioned before, we would like to understand the particular experiences of women and financial precarity/class which led to homelessness, as well as what are the consequences of these intersecting categories of differences to formulate insights that could be of help during future (health) crises. We are interested in understanding if and how the Hannah Arendt House was able to mitigate negative effects of the pandemic for this vulnerable group. Further, we ask how the women experienced living through COVID-19 under their given conditions and what role trust towards staff members of the Hannah Arendt House played in managing the pandemic.

SYNYO wanted to study contexts in which women are particularly exposed in a syndemic situation. More specifically, to investigate this issue of women's susceptibility to COVID-19, several attempts were made. Due to external circumstances beyond our control, SYNYO was forced to change their case study design three times. Due to lack of time and a lack of options to choose alternative supermarket chains (i.e., the initial case study subject), we changed the focus and selected the current case study.

Therefore, the research questions concerning the previous case study of female frontline workers read as follows:

- RQ1: How did women working at the frontline in SPAR supermarkets perceive the infection risk they were exposed to at their workplace?
- RQ2: How did they feel valued and protected by their co-workers, their employer, the government and the customers?
- RQ3: How was their overall risk perception and feelings of safety throughout the COVID-19 pandemic and how did it change over time?
- RQ4: What was their lived experience of risk and safety of working through the pandemic at the frontline?

Due to the different demographic we also had to adjust our research questions. Whereas our initial research interest focused on the experience of risk and safety of frontline workers at their workplace we currently focus on the experiences of a particularly vulnerable group within an institutional support structure. Thus, the main research questions that we used for this case study are:

- RQ1: Was the HAH able to mitigate some of the risks of COVID-19 for this particular vulnerable group?
- RQ2: What were protective factors and what were factors within the HAH that potentially made the inhabitants more vulnerable?
- RQ3: How did women living in socially assisted and permanent housing experience COVID-19?

The findings of these study will shed light on the needs of a group that suffers under multiple forms of discrimination and vulnerabilities. Further, the findings could provide important insights to support institutions and their vulnerable clients in future (health) crises.

2.1.3 Method

We interviewed eight women from the Hannah Arendt Haus (HAH) as well as one member of the management and one social worker who has been working there for several years. The interviews we conducted with staff members were expert interviews which lasted for about 60 minutes. We tape recorded and transcribed them for analysis. The staff members of the house selected the women we interviewed. They selected the women based on their German language skills as well as willingness to participate in a semi-structured interview. The interviews lasted between 25 and 60 minutes. The interview guide followed a problem-oriented approach and started off with two narrative questions about their lives as well as their overall memories of the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic). For most of our interlocutors this approach worked well. However, some women only gave very short answers or did not engage in the questions we asked but talked to us about unrelated topics. Reasons might have been a disinterest in the topic or mental illness. Half of the interviews were conducted with two researchers (one senior and one junior) present. The other half have been conducted only by the senior researcher. More information on the interview setting and analysis can be found in Appendix A, Annex 1. More information on the individual interviewees can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Socio-demographic data of the interviewees (Austria Case Study).

		Interview 1	Interview 2	Interview 3	Interview 4	Interview 5	Interview 6	Interview 7	Interview 8
Socio-demographics	Gender	Female	Female	Female	Female	Female	Female	Female	Female
	Age	59		56	67	54	66	61	
	Birthplace	Austria	Austria	Austria	Austria	Austria	Austria	Austria	Serbia
	First Language	German	German	German	German	German	German	German	Serbo-Croatian
	Marital Status	Widowed		Divorced	Widowed	Widowed	Single	Single	
	Current Occupation	Not employed		Not employed	Retired	Not employed	Retired	Retired	
Life Stories	Last Job Title	Cleaning Person		Butcher			Sales	Hospitality	
	Time in HAH & previous residence	13 years	2 months Other permanent shelter in Vienna	6 years Mother-child home		2 Years	2 Years		11 years Mother-child home
Social Contacts	Children	0	4	0	3	3	1	1	2
	Family In contact?	Yes No contact	Yes, 4 children In contact with 2		Yes Mainly with her sister	Yes Not with her children	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Friends								
	Pets			Yes, two cat	Yes, a cat	Yes, a cat			Yes, a dog

2.1.4 Results: Data Reporting

Figure 4. SYNYO, Austria – Coding Tree.

2.1.5 Results: Analysis and Interpretation

Translated citations from the interviews can be consulted in Appendix B, Annex 1.1.

Mitigating Vulnerabilities at the Hannah Arendt House

Support

In the HAH there are two levels reserved for women. Access is only enabled through a swipe card system to protect the women from potential dangers. Each of the apartments is around 25qm² big and has a private bath and kitchen. There were legal changes to the contracts in the last couple of years. Originally the house provided assisted housing whilst the legal term has now changed to stationary housing. This change was introduced by their funding body FSW. According to the management the difference lies in the contracts of the inhabitants. These are now in line with the tenancy law and the inhabitants have more rights. For example, the contracts are harder to terminate, they now also get regular periods of notice in line with the tenancy law. Other changes include for example that inhabitants can now have visitors over without needing to give a notice. In many legal perspectives the apartments are now on equal terms with private rentals. Nonetheless, the Hannah Arendt House still has the final responsibility and provides assistance to the inhabitants. Shortly after the inhabitants move in, they will be assigned to a social worker. The frequency of their meetings will depend on individuals' needs. Besides, this inhabitant can always go and get support in urgent matters from the social worker on duty. Most people who live in the house receive a pension or a disability pension. Currently only one person is receiving a salary through work. The Hannah Arendt House is for people who are still able to live alone. Some receive unemployment money or the so-called Mindestsicherung which is paid by the City of Vienna. The FSW pays 900 Euros for the accommodation, the support of the social workers as well as the upkeep of the facilities. That brings the actual rent down to 343 per unit. The inhabitants have to pay this rent themselves. The idea is that inhabitants have their own independent living space which they are free to organise as they please.

It is really thought of in such a way that the people here have their own individually designable living space. The limits to this are the house rules, so what that means is that it is not possible to disturb the peace after 10 o'clock p.m. Violence, discrimination, racism, these are things that we do not tolerate in the house. That can range from a warning to, depending on the severity of the incident, to um a ban from the house or even loss of residence (...) So in the case of incidents of violence, it's usually the case that loss of living space is possible (Management 1).

Staff working at the Hannah Arendt Haus are: four social workers, 10 housing support staff and two nurses. Additionally, there is a GP coming twice a week, a psychiatrist that visits the house once a week as well as two psychologists (one for men and one for women) who are also present once a week. Supporting inhabitants with their medical needs is one of the biggest tasks of the social workers along with providing support in financial matters, particularly in that they receive the money that they are eligible for and other bureaucratic issues.

[...] Financially, also the basic material security, as it is called. That means, we make sure the people receive the money that they are entitled to (Management 1).

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Most of the inhabitants are fairly independent but some need daily support from their social workers with finances, conflicts, organising doctor's appointments, etc.

Vulnerabilities of the inhabitants

The inhabitants of the Hannah Arendt Haus are affected by multiple vulnerabilities. Here, social and economic vulnerabilities bring about health vulnerabilities and vice versa. Many inhabitants have depression, anxiety, obsessive-compulsive or borderline disorder although not all of them are properly diagnosed. According to the management around 25% of the participants are in substitution treatment.

Exactly, so what's already striking is how many people here so in homelessness in general have health problems, whether it's mentally or physically (Management 1).

Due to the vulnerable health status of many of the inhabitants the management decided to be extra cautious as they were afraid that the virus could cause many fatalities and severe cases of COVID-19 infections. Due to their risk management, they only had very little COVID-19 cases, particularly in the beginning of the pandemic. Cases only increased during the Omicron wave where already many inhabitants were vaccinated.

And the biggest concern for us was that there are just so many vulnerable groups of people in the house, and the fear was that if we become infected and spread it in the house, there will be many infections and perhaps even many deaths. So that was the fear at the beginning. And, if you look at it now in retrospect, it worked amazingly well, that it [the spread of the virus] didn't happen. What was rather problematic, and still is, are the consequences of social isolation (Management 1).

At HAH they were happy to see that their method to prevent the spread of COVID-19 was effective. However, according to the management they can now feel the secondary effects of the pandemic, particularly the negative consequences of social isolation. According to them there is an increase in alcohol consumption and psychological crisis. One of the management staff also observed an increase of conflicts between the inhabitants. In their opinion this could be the effects of long periods of social isolation. Interestingly, the risk management was so effective that nobody died of COVID-19 in the HAH. They also managed to keep the infections very low until the beginning of 2022.

Rules and Regulations within the Hannah Arendt House

The key rulebook of the HAH are the housing rules in the HAH. It outlines some basic rules on how to behave and create a communal living experience for the inhabitants of the house. This document already existed prior to the COVID-19 pandemic and has not changed much throughout the pandemic. It contains certain rules that the inhabitants must adhere to. Disobeying the rules comes with a warning and a mandatory conversation, if, however, their behaviour does not change, this further leads to an immediate termination of the housing contract or ban from the house. Such incidents include: inhabitants exercising physical and/or psychological violence, threatening other inhabitants, committing theft, trafficking drugs, damaging the property, constituting a danger to others and/or themselves, being expelled by the police or having their funding approval withdrawn or not renewed or non-use of the place of residence.

In addition, the housing rules clearly states that the HAH is not suited for residents whose illness or other general (physical or psychiatric) condition requires the permanent presence of medical staff as

the HAH is not equipped for offering this kind of support. Instead, they offer to seek out a suitable follow-up residential facility together.

The Hausordnung further contains regulations concerning the nighttime quiet hours between 10 p.m. and 6 a.m., in which the noise level should be kept low. It also states that social workers do have access to all apartments but generally seek to respect the privacy of the inhabitants. If inhabitants seek to stay away for more than 24 hours they must inform the housing administration, if they stay away unexcused for more than 14 days, they lose their apartment. Nevertheless, the housing rules also contain certain rights the inhabitants have, such as inviting family or friends over (but visitations from underagers must be agreed upon beforehand), having pets, drinking alcohol, consuming drugs etc.

COVID-19 management

According to the management there was a pandemic plan. However, this plan needed to be adjusted to the COVID-19 pandemic due to limitations of the original version. Plus, like everybody – government, other institutions and individuals – the HAH and its staff had to face quickly changing rules, regulations and information.

On one hand, the HAH had to apply the regulations and rules adopted by the government, on the other hand the HAH also had to follow specific rules of the organisation that the house is part of - the overarching institution of HAH. In addition to these obligatory measures, HAH staff decided upon how they could be implemented in the house and discussed the realization of HAH-specific measures. As the institution deals with very vulnerable people, they, on times, decided to implement stricter rules than the government required. For example, the HAH obliged its inhabitants to wear masks longer than e.g., the government did, until February 2023 and implemented a separation of staff shifts in order to reduce personal contact.

I: But from where did they [the measures, rules and regulations] come then?

B: Partly internally, partly it was quite clear that it happened through the regulations that were given by the government and partly we had even stricter regulations than the government had given. But that also varied from phase to phase. But, for example, when the obligation to wear masks was lifted at the end, we still wore them in the house, for example.

I: Ah, really?

B: Well, we delayed the end of it, and that was an internal rule of organisation, for example (management 1).

Before the pandemic there were two shifts, one morning and one afternoon, both would overlap around midday for an hour. Once the pandemic hit, the organisation needed to take measures to provide for their own safety and to ensure continuous service and support to the inhabitants. This was a particular worry in the first phase of the pandemic when the supply of protective gear such as masks was limited and hard to access. While face masks were missing, staff received plexiglass walls which should provide safety while talking face to face. Another solution was that the staff was divided into two teams with a rotating roster for the morning and afternoon shift. Additionally, the shifts did not overlap anymore. Thus, the two teams had no physical contact anymore. This would guarantee that in case a staff member got infected and the whole team needed to quarantine, the other half of the staff could continue their work uninterrupted.

It was, there was also a big tough process behind how this [the regulations] could be realized, so that it would be as safe as possible for everyone and this especially when there were no masks at all and no privacy screens or anything. Disinfectant was difficult, it went to the rescue service at the beginning. So we had to economize it. And it was simply the fear that was everywhere, because I am just as much a person who has never heard of it, like everyone else. And then you just go to work like always, but it's not like always, you think to yourself: "I'm also terribly afraid of it. Maybe I'll die and what if it spreads in the house?" That was the biggest fear of ours (...) in the house when it gains momentum, that it's unstoppable. But it did not happen (Staff 2).

Inhabitants of the house had to wear masks in the hallways and staff members were obliged to wear masks when in contact with inhabitants. During the acute pandemic phases personal contact between staff and inhabitants should be kept to a minimum. Another recommendation was that inhabitants should have as little visits as possible, particularly not from people outside. However, they were also encouraged to limit visits from within the HAH

The organisation that the HAH is part of belongs to the social economy of Austria and is also active in Emergency medical services that had early access to vaccination. They also organised vaccination for the inhabitants directly in the house to make it easier accessible. Staff members would also accompany inhabitants to the so-called vaccination streets if necessary. These efforts were successful and the vaccination rate of the house was higher than the average in their district (approximately between 60-70%).

Overall, the COVID-19 management paid off. No COVID-19 related death occurred within the house. According to the stories of the management there were only small clusters of cases amongst groups of friends. However, they managed to isolate those clusters so that it never led to a big infection wave within the house.

No, the only thing that comes to my mind is, at the very beginning of the pandemic, we all believed that it was going to break out right away in there. And we were one of the last houses where people had COVID. That only happened last year. So, the whole house paid attention to it, not only the staff, but also partly the residents (...) even the home helpers were afraid that it would break out immediately and so, because there are a few people in here, who did not wear a mask and didn't keep distance. They went to their friends at Praterstern [tram station in Vienna] or somewhere or so. And we believed that it would spread in here immediately (Inhabitant 3).

Challenges

Overall, the inhabitants *accepted* and followed the rules of the HAH. According to the management the biggest issues and discussions evolved around mask wearing.

It was difficult to enforce, among the people, the obligation to wear a mask, which then came- There was always the question [...] how to enforce it, it's basically, I'm not the police, I'm not a judge, but it's just in the interest of everybody in the house, if everyone goes along with it. Then there were the conspiracy theories that it's [Covid-19] all just bullshit and it's just a cold and a flu and that was extremely time consuming, to enforce this mask requirement for a while (Staff 2).

This is also reflected in our interviews: on the one hand inhabitants told us how they were confronted with others not wearing the mask and on the other hand interlocutors told us how skeptical they were of wearing masks. Amongst the people we interviewed we found many who appreciated mask wearing as a personal safety measure whereas others gave us the impression that they rather not wear masks but they are doing it for the ‘greater good’ which in this case are the other people in the HAH.

[...] I mean at certain times I wear it [the mask] too, it's obvious. When there are too many people or when you know they're not clean or something. Then I wear it too. But otherwise I want to feel free, I want to be human. (Inhabitant 5)

[...] but there are some people in here that didn't wear mask and didn't keep distance (Inhabitant 3).

One big challenge that the house encountered was the direct implementation of the government's rules. It was nearly impossible to explain and reinforce lockdowns as well as other measures to people with severe mental illness such as schizophrenia. Particularly inhabitants that suffer under paranoia displayed great mistrust against the government even prior to the pandemic. This made it even harder to reinforce governmental rules. It highlights that rules were designed for particular groups in mind where the lived realities of particular groups could not be considered when implementing the public health orders. Organisations such as the HAH were then left alone in dealing with vulnerable groups and finding ways of protecting them and others around them.

It was rather the things that were imposed by the state or so, mandatory confinement and so on, you just can't implement that with severely mentally ill people, that doesn't work (Staff 2).

Perception of care

Overall staff would say that they have a good relationship with most of the people living at Hannah Arendt House (HAH). This is also reflected in the interviews with the women living there. Generally, the inhabitants of the HAH were very thankful towards the house itself and all of them appreciate the opportunity to be able to live there:

I2: Is there something that you are especially thankful for, here in the house? During the pandemic and so?

B: I am very thankful to be here (Inhabitant 5).

And although the apartments are quite small, the women were able to “love” (Inhabitant 3) them or described them as their “oasis of well-being” (Inhabitant 6). This thankfulness especially showed in the interviews with the two women who had moved into the house in the beginning of Covid. Despite some difficulties in the HAH, they found it much more accommodating than the previous facility they had stayed in, which had turned into a “horror house” (Inhabitant 2) during Covid or living rough.

Besides the living space as such, women valued the support they received from the social workers.

Well, I have a lot to be thankful for. I am thankful for being allowed to be here, that I am really well received. And that the caregivers are so supportive that I know that if I have any problems, they will be the first ones there (Inhabitant 4)

I: How is your relationship with your social worker?

B: Yes. [...] There was even a doctor in the house, a psychiatrist was here because of my depression, medicine and so on. [...]

I: And now you are feeling better already?

B: Yes, now it's ok. A bit, but sometimes the sadness comes back, I don't know why. But during the Covid-time, it was very sad for me, very bad (Inhabitant 8)

While talking about her mental health issues the women explained to us how well cared for she felt by the staff of HAH during COVID-19. Her comment illustrated the holistic care she received which was entirely organised by the HAH. Although the woman still feels depressed on time she also explained that she already feels much better and she is often able to cope with the everyday demands of life.

The women we interviewed were generally happy with how the COVID-19 pandemic was managed. Moreover, the inhabitants trusted the social workers because of the respect they show the women:

First of all, the trust comes from how you treat people. [...] He [the social worker] talks with you as if you be equal to him, which is already a lot (Inhabitant 6).

This trust also shows as the percentage of those vaccinated in the house is rather high, nevertheless not every inhabitant abided by every measure strictly. This is also reflected in the interviews with the women, while the staff was regarded positively throughout. However, the opinions of their co-inhabitants varied. Further, as already outlined above the staff of Hannah Arendt House looks in many aspects after the inhabitants' wellbeing. Particular areas of focus are health and finances. Interestingly the inhabitants, although all very satisfied with the HAH, did not mention this support explicitly in our interviews.

In our interviews the women told us that they had very little contact with staff of the house during the heights of the COVID-19 pandemic. Some sounded a little disappointed about this. Nonetheless, overall, they felt even through the lockdowns they received the support needed.

Secondary effects of the pandemic management

Despite the efforts of the social workers to mitigate the vulnerabilities of the women living in the HAH, they were not able to alleviate the toll Covid-19 took on everybody - the general population and formerly homeless alike. The effects that were felt strongest were: fear from the unknown, social isolation and loneliness, fear for one's health and life, risk of depression and other mental illness amplified by isolation. When remembering the Covid-19 pandemic one of the interviewed women expressed the memories as:

[...] being eternally locked-in. Being alone. At the beginning you were just really afraid, after it had broken out. Whether it's really so extremely contagious, whether really so many people will die [...] (Inhabitant 5).

Particularly in the beginning, when the consequences of the pandemic were still very unclear, this uncertainty put a strain on the women. This, at some point in time, could also turn into an information overload, thereby also affecting the women negatively. However, this was only stated by few – most of the women reported on feeling bored, depressed, isolated and tired. COVID-19 also worked as an amplifier for the vulnerabilities that the women had already suffered from prior to the pandemic (e.g., alcoholism, depression). Due to COVID-19 some women also resorted back to negative coping-strategies, such as isolation or alcoholism:

And to be honest, we just drank a lot most of the time (Inhabitant 3).

In addition, women had to deal with the loss of social contacts inside and outside of the house, be it by moving away, difficulties of keeping contacts upright digitally or even death. Lockdown was particularly hard on one of our interviewees who lived on streets together with a group of others. For her the isolation was particularly hard as well as the feelings of being locked in. She was used to being surrounded by others all the time and enjoyed some sort of freedom while living on the street. Not having any friends at the HAH made lockdown even more difficult. However, with time she developed close friendships and built a network of people surrounding her. Nonetheless, the interviewees were quite isolated from the outside world and those who had social contacts outside were cut off from them.

Many died. Moved away. This one, the nice one moved to Germany with his new girlfriend. One is in prison because he committed an aggravated robbery (Inhabitant 5).

And then Corona was for me, how should I say, very difficult, because I couldn't go to my children (Inhabitant 8).

In our interviews only a few women talked about hobbies that they engaged with during the pandemic. For example, one woman became very active in gardening during this time. However, the majority described their routine as limited to watching TV. One woman told us that she really wanted a pet but she did not have the financial resources to afford one. The narratives highlighted a difference between, on the one hand, an increase of hobbies such as baking, music, crafting, cooking and sports in many segments of Austrian society and the lack of hobbies and activities of the women we interviewed. A possible explanation could be the lack of financial resources as the women have to survive from a minimum pension or an invalidity pension. Another potential reason could be mental health issues which make it harder to engage in such activities. Maintaining social contacts within the house was also difficult as many of the communal areas, such as the cafeteria had to be closed and visits were officially not allowed.

Social Networks

The loss of contacts then again fed into the specific vulnerable situations the women are in. Homelessness and financial precarity often goes hand in hand with social exclusion (ref is missing). For example, in our interviews we found that only two of the women talked about friends who they regularly met up with. One woman said that she regularly skyped with her former work colleagues but that she held off on meeting up in person with them as she is too ashamed about the weight gain she experienced during the pandemic. Thus, many of the inhabitants already had limited social contacts – their families included- outside of the house already prior to the pandemic. Only four women spoke about being in regular contact with their children and other family members. Within the women we interviewed the impression arose that only the women who were not affected by substance abuse disorder had regular and strong relationships to people outside of the HAH. Somehow those women who did not have strong social contacts beforehand reported feeling less affected by isolation, social distancing and a small social network.

Approximately half of the women we talked to explicitly told us that they stay to themselves and that they do not socialise much with other people living in the house. This has not changed much during COVID-19 as they always preferred to keep to themselves in the house. Some also said that they also prefer not having many contacts within the house to stay out of trouble as some people like to lend money and this can lead to conflict. Interestingly, it was those women who did not have much contact with family, friends or other inhabitants who also said that they did not desire it and hence, also did

not report suffering from the lockdown. In some cases, being alone was a protective measure that helps to deal with everyday life.

I: You didn't feel alone?

B: No (Inhabitant 1).

I don't go outside that much anyway, because of my mental state. And for me the lockdown wasn't the worst thing (Inhabitant 3).

Interestingly, many of the women had pets, in particular cats, to keep them company. Based on their narratives the pets were central to their lives. Most of their worries concerned them. This became particularly clear when the women talked about their experiences of being ill with COVID-19.

I have had everything that God has forbidden. The full course. I lay down for a week and I didn't even know anymore if I was a male or a female, partly. The only thing that made me move in any way were the cats, because they needed food. Well, I always have a lot at home, I didn't have to go shopping, but still I have to feed them, fresh water, fill up the box. That was hard work for me (Inhabitant 3).

Their cats and dogs are important points of references to them. They are also a connection to other people as they connect with other inhabitants through their pets and finally, they helped coping with the COVID-19 pandemic.

Roughly the other half of the women were part of a tight friendship circle that developed inside of the HAH. Based on the stories we have heard, central to this friendship group is the garden and the garden pavilion. In charge of the pavilion are a man and a woman who both also carry the official roles of confidant for the other inhabitants within the HAH. The garden is important as it became a project to embellish this communal space through little improvements. By the time we conducted the interviews the garden already turned into a little oasis. The pavilion provided an additional outside sitting area beside the area outside of the cafeteria and the garden. The group usually comes together in the pavilion. During COVID-19 the group met there to have breakfast together or to enjoy some drinks together in the early evening. The group decided to sell drinks at the pavilion so that they could use the money they made to invest into the garden. The women told us that, unfortunately, there are also some conflicts surrounding the pavilion so that, at the time we conducted the interviews, the inhabitants who regularly used to spend time in the cafeteria split up in two groups. The one group who looked after the pavilion and another group who also wanted to use the space but did not follow the rules that were set up. We often heard that the latter group was a bit jealous and often tried to rebel against those in charge of the pavilion. Our interlocutors hinted on drug abuse disorders that may have made interactions more difficult. Other than that, we also heard that the same friendship group would regularly eat together on Sundays.

These friendships grew during COVID-19 as the group started to look out for each other, provided food if needed. Further, we could also observe that they engaged in communal sense making regarding the COVID-19 pandemic. Although some of the group was described as COVID-19 deniers and others held high trust in the government and their pandemic management they respected each other's opinion. We have not heard of any major conflicts. Two women told us that it was through the pandemic that they became part of the friendship group. One already lived in the house for a long time but did not make many connections to others besides her immediate neighbors who also had cats. The other woman was new to the house as she lived on the streets. After a period of isolation and loneliness that

was very hard on her, she met the group and started enjoying herself. These social connections alleviated some of the negative consequences of the pandemic. The women did not feel alone as they had a sense of belonging and they felt supported.

I: And that means, how were you? Did you feel alone or lonely ?

B: No. Just when I was locked in ten days. But I also have to say that I was actually fine, because I'm in this group, yes. XXXX called me every day, asked "XXXX, do you need anything? Do you want me to bring you something ?" So I was not alone (Inhabitant 4).

COVID-19 Risk communication

The team of the HAH kept the communication about COVID-19 to a minimum. They only understood the communication about rules and regulations from the government as well as internal ones as their responsibility. Only communicating what was necessary was also a strategy of the staff members to avoid conflict with inhabitants. To communicate rules and regulations they used the communal white board and information sheets next to the elevator. They also tried to inform their inhabitants personally about the current regulations when necessary or provide further explanation where needed. They also recommended vaccination and provided easy access to it. Particularly the nurses put effort in explaining the vaccination to the inhabitants, especially to risk patients. However, when it came to the vaccination the management and staff did not try to convince the inhabitants. Nonetheless, staff were clear that they did not try to convince inhabitants to get vaccinated.

We definitely didn't force anybody, we provided the information, we did, yes we provided information like where you can go and regarding the rest everybody has to decide for themselves. So we didn't force anybody (Staff 2).

The matter was more complicated with mask wearing. Staff over and over emphasized that it felt exhausting to them to repeatedly remind inhabitants of their duty to wear a mask.

The inhabitants of the house have a trusting relationship with the staff of the Hannah Arendt House. This had a positive effect on trusting them about the information that they shared and taking it seriously, and subsequently, on the compliance with COVID-19 rules as well as vaccination recommendations.

[...] Or the manager of the house. If he said something, that was also a matter for me, yes. Because he is a very thoughtful person and you can believe what he says. 100 percent (Inhabitant 3)

Some of the women we talked to also explained to us that they have not only a lot of trust in the staff members and the COVID-19 information they received from them but also in the general practitioner that is once a week at HAH. Their trust was the reason why they got vaccinated.

During the interviews we could observe that some of the inhabitants made tongue and cheeks comments about 'how annoying' and 'unnecessary' some of the measures were and added that they only followed them to please staff members. These comments illustrate their annoyance but simultaneously also express their respect and sympathy for the HAH staff and showed us that the inhabitants respected the rules even though they might not always agree with them.

Yes, we were informed constantly. Always something new. To wear the mask, that a new virus is spreading, an old virus is spreading, to wear a mask, to wash your hands, to not sit together.

That's what the house did. They told us what was going on, what we should do and how (Inhabitant 4).

The majority of our interlocutors expressed mistrust and dissatisfaction towards the government's COVID-19 communication including the regular press releases. A particular point of contention that our interlocutors talked about was the ever-changing information about COVID-19 and the changing rules and regulations that went hand in hand with that. For example, some found information around the various COVID-19 strains implausible. Others had a hard time to understand the rationale behind the rules for mask wearing in the later stages of the pandemic. Some of the inhabitants made the same jokes about these regulations.

No, but you do ask yourself, if you think about it, what's the point, if you put on a mask at the Billa [local supermarket chain], then you go two stores further because you're shopping at the DM and you don't need a mask there. I have to put on a mask at the pharmacy. The store next to it is the Frick, the bookstore, that's where I buy my crossword puzzles and I don't need a mask there. So, the COVID virus, it knows exactly where to go in and where not to go in. Yes, it's illogical (Inhabitant 4).

During our interviews we heard this joke on several occasions. It illustrates how, in Austria, the government's public health directives, at times, have failed to communicate the reason for certain measures. Mask wearing continued to be mandatory in supermarkets, pharmacies and doctor offices to protect vulnerable groups as it was assumed that vulnerable groups have no choice but to visit these places whereas they do not necessarily need to enter a, for example, book shop. The government failed to explain this in a way that it was comprehensible to a broad audience.

The reappearance of the same joke in a third of the interviews hints on the inhabitants talking to each other about COVID-19 and engaging in a communal sense making process. This communal sense making takes place despite varying viewpoints and opinions about the pandemic. Some of the women we interviewed would not fully believe in COVID-19. Some others had high trust in the government, science and the HAH. However, although they disagree about some fundamentals regarding the disease, they still turned to each other to process the pandemic. Here too we found expressions of trust regardless of conflicting opinions.

Although what he told us was 90 percent true. He just always added some things [that were not true], because he's a denier. But otherwise it was fine... (Inhabitant_3).

At other points in our interviews some of our interlocutors told us that some of the information was just too much and not relevant to them:

For me, for example, it didn't matter whether the virus is called one thing or another, because there's been another one now. I don't know what it's called. For a while, I knew, but then I said I'm not going to engage with it anymore. And I didn't care what it's called. To me, it's just one thing, it's dangerous. And I don't need it to be named Lieselotte or Aaron or whatever. That doesn't interest me. So, what it's causing, that's what's relevant to me, I would say. (Inhabitant_3)

The interviews showed us that there was a sense of being overwhelmed with all kinds of information around COVID-19. We have found that in the HAH, the inhabitants that we talked to either became skeptical of the (government's) COVID-19 communication or they turned to trusted sources such as the staff members or friends. Turning to trusted sources could have been a strategy to cope with the

overwhelming amount of information and difficulties making decisions about what to trust and believe from sources such as government representatives, mainstream media and social media.

Nonetheless, trust was a recurring theme in our analysis. Some of our interlocutors told us that COVID-19 is just a cold or did not believe in COVID-19 at all. When we then asked them if they were vaccinated, they said regardless and explained to us that it is better to be safe than sorry. Or who some put it in a very Viennese manner: 'if it does not help it won't cause any harm'. Here, we could observe contradictions within our interlocutors' decision making: against their own beliefs they trusted the staff and followed their health recommendations. Thus, the trust they had developed towards the staff of HAH was something that they relied on and guided them in important decisions.

2.1.6 Conclusions

HAH played a major role in mitigating the Covid-19 crisis and related risks. Trust was crucial enabling component. Already through its role and structure the Hannah Arendt House was able to support every woman with their individual respective needs, those who needed more help (e.g., with their mental help) received it, those who desired more social contact were able to connect with other inhabitants and involve themselves in house projects, such as the garden, but also those women who just want their peace and quiet were able to have that by closing their door, minimizing contact and living by themselves. By having established a good, trusting relationship even prior to the pandemic, the staff was able to build on this trust. Key to this trust was respect towards the staff and management of the house as well as vice versa. Inhabitants had positive relationships with the staff due to the feeling like they are treated with respect. Most women stated to have respected the house rules, pandemic measures and relied on the information the house provided (see vaccination rate and general testing). The only criticism women voiced in the interviews were towards other inhabitants who did not follow the directives.

Particularly interesting was that there was such a high level of trust that the majority of the women got vaccinated. In some cases, even though they did not believe in COVID-19 and/or in its severity. However, the recommendation of the HAH outweighed their doubts.

Nonetheless, the staff experienced the implementation of the government's rules as challenging at times. Inhabitants with mental health issues, in particular schizophrenia, had a hard time to obey the rules. Governments and public health authorities should keep this in mind for future pandemics as organisations such as the HAH were left alone in dealing with vulnerable groups and finding ways of protecting them and others around them. Mask wearing were also reportedly harder to implement than other measures. Nonetheless, mask wearing was perceived as very effective by most people in the house. Overall, the COVID-19 management within the Hannah Arendt house was effective. There were no death and the majority of the infections only took place once vaccination was already available. However, the staff could feel the secondary effects and their negative impact on inhabitants. In some instances, substance abuse behaviour increased and mental health crises occurred.

Those with social contacts to family and friends outside of the house seem to have the most stable mental health and they made it relatively well through the pandemic. Some have made new friendships within the house during the pandemic. Some have intensified their contacts during this time. Both have led to positive experiences during the COVID-19 pandemics. Inhabitants are all grateful for their apartments and the service provided by HAH. Many have lived in other institutions before and feel much more comfortable in HAH than in the others. Reasons are the high level of care provided

by the variety of staff such as a GP and mental health professionals as well as the caring and respectful contact of the staff and management.

As mentioned, our main objective was to understand if and how the Hannah Arendt House was able to mitigate negative effects of the pandemic for this vulnerable group. All the data seems to confirm that the spectre of the homeless living, clearly a very present feeling, was of utmost importance. The physical structure, the rules, the possibility of organizing autonomously the small, but certain, income, was such a positive alternative that outweighs most strains. This idea is consistent with the literature discussed in the state of the art, i.e., the benefits for PEH of having received the opportunity of permanent shelter outweighed the negative effects of lockdowns and isolation. Aspects such as security and safety as well as acceptance are valued higher. Thus, yes, the existence of permanent shelter is an essential stress release mechanism. Important to mention though, that the effect is only apparent if the people in question had a prior homeless experience.

Although these women remain particularly vulnerable due to other compound factors above, this context lessens the negative impact of their COVID-19 experience. Other factors like the institutional support, for example when hospitals were full and sent patients back, and the control of their financial precarity, that did not increase for the women due to COVID-19-Pandemic, also explained the above result. Finally, the emphasis of autonomy, particularly within their apartments, as well as the permanency of the housing also positively impacted the women.

2.2 Belgium, UANTWERPEN

2.2.1 Introduction

Our case study settings are the Antwerp districts of in Borgerhout and Antwerpen-Noord. Antwerp is the capital of the Antwerp province, located in Dutch-speaking Flanders. In 2020, the city of Antwerp had a little over half a million (530,000) inhabitants, of which around 46,000 live in the Borgerhout district. Diversity is pronounced in Borgerhout and Antwerpen-Noord. In 2023 (Stad in Cijfers), 36.2% of residents in Borgerhout have two Belgian parents, compared with 25.5% in Antwerpen-Noord. Meanwhile 24.9% of residents in Borgerhout are first generation migrants, and 38.9% in Antwerpen-Noord (Stad in Cijfers, 2023). The incomes of Borgerhout residents are relatively low compared to the rest of Antwerp. In 2020, the median taxable income was €16,156 in Antwerpen-Noord and €18,158 in Borgerhout, compared to €19,649 in the City of Antwerp (Stad in Cijfers, 2023). This wealth difference is also reflected in other indicators, such as the percentage of people eligible for 'increased compensation' (*Verhoogde Tegemoetkoming*) for the reimbursement of medical costs. In Borgerhout, 37.9% of residents received the Verhoogde Tegemoetkoming in 2018, compared to 29.3% in the City of Antwerp (Stad in Cijfers, 2022). In addition, green spaces are not easily accessible to all residents. For example, Borgerhout has the lowest percentage (50.6%) of inhabitants living less than 5 minutes walking distance from a park in Antwerp (Burbidge et al., 2022).

Figure 5. UANTWERPEN, Belgium – SES Framework.

2.2.2 Purpose and Research questions

In this case study, we will address the question of how the COVID-19 pandemic has impacted the mental health and wellbeing of migrant community members, looking at the key drivers of mental health impacts, and how they are embedded in community networks and neighbourhood characteristics. Next, we will explore how local and community level responses played a role in meeting demands for mental health-related support and care.

2.2.3 Method

Descriptive case details are partly taken from D5.4 and previous deliverables. Furthermore, we have based two academic papers off the data collected as part of the case study, these have not yet been published but it is important to mention for self-plagiarism reasons.

The qualitative case study engages with members of migrant communities themselves, as well as with local (mental) health professionals, social workers, and representatives from local Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and other relevant community-level organisations and initiatives. The first stage of the case study consisted of exploratory interviews with n=10 local (mental) health professionals and representatives from community-level initiatives. The second stage of the case study involved n=19 in-depth qualitative interviews with first-generation migrants living in Borgerhout or Antwerpen-Noord. Participant characteristics can be consulted in Table 2.

For the exploratory interviews in the first stage of the case study, we pursued convenience sampling by compiling a list of relevant organisations and services in Borgerhout and Antwerpen-Noord through online searches and then contacting representatives of those organisations and services. Although most of the organisations and individuals we contacted work directly on mental health-related issues (e.g. psychologists and psycho-social care providers), some have a more indirect link to mental health service provision (e.g. a local community centre which offers a range of services and which has an in-house psychologist). We contacted organisations in Borgerhout and Antwerpen-Noord who have migrant communities as (one of) their main target groups. Our convenience sample included organisations which have received funding from the City of Antwerp in the context of the *Coronababbels* ('Corona chats') project, which were funds awarded to a total of seven community organizations in Antwerp in 2021 to organize activities with the aim of providing psychosocial support, strengthening people's social networks, engaging in dialogue about these groups' concerns, and providing feedback signals to policymakers.

For the qualitative interviews with migrants, participants were recruited through organisations or actors working with migrants in Borgerhout and Antwerpen-Noord, as well as via snowball sampling. Recruitment occurred first through local CSOs or NGOs working with the target population and located or operating within the selected neighbourhoods, where they provided practical or financial assistance. This meant that the majority of those interviewed were low-income migrants, although there were also some residents interviewed who held 'white collar jobs' with a higher income. Within the heterogeneous group of 'migrants in Borgerhout and Antwerpen-Noord', we aimed to include variation in terms of the length of stay in Belgium (providing it was over five years), gender, age, and country of origin. Further recruitment strategies that were used included engaging with community health workers as 'gatekeepers'. Community health workers had many contacts and were typically well-trusted by members of the target communities. Working with organisations or bridging links to the target population helped the respondent to feel more comfortable speaking openly.

In-depth interviews with professionals in the local psycho-social care sector were carried out in Dutch during the months of June and July 2022. Interviews with migrants were carried out in the period June/July until November 2022 in Dutch or English. For both types of interviews, an interview guide was used that listed topics and issues to be covered in outline form, allowing for a situational and conversation interview-style. The topic guide included main questions following the logical flow anticipated in the interview, as well as follow-up questions and probes which helped move the discussion to a deeper level by asking for additional details. Written informed consent forms were used. Out of the interviews with the professionals in the local psycho-social care sector, seven interviews took place privately at respondents' workplaces, and the remaining three interviews were done virtually using Microsoft Teams. Interviews with migrants were conducted in CSO spaces or in cafes in the respondent's neighbourhood, which helped facilitate their willingness to talk openly. Interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed shortly following the interviews. Notes on nonverbal clues, as well as any interruptions to the interview, were written down and incorporated into the transcriptions. Interview transcripts were translated from Dutch to English by JM and HR, who are fluent in both languages.

Thematic analysis of the transcripts was undertaken by JM and HR to identify themes consistent with the study objectives. An initial stage of analysis involved open inductive coding of transcripts to identify and preliminary themes and sub-themes. A codebook was developed based on this initial stage of coding, which was then used to re-code all interviews. The qualitative and mixed-methods software NVivo was used for a thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Table 2. Participant characteristics (Belgium Case Study).

Characteristics	Migrants	Psycho-social care professionals
Number of participants	19	13
Countries of birth	Afghanistan (1), DR Congo (1), El Salvador (1), India (1), Indonesia (1), Morocco (5), Philippines (1), Poland (1), Russia (1), Somalia (1), Sri Lanka (1), Syria (1), Turkey (1), Uzbekistan (1), Yemen (1)	Belgium (11), Morocco (1), Sri Lanka (1)
Age (years): 18-30	4	1
31-40	5	4
41-50	5	3
51-60	3	3
61-70	2	1
Gender: Male	9	4
Female	10	8

2.2.4 Results: Data reporting

Figure 6. UANTWERPEN, Belgium – Coding Tree (1).

Figure 7. UANTWERPEN, Belgium – Coding Tree (2).

2.4.5 Results: Analysis and Interpretation

How has the COVID-19 pandemic impacted migrant community members' mental health and wellbeing, looking at the change over time?

This case study report first examines the changing impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental health and wellbeing of migrant community members in two neighborhoods in Antwerpen. The findings reveal that the pandemic has had a heterogeneous yet far-reaching effect on the mental health of migrants, attributable to various factors including social isolation and loneliness, health concerns related to COVID-19, working conditions and financial situation, housing and built environment, and increasing digitization associated with COVID-19 measures. Additionally, the study highlights a clear gender divide in the experiences and challenges faced by migrant community members.

Social restrictions and loneliness

Social restrictions and loneliness emerged as major contributors to poor mental health among migrants during the pandemic. Migrants living alone or far from family, lacking internet access or language proficiency, experienced heightened challenges related to social isolation. As one resident highlighted:

"It is hard to learn a language when you live alone and have to stay at home every day, not talking to other people, especially as I have no internet at home and no laptop. Then I started drinking alcohol. I like to talk to people. Not stay at home. I have problems if I stay at home".

(Man, India)

The closure of support organizations and difficulties in grieving further exacerbated the mental health impact on certain residents:

"My mum said "Please come visit me. I have three days left to live." I said "I am sorry mum, but three days....". Before yes, three days, I could go straight to the airport. But in lockdown, I needed fourteen days. Three days is impossible with the corona controls. So I could not go. And I have lost my mother." (Man, Sri Lanka)

Health concerns

The fear of contracting the virus and its physical consequences significantly impacted the mental health of migrant community members. Vulnerable individuals, such as older adults and those with pre-existing health conditions, experienced heightened anxiety. Low-income residents faced additional risks due to crowded living conditions and reliance on public transportation, leading to increased fear and depression. As one resident noted:

"I had an appointment with my specialist, rheumatoid. And my husband didn't have a car. I have to take the bus. I got so scared, but still. That was the first day in three months. But other places, I never go. . Because I have a lot of disease of rheumatoid. And I always had fear, I go somewhere and I get sick: am I going to die. So better stay in my home. I was so panicked. I know a lot of people who have died. And I see among our neighbors there are many people... If you get sick, maybe you can die or you have to go to hospital. People who go to hospital never return, they have died. I was depressed, I didn't want contact with people. Nothing, nothing. I was also sick. That's not good, because when you're depressed or sick, you don't feel like doing anything." (Woman, Morocco)

Work and financial situation

The economic repercussions of the pandemic affected the mental health of migrants who lost their jobs, leading to financial worries and isolation. The absence of documentation or a resident permit further complicated some people's situation, preventing access to legal employment and unemployment benefits. Remittance pressures were also observed among some migrants, worsened because of the global economic crisis, exacerbating their stress.

"A problem was that my work stopped. I worked in the restaurant, washing dishes. And then because of corona everything is closed. That was regretful and difficult for me. Not so good. I was looking for other works and during corona is very difficult to do that, especially because I had a day contract and needed proper papers for a long-term job. I received my papers in March 2020, but the next day was the lockdown." (Woman, Uzbekistan)

Digitalisation

Increased digitization during the pandemic had both positive and negative effects on mental health. While online spaces provided a lifeline for some migrants, allowing remote work and study, increased surveillance and lack of privacy negatively impacted mental wellbeing. For example, one participant

recounted their experience of being required to stay on a video call for eight hours to ensure that they were working whilst working from home.

“Some employers don't trust workers. So the manager asked us to stay on the video call for eight hours. To make a check that you stay in the office for eight hours. At your own office actually. So we open the cameras tomorrow and stay in the call, the Teams call, chatting, talking, and working on camera. For control.” (Man, Syria)

The digital divide further deepened mental health disparities, particularly for migrants with limited language or computer skills. Some respondents mentioned failing their school exams or language courses as a result of poor internet connection during the lockdown. Parents with children studying from home also faced challenges with internet access and providing equipment. Additionally, making appointments online was difficult for some migrants, and physical spaces or organizations that could usually provide help were closed due to the lockdown. Participants discussed the impact of the pandemic on their ability to access resources and navigate the digital world.

“I'm from Somalia, and I was bad with computer. To make appointments. That's difficult. Everything is online. No more appointments during corona, I couldn't come here (to CAW). You have to come in for help, but then was not closed. Without agency, I can't work, you have to wait too long to make appointments online. I have internet, but it's just hard. 9 years. It is very difficult. Although that I talk to her through WhatsApp. And then during corona we could not go inside to this office to put papers in order.” (Man, Somalia)

Housing

The research findings emphasize the significant impact of individuals' living conditions situations on their mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic and associated lockdowns. Specifically, individuals residing in poorly maintained or overcrowded rental or social housing faced challenges in terms of their well-being when restrictive measures resulted in the closure of public spaces. The disruption of adaptive strategies to cope with living conditions and the increased need for homes to accommodate multiple functions were evident among respondents. In contrast, those who lived in bigger houses, had a garden or close access to a park, found these spaces to be a saving grace for their mental health.

The pandemic highlighted the intensified poor living conditions and brought attention to the limited availability of affordable housing alternatives, which was partly influenced by the economic consequences of COVID-19. This issue particularly affected migrants lacking legal documentation and low-income families, as they struggled to find affordable and suitable housing. The demand for social housing exceeded availability, and rental costs escalated during the pandemic. Landlords were reportedly less inclined to lease high-quality housing to lower-income or larger migrant families. Consequently, many respondents in Antwerp found themselves living in crowded and unsuitable housing while being unable to afford better alternatives. The interviews revealed specific instances illustrating the adverse effects of poor housing conditions. For instance, one respondent highlighted the challenges of living in an expensive and cramped space shared with multiple family members.

“Without gas and electricity, it is 700 euros per month. With bills, it is 1000. This is very expensive. And it is also small. We all live together. I sleep on the couch, in the living room. Because there is not enough room for us. I live with my daughter and her husband and their three children. Sometimes one grandchild sleeps in the parent's room, then I can sleep in the bedroom. This is a problem. We are always looking for a new place to live.” (Woman, Morocco)

Another participant with a physical disability described the difficulties faced when the apartment's lift broke down, leading to him sleeping on the street.

“When the lift is broken to my apartment, I must sleep on the street. A week ago, I had to sleep twice on the street. Because the lift was broken, and it was the weekend. Two years ago, during the lockdown, I lived in an apartment on the third floor without a lift. I had to lift myself up the stairs, with help from a friend, every day. I was living with a friend because I had no money.” (Man, Morocco)

Built environment

These experiences further underscored the detrimental impact of inadequate housing on individuals' well-being during the pandemic. Income disparities emerged as a key determinant of the spatial implications of COVID-19. Respondents with access to gardens and larger living spaces reported fewer psychological difficulties. Owning a car was predominantly associated with higher income levels, leaving lower-income residents more confined to their immediate locality. This limited mobility had consequences for social interactions and access to essential services. The unequal distribution of public transportation options between different localities also posed additional challenges for individuals residing in low-income neighborhoods.

“There is just one bus that comes every 20 minutes to Luchtbal. It is a problem here. If the bus doesn't come, we just keep waiting. If we want to go to the market here in St Jansplein, we don't have a bus that goes there, so you have to walk. I am sick, I have problems with my knee and my back. For old people, that doesn't go well. We don't have anything. There used to be a bus next door which stopped close to the market. Almost three or four years ago. But now we don't have any. We must walk to the market.” (Woman, Morocco)

The economic downturn induced by the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in shop closures and transformations in high streets. The increased prevalence of online shopping and digitalization during lockdowns posed additional difficulties for businesses operating physical stores. This trend threatens the fabric of neighborhoods, particularly those already grappling with socio-economic challenges, as evidenced by the disappearance of shops and services.

“I think it was nicer before. There were many shops. There was a butcher, keymakers, everything. There was a wash salon. You could buy TV's, electronics, lamps, everything you could buy at 'Den Dam' [neighbourhood]. There was everything here before. But not anymore. There is nothing anymore. Everything has gone. 'I don't know why. All the people who were here, they left. Or they died.” (Man, Morocco)

In summary, the research findings underscore the considerable challenges faced by individuals residing in low-income neighborhoods in Antwerpen-Noord and Borgerhout due to their spatial circumstances, which had a negative impact on their mental health. These challenges include limited living space, reduced public transportation options, and economic consequences stemming from the pandemic. However, the research also highlighted some positive aspects, such as reduced car traffic within these neighborhoods, which typically experience high levels of congestion.

Unpaid work and caring responsibilities (gendered dimension)

During the COVID-19 pandemic, women faced an intensified burden of gendered care responsibilities, which had significant implications for their mental health. The research interviews revealed that teleworking arrangements and increased care obligations, particularly in households with children,

added further challenges for women. The prolonged time spent at home resulted in a heavier workload as they juggled household tasks, work responsibilities, assisting their children with homework, and attending to their husband's needs. The accumulation of these multiple responsibilities often led to exhaustion and mental distress, resulting in conflicts within the family. Single parents who were distant from their family members experienced considerable challenges, as they heavily relied on family support for childcare. With the closure of nurseries and the need to take care of their children alone, the absence of familial assistance and the uncertainty of the situation intensified their fears and anxieties about their children's well-being.

One woman shared her experience, expressing the difficulties she faced as a single mother during the pandemic:

“I was working. But then the work stopped. The nurseries were closed so I had to take care of my child. It was so hard, 2020, 2021. I was always crying. I'm going to die, I thought. And then what are my kids going to do? I am a single mother. I was so scared. My child should be adopted. Because who would have no mom or dad, and have to be alone. It was so difficult. Yes, I panicked because I have no family here, and I'm in Antwerp, what's going to happen?”
(Woman, Somalia)

Moreover, the pandemic exacerbated the existing gendered power dynamics and complexities surrounding women's relationship with public spaces in their neighborhoods. Women expressed fears of harassment and gender-based discrimination, which hindered their utilization of public spaces as sources of resilience. This further perpetuates gender disparities in urban environments. This combined impact of these gender inequalities and increased care responsibilities affected women's mental health during the pandemic.

“And of course, the parks, you have the Park Spoor Noord. But then you have to go through a less nice neighbourhood to reach it. And as a woman I don't always find that so easy. Because I am constantly harassed. I don't know if that is impacted by Corona. I think it was there before. But when people couldn't go to the cafes, they were all standing on the street. And that has its consequences. And then after COVID, I think it has become worse because men have been locked up for 2 years or so, they forget how to behave. If you come at this hour (20:00) on the street, there is barely any woman still outside. You just see men who are likely to harass you, and that is it.” **(Woman, Poland)**

In summary, the COVID-19 pandemic amplified gendered care responsibilities, impacting women's mental health significantly. The increased workload, limited access to public spaces due to safety concerns, and the lack of familial support for single parents all were drivers of poor mental health during the pandemic.

How have local/community-level responses played a role in meeting demands for mental health-related support and care?

The second part of the case study report is looking at **response** and is divided into two main sections, focusing on community-level responses to mental health-related needs. The first section highlights the crucial role played by local-level services and organizations in providing mental health services, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. We found that local-level organizations possess qualities and characteristics that make them uniquely valuable and indispensable, such as their awareness of

local needs and capacity to respond to a broad range of needs, their flexibility to address bottlenecks and fill gaps left by other services and ability to offer culturally sensitive care and support.

The second section of our report addresses the fragility and fragmentation of these local-level services and initiatives. We found that the COVID-19 crisis has created serious challenges to the physical accessibility of organizations' services, overloaded services and initiatives, and a widespread fragmentation and lack of oversight that poses a significant barrier to both service users and providers.

Unique value and indispensability of community-based organisations and initiatives

Based on the interviews with residents and community-based organisations working directly with them, the unique value and indispensability of these organisations and initiatives are shown in the following section as:

- Being aware of the local needs of people residing in this particular area and being able to respond to a broad spectrum of needs
- Flexible nature and able to fill policy gaps
- Offering culturally sensitive care and support

Being aware of the local needs of people residing in this particular area

The COVID-19 pandemic magnified health concerns, especially regarding the risk of contracting the virus and its physical effects. These concerns were further compounded by individual vulnerabilities associated with migrant status, family circumstances, and physical frailties, which were exacerbated by structural disadvantages such as lack of residency or work permits, unstable contracts, inadequate housing, and unfavourable built environments. In response, organizations had to adapt their successful practices to reach out to people and develop a deeper understanding of local needs. Local community-based organizations demonstrated their ability to address the specific needs of diverse target groups by adopting an intersectional approach and understanding the cumulative needs of individuals. The interviews shed light on the knowledge possessed by community-level actors regarding the direct and indirect effects of the COVID-19 crisis on their target groups, as well as their deep understanding of the emerging needs. A social worker from a local branch of a community service organization (CSO) noted a significant rise in requests for psychological support immediately after the outbreak of the pandemic in 2020, stating, *"We saw a large increase in psy-requests, a lot of people with stress complaints... really an increase compared to the previous period."*

CSO participants emphasized the accessibility of their organizations as a key factor in staying closely connected to the impact of the crisis. A coordinator from a local branch of a psycho-social care organization acknowledged the complexity of mental health services and the challenges people face in navigating the system, particularly for individuals with limited financial means who often find it easier to approach their organization: *"when it comes to mental health problems, finding your way around that entire landscape is not easy. I think they come to us more easily, especially people with little financial means"*. Another respondent, who is a trained psychologist and founder of a local drop-in centre for young people and women, emphasised accessibility as a key strength of her organisation:

"For example, a woman might pass by who is not feeling well at the time, who has never come here before. But she sees a dynamic, so she comes in and says, 'what is it all about, what do you all do?' Then we start telling her, and all at once a very big story emerges. 'I've been

through this and this, and I'm alone, and I don't feel so good and I don't know which organisations I can turn to."

Another shared sentiment among the respondents was that a core strength of their organisations is their capacity to respond to a broad spectrum of needs. As previously noted, many of the professionals interviewed take a coaching approach to mental-health related issues. Particularly in the COVID-19 crisis, when many support services became more difficult to access, respondents felt one of their key responsibilities was to link clients to support across different life domains. A psychologist working with children and families explains: *"We try to make a plan with families, and look at the different life domains in which they have questions. Then we see whether there is a professional service that can support them, or whether we can turn to their network. That is our vision, to try to activate people's own network. Can someone be approached, someone at school, a neighbour, or someone else? We work with people to see how support can be strengthened in different life domains."*

Respondents underline the psychosocial nature of their work, which frequently combines offering practical and therapeutic support. A social worker at a local CSO branch said: *"Yes, it really is psychosocial work. Even with people who are not specifically looking for psychological support... people have a lot of baggage and have a need to talk. Many people are in a kind of survival mode and have gotten the run-around from various agencies, and just listening to their story can do a lot. That they just feel heard."*

These quotes demonstrate the unique value of local community-based organisations in dealing with existing and aggravated mental health issues. Nevertheless, these issues cannot be separated from wider needs, especially not during the pandemic. Community-based organisations cannot fully fill the gap caused by structural problems, such as housing, which also needs addressing at a higher political level. Community-based organisation and initiative representatives were aware that there were many unmet needs.

Flexible nature and ability to fill gaps

Apart from their proximity and long-standing embeddedness in their locality, a unique value of community-level organisations is their relatively their services in response to changing needs. This quality turned out to be particularly important in a crisis context, as it allowed organisations to address bottlenecks and fill gaps left by other services and governmental agencies. Particularly at the beginning of the pandemic, when many governmental services closed their front-offices, community-level organisations found themselves having to adapt the scope of their work. A psychologist and founder of a local CSO explains: *"At that time, we were no longer just doing youth work, but we also became social services... and we tried to deal with all the questions that came in as best we could"*. She feels that filling this gap was much needed: *"I think that with our open drop-in house, we really were a beacon of hope. People said: 'we can go there, we can talk, we can get help, at least they are physically open. We don't have to call or talk to them online, we can really go to them.' At the very beginning there was nothing open at all, but we gave them a bit of perspective."*

As many of the local-level organizations and initiatives are relatively small, it was easier for them to rapidly adjust their services to meet their target groups' needs. Most of the community-level organisations had already been in existence for several years prior to the pandemic and had built up strong ties with the neighborhood, which was a significant asset in the COVID-19 crisis situation. National and regional governments focused heavily on vulnerability in terms of physical health status, particularly in the early stages of the pandemic, yet professionals attuned with their local

neighborhood had a more nuanced understanding of which groups of migrants were particularly vulnerable. This included an understanding of gendered differences, such as the caring responsibilities shouldered predominantly by women, as well as the unique challenges faced by undocumented migrants in the neighborhood. A social worker at a local CSO branch noted that *“the government was busy with other things”*, and grassroots organizations were left to pull a lot of weight in working with people *“who do not appear in government statistics, but who are actually there”* such as undocumented migrants and other marginalized groups.

Some respondents lamented how governmental COVID-19 responses focused heavily on groups that were vulnerable in terms of physical health status, such as the elderly. They felt the target groups they worked with, such as undocumented migrants, were not sufficiently considered in the ‘official’ responses, leaving grassroots organisations to pull the weight. One social at a local CSO branch stated: *“The government was busy with other things; nobody was thinking about our target group. Even though there is a very high risk there, and there are also chronic risk patients and so on. They said: ‘first we’re going to vaccinate the over-80s’. But what about people who live on the edge of society, so to speak? Who do not appear in your statistics, but who are actually there?”* Yet, other professionals noted that even though they often felt their target groups were perhaps not prioritised in governmental COVID-19 responses, they still felt seen and supported in their efforts to address the pandemic impact. A psychologist who established a CSO during the COVID-19 pandemic noted: *“I think that our social fabric has weathered the crisis relatively well thanks to a lot of government support measures. Had there been less, I think things would have been much worse. All kinds of organisations were given the chance to develop initiatives, for example around the theme of loneliness.”*

Another challenge addressed by community-level organizations was the waiting lists for secondary-level mental health services. Professionals working at this level often had to adopt a coaching approach, providing short-term support to help individuals cope with immediate concerns. A psychologist and founder of a local CSO explains: *“There are a lot of waiting lists, and that makes people lose perspective. So we say ‘OK, we can support you in the short term’. One to two or three conversations, to get to work with these people in a coaching way. ‘What is going well? What is going well? What can help you?’ It’s an intermediate step, and it’s a bit of a fire-fighting exercise. Because people have to wait for so long... We certainly do refer to secondary mental health services, but whether those people actually get help, that’s another story.”*

Despite the pre-existing and high number of waiting lists for professional support, many structural causes - that increased during the COVID-19 pandemic - were harder to resolve by mental health support and demand a more holistic and combined approach.

Culturally sensitive support

The interviews also highlight the importance of culturally sensitive support when dealing with the mental health impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. This includes awareness of the stigma surrounding mental health issues, which can impede support seeking. A psychologist and founder of a local CSO points out that *“many people are very ashamed of their situation”*, and might not seek social support from friends and family because *“it always has to go well for you, it is not OK if it goes badly for you”*. Assisting with structural challenges could provide an opening to discuss mental health issues, regardless of how someone might label them. One of the psychologists interviewed underlined that culturally sensitive support often requires a move away from *“the Western model of how psychopathology works”*, and being open to the different ways in which people make sense of their mental

health. Many community-level services represent the diversity of the neighbourhood, helping them to offer culturally sensitive care and support and overcome language barriers, as shown by this quote of a psychologist and founder of a local CSO:

“There are many people here in Borgerhout who do not speak the language and who cannot find their way in the services on offer. People really seek us out, because we work in a culturally sensitive way. [...] We have a Ghanaian working with us, we have Belgian people working with us, we have Moroccan, Turkish people working with us, so we are actually very diverse in our team. This means that we really reach the different target groups and can help them, because we are approachable and we know the language.”

Working with a multi-lingual team, sometimes including interpreters, was described as a key prerequisite for offering culturally sensitive services. Combined with organisations’ nuanced awareness of a broad spectrum of local needs and their flexible nature, this was considered a key strength of community-level initiatives.

Fragility and fragmentation

The second section of our report addresses the fragility and fragmentation of these local-level services and initiatives. We found that the COVID-19 crisis has created serious challenges related to:

- Physical accessibility of organizations' services and digitalisation
- Overloaded services and initiatives
- Widespread fragmentation and lack of oversight

Physical accessibility and digitalization

Community-level organizations and initiatives encountered significant challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic, with physical accessibility and digitalization being key issues. The closure of physical spaces and the increased reliance on digital platforms posed difficulties for both service users and providers.

Digitalization created additional barriers, especially for vulnerable groups who faced language barriers or lacked digital literacy. A social worker acknowledged, *“All this digitization is a very big threshold, and it is precisely that awareness that was not there. A very large number of people simply fall by the wayside.”* Many community-based organizations lacked the capacity to swiftly adapt to digital communication structures, resulting in limited access to services for certain individuals.

The pandemic underscored the importance of personal contact and face-to-face interaction with target groups. Organizations quickly realized that online communication was not a sufficient substitute. A coordinator of a local community centre emphasized, *“What has become clear to me is that even when things are complicated, when there are restrictive measures, personal contact must be maintained.”* The loss of personal contact had a profound impact on individuals, and finding ways to facilitate personal contact became a significant challenge for organizations.

The rapid digitalization required major adjustments in the operations of organizations, but many struggled due to lack of internal training and resources. A social-cultural worker highlighted the difficulties they faced, stating, *“Before we were able to work a bit with Zoom or with Teams - man, I think a year had passed. Of course, there are a few people in our organisation who were able to do it, but for others it was a disaster. Internally, let alone with our target group. If you work with vulnerable groups and with participatory projects, it is almost impossible to do.”* The importance of physical

presence and personal interaction in the community remained crucial, especially for reaching migrants and residents in Borgerhout and Antwerpen-Noord.

In conclusion, community-level organizations encountered obstacles related to physical accessibility and digitalization during the pandemic. While digital platforms offered some alternatives, they often fell short in meeting the needs of vulnerable groups. The significance of personal contact and face-to-face engagement became evident, emphasizing the importance of finding ways to maintain such connections. The pandemic exposed the digital divide and the need for adequate resources and training to ensure effective digital communication strategies.

Overloaded services and initiatives

The COVID-19 pandemic placed significant strain on local-level organizations and services, leading to increased workloads and overwhelming demands. With the closure or digitalization of other governmental services, community-level organizations became the primary source of support for many individuals. However, this sudden influx of requests, often outside of their regular scope of work, left many professionals feeling overwhelmed and powerless. As one social worker at a local CSO branch explained:

“A lot of organizations and social services were closed, so we saw a very high demand. Organizing access to healthcare is our organization's core business, but if a client says: 'I have received a reminder from the bailiff and there will be additional costs if I don't respond within fifteen days', then I'm not going to say: 'It's not my job to help you with that'. Of course, I will take that on.”

The increased workload not only encompassed the additional administrative burden but also the need for a holistic approach to mental health. One psychologist characterized prioritising supporting people in the short term, as *“an intermediate step, a bit of a fire-fighting exercise”*. Professionals recognized that they were unable to meet the needs of everyone seeking support, let alone those who did not reach out to their organizations. This led to a sense of powerlessness in addressing the underlying causes of mental health issues, as the quote below from a psychologist and founder of local CSO illustrates:

“If we really saw that it did not fall within our field of work and that we could not handle a question, we tried to refer people elsewhere. But it was hard, because everything was closed, everything was online... And for us it gave an enormous feeling of powerlessness because we couldn't find a way to help people.”

Widespread fragmentation and lack of oversight

The interviews conducted shed light on the challenges posed by fragmentation and lack of oversight within the available services, presenting barriers for both service users and providers. While some respondents noted increased collaboration among organizations during the COVID-19 crisis, the overall consensus was that significant fragmentation still exists. A psychologist highlighted the difficulty of fully grasping the range of available services:

“But the thing is, I don't know exactly what's out there... For example, I recently referred a mother with postnatal depression to an organization where I know they have Arabic-speaking staff, and she can go there with her baby to a support group and meet other mothers. So I thought that was good, but that was because I happened to have been there myself and I knew how it works.”

The need to bridge gaps and break down walls between organizations was a recurring theme among the respondents. Particularly when working with specific groups like migrant communities, establishing a collaborative network of partners with local expertise was deemed crucial. A coordinator of a local community centre emphasized the importance of focusing on facilitators and building bridges to overcome existing barriers: *"We need an increased focus on social work, on facilitators, on building bridges between different organizations. Because there are often walls and everyone just works within their own field, not looking beyond those walls."*

Two respondents mentioned working for organizations that share staff with different social and health agencies, enabling them to develop a comprehensive local network. However, this approach also presented organizational challenges, as individuals struggled to maintain focus when splitting their time across multiple teams. As one coordinator of a local psycho-social care organization branch explained: *"For example, they work in their home team for 9 hours and then another 9 hours with us. And there are people who get lost in that, they feel they can't focus enough when they are working here and there. We're still learning about how best to tackle that; it is a challenge."*

The locally-tailored nature of community-level organizations' work has both advantages and drawbacks, as it contributes to a fragmented landscape that is difficult to navigate and poses human resource challenges. While this issue predates the COVID-19 pandemic, its impact was further highlighted during the crisis when the everyday working realities of psycho-social care professionals were heavily disrupted.

2.2.6 Conclusions

The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the mental health of migrants residing in Antwerpen Noord and Borgerhout, as evidenced by previous studies (Allwood & Bell, 2020; Spiritus-Beerden et al., 2021). Social restrictions, loneliness, and the closure of support organizations contributed to poor mental health among migrants. Factors such as living alone, lack of internet access, and language barriers intensified the challenges of social isolation. Health concerns and the fear of contracting the virus had a detrimental effect on mental well-being, particularly among vulnerable individuals such as older adults and those with pre-existing health conditions. Economic repercussions, including job loss and financial worries, further impacted migrants' mental health, especially those lacking documentation or resident permits.

The pandemic further highlighted the digital divide, with limited language or computer skills hindering migrants' access to online resources and appointments. Inadequate housing conditions and the unequal distribution of affordable housing exacerbated mental health issues. Women, in particular, faced gendered challenges, including intensified care responsibilities and limited family support. The impact of these factors on mental well-being was evident in personal accounts shared during the interviews. The study thus reveals the diverse challenges faced by migrants, which emphasise the need for comprehensive support measures that address these intersecting factors at individual, interpersonal, community, and structural levels. Although many of the drivers of mental health impacts identified in the study were not unique to migrants, they were disproportionately experienced within this population.

Community-based organizations and initiatives demonstrated their unique value and indispensability in addressing mental health challenges during the pandemic. They displayed a deep understanding of local needs, offering culturally sensitive care and support. These organizations showed flexibility in adapting their services to changing needs and filling gaps left by other services and government

agencies. Their ability to adjust rapidly was facilitated by their smaller size and strong ties to the local community. They also played a crucial role in supporting vulnerable groups, including undocumented migrants, who were not adequately considered in official responses. However, the fragility and fragmentation of local-level services posed challenges, including physical accessibility, digitalization, and lack of oversight. Collaboration and coordination among organizations were crucial for addressing fragmentation and improving service provision. Bridging gaps between organizations and establishing collaborative networks with local expertise were identified as necessary steps. Additionally, improving physical accessibility and addressing the challenges posed by the digital divide were crucial for ensuring comprehensive support. Finally, it is also recognized that local organisations cannot fully address structural problems, such as housing, which require higher-level political interventions. A response solely centered on specialized mental health services would also not be sufficient to address these needs.

2.3 England, MDI

2.3.1 Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of effective and inclusive communication in mitigating the spread of the virus and promoting public health. However, minority communities, referred to as "hard-to-reach communities" by policy makers in England, face unique challenges in accessing and engaging with official government COVID-19 policies and communication efforts. This case study adopts a systems theory approach (Parsons 1970; Luhman et al 2013) 4 to examine the communication system within these communities. By looking at the interplay between government COVID-19 policies and their effects on "hard-to-reach communities" and considering the broader context of the pandemic, as well as the specific characteristics of these communities, the case study of England aims to contribute to our understanding of COVID-19 vulnerabilities and the role of in-group communication in responding to the pandemic crisis.

Systems theory provides a valuable framework for understanding the complex interactions and interdependencies between various components within the health system. Based on the idea that social systems can be analysed as complex networks of interdependent parts, and that these systems can be understood through the study of interaction between their parts – Government, NHS, media, communities - we can gain insights into the multifaceted nature of COVID-19 communication, the dynamics between government policies and minority communities. Scholars have been calling for greater attention to the questions of in-group communication within the context of crisis. The non-linear interactions and effective communication and self-organization within communities will be explored to investigate the importance of context in communicating on COVID-19. Effective communication has proven essential in disseminating crucial information about the COVID-19, however, minority communities have faced significant barriers in accessing and engaging with official government policies and communication efforts. Examining their experiences in getting the pandemic information has a potential to offer lessons that might have relevance in other, similar contexts. While the Government policies play a pivotal role in responding to the COVID-19 pandemic, including the implementation of lockdowns, social distancing measures, testing and vaccination campaigns, and the provision of information and resources, the effectiveness of these policies relies on their accessibility, inclusivity, and the extent to which they address the specific needs and challenges faced by various population groups.

In England, city councils use the term “hard to reach communities’ to describe ethnic and religious communities, and other minority communities who do not necessarily interact with wider community. Jones and Newburn (2016) introduced the term in one of policy reports pointing out that the term could be ‘misleading’ and ‘potentially stigmatizing’ but useful in investigating how particular characteristics of social sub-groups could be relied on in policy work. The term is widely used by local councils in England to identify groups which are difficult to engage with in terms of policy perspective “because they do not feel empowered to do so, or due to barriers which may be overcome”. (Haringey Council, 2021). The term ‘hard-to-reach communities’, problematic as it is, encompasses a diverse range of groups that face barriers in accessing and engaging with official government policies and their communication efforts. These communities may include people with limited English proficiency, low-income populations, rural communities, homeless individuals, and those with limited access to technology or healthcare facilities. The specific characteristics and challenges faced by these communities vary, but they share a common experience of marginalization and limited access to resources and information.

This case study is carried out by a team of researchers from the Media Diversity Institute (MDI), who have been engaged in projects aimed at understanding the complexities and challenges faced by marginalized communities. The case study examines the communication practices and experiences of these communities throughout three phases of the COVID-19 pandemic in England:

The first wave of COVID-19 is estimated to have started in March 2020, and concluded towards the end of May 2020 (UK Government, 2021). The second wave of COVID-19 in England was between 1 September 2020 to 22 May 2021 (UK Government, 2022). The third wave of COVID-19 in England was between 23 May 2021 to 10 December 2021 (UK Government, 2022).⁷

By identifying and analysing the communication challenges and experiences of these communities, we discuss and conceptualise the COVID-19 communication in terms of minority groups’ vulnerabilities during the public health crises.

Figure 8. MDI, England – SES Framework.

2.3.2 Purpose and Research Questions

The overarching objective of the case study is the identification of communication practices developed within minority groups named ‘hard-to-reach communities’ as a response and adjustment to pandemic adversity. In our case study, people are foregrounded, rather than subjects of examination – an approach that encourages research as action. The impact of COVID-19 and associated policy responses in our case study is significant. The rate of death involving COVID-19 was highest for the Black African group (3.7 times greater than for the White British group for males, and 2.6 greater for females), followed by the Bangladeshi (3.0 for males, 1.9 for females), Black Caribbean (2.7 for males, 1.8 for females) and Pakistani (2.2 for males, 2.0 for females) ethnic groups (UK Government 2021).

Combining journalistic and academic methods of interview (in-depth semi-structured conversation), visual ethnography, and thematic analysis, the project aims to assess the existing communication practices and assists in developing new forms of crisis communication that follow the idea of an inclusive society, society of all and for all.

Our case study is guided by the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** What communication channels hard-to-research communities relied on during COVID-19? (mainstream media, community media, billboards, public talks, GPs...)
- **RQ2:** What additional communication channels these communities developed during COVID-19?
- **RQ3:** What are the main characteristics of alternative communication channels (origins, people involved, frequency of posts, interactivity, number of people involved, links with the external news sources?)

Our case study provides an in-depth understanding of the COVID-19 communication, its constitutive processes, and the actors involved (following on Gagnon 2011). It describes and explains communicative practices related to crisis communication in order to generate a set of factors that might be useful for examining communicative strategies that could be developed for dealing with a pandemic or more broadly global crises.

2.3.3 Method

The approach in this case study is two-folded: instead of searching for a representative sample of minoritized communities and trying to go through every ethnicity and every religion in England, we conducted interviews with people who had a story to tell and who belonged to a minority community. Identification and selection of storytellers was based both on the researchers’ engagement with the community and on the relevance of specific individuals with some level of agency as members of minority communities.

Deploying journalistic methodology in academic research has been practiced in creative disciplines as practice-led research, where the professional practice and its outcome becomes a vehicle of inquiry and a ground for examination of the logic of social phenomena (Crotty 1998)⁹. Although journalists rarely admit, interviews used to collect facts and views are semi-structured: before approaching the interviewee the reason for an interview and the nature of the conversation to come has been carefully planned. Similarly, in academic research semi-structured interviews are based on a set of broad planned interview questions that are usually explained to interviewees in advance. Those questions were then refined, elaborated, and extended during the interview. This type of conversation “allows

people to answer more on their own terms than the standardized interview permits, but still provides a greater structure for comparability” (May 2001, p.111).

Purposive sampling was used and 31 interviews were made, using phone, email and face to face. The interviewer had some relationship established with participants prior to the data gathering process, paying attention to variables of gender, religion, ethnicity, age, and community role within minoritized (“hard-to-reach communities”) in England. It was found that saturation for these qualitative interviews was reached with the sample of the 31 participants.

Ethical considerations were observed at all times by the researcher throughout the interviewing process. Since an essential component of this study involved a direct rapport with interviewees belonging to minority groups and weighting their opinions, much emphasis was placed in carefully following ethical principles when working with these groups.

Qualitative research methods involving direct contact with respondents, such as semi-structured interviewing, emphasize the need to protect the interviewees’ interest and to communicate to them transparently and professionally the nature and purpose of the research (Ryen 2004). This was carried out at all times by the research team.

The thirty-one interviewees offered their individual consent to participate in the research – this was done in the form of an explicit oral confirmation before each interview began. Also, the rationale of the interview was explained to all participants prior to their engagement in the recordings.

Every interview was video-recorded, lasting approximately one hour each. Video interviews with members of various diversity focused on experiences of covid by asking questions such as here did they get their information from, how they counter misinformation, how they communicate among themselves, what actions do they take, what impact they consider to be the most significant in terms of social isolation, time spent indoors, and the disruption of everyday life. Questions were refined by members of the research team, based on the expert or scholarly literature reviewed. Field notes were taken too. The interviewees were not interested in reading the transcript. Some were interested in seeing the short videos, and MDI will provide these to them.

These interviews are transcribed, coded, and thematically analysed. Subject to the interviewee’s agreement, and in line with the main results of the academic investigation, the video interviews will be edited and turned into a video story for publicizing on the project website.

2.3.4 Results: Data Reporting

Figure 9. MDI, England – Coding Tree.

2.3.5 Results: Analysis and Interpretation

The theoretical framework and existing literature informed to an important degree the themes by which the interview questions were designed, and the way the data gathered was organised for analysis. The thematic strands or codes that were defined in this study were not destined to measure quantitative data, instead their central purpose was to support the qualitative organising and analysis of the interviewees' opinions and views, in alignment with the research questions. Thus, three main thematic strands were elaborated:

- Communication channels, strategies, and patterns;
- Communication changes during different timepoints of the pandemic;
- Vulnerability, trust, and attributes.

Communication patterns, strategies, and channels

Under this thematic strand this study seeks to assess how members of minority communities in England used (or not) specific channels of communication, what alternative channels they developed, what characterised alternative communication channels, and which strategies they developed when using various sources of information and communication in relation to the pandemic.

The interviews revealed that information gathering and dissemination about COVID among minority communities was obtained in hybrid and diverse ways, resorting from a vast array of communication sources, mainstream media and trusted professionals or experts. It can be implied that in addition, majority used social media, mostly WhatsApp, and video-telephoning platform Zoom as the main source of consuming and circulating information about the pandemic. However, information from mainstream British media, regional English media, international outlets, institutional or governmental messages, word of mouth from community leaders and other members, were all consumed and exchanged constantly among minority communities. It is worth noting that public health sites such as those belonging to the National Health Service (NHS) and the Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE) were used to some extent, whereas alternative or non-mainstream broadcast and podcasts were hardly used.

Some interviewees argued that this pattern of using and consuming information about the pandemic was, partly, an organic and secure manner to make sense of what was happening, to obtain reliable guidelines to deal with the pandemic, and to reduce the risk of misinformation. This, arguably, can be summed up in the opinion of an interviewee:

“People were getting information from many sources. We had to make sure that people didn't get the wrong information... It was important to check the usual media [mostly mainstream media, such BBC News], but also several other media, from the hospital radio to the Internet.”

It can be argued that most members from these communities, based on their answers, relied on multiple channels of communication during the COVID crisis. Just as importantly, they elaborated organic strategies to establish networks between members of the community, family members abroad, and local organisations – faith or religious based – and authorities. “There was intense local community action during the pandemic”, said an interviewee.

Another participant expressed a similar idea in general strategic proceeding: “It was about capturing all that information and making those relationships [between community members] still live on beyond pandemic, beyond COVID, because there's safety in numbers... It was about getting those

networks going and keeping them alive as well as the databases". Indeed, the vast majority of interviewees expressed having been part of communitarian networks, which were mostly set up during the pandemic, and that such networks played a crucial role in seeking expert and professional opinions, exchanges reliable data, encouraging specific medical or health actions among the public, and reinforcing a sense of communitarian belonging.

It is worth stressing that trusted professionals – including experts in the area of social health, medicine, social services, council authorities, and carers – were consulted in an almost systematic manner and many worked jointly with some minority communities. Faith and community leaders were consulted and used as part of agents of expert data – albeit not as much as the type of professionals previously mentioned.

Many of the interviewees, when asked about their communication uses and strategies in obtaining reliable information about the pandemic resorted more to local or national channels, social media, professionals, and less so to official government information. Part of this, some interviewees mentioned, was possibly the product of then PM Boris Johnson's alleged lack of connection and reliability as a leader when dealing with the pandemic. However, most participants were of the view that, as minority communities – often with [English] language barriers and because of specific cultural practices – they tended to use and rely more on other community members or professionals who disseminated information from various sources – including some for other countries – that belonged, at least partly, to mainstream media in various formats.

A significant number of interviewees mentioned that, although some individuals who identified themselves as leaders of faith or cultural communities, often were unable to offer adequate guidance through which to navigate the hardships caused by the pandemic. This was mostly a reflection of a lack of knowledge of their community's needs and limited communicational skills. As expressed by one participant: "many so-called faith leaders or community media spokespeople would meet dignitaries if they visited the city, but often they really don't have a clue about what's going on in their own communities". This, in some cases, forced some community members to identify professionals who, as explained by an interviewee, "would have genuine on-the-ground information about how their places of worship, their community centres, their schools would be responding to government instructions regarding the pandemic."

Some nuance could be added to these critical views. For example, around half of the respondents mentioned cases in which in some places of worship, under the auspices of faith leaders, informative assistance was offered to both congregation and non-congregation members. For example, some religious establishments in cities across England offered open assistance in terms of communication guidance to anyone who lived in the neighbourhood or area regardless of their ethnicity, religious or cultural background.

Five examples of faith-based initiatives that decided to operate beyond a limited informative role were mentioned by some interviewees. Arguably, a case that mirrors this well, as expressed by an interviewee, is the Jain Health Initiative in England, where "about 32-odd organisations in the Jain community came together to start health promotion around COVID and increase the vaccine uptake". This health initiative, according to the same source, elaborated a plan where people of scientific backgrounds came together, researched, and disseminated scientific-based information about COVID in both Gujarati and English language in order to communicate effectively factual and reliable content with the community.

Interviewees expressed some ambivalence towards the role of local councils and the NHS in disseminating in a clear and inclusive manner key information about COVID pandemic, vaccination, medical assistance, and general guidance. However, it was found that both the NHS and local councils provided a more trusted and widely used source of information via multiple media platforms compared to, for example, certain data published on social media or reproduced notifications by the Prime Minister or Cabinet members in mainstream media.

Some members of the ‘hard to reach communities’ resorted to translated versions of information provided by the NHS and city councils. This group of interviewees expressed the need to seek professional and well-informed opinions and, importantly, for this to be translated to the language of their community. As one participant explained: “the city council reached out to the community leaders, aware that minority communities were dying of the virus more, and they were not having the vaccination”. There were various cases mentioned where city councils reached out to people of the minority community, sought its leaders or some spokesperson, and asked them to work with them in translating key messages and information regarding the pandemic and the vaccination. An interviewee expressed that this liaison was “a great way of reaching out”. Another example of this is charted well by another participant: “in the West Midlands we had someone from the council, who was giving us monthly meetings via Zoom with information at the West Midlands level, and also we had a different channel from a local authority, Coventry, that we were sharing [information] with as a community.”

Regarding the information from the NHS, a slight majority of interviewees was of the opinion that this was, indeed, useful, yet often not sufficient, needed to be expanded, and at times translated to specific minority community languages. A community leader said: “I would always relate back to the NHS people that I was in touch with, to the information they gave, and then work with this together with the city council team and the community”. Another interviewee stated that “when the NHS texted you on the phone to get your vaccine, many people just didn’t understand that... it seemed to them a simple hello from the NHS. So, the NHS could have been clearer, give more detail, do a little bit better”.

There appears to be a pattern among most interviewees to suggest that the NHS was always informative, and its channels of communication were acknowledged and consulted; yet they tended to require a “mediator” of sorts, a translator. The latter appeared to emerge mostly from the various minority communities, and at times – albeit not in all cases – in liaison with members of specific city councils. This proved to be a decisive component of the new communication strategies to emerge during the pandemic among these communities in England. The relevance of translation work can be highlighted in this participant’s example: “I would translate NHS messages, short messages, in my language and send this to the Urdu and Punjabi communities. We also made fifteen videos and sent them to our communities via social media, reaching around 26,000 people and encouraging them to get the COVID vaccine.” According to the vast majority of the interviewees, the language translation – an initiative of many community members – played a crucial role as communication agent among minority communities during the pandemic and could be considered a sign of both collaborative effort and resilience in times of crisis.

Communication changes during different timepoints of the pandemic

Under this thematic strand questions are asked about how communication and messages changed within minority communities in the nation over the course of the pandemic. Here, there are three main timepoints: pre-pandemic, pre-vaccine, and post-vaccine, with tributary ones added – as they emerged and were coded from the interviews. It is worth noting that, in the participants’ perceptions and

answers, there can be some slight overlapping in terms of the understanding of the different timepoints.

Pre-pandemic

From the accounts of most interviewees, before the pandemic – prior to February and mid-March 2020 – some mainstream media was used by members of the minority communities to become informed about news events locally and globally. The first coverage about the COVID pandemic was seen and/or heard via mainstream media. Yet, the initial reaction for most people was, to paraphrase one interviewee, that this “was happening in China and that for someone living in England it was out there somewhere and [we] needed not to worry about it”. At the time, social media was used mostly for other purposes, according to interviewees, and hardly for exchanging information about issues of pandemics or medical or social health. Many members of community groups with ties to nations geographically near China – including India – also expressed similar views.

In the Chinese community of England, however, it became evident soon after the outbreak of COVID in Wuhan City that this was a health crisis of global proportions and that it was escalating in a very fast way. Moreover, and as explained by a Chinese interviewee, there was concern within their community that in the UK the government was not producing and disseminating responsible and reliable information about the spread of COVID and the risks it entailed for the wider society. According to the opinion of some interviewees, some minority communities in England began taking actions – including creating initial communication networks for circulation and exchange of information – towards the pandemic crisis. This represented yet another strategic shift in communitarian communication, and could be briefly summarized in the following account: “By the end of February [2020], weeks before any lockdown measures were taken by the British government, we had decided that it was time to shut down the Zoroastrian Centre, especially because our demographics are such that we do have an elderly population... so, we officially shut down before the government had even suggested it”. Similarly, another interviewee noted that their community, having experienced a previous pandemic in Asia, were aware that the spread of the COVID virus represented a real threat. Yet, in January 2020, the UK government spokesperson said that the risk of the virus was low. This interviewee added “The government’s policies and communications [regarding COVID] were, at first, very slow and a bit confusing.”

A majority of interviewees agree with this view. Many coincide with the idea that the governmental and institutional communication regarding the virus and its pandemic character was not clear enough for their communities when the first cases of people with COVID in England emerged. The alleged lack of clarity in official communication, slowness in conveying governmental policies for social health actions, and the general uncertainty about (mis)information circulating created a general state of social anxiety among members of these communities. In the months right before cases of COVID were first registered in England, “people were very anxious because it’s like: what’s happening with our lives? ... day by day we’re hearing this, we’re hearing that, but nothing is really changing”, according to a participant. A few other interviewees expressed that in this time (first wave of COVID, in February and March 2020) young members of the community seemed to be most confused in terms of the scale of the pandemic and how they should act or (not) engage socially.

On the other hand, older members of the community seemed to struggle to come to terms with the information produced and exchanged. This, as per the interviewees, was closely related to issues of limited media and IT literacy and of weak level of English. This situation can be exemplified by the

following comment of an older member of the Pakistani community: “Many of us, over 70-year-olds, did not know how to connect with people through social media or the Internet... then slowly, very slowly, watching Facebook, Zoom links, YouTube, we got some technical knowhow... but this took some time”. This person also expressed that help was offered by their family and community members in assisting with technological skills and understanding social media platforms and video technology, such as WhatsApp and Zoom, respectively.

Pandemic outbreak and pre-vaccine

Most of the interviewees’ opinions offer an idea that there was confusion among most minority community members in the early stages of the pandemic, which was between February and mid-March 2020 but before COVID vaccines became available in England in mass scale.

The confusion, according to many accounts, originated from various factors. One was the apparent lack of clear and accessible information about the outbreak and vaccination from media outlets at the time. Another factor was the surge – mostly in social media – of different narratives around the pandemic and the COVID vaccines, many of which were speculative at best, and informative dysfunctions in their worst forms. Misinformation or disinformation about the nature, process and effects of the vaccination became more prevalent, and this led to confusion among many members of the groups studied.

A third factor was the initial polarization of opinions – often by community leaders, but mainly via the media – regarding medical, religious and cultural discussions around the pandemic, and particularly about being vaccinated or not. “Once there was the outbreak of COVID in England” – as explained by an interviewee – “it became hard to be specific in terms of advice on what we do when there is so much uncertainty even about the virus... the opinions are divided, [in England] the only way that division of opinion is conveyed through the popular media is through sensationalising the two extreme views on this”. Similar accounts about the tabloid media’s unethical take on the pandemic, its misinformation and bias were recurrent among some interviewees – especially after the first calls for vaccination were made by the British authorities and health institutions.

In this phase, starting after March 2020, the UK government did very little to present a clear communicational agenda – as well as a political one – about the outbreak of the pandemic in the nation. As recalled by a participant of this study: “on the one hand we had [Prime Minister] Boris shaking hands with everyone, and on the other the first person dying of COVID here [in Great Britain] ... and some media quoting some doctors who were advising not to shake hands, to wash hands in this way, to keep distance with other people”. Incongruencies such as these, as disseminated in some media outlets and more so via social media, reinforced the sense of uncertainty about the nature of the pandemic and the actions people should take. According to some accounts, social media significantly magnified these incongruencies and contradictory stances. One interviewee said that they, as a family group, “desperately tried to stay off social media to avoid all the myths about the pandemic and personally trying to debunk a lot of the daft [misinformation] nonsense that was going round.”

Part of this confusion, perpetuated by certain narratives in different media formats, was reflected in members of these communities carrying out COVID tests and having the vaccine. As explained by a participant: “When the first injection came, the first jab they were a little bit worried, what are the reaction? What if I have it and then something happens, the doctors don’t come to see me or I can’t go to the doctor, what happens then?... I was very unsure about the vaccine, and the same happened

to many in my community”. It is of note that, according to some interviewees, some religious leaders were hesitant about recommending the vaccination. This position, it was argued, emanated mostly from cultural and religious beliefs, but was also fed by specific narratives propagated by some online publishers globally.

One interviewee mentioned that these religious leaders had particular influence over the older population of minority communities, but that most younger adults decided to obtain more precise and reliable information from other sources. Such data was obtained, partly, from social media which allegedly resorted to scientific and/or medical reports, and more so from mainstream media that broadcast or published guidelines and reports by medical and health professionals. Some of these initiatives – in few cases – became systematized and managed to incorporate some trusted professionals, medical doctors, and health scientists. A member of the Jain community explained that some fellow members sought the assistance of “specialists and started to really work on getting the vaccine message across, really addressing the hesitancy amongst vaccine uptake, and really explaining what was going on with COVID.”

Lockdown and post-vaccine

Compared to the pre-vaccine period, during lockdown and while many people in England began taking vaccination against COVID – a time frame which includes part of what has been defined as the first wave of COVID, all of the second wave (September 2020 to May 2021), and beyond – almost all interviewees agree that their communities gradually gained more trust in the media-produced communications about the pandemic and were able to develop communitarian networks to exchange and discuss information, much of which was initially provided by mainstream media while resorting to expert sources, such as medical experts, health authorities and institutions, and government spokespeople.

However, a minority of interviewees mentioned that, overall, communication about the vaccination effects and some lockdown rules could have been made clearer by government and NHS channels. As one respondent explains, “there was a lot of people feeling like they were being forced to take the vaccination, rather than it being a choice... on Twitter you’d see [messages], when the NHS text you to say ‘get your vaccine’ and people just didn’t understand that, [some people thought] it was a simple ‘hello’ from the NHS or took it as a joke”.

A slight majority argue that community groups of minority ethnic and religious background sought to create a well-informed view about the vaccine and its benefits. They began promoting this information in community spaces – mainly in temples and churches – and mostly through social media. In many cases, the liaison with professionals, local authorities and translators to other languages was key to producing messages that sought medical expertise and media accuracy, credibility, and transparency. A member of the Hindu community explained that “once the vaccines were available, we spread out the positive word towards the vaccine and we encouraged our old and the young generation to go forward and to take the jabs”. This person also explained that some members of the community were hesitant to take the vaccine, yet were later convinced once they read or listened to the newly-produced information and appreciated the rigour of the medical evidence and the anecdotal information that the messages produced by community members conveyed.

A factor that arguably contributed to people of these communities to further understand the urgency and complexity of the COVID crisis was their exposure to broadcast images of lockdown in the UK and globally. This, according to three interviewees, helped reinforce the idea of the pandemic’s severity

and the need to follow specific lockdown rules. Here, mainstream media was of much relevance to inform about the pandemic issues at both local and global scales, while highlighting the new government measures to stay safe during lockdown and continue taking the required number of vaccinations.

Some interviewees said that the hybrid or mixed use of mainstream media, trusted professionals and community leaders, online exchanges among community members, and social media gradually helped dissipate wrongly informed ideas about the pandemic, vaccinations and lockdown, ultimately creating a more auspicious setting for rational discussion among community members. One participant explained that “many people wanted to know more about the vaccination, and not just be treated as a number and just, you know, they wanted to have all the right information so couldn’t make that decision... and we gradually managed that”. For this to happen, most interviewees concur, it became crucial for the community to have access to and be able to process as much accurate and factual information as possible. “When we ran the Zoom sessions [with community members], during the interval between the first vaccine and the second vaccine rollout and all of that changing overnight, it was just a tremendous amount of information that you needed to be on top of... Many of us did that work, we stayed up to date with what was going on, with the information about COVID”, said an interviewee.

Still, some elders needed assistance from their family or community members to come to terms with the rules and nature of lockdown. Here, again, the role of translated information was crucial. The latter was usually carried out by local members of the community. Additionally, personal isolation was a factor that affected many, particularly those older people living on their own. This was mentioned by various interviewees.

More than half of those interviewed are of the opinion that efforts were made to create a communication network among community members with the partial aim to fight negative isolation and, together, share experiences of lockdown and remain in communication. Creative initiatives began to emerge for these purposes: from amplifying chats in social media – mostly via WhatsApp – to elaborating online groups with members of the community to play games.

An example that can illustrate this, as explained by a participant: “we recorded a film, obviously with consent and everything else, of children communicating with their grandparents to look after themselves... Because the grandparents were in isolation in their houses and away from their grandchildren... So, the message of looking after your health to the grandparent, that was communicated through young people”. Another online platform that was used during lockdown by a significant portion of interviewees was Zoom. In this sense, a member of the Bahá’í community expressed that “the number of activities being held in the community increased quite markedly during the lockdown period, because some people would want to have an event in their house but, instead, they could then act as the host of something taking place on Zoom.”

From the opinions gathered it seems that online platforms or publishers, telephone apps, online chat and video tools played an important role during lockdown as communication technologies to reinforce a sense of solidarity and companionship within the community while also providing the possibility to exchange punctual information about the pandemic.

Vulnerability, trust, and attributes

This thematic strand gathers and assesses the vulnerabilities within minority communities studied that lead to significant impact of COVID, as well as some strengths highlighted by the communities when facing the challenges brought forth by the pandemic.

Vulnerabilities

Most of the participants of this study were of the view that members of minority communities in England face social, economic, and cultural disadvantages or vulnerabilities. These were exponentially magnified – and made more visible to them – with the COVID pandemic and the crisis it represented and still represents.

Observing the responses and opinions, one can argue that five types of vulnerabilities predominated. These are:

- language barrier
- limited digital skills
- media literacy
- health and social conditions, and
- education

Many members of these communities are non-native English speakers. Moreover, some have scant command of the English language. During the pandemic, according to most accounts, the use of non-English languages became crucial – especially among the elderly – to navigate media content, understand key information about COVID and lockdown rules, and exchange ideas and views with others.

In this sense, one interviewee argued that “people here [in England] have to communicate in different languages, to different community groups, across all media platforms”, and that after the pandemic it would be ideal to take on board “a lesson” and have information published and broadcast, in an accessible manner, in these different languages, so that “people can access the content really quickly.” During the pandemic in England, translators – the bulk of which were volunteers – played a most significant role as communication agents and as community assistants. Various testimonies of the work of voluntary or communitarian translators during the pandemic were gathered. Here is one of many: “As part of the [health] campaign, I did a bit of work on radio talking in Gujarati addressing on the local Indian radio stations in and around England, talking about vaccine, putting the government’s message out in languages that were understandable... Of course, we gave the opportunity for people to ask questions and to say ‘I don’t understand this’, ‘how do I do that?’ and explaining it in really simple everyday language.”

While language was arguably the main barrier for some community members to access information during the pandemic, the different (non-Western) education and scant digital skills also proved to be significant limitations, according to many accounts. Here, again, it was the elderly that experienced hardships when trying to process and understand certain statistical data offered by mainstream or social media, while also struggling with use of certain Internet and digital technological devices and applications. The pandemic, as mentioned earlier, brought to the foreground a surge in the use of video telephoning and online chatting – many older members of these community had never used this technology and lacked the media literacy skills to operationalise them. Importantly, it became

problematic for this demographic group to access online media and be able to virtually assist religious worship and have conversation with their spiritual leaders or mentors.

Two interviewees mentioned that young members of the community assisted with Internet and online technology those that had scarce knowledge. “It wasn’t such a problem for the youngsters because they have IT skills”, said one participant. Another added: “Because the elderly people are not used to Zoom, they can’t even use iPhones, I started a WhatsApp group called [spoken in a foreign language], the garden of Jesus, Gethsemane... they were really happy because with WhatsApp you don’t have to type, you can leave voice messages.” According to most views, the most used online/video platforms or publications were Facebook, Zoom and WhatsApp – the latter being more used than the others. These same interviewees, as well as four more, mentioned that most of the adult community members quickly learnt to use Zoom, MS Teams, WhatsApp and to carry out online conversations with smartphones, facetimeing.

An important vulnerability among some members of these groups, as expressed by certain interviewees, was the clash of their social practices and lifestyles, with the set of government policies and new laws imposed during the pandemic. In this sense, a problem that was highlighted was the fact that some members of these communities live in frail and vulnerable – at times hostile – environments. Here, some interviewees resorted to first-hand experiences but also cited government documents and reports which shed a light on the delicate issues of overcrowding, dysfunctional family setups, alcoholism and substance addiction, physical and mental health issues. These, according to some opinions, were magnified during the pandemic, and the victims generally struggled to find effective assistance from the authorities or other institutions and communication was restricted mostly due to the lockdown rules.

Similar accounts were expressed by an interviewee from the Caribbean and one from Southern Asia. The latter explained that “we have an ageing population in the South Asian communities [living in England]. We have social issues, we have overcrowding, a big number of people living in one household in a heavily built area. Many of these people, because of the nature of job they do, they could not work from home. So, during the lockdown those people had to go into work... facing many risks.”

Trust and attributes

In the data gathered during the interviewing process it became evident that key factors in the use of media and elaboration of communication strategies by these groups, were issues of:

- trust in outlets and/or sources;
- reliability in the information disseminated and consumed;
- non-bias and consistency in the media content propagated;
- misinformation.

Most interviewees argued that the biggest challenge in terms of trusting media content and using it during the pandemic was its factuality, accuracy, timeliness, and precision. In other words, its ‘truthfulness’. With the surge of a new type of misinformation in the last decade or so, distinguishing what is factual and verifiable media content can be a complex task – these minority communities were no exception.

Many respondents mentioned the challenges they faced when trying to decipher the veracity of some (mis)information or ‘news myths’ – as some called them – they read or heard. As explained by one of

them: “You had Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp... people were sending messages... But you do not know the authenticity of these messages coming through WhatsApp and YouTube and Facebook. If they match well with the information we already had, I will use it or forward it to my friends or other people on WhatsApp, and if I find it’s not true news I will stop it, block it there... but this was not always easy”. Another interviewee explained that if social media such as WhatsApp is saying [something] but the data shows this is not correct... I would not pay attention. Or if somebody had posted something a bit silly, I would privately message them back and say, ‘this is not quite correct, please don’t send it to anyone else.’”

According to various accounts, members of the community organised themselves, often with the assistance of religious leaders and facilities, to check and verify information about the pandemic – especially about the vaccine, as some people were hesitant in taking it – and only if factual, accurate and balanced they would disseminate it within the community. At times this meant challenging certain views of local religious authorities, as expressed by an interviewee: “We heard some time in London some of the pastors were not in favour of people should get the vaccine. So, messages like this need to be stopped, because God also has given us the mind and the brain, facilities to use them for our benefit and benefit of the community.” Most of the participants that talked about challenging misinformation and ‘media myths’ about the vaccines and the pandemic, said it was a difficult task, particularly when it came to discussing the speculative and fake narratives created about the effects of the vaccines. They worked both individually and collectively in strategically debunking these misleading views, finding factual and verifiable information, and disseminating it face to face or via social media.

The reliability, timeliness, consistency, and credibility of the information about COVID – according to most participants – depended on the sources consulted. Hence, as many argued, it was imperative to read, listen, watch, consume content from media outlets or digital sites that were trustworthy. Many found unreliable content about the pandemic circulating in social media and, less often, in the tabloid press. Yet, most British Tv news outlets and broadsheet newspapers presented information that resorted to experts on the field on health and medicine, and which was factual, reliable and could be verified. One interviewee said that what one typically found was “that the papers that are coming out have obviously taken months of research from hospitals to combine. So, when we’re treating patients in a hospital you’ve got to take the evidence based on stuff that we know works, what we’re seeing day to day.”

Four interviewees said that together with community members, they began to identify which sources or information actors were reliable and which should not be trusted. Also, they took note of the expert sources used, the periodicity in which they continuously produced factual content, and the way this information circulated – be it via broadcast, print, or in digital format.

By most accounts, the constant misinformation and newly-created ‘myths’ – religion-based or otherwise – contributed to creating and perpetuating a state of general fear and anxiety among society but given their condition of vulnerability and underrepresentation, this affected minority communities significantly. As one interviewee explained: There was much fear mongering with some false information... there were misconceptions around how the vaccine or this disease were, people saying that [the pandemic] was a way that God was punishing us”. Similarly, some believed the communicational strategies of the government did not help to minimize this fear among these communities. On the contrary. Many found the government’s messages regarding the pandemic, new

rules and guidelines confusing at best. “There was a lot of fear and uncertainty, and just not enough information from the government, their messages weren’t so clear.

Importantly, much of the precise, timely, accurate information at times proved to be overwhelming for many members of these communities. Particularly, they argued, statistics showing the death toll due to COVID in England, the way the viral contagion was fast advancing, the many struggles the NHS was facing and hardship front-line workers were facing, the economic and financial effects of lockdown for most in the nation, impossibility to travel, etc.

Some interviewees expressed that an additional factor to the surge of social fear was that, as members of minority and underrepresented communities, many were apprehensive about not being taken into consideration. Not only in terms of medical or health assistance, but also in terms of being considered by the media and other powerful institutions as citizens and residents that require inclusive media and adequate, accessible communication – one that they can relate to culturally and that reflects their visibility as part of the fabric of England.

2.3.6 Conclusions

The high diversity of what is commonly and mistakenly referred to as 'hard-to-reach communities' is evident in this study. This diversity is reflected in the different information-gathering strategies and the importance that various sources (for example, the church) have taken in different communities and groups. However, it is clear that much of the communication, particularly regarding specific behavioural strategies, typically requires an intermediary within the community who not only provides trust but also decodes the message clearly. The importance of such 'decoders' is fundamental in the risk communication and behaviour advising strategies in minority communities and should always be part of public health strategy.

2.4 Germany, SINUS & Sweden, UGOT

2.4.1 Introduction

The overall purpose of this case study is to strengthen society's resilience to future pandemics – or similar crises – by studying information-gathering behaviour, communication behaviour, and willingness to comply with health-protective measures and vaccination policies among vulnerable groups in society. Specifically, the case study identifies ethnic minorities living in socially and economically vulnerable neighbourhoods in Sweden and Germany as groups that are vulnerable to both the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and the “infodemic” that has accompanied it. The focus of the study is on information-seeking and communication behaviour.

The study is based on comparative interview data (semi-structured personal interviews) collected in Sweden and Germany. Fieldwork has been conducted in Gothenburg, Sweden and Mannheim, Germany. Interviews were conducted in Swedish and German or in English. Qualitative interview data were compared to results from previously-collected nationally representative survey data in both countries, thus applying a multi-methodological approach. Results from interview and survey data were used to develop policy guidelines and recommendations for best practices.

The more specific objectives of the study were to identify what media (local, national, international, social media) and means of communication ethnic minorities in Gothenburg and Mannheim have used to inform themselves about the COVID-19 pandemic, to identify misconceptions about protective

measures and vaccines among ethnic minorities in Gothenburg and Mannheim, to study the impact of communicative behaviour among ethnic minorities in Gothenburg and Mannheim on vaccination willingness and adaption to protective measures, and to study how information seeking and communication among ethnic minorities in Gothenburg and Mannheim differ from communicative behaviour in the majority society.

Figure 10. SINUS, Germany & UGOT, Sweden – SES Framework.

2.4.2 Purpose and Research Questions

The present case study focuses on information seeking among ethnic minorities in Mannheim, Germany and Gothenburg, Sweden, specifically in relation to the implementation of protective measures and vaccination willingness.

The primary research questions are as follows:

- RQ1. What communication strategies and practices have local government, health authorities and stakeholders implemented to inform ethnic minorities about protective measures and vaccines?
- RQ2. What sources/where have ethnic minorities/socio-economic vulnerable groups searched for information about protective measures, and vaccines?
- RQ3. What protective measures, including vaccination, have ethnic minorities/socio-economic vulnerable groups implemented to protect themselves from infection?
- RQ4. To what extent are there misconceptions about protective measures and vaccines among ethnic minorities/socio-economic vulnerable groups?
- RQ5. Are there mismatches between residents' and local stakeholders' understandings of the pandemic and the accompanying "infodemic"?

2.4.3 Method

The case study was conducted by researchers at University of Gothenburg (Sweden) and SINUSMarkt- und Sozialforschung GmbH (Germany). For details on the research teams, please see the relevant COREQ tables.

The target population on which the case study focused was women and men with low socio-economic status, with and without a migration background (defined as the participant or at least one parent having been born outside the country of residence), living in the neighbourhoods of Östra Bergsjön and Hjällbo, Gothenburg and Neckarstadt-West, Schönau, and Jungbusch/Innenstadt, Mannheim. These neighbourhoods were chosen due to their comparatively high percentage of persons with a migration background and their comparatively poor performance on socio-economic indicators vis-a-vis municipal and national averages.

The samples consisted of N=6 women and N=6 men in Gothenburg, and N=14 women and N=4 men in Mannheim. The imbalance in the German sample was due to unanticipated difficulty recruiting male participants. Participants were recruited via intermediaries such as civil society organisations, as well as via snowball sampling.

Interview guides were designed including questions to guide the interviews. Different guides were used for interviews with citizens and institutional actors. Each guide contains a beginning section with a brief explanation of the project to be provided to the interviewee prior to the interview, without going into details so as to not bias their answers. Official consent forms and project's info sheets were also administered.

The interviews were recorded, transcribed, and anonymised, then analysed using the qualitative data analysis program QDA Miner v5.0.35 (Provalis Software). Structural codes were applied in accordance with the interview guide flow, while thematic codes were applied based on the interview contents.

2.4.4 Results: Data reporting

Figure 11. Germany, SINUS & UGOT, Sweden – Coding Tree.

The Codebook with the categories and subcategories that emerged from the interviews can be found in Appendix B, Annex 4.1. The SES framework compared and integrated with these codes can be consulted in Appendix B, Annex 4.2.

2.4.5 Results: Analysis and Interpretation

A brief description of the major case study findings follows.

Legacy media as main or only channel

A central aspect of crisis communication is how citizens seek information, which sources they use and how they are evaluated. Even in a high-choice media environment saturated with social media, legacy (or traditional) news media plays an important role in how citizens inform themselves about the crisis, how things develop and which action is needed for self-protection.

The interviews show a variety of traditional media use where limitations due to life conditions are prevalent, for example when managing the daily life puzzle, radio news becomes central to receive information about the pandemic as expressed by one interviewee *“I don't have time for newspapers, because in the morning I have to make sure that my children are dressed, and then the running starts”* [Female, Mannheim, from Kosovo]. Others choose news channels due to accessibility, where no cable-tv access or even a television set limit their media use. However, many other voices point out the usage of a variety of traditional news media, both tv and newspapers (online and offline). This perspective can be illustrated by a Somali woman from Gothenburg: *“Yes, we read Aftonbladet, SVT, Göteborgs Posten. Like this, different ones. [...] Somali channels I have watched. We mostly watch Swedish when we are here”* [Female, Gothenburg from Somalia].

Accessibility to news due to language issues are also mentioned frequently. There are experiences of news orienting towards foreign news media because of language issues, but some also combine foreign and national news media. This tension between news orientations is captured in one quote from a woman living in a Swedish suburb with Somali background where she describes a discussion between her and her husband who listens to Somali news and she argues they should orient themselves toward Swedish news sources instead.

“We listened mostly to the news. My husband listened mostly to the Somali news. I said you don't need to listen there. Aftonbladet [Swedish online tabloid], the news, regular morning news, read on, what is it called, this care centre. What is it called? Not 1177 but... somewhere.”
[Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia]

Media fatigue

Events affecting major parts of the public - such as the COVID-19 pandemic - tend to receive extensive attention, both in traditional news media and in social media. Moreover, if they are extended over a long period of time - as the pandemic was - they will dominate the news flow. Individuals may feel overwhelmed and exhausted by the amount of media content, and the information overload will trigger so called media fatigue, as illustrated in the following quote from one interviewee, *“... but quite honestly, at some point I couldn't take it anymore”* [Female, Mannheim, from Türkiye]. The common way to deal with fatigue is to stop using media, mainly news media but also social media. Since media, and news media in particular, are the main channels of information during societal crises, from a communicative perspective this constitutes a problem as important information about risks might not

reach the affected public and target groups. Media fatigue did occur among residents living both in Germany and Sweden, albeit for different reasons. As one interviewee expressed it: *“And then at some point I didn’t look at all. I didn’t even want to read the news anymore, I didn’t feel like it”* [Female, Mannheim, from Türkiye]. However, the reasons for avoiding information about the pandemic varied. Some expressed feelings of anxiety triggered by the news reporting, *“... at some point it was very stressful”*, others boredom, *“After a while, to be honest, it didn’t interest me anymore”* [Female, Mannheim, from Albania]. There were also cases where media content was perceived as meaningless, *“... and at some point, it was really too stupid for me”* [Female, Heidelberg-Mannheim region, from Germany] or as admonishing, *“Nah. I’m not interested in that. I want to live my life the way I want to and stick to the rules that exist for that”* [Female, Mannheim, from Albania].

Language issues (this was a topic in Sweden only, not in Germany)

One key issue in government authorities' crisis communication is to reach language minority groups. How to reach groups with limited knowledge in Swedish was early on recognized as a key issue and The Public Health Agency (PHA) translated brochures, videos and other information to many languages spoken by minority populations in Sweden.

Language gaps were discussed during the interviews and there were some concerns about this being a problem, especially in the early phases of the pandemic where information was unavailable in other languages. This led to some groups maybe not taking the pandemic and advice for self-protection seriously. This situation also created a need for interpersonal communication where interviewees functioned as interpreters to other people in the minority language population. *“Because, well, I don’t know it in Somali, these medical terms or whatever, but I know it in Swedish because that’s my strong language. So then it was like, ‘Well, okay, I’ll call my mum.’ Then I ran home to my mum and ‘How should I explain this? What does this word mean?’”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia]

Over time this concern seems to be less important, both due to the efforts made by government authorities in translating information, *“In hospitals and health centers there were many brochures in all languages. Persian, Arabic. There were many languages”*. But the interviewees also express the confidence in people's ability to find relevant information from the foreign and national news online. One informant says: *“So, old ladies of 70 years with other origins than Swedish are connected to the internet and they are connected to their news channels whether Arabic, or Swedish, or Somali and they have COVID information”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia].

The only ones seen as vulnerable in terms of receiving information in later stages of the pandemic were those who did not speak Swedish and were unable to read written text. One respondent claimed that everyone else could find the relevant information online if necessary. *“If you need information and want to check, you have to google. Those who are illiterate may find it difficult, but everyone else.”* [Male, Gothenburg, from Iran]

Friends and family as a source of information

As already noted, most people used more than one source of information to stay updated about the spread and impact of the pandemic, both in Germany and Sweden. The most commonly used was traditional news media, mainly because they were considered the most reliable. However, it was also common to obtain information through conversations with other people, especially family and friends. The extent to which people use and rely on this type of oral information varies among different groups

in society. Swedish surveys show that oral information is a more common source among migrant residents than among the Swedish public at large (Esaïsson et al., 2020).

Interestingly, the information passed on orally about the pandemic often referred back to other sources. In other words, oral information was mostly about passing on information from news media, social media or other personal sources, *"[I got] informed about the news on TV or about my friend. She has teletext. Whenever something happened, she would call me and say, "Did you hear the latest?" Then I would say, 'You know very well. I don't have teletext.' Then she read it to me. Yes"* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany].

During the interviews with migrant residents, it emerged that some of them more or less took on the role of information hubs in their local environment, *"[My mum] gets the information from me or my sister or something"* [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia], or were assigned the role, *"I have my father and he finds out about everything and then passes it on."* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany (second generation)].

The interviews also indicate that some respondents actively sought and kept themselves informed through friends and relatives, *"You have to stay informed. Sometimes, of course, I did my own research, it's not like that, but it was often the case that I spoke to her, i.e. via WhatsApp, and then she always said that and that and that were the latest news"* [Female, Mannheim, from Kosovo]. Others did not actively seek information through conversation, rather, it was provided as part of a social interaction, *"... every morning we meet, then he talks, he tells me what happened"* [Female, Gothenburg, Vietnam]. Social interactions also offered occasions for comparison and evaluation of information from different sources, *"I check with others that it is correct in the same information that I read. For example, what I read in Aftonbladet is consistent with SVT or if someone else has read a source, we check"* [Female, Gothenburg, case 21].

Communication of CSOs mostly unnoticed

Both in Sweden and Germany civil society organizations, CSOs, partnered with public authorities in reducing the impact of the pandemic on individuals and society. Among these were the Red Cross, religious groups, sports organizations, ethnic and cultural organizations, etc. In addition to providing care and assistance to those affected by the pandemic, several CSOs were also involved in information and communication activities. Not least in connection with the vaccination campaigns. In both countries CSOs were involved in information activities targeting migrant residents. The means of communication that were used included posters, advertisements and to some extent outreach activities.

In Germany, interviewees paid attention both to the posters and adverts calling for vaccination and to the physical premises for vaccination that were set up. However, there seems to have been poor knowledge of who was behind the information efforts, *"So I saw that [posters, advertisements]..., but I don't know now who that was. Whether it was Caritas, whether it was the health department, I don't know"* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany (second Generation)]. In this respect, CSOs went by rather unnoticed. There were also comments that the information available was insufficient or unclear, *"... if you had symptoms or something, a hotline was set up where you could call. But I think that is not presented enough, you know? Well, I think that people know what it is, but I myself, for example, couldn't even call the number or something. So I think there's too little advertising for things like that, support helplines and things like that."* [Female, Mannheim, from former Yugoslavia].

In Sweden, apart from reaching out through ads and posters, CSOs were also used for outreach activities. In the two analysed neighbourhoods so called “vaccination guides”, recruited among migrant residents speaking several languages, were employed by the municipality to inform about why, where and when vaccination was available. Both the guides themselves and migrant residents regard this as a successful initiative. The residents were approached by persons familiar to and with their own experience from the resident’s cultural ambience, and capable of giving information and answering questions in their own languages

Government campaigns received more attention – especially vaccination campaigns

Government campaigns on different levels - national, regional and local - was the main producer of campaign material even if NGO/CSOs also contributed. A critical issue was to reach out to minority populations using different channels. The interviewees give different examples of how they were exposed to campaign messages such as advice to wear a face mask, hand wash and take the vaccine. One interviewee mentioned how the repeated campaigns of wearing face masks helped to emphasize the importance of self-protection. *“Yes, advertising with masks and so that you should wear it, or even when you went shopping, always this request, the masks and then such a short advertisement about it. Every day about Corona, mask, Corona, mask, I think we had that for a year continuously.”* [Female, Mannheim, from Turkey. Others mention seeing campaign messages on different platforms, such as website ads just like commercial ads, which was commented: *“The advertisements even appeared on websites, just like an advertisement appears when Adidas presents their shoes. Instead of an Adidas advertisement, it came from the federal government, and I thought that was quite good.”* [Male, Mannheim, from Turkey]. Comments, both in Germany and Sweden, were made about long waiting in telephone lines, which caused frustration when trying to book an appointment for vaccination. One interviewee explains: *“Or rather, there was a vaccination campaign by the city in the public library, and you couldn't get through to this telephone, which was indicated. I then called the service telephone of the city of Heidelberg, described the situation, and was told, “Okay, you're not the only one who wants to be vaccinated. So I know that too. So it was just so meaningless.”* [Female, Heidelberg-Mannheim region, from Germany]. More than one interviewee from Sweden gave the online health care service 1177 good ratings as updated information always was available, when it was difficult to reach health care on the phone. A woman explains: *They had the information out there all the time. So there were updates on what was going on and happening. So I thought that was great. There was enough information.”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia]

Strong requests for information by traditional mail (apparently only in Germany)

Even if most people watch the news, one way or the other, there might be citizens who are news avoiders and not regularly following the news. In the German interviews some respondents emphasize the need for written information delivered in mailboxes to reach households where residents have chosen not to follow the news reporting. One interviewee explains: *“Many people do not regularly listen to the news and so, you would have to inform the people differently, maybe throw letters into the mailboxes, that you could contact them, if something happens, and with phone numbers or addresses or so, that you also have a contact person, like Caritas or something,* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany]. Using messages delivered in the mailbox (on paper) is also seen as a way to signalize the importance of the message. Mail from the government is not something flashing by when surfing online, it tells you these things are serious matters. *“So, I would have expected to get a letter from the health department or a flyer, where it says, this and this and this must be done. Or this is obligatory and that would make sense. But there was nothing.”* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany].

Communication with HCW – higher trust, even online

Trust in healthcare is generally high in Northern and Western Europe, and even increased during the COVID-19 pandemic. Further, trust in healthcare professionals is higher than in healthcare in general. It is therefore not very surprising that interviewees expressed high trust in health care representatives and in advice and recommendations they provided during the pandemic, *“I thought if a doctor, or a nurse, or an assistant nurse, for example, come and visit and give us the right information. What will happen? What will it be? What do we see? Such ... maybe it could be a little ... strengthen us! From the hospital, I can say. Because the rest of us are just mouth-to-mouth, we know nothing”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Vietnam].

Advice and guidelines from doctors and nurses were perceived as expert counselling compared to information disseminated by non-professionals. They were also considered to be a counterbalance to conspiracy theories and speculations that flourished on social media, *“What was also important for me, if I may say so, was the balance to the conspiracy theories. At the beginning, many people told me that the disease didn't exist, and my friends who were doctors or nurses were scratching their heads. They said they should come to the hospital and take a look at the victims or the sick, and they got first-hand information from their work”* [Male, Mannheim, from Turkey]. The medical expertise was highly appreciated and trusted also when not given face-to-face, but through social networks, *“You also talk to friends, family, and then also on social media, where nurses also talked, where you then read through and talk to, and everyone then exchanges their experience and so, yes”* [Female, Mannheim, from Turkey].

Communication with HCW – challenges

HCW are first line responders who expose themselves to the virus while helping others. However, the precautions to protect workers from being exposed also caused anger, frustration and confusion among residents. A woman describes her frustration in the contact with HCW: *“Yes. I went to my ENT doctor, I really just wanted to get rid of those FF2 masks. I would have put on the others, so no problem. Then he yells around, ‘I can't just free you with your pre-existing conditions, that's not possible’”*. [Female, Mannheim, from former Yugoslavia]. Others describe the confusion of not receiving any information when contacting HCW and how they turned to other people to find out how they could test themselves: *“I'm from Somalia and I've met people outside the health centre or something and they've asked questions. They have asked ‘Well, do you know what I should do? I suspect Covid. Can I come?’. So they had no information or they went straight in. I had the opportunity to talk to some individuals and explain ‘Yes, this is what you do. Test yourself, you can buy these tests here’”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia]. Similar problems of accessibility were mentioned as the health care did not allow citizens to come to doctors when having symptoms of COVID-19. This frustration was described like this: *“What can we do? We didn't get help and stuff, we didn't get help. Not the emergency room, not the health centre, they didn't treat us. [...] And when you say the symptoms exactly like Corona symptoms they say ‘no, but you can't come’. But I have to!”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Vietnam]

ICT to stay connected

For many, and especially in the countries that imposed lockdown during the pandemic, the isolation from other people was perceived as very stressful. People kept in contact via telephone and SMS, but no doubt, modern ICT offered an important way out of isolation through applications like Zoom, Teams, Skype and WhatsApp, where individuals not only heard but also could see each other. People

met and socialized virtually both on an individual level, *“Yes, we exchanged information on social media sites and gave each other comfort. Yes, so friends also through the Internet very much, or WhatsApp, video camera, phone calls and so on. It's not the same, but at least something”* [Female, Mannheim, from Turkey] and in groups, *“Although, true, true we sometimes talked through video. Yes, such video, Zoom. In the group, we always did video chats and so on. Everyone was at home and talked a bit”* [Male, Mannheim, from Germany (second Generation)].

Online group encounters could also involve specific activities that the group members did, if not together, then at least simultaneously, *“There was also a time when we cooked online. Everyone did their own shopping or what was available at home. You could do it. We learnt different recipes for each other. It was fun. And you see each other on camera”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia].

The use of ICT to stay in touch with relatives and friends seems to have caught on also by elderly people, who usually have less experience with modern technology, *“We also skyped, I even got to know that in my old age [laughs]. I didn't grow up with that stuff either. And then, what's it called, Zoom. Exactly. Through the senior centre, carnival party. I remember that, it was organized through Zoom...”* [Female, Heidelberg-Mannheim region, from Germany].

ICT as a source of information

Apart from legacy news media and government information campaigns, social media channels can help citizens to search for information on how to protect themselves. The interviews give many different examples of how information COVID-19 was surrounding them in their daily use of social media. Different platforms like YouTube, TikTok, Instagram and other apps were saturated with information about the pandemic. One respondent gives an example of how an app used for other purposes (rap, football and news) also regularly had updates about the pandemic. *“I actually just used one app, they used to give updates on rap, and then they started, just before Corona time, used to also be about soccer and news and I don't know what, and then they also had Corona updates. And then always came something about Corona.”* [Male, Mannheim, from Germany (second Generation)]. Others describe how their communities started to share information about the virus. *“We have a Whatsapp group, for example. We talk a lot there. If a new measure has come, then someone has already made a post that there is something.”* [Male, Mannheim, from Germany (second Generation)]

Others searched more actively on social media to find information using Google to search for new updates on the virus. Some did not search for specific pages, like government health care sites, instead they googled for updated information as one woman from Albania living in Mannheim explains: *Directly, I wasn't on special pages. I just typed it into Google and then read what it said. I made sure to check on several pages. Does it say the same thing?”* (Female, Mannheim, from Albania). Notably this interviewee gives an example of what in research is called convergence or milling where citizens seek for information to confirm information from different sources to create a coherent picture of the situation.

Trust/distrust in official information

Trust is an imperative factor in crisis management. When the public has trust in government institutions it follows regulations and issued recommendations which facilitates mitigation of the crisis. In contrast, when the public distrusts authorities the crisis risks getting out of hand and the negative consequences to be more serious and widespread.

Societal crisis communication relies on a chain of actors from sender to receiver of a message. A very important intermediary is the communication channels, i.e. the media that convey the message. These can be traditional news media such as the public service, private broadcast media or established newspapers, but also online networks such as Facebook, WhatsApp and TikTok. Successful crisis communication requires public trust in both sender and channel, i.e., in both authorities and media.

The interviews suggest that there was general trust in the authorities during the pandemic, both in Sweden and Germany, *“So, for the most part, I believed our Mr. Lauterbach. Although many think...no. I believed him...everything the man said”* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany]. Trust was most pronounced for the measures taken, while it was lower for the vaccination programme, *“So, what didn't come across to me as trustworthy was this vaccine...Because everything about it...It came across to me as if everything was put into it that it would be sold as quickly as possible or brought to the market”* [Male, Mannheim, from Germany (second Generation)].

Trust in the media was more diversified. Interviewees made clear distinctions between different media, with public service and established newspapers being more trusted than tabloids and social media, *“..., with BILD, for example, you generally know it's most likely not the most trustworthy source, but if I then, for example, with ZDF, so with really national things so somehow watch news at 8 p.m. or other, then I have much more trust in it”* [Female, Mannheim, from former Yugoslavia]; *“First you trust Al Jazeera because they speak Arabic. Then you trust SVT [Swedish public service television] when they speak the truth. [...] Youtube anyone can come and talk. So you don't trust.”* [Male, Gothenburg, from Iraq].

Then there were also those who expressed total distrust of the media, *“They always said: ‘So and so many have fallen ill. So and so many have died.’ Etc. If I add up all the people that have died, no one should be alive anymore. So [laughs]. Well, after a while I felt like I was being made fun of. Then it was so much fear mongering. Yes. That people just panicked or something. [...] Because you really can't believe everything, you know. [...] But the media itself. I don't know”* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany].

Misinformation

Misinformation spreads easily during crises as the need for information is vast in combination with shortage of verified information. Rumours also spread easily. Crises are situations of frame contests and spread of conflicting messages, some true some false. The respondents share experiences of this communication environment where conflicting voices can change citizens beliefs and behaviours. One interviewee explains: *“Yes. At first, when you went shopping, it was said that the bacteria were on the bags, on the cans. Of course, I disinfected all the cans at home and disinfected everything I could. Then I was told again, “No. This is a droplet infection. You can only get infected if you have very close contact.” So, that was all confusing again, too.”* (Female, Mannheim, from Germany). Others mention how news media exaggerate and create panic by framing statements from experts in a dramatic way. Interviewees also highlight concerns of spreading misinformation themselves since there are difficulties to evaluate information: *“I don't want to spread fake news in any way. Of course, that doesn't always work, especially since we're always surrounded by a media frenzy and there are so many influences that it's sometimes hard to tell what's real and what's fake, but you still try to manage somehow.”* [Female, Mannheim, from former Yugoslavia], while others experience they can evaluate crisis messages by checking facts and comparing different sources to verify information: *“No, but you just do your own research like ‘Where did they get this?’, ‘What is 5G?’, ‘How does it affect the body?’.*

Just check independent sources and just check 'What is it?', 'Can there be any truth behind this?'. [Female, Gothenburg, with Somali background].

Belief in conspiracy theories

During the pandemic, several speculations and conspiracy theories circulated in social media. A conspiracy theory is an unsubstantiated belief or theory that seeks to explain a historical, political or social event by an underlying secret plot usually involving powerful people, when other explanations are more probable. During the pandemic such conspirative theories were that the virus was spread deliberately from a laboratory in China, that the vaccine contained a 5G chip, and that vaccinations would cause serious, undisclosed, side effects since it had been produced in such a short time.

Studies show that a significant proportion of the population in many countries has a conspiratorial tendency, but also that it is stronger among some groups than others (Strömbäck, 2022). These include those with low education, low interpersonal trust, those who are not at all satisfied with the functioning of democracy, and those who make extensive use of social media and right-wing alternative media.

Among the interviewees, some admit to support conspiracy theories, *"Yes, I actually also believe in Corona, because I have seen how many people have fallen ill with it and so on, but just that in my eyes it is also just a game and there is something bigger, but we don't really have access to it. Because there is so much illogic, that's why"* [Female, Mannheim, from Türkiye]. Others are more uncertain of what to believe, *"So, for example, if it was on the news how many people died. So, I think we would have to be underpopulated to believe that. I still don't believe it today"* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany].

Others again, believe in some conspiracy theories but not in others, *"Yes, there were all sorts of strange things. For example, this thing about 5G being linked to vaccination. [...] I understand that people were restrictive to the vaccinations because it was a vaccination that had been developed so quickly. [...] So I understand that people were restrictive about it, and there is some truth to these conspiracy theories, because the Swedish Medicines Agency says that there should be no side effects whatsoever. Nobody believes that. I, at least, did not believe it. But then there were some conspiracy theories that were a bit like that.... Like the one about 5G"* [Female, Gothenburg, with Somali background].

Lack of information and conflicting messages

Apart from misinformation and conspiracy beliefs, interviewees draw attention to lack of clear and consistent information. Theories of self-protection emphasize the need for information which is both explanatory and action-oriented and respondents showed frustration of the lack of information fulfilling these needs. One interviewee says: *"Above all, I would need a clear statement now: What will be done. What do you mean decided again? Why is it decided? Why must the mask continue to be worn? Where does it have to be worn? How long will it last? And. And. And. What can be done about it? How many times will the virus spread?"* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany]. Another problem related to this was the constant changes of advice and restrictions as health authorities learned more about the virus and how it was spread. As one respondent explains: *"This back and forth. "Oh, we do it this way. Then this way again. And then to 10 and then to 11." So, it was really bad, this back and forth and constantly new regulations. And that was totally confusing, and also the vacations. You stay at home, man, and see if you can get around it, and maybe next year you'd rather go on vacation."* (Female, Mannheim, from Albania). This kind of confusion was also related to the vaccine, where the vaccination was believed to protect from getting COVID-19 when it turned out to mainly protect from

getting seriously ill. *“I thought that it was like, first there was talk about public immunity and if we reach that, it will be good. Then there was talk about vaccination. First there was one and then there were two. It was that if you take a vaccine you are protected. Then it turned out that it wasn't quite like that, but you needed another vaccine and another and then maybe a boost [...] and it's a bit of a mixed... double message and it's hard to take. You don't know how to interpret it properly. Without confusion, you get confused. So I wish they could be more just say ‘We don't know. But we'll start with everyone getting vaccinated.’ instead of saying that it is absolute and not that it has changed so much.”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia].

Vulnerabilities due to age

COVID-19 became more dangerous with growing age and in order to protect them (and other vulnerable groups) societies closed down. When comparing the experiences of vulnerabilities between Germany and Sweden there are clear differences in perceptions due to the stricter lockdown in Germany. Interviewees have concerns about children's mental health as playgrounds, schools and other activities were closed. *“I have noticed that it has changed them psychologically, so to speak, that they are no longer as social as before.”* [Male, Mannheim, from Germany (second generation)]. The experiences from Swedish respondents are less dramatic even if they also raise concerns, but mostly about children with asthma or slight colds having to stay home from school as they were suspected to be infected by COVID-19.

There is a consensus among interviewees that older people were more affected by the pandemic and the restrictions than younger people. Partly because they were more restricted to social distance and isolation, *“My father is only home for more than a year and a half, only inside. He got sick. He wants to see his grandchildren. They just came from the window and cheered. They can't hug, they can't get close to each other, it hurts. It's a lot. Maybe we as young people can cope, but not the older ones. It's very difficult for them”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia], and partly because they were unable to carry out practical tasks, *“For example, when I lived in our house, there was an old woman who couldn't even manage to walk and because of these contact [restrictions], she no longer had the opportunity to have someone go shopping for her or something, because her daughter and all that, were very afraid of it. And then sometimes we went shopping for her. She wrote a list and we went shopping”* [Female, Mannheim, from Macedonia].

Vulnerabilities due to ethnicity and gender

The difference in pandemic strategy in terms of having stricter regulations in Germany compared with Sweden also seemed to affect experiences of vulnerability in relation to ethnicity. A number of interviewees in Germany can give examples of how they were treated differently because of ethnicity. Since face masks were mandatory in Germany this became a very visible way of how restrictions were followed and respondents give attention to the fact that they are treated differently because of their foreign origin. *I have my reasons why I don't wear a mask, but that's happened to me so many times now. And these are mostly the older people or just really Germans, really German. I was almost thrown off the train by two older men.* [Female, Mannheim, from Macedonia]. Other voices compare how people are treated differently when not following the regulations of wearing face masks due to their ethnicity: *“I'm still bothered by it today, because I travel a lot by public transport and so often you see people only up to here the mask, no mask at all. And then I always think, if these are foreigners, I would like to expel them [laughs], because I think it's impertinent.* [Female, Heidelberg-Mannheim region, from Germany]

According to the interviewees, both men and women were affected, but in different ways. The women who normally take care of the home were given an extra burden during the lockdown, *“Let's put it this way, if they [women] have children, yes, because they had a double burden. So I would say they would have needed more support. Most of them did their job from home, and then the children were still at home, and maybe the husband was still at home. Yes. That was a double burden for the women”* [Female, Mannheim, from Germany]. Men, on the other hand, who usually worked, were more psychologically affected by the isolation, *“I think, I don't know, but I even think that men have it more difficult. Well, I've noticed that women don't have such a problem being at home. I have the feeling that men prefer to be outside. [...] My mother always says: ‘Men have nothing to do at home. They always have to go outside’”* [Male, Mannheim, from Germany (second Generation)], and were more likely to be infected by the virus.

Protective measures (hygiene, masks, social distancing, vaccine)

During the pandemic, a series of protective measures were introduced to limit the spread of infection. Broadly speaking, it was about the same measures in all countries, but the severity of the restrictions varied. In Sweden, for example, it was not mandatory to use a face mask, while in most other countries, not using it in public spaces entailed a fine. To what extent pre-schools and schools were closed also differed between Sweden and Germany where in the latter remote teaching was only used in high school and university.

The interviewees' attitudes to the various protective measures differed. Washing hands seems to be a protective measure that was generally accepted and implemented by most, *“I think that ..., well, I think that hygiene is actually quite good, because I think that everyone washes their hands now, that's also good sometimes”*, [Male, Mannheim, from Germany (second generation)]. Also, social distancing seems to have been a restriction implemented and accepted by most people, both in public spheres, *“Yeah first of all I stopped going outside. Only for some emergency or some important things. Let's say to buy some provisions, such as food, or medicine. Otherwise, most of the time I stay at home. Also, when I go outside I use a mask. I keep my distance if I'm in the supermarket or if I'm in the pharmacy”* [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia], and in private, *“We in our family are like that anyway, we are warm, we hug each other as often as we can. Yes, that was difficult, and it took everyone a while to realize: “Ah, stop. That's not possible. We're not allowed to do that””*, [Female, Mannheim, from Albania].

In Germany, where face masks were mandatory, it seems that most people did use it, but reluctantly and with some discomfort, *“The masks, I wear glasses, then my glasses fog up, I suffered a lot from the masks, really. So I really say that, I sometimes even panicked slightly, because everything fogged up, I ran out of air, I couldn't cope with it”*, [Male, Mannheim, from Turkey]. It also turned out that some were sceptical to the actual efficiency of the masks, *“I worked as a laundry attendant and I had to go through all the laundries every day. Just as if I could protect myself with a mask, face mask, gloves, hand sanitiser, distance... So, it sounds okay but it doesn't help. It doesn't help when I go in and maybe... and that disease is everywhere, they say something comes from the air, comes from people, comes from the distance”*, [Female, Gothenburg, from Vietnam].

A point made by the German interviewees was that socio-economically disadvantaged people would have benefitted from financial support or free access to more protective equipment during the pandemic, *“And perhaps they should have issued more masks earlier, especially for the socially*

disadvantaged. Because what good is it if they give every citizen 3 masks? Yes, one of them wore the mask for 3 or 4 weeks. Then it was no use either” [Female, Mannheim, from Germany].

Vaccination

Vaccination levels are generally lower in groups with low socioeconomic status and this is also true for minority language groups and migrant dense communities. In both the German and Swedish population we find examples of respondents taking the vaccine and believing its effectiveness. *“Yes, you vaccinate yourself against the virus so you can be affected and get sick. You feel this concern. But we thought when everybody gets vaccinated and it must have been a long process in the government and regulations.” [Female, Gothenburg, from Somalia].* Respondents with other diseases and belonging to risk groups were also more prone to take the vaccine even if some had their doubts.

Still a number of quotes can be found where interviewees are sceptical towards the vaccine. Some believed it would not work or that there might be side effects. One respondent expresses this concern: *“Yes, so last year, they said you should get vaccinated. But then I heard in the news and from many other people that the vaccines had not yet been researched and tested, and so I was a bit afraid.” (Female, Mannheim, from Macedonia).* Beliefs of serious side effects, like not being able to have children was mentioned, *“Someone says in the future maybe they won't have children, maybe there will be something. So, we didn't dare anyway. We said they are children and their defence may be stronger than ours, maybe they will survive. We thought like this. So I didn't want my children to get vaccinated, and they didn't want to either.” [Female, Gothenburg, from Vietnam].* What is common in these quotes is referring to what “someone has said” and not pointing at official sources, which could indicate these beliefs stemmed from interpersonal communication.

2.4.6 Conclusions

An unexpected main finding is that migrant residents in both Germany (Mannheim) and Sweden (Gothenburg) often did not differ remarkably from the majority society in their way of understanding and reacting to the pandemic. Also, there were very few differences found between German and Swedish migrant residents.

- Migrant residents in both Mannheim and Gothenburg felt they were well informed about the pandemic, its stages and consequences, and what protective measures to take.
- Trust in public authorities and government was generally strong.
- They got their information through media; mainly news media - national and international- and social media.
- Established news media were more trusted than tabloids and social media.
- Mis-/disinformation, contradictory messages were prevalent to some extent.
- ICT was widely used to keep in contact with relatives and friends.
- Protective measures were generally implemented, although at times with reluctance and discomfort.
- Vaccination was seen in a more critical way than protective measures.

Key lessons learned from the case study are:

- Albeit the migrant residents were well informed, they still vaccinated to a lower degree than the rest of the population, both in Germany and Sweden. One possible explanation is that by accessing foreign media and relying more on social media, they were exposed to more contradictory messages about how the pandemic was best contained, as well as about the benefits and safety of vaccination.
- Written information through posters and ads is less effective than personal contact with informants familiar with migrants' cultural diversities and languages.

2.5 Greece, KEMEA

2.5.1 Introduction

The case study of KEMEA (Greece) focuses on policing in times of pandemic: the COVID-19 impact on the role of Law Enforcement Agents (LEAs) and its effect on perception, social interaction and measure compliance, communication and trust of vulnerable (minority) populations, in Greece.

The interaction between the governance system and relevant actors, particularly Law Enforcement Agents and minority groups during COVID-19, as well as the implications of implemented measures, mechanisms and impact they subsequently had on social interaction, trust and perception has been identified to be significantly under-research and under-reported within the scientific and academic community.

This case study predominately focuses on the interaction between the governmental response, governance system and relevant actors such as Law Enforcement Agents and minority groups to identify how social interactions, measure compliance, public perceptions, communications and trust have been impacted due to COVID-19. The case study explores how the governance response system and relevant actors were prepared and responded to the pandemic, and how their role has been generally affected by the COVID 19 pandemic. Concluding, this case study aims to identify lessons learned which can be interpreted into policy recommendations within the context of the COV INFORM project, for policy and decision makers, governmental actors and stakeholders that have an active role in the pandemic responses, reinforcing effective and efficient response mechanisms.

Figure 12. KEMEA, Greece – SES Framework.

2.5.2 Purpose and Research Questions

The main, overarching purpose and objectives that have been set in WP3 (D3.4), within the context of the COVINFORM research project:

- Identify vulnerability and protective factors of both vulnerable populations and the systems/settings they are a part of, by describing the variables and indicators which characterize the relevant systems involved, providing insight regarding the resilience of such – from a system-driven point of view;
- Understand how those factors accumulate to enhance COVID-19 impacts (cumulative), as well as how they interact with one another (synergic), throughout several time points of the pandemic, providing insight to the risk assessment framework being developed in WP2;
- Understand the commonalities across several relevant dimensions (e.g., governance – WP4; public health – WP5; community – WP6; and information – WP7) and what is and is not generalizable across case studies;
- Identify continuous data collection needs in order to later provide input for public-facing material created in WP8 (e.g., recommendations, guidelines, and tool development) regarding the lessons learnt so far.

2.5.3 Method

In the case study “*Policing in times of pandemic: The COVID-19 impact on the role of Law Enforcement Agents (LEAs) and its effect on perception, social interaction and measure compliance, communication and trust of vulnerable (minority) populations*”, the participants were 5 LEAs and 5 members of the Roma community and/or refugees and/or migrants.

The case study is divided into four distinct sections that examine perception, social interaction and compliance, communication and trust. Specifically:

Section 1: Main research question: What is the interviewees personal perception of COVID-19 and how it has impacted on their daily life and professional environment?

- Identify the personal perceptions about the COVID-19 pandemic and how it has influenced the interviewees’ personal and professional environment.

Section 2: Main research question: What is the perceived impact of implemented COVID-19 measures on LEAs, minorities & vulnerable groups?

- Understanding measure effectiveness and implementation from the interviewees’ point of view. Identifying and analysing the impact and consequences of the adopted measures in target groups.
- Understand the target groups’ difficulties (if any) in abiding to the implemented measures and vaccination procedure.
- Understand people’s active/passive role during the pandemic period regarding imposed measures and how people feel about it.

- Collecting target group's opinion and objections about the implemented measures and what could have been done differently, if they have been given the opportunity to voice their concerns.

Section 3: Main research question: How were communication and vaccination campaigns against COVID-19 perceived by vulnerable groups, minorities and LEAs? How have these responses affected people's measure and vaccination compliance?

- Understand how communication and vaccination campaigns were perceived by our target groups and how they impacted on their vaccination compliance.
- Identification of perception revolving around credibility of sources (including traditional and contemporary sources).
- Understanding the perception in relation to measure implementation and compliance based on our target group point of view.
- Collection of target groups' opinions about clarity and relevance in communication from the respective spokespeople.
- Identification of the impact of information campaigns in relation to measures and vaccinations.

Section 4: Main research question: How has COVID-19 management affected people's trust towards authorities?

- Identifying the impact of COVID-19 management in terms of trust between target groups and authorities.
- Understanding how target groups were perceived, approached and treated by relevant main target groups and how it had altered, if at all, their perception and levels of trust.
- Understanding how pandemic management in distinct and specific pandemic phases has impacted trust and in what ways.
- Understanding how the interaction between minorities and LEAs has impacted, if at all, levels of trust whilst comparing pre-pandemic, and phases during the pandemic.
- Identifying personal perspectives of each interviewee, their interpretation of changes in social life and people's attitudes whereas simultaneously allowing interviewees to add further comments on all topics as well as additional remarks that may have not been discussed.

This case study will allow the consortium of COVINFORM to acquire in-depth responses on how Law Enforcement Agents have responses to a contemporary health crisis, how their role has been impacted and how trust, measure compliance communication and perceptions of both LEAs and minority groups were impacted. This case study takes into consideration vulnerability as well as cultural, political, legal and socio-economic aspects human behaviour and social dynamics, thus, expand on physical and mental well-being of both target groups illustrating the impact of the pandemic on a daily basis (e.g., anxiety, fear, burnout, pressure factors, dealing with COVID-19 vulnerable populations etc.).

This case study has been designed and was carried out in Greece by KEMEA. Nevertheless, due to the common methodology utilised between consortium members, it fulfils the criteria of transferability and sustainability. Specifically, it is feasible to conduct similar research utilising the same methodological framework in additional target countries, whereas the research outcomes are intended to provide sustainable recommendations, lessons learned and outputs via policy briefs, white

papers, research outcomes within relevant COVINFORM deliverables particularly within the context of WP8 and the COVINFORM COVID-19 Knowledge Repository.

The added value of this case study is the in-depth examination of perceptions, social interaction and measure compliance, public trust and communication between Law Enforcement Agents and vulnerable – minority groups, aimed to produce specific policy recommendations on aforementioned thematic areas that would highly contribute in the work of stakeholders, particularly in reinforcing governmental responses and the tailoring pandemic management response system.

This case study utilises qualitative research methods, more particularly interviews with open-ended questions while it remains directly connected to WP4 (Government responses and impact assessment), WP5 (Public Health responses and impact assessment), WP6 (Citizen and community responses and impact assessment) and WP7 (Inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation).

2.5.4 Results: Data reporting

The case study of Policing in times of pandemic: The COVID-19 impact on the role of Law Enforcement Agents (LEAs) and its effect on perception, social interaction and measure compliance, communication and trust of vulnerable (minority) populations, includes an in-depth examination of twenty-seven socio-demographic related questions. For further information, please see Appendix B, Annex 5.1.

Figure 13. KEMEA, Greece – Coding Tree (1).

Figure 14. KEMEA, Greece – Coding Tree (2).

2.5.5 Results: Analysis and Interpretation

Section 1: Law Enforcement Agents – Minority Groups & COVID-19

Main research question: What is the interviewees personal perception of COVID-19 and how it has impacted on their daily life and professional environment?

All law enforcement agent participants suggested that COVID-19 influenced them on multiple levels within their daily lives. Specifically, LEAs suggest COVID-19 impacted their personal life, professional environment, interpersonal relations and the degree of fruitfulness in meaningful activities that were carried out during the pandemic. The majority if not all LEAs, experienced an increased workload and stress, widespread fear due to the unknown health-related impact COVID-19 might have had on themselves and their families, negative and abrupt change on their interpersonal relations and behaviour, as well as a negative impact on their mental wellbeing.

“My daily life was impacted in many degrees, mainly on a professional level, because as a police officer I am called upon on a daily basis to face crisis situations, let alone such a situation, which was something new for us, as it was for the rest of the world, with the pandemic, being something very difficult to manage, while at the same time on a personal level, in terms of relations with relatives, people that in many cases came from vulnerable social groups, so there was a bit of fear and especially distance. Surely because of the fear of the people, the distance between them has increased.”

All minority group participants suggested that COVID-19 and the relevant movement restriction mechanisms such as the curfew, has had an immensely negative psychological impact on their daily lives and well-being, which still affects some participants to this day. Indoor confinement and the lack of social interactions have increased the feeling of loneliness and demanded a swift change of on-site to digital, remote interaction and discourse with colleagues, friends and family for most if not all minority participants. One participant suggests that during the COVID-19 pandemic phases, several close friends passed away due to coronavirus, despite being vaccinated, which has caused emotional damage. Moreover, participants indicate that the change of living conditions also had a negative impact on their financial status, since business opportunities and employment were restricted and challenged by COVID-19 measures and regulations.

“I felt like I couldn't do anything, couldn't work and had to work from home. Daily life changed radically, and being alone within my home, it was really difficult for me.”

Most law enforcement agents believe that Greece has managed the pandemic effectively overall, though they also offer suggestions for further improvement. Generally, these agents emphasize that the pandemic has affected their lives much like it has for the broader population, albeit to varying degrees. Specifically, some agents note a significant impact on their quality of life, while others report less severe effects. When it comes to possible enhancements, there is a call for increased funding to bolster the healthcare system, particularly for the expansion of Intensive Care Units (ICUs). From a community engagement standpoint, law enforcement agents recommend that local municipalities take a more proactive role. This could include hosting informational sessions and disseminating educational materials, not just for the general public but also for targeted initiatives aimed at minority and marginalized groups.

“I wouldn't say it has been affected so severely. Perhaps it may have also brought some good occasions. For example, internet use for online shopping has increased. However, there are of

course also some other parameters, like the issue of safety where people are needed to be much more careful, wash their hands more often with alcohol and use a mask. Perhaps this has tired people, but I don't think for me, at least and in the situation where I'm in, since I'm not in a vulnerable social group, that my quality of life has changed significantly. Concerning the steps, I think that so far everything that has been done is for the best. I don't think that there was something else that could be done, that would produce a better result, even in informing the public. Maybe it would be best at a local level, if the municipalities could hold gatherings and meetings, to better inform people who do not have access to the media, due to their social class, etc. This perhaps could have taken place to an extensive level, for the vulnerable social groups, such as Roma, or immigrants, who are people who can hardly find the informative material that we have access to."

All minority group participants indicated that the pandemic has influenced the quality of life and people's attitude – behaviour negatively, which were expressed via acts of violence, particularly in forms of domestic abuse and anger, frustration and disobedience to healthcare protocols such as wearing a mask in public means of transportation, widespread insecurity and lack of communication. Moreover, most if not all minority participants suggest that decision makers such as politicians hold a certain degree of accountability as well as the media in relation to how the pandemic was managed and mishandling the pandemic, politicization of COVID-19 by politicians who intended to reinforce their political narrative thus increasing their personal political gains, as well as the way information was conveyed by the media. Participants suggested that both media and decision makers ought to be honest disregarding the political cost while facing such healthcare crises and opt in for more human-centered approaches to combat healthcare risks and threats of that scope. In addition, participants suggest that it is rather important that decision makers orientate the governmental responses with a post-pandemic perspective and financially assist both vulnerable businesses, vulnerable citizens and employees, reinforce the healthcare system, proceed with an open dialogue to identify lessons learned, mistakes and how to improve responses for future crises as well as address the negative psychological impact that COVID-19 caused. Concluding, a lot of systemic challenges on an EU scale emerged according to minority group participants who suggested that there are lessons to be learned in order to actively work towards better governmental responses both in Greece and in the European Union.

"People become alienated, increasing their digital presence created several negative outcomes and consequences on behaviour and psychological state of people as we can understand with a different way others in a digital environment because we cannot see their expressions or comprehend their emotions... in-person communication may have a different outcome and interpretation of information. Besides that, people opt for personal safety within our "bubble", therefore COVID-19 has encouraged people to keep within themselves and it might have had an added toll on our psychological state. The measures that have been implemented, mainly utilized fear which created a disproportionate amount of insecurity in the public, while in my opinion a more human-centered approach should have been chosen. It was also apparent in the adopted strategies that fear was the prominent tool, as for example, when there was a rise of infected cases, stricter measures would be adopted but when the infection rate would be reduced or when the touristic period would initiate since the foreign capital/wealth is required, measures would be alleviated or their intensity would be reduced. I strongly believe that a more human-centered approach would be a better option."

Most if not all LEAs suggest that their workload and risk has increased significantly as new work-related duties and responsibilities have been added, which impacted their daily professional activities to a moderate or high degree. Specifically, most LEAs observed a radical change in their daily duties, which mainly involved COVID-19 related activities such as ensuring movement restriction rules were adhered by citizens and business owners adhered to COVID-19 hygiene and capacity allowance protocols. In addition, most LEAs suggest that although the pandemic had a negative impact on European societies, it has also acted as a reality check and had beneficial impacts on both Law Enforcement Agency personnel and citizens as well. LEAs underlined that their colleagues and fellow citizens would not pay too much attention to hygiene protocols, particularly in the field of law enforcement in relation to being exposed to healthcare related risk factors such as substance abusers or citizens who may have had transmittable diseases. COVID-19 made LEAs and citizens realise how important hygiene protocols are in their line of work and social life, particularly wearing masks, social distancing and getting vaccinated. For some respondents, the COVID-19 pandemic impacted their work environment gradually at later phases due to pending work-related obligations and activities that could not be performed during the pandemic. Concluding, LEAs appear divided in relation to their perception on when the pandemic will cease, since some respondents suggest that COVID-19 will certainly cease to exist in the future, whereas other LEAs indicate that the society will co-exist with COVID-19, while the degree of risk will significantly be reduced due to vaccination efforts.

“My professional daily activities changed negatively during the pandemic but resumed back to the normal routine. Once more, police were utilized as a means of suppression and not prevention in relation to the pandemic. The working environment has a clear contextual frame, similar to the military. The pandemic will “cease to exist” once we are told that it has ended. The measures that have been taken such as masks, social distancing and other good hygiene related measures that were successful, will most likely be maintained as lessons learned for a potential future crisis such as COVID-19.”

All minority group participants suggested that their work environment, daily activities and perception radically changed due to COVID-19 and relevant restrictions. Participants became more cautious and enforced personal hygiene habits, abiding to healthcare protocols which were recommended and implemented by the governmental mechanism. COVID-19 has had an immensely negative impact on businesses which reduced their income due to decreased business movement, since restrictions severely challenged tourist and hospitality, food and entertainment among other industries. Currently, participants identify several fellow citizens that still abide by healthcare measures such as wearing a mask while others do not, claiming that it is a matter of interpretation. Most minority participants highlight that remote working has been rather challenging and negatively influenced their work environment, albeit some consider remote working during the pandemic a necessity. In addition, minority participants strongly criticize how employers take advantage of systemic grey areas and legislative weaknesses of the labour law, which fails to protect employees who work on a remote basis. Participants suggest that employers frequently infringe employee rights by reducing the wage of remote working employees, increase their workload and do not respect the set work hours which, according to participants, can significantly reduce their productivity and lead to a cascading phenomenon of employee rights violation, even after the pandemic. Concluding, minority participants appear divided in relation to when and if the pandemic will cease. For some participants the pandemic has ended, while some others suggest that it will end in the near future. Other participants suggest that COVID-19 will continue to co-exist with us but the mortality intensity will be reduced as more

effective vaccines will be invented, while citizens ought to comprehend their role and responsibilities in relation to the pandemic and behave accordingly.

“Many businesses would be forced to shut down and there was the feeling of insecurity. As time passed, to a point, an environment of safety was created ... slowly but steadily active steps were taken to respond to COVID-19 at its core.... I believe that people do not have the proper approach in responding to the situation that the pandemic has created, as I’ve talked to many people about COVID-19 and understand that the majority has dealt with it in a state of ignorance and denial. Fear and ignorance simply create a psychological environment that discouraged critical thinking and most people would receive information without the ability to wrap their mind on the aforementioned information. COVID-19 has significantly negatively impacted the thinking and decision-making process of people. People could not understand the essence of the conveyed information which is why we observed many cases of measure-disobedience... the pandemic will end once we all realize our own responsibilities and the strategic management of the pandemic becomes more concrete. This is the only way to move forward, not with fear neither with ignorance... a step forward is to achieve group immunity and invent a vaccine which will be more sustainable... a lot of things have changed in the working environment and the work ethics code of a company as well as the degree of safety that is being implemented with measures. Frequent cleaning, the instalment of plexiglass and the use of masks are measures that have improved the working environment which will continue to change as COVID-19 has been a catalyst in this change.”

According to all participants, LEAs have not changed their view towards minority groups due to COVID-19 pandemic. In general, LEAs appear to be more cautious towards all socio-demographic groups including minority groups due to the societal changes that the pandemic regulations have introduced such as hygiene and infection confinement measures. In addition, all LEA participants have underlined to be in a highly frequent interaction with minority groups, particularly with the Roma community, migrant and refugee community, individuals with disabilities, citizens with different ethnic, religious or sexual orientation and preferences, as well as substance abusers, delinquent minors and citizens living on borderline or in poverty. Further, most LEAs identify their role as both enforcers of civil order and peace but also as educators or awareness raisers, since due to the socio-economic challenges that marginalised groups face, several members of the aforementioned communities may not have understood completely the implemented healthcare protocols and measures. Therefore, it is observed that LEAs do not focus on punitive actions but rather as educators, awareness raisers and facilitators of assistance towards minority groups who may encounter educational, cultural and communication issues due to pre-existing vulnerabilities, and act in an educational manner.

“Yes, daily with Roma, immigrants, refugees, drug users, people living on the edge of poverty, also delinquent minors, although some might claim that children do not belong to vulnerable groups. Of course, we should not forget people with disabilities. Regarding the way I view those groups, I personally have not changed my perception due to COVID-19. On the contrary through my work, I try to educate people, because as I told you before, they may not have access to informational material. They may not have someone to help them with the day to day, let's say care. I'm taking on that part. Now from a group perspective, there are quite a few problems, because for example, the Roma are also looking for ways to sustain themselves, by collecting scrap metal, or through trading junk, etc., and may not have been informed about the measures. We were working during the pandemic, and we met people from vulnerable social

groups, who did not even know about the quarantine. So, we had to play a role there too, a little educational.”

The majority of the minority participants did not have a lot of interactions with law enforcement agents in their work environment. Nevertheless, they encountered LEAs in their daily activities for routine checks. For most minority participants, their perception towards the aforementioned group (LEAs) did not change during the pandemic, while they appear to sympathize with LEAs suggesting they interact in a certain way due to their role of peace and order agents who simply follow orders. Instead, one participant has criticized decision makers' lack of having a clear and viable plan in relation to the management of the pandemic. Several respondents highlighted that the governmental mechanism ought to take into account the weaknesses of minority groups such as the Roma and Asylum seekers in order to mitigate the socio-economic consequences of the pandemic which intensified pre-existing financial and social issues that challenge these communities and even posed a threat to their survival. Concluding, only one respondent has a negative perception towards LEAs but according to the statements, this respondent appears to be negatively biased against the law enforcement agents in Greece.

Section 2: COVID-19 and Measure compliance

Main Research question: What is the perceived impact of implemented COVID-19 measures on LEAs, Minorities & Vulnerable groups?

According to the interviewees, the implemented measures have been hard on both the vulnerable community members and general population, while they were not perfectly aware of the restrictions and limitations, nevertheless, measures have also been hard on Law enforcement agents while not to that degree due to the modus operandi of LEAs. LEAs believe that due to their role, they should abide by the implemented rules and regulations as they interpret and perceive themselves as a societal role model, which the rest of the social groups will look up to, therefore a sense of responsibility on upholding the rules is observed. In addition, most LEAs suggest that rules and regulations have been extremely strict due to the high amount of fines, indicating that due to that factor, they have also demonstrated leniency towards fining other social groups, whenever possible. Concluding, LEAs suggested that amongst the vulnerable groups, the Roma community would not abide by the rules and regulations most of the times.

“For Law Enforcement personnel it was a little easier to discipline, because of the regulations that govern the Corp and the perception among all staff that we follow the rules because we enforce the law. We are responsible for the “authority”, as a law enforcement authority, because this is also the name or otherwise the standardized international term of what we are. As for social groups, I think that things might have been a little more difficult, because we are talking about the aforementioned vulnerable groups, who might have had some problem with regard to the issues that the pandemic has aggravated.”

In general, most minority group participants criticize the pandemic management mechanism and decision makers for failing to address the intensified weaknesses of vulnerable populations and failing to address or mitigate the consequences of COVID-19, therefore participants' opinions in relation to decision makers are considered negative. Moreover, one respondent suggested that some citizens would still put their faith in the system despite issues of mismanagement. In relation to LEAs, the majority of respondents, similarly to the previous section, appear to sympathize with the role that LEAs have and underline that their opinion towards LEAs has not been influenced. In addition, respondents

suggest that in some cases the zeal, intrusiveness in relation to questioning citizens and mismanagement of some officers, particularly in the event that took place in Nea Smyrni square, drew negative attention and public outrage, nevertheless respondents recognize the tough role LEAs have who out to protect citizen rights and liberties on the one hand and on the other, they are forced to implement measures that restrict individual liberties, which is contradicting. Minority respondents moreover suggest that LEAs have not changed their approach towards minority groups and have not abused their power, which was increased during COVID-19 phases. Concluding, minority respondents suggest that vulnerable groups such as minorities abided by the pandemic policies and measures as much as they could with the exception of cases in which reduced income posed a threat of survival, illiteracy, lack of resources and ignorance. Concluding, minority groups respondents suggest that the society ought to learn the lessons from the pandemic which could mitigate the consequences on a future pandemic, such as having unregistered employment could increase the vulnerability of citizens due to not being entitled to financial benefits.

“In my opinion, the management of the pandemic was rather a tragic case, nevertheless, minorities also adapted to the new status quo, followed the guidelines and instructions provided by EODY. I’d say that a bigger emphasis should have been placed on minorities since most of them are illiterate and there was an issue of understanding several terms and subsequently made it harder to understand what is COVID-19. They did abide by the measures as much as possible. Some of them, due to the lack of resources didn’t have a healthy diet, so they were more exposed to being infected. I remember some mothers feeding their children chips for breakfast, because it was cheap. I teach people that are over 18 years old but come in contact with both older and younger refugees.”

LEA interviewees, in relation to measure conformity and compliance regarding the vaccine, they did not have issues on abiding to the rules and getting vaccinated, however report that several LEAs did not get vaccinated even if the modus operandi within the law enforcement agency stricter than other working environments. Moreover, in some cases the immediate environment of LEAs (i.e. family members) would refuse to be vaccinated as they would consider it a conspiracy or due to the obligatory nature of the vaccine, imposed by the government. LEAs would also indicate that they perceive the obligatory nature of vaccinating negatively as it incites negative reactions. Most LEAs would also suggest that they have been engaged in altercations in non-conformity measures with citizens and would often argue over the details of measures such as movement restriction measures. LEAs indicate that they have been perceived in a negative way by citizens and vulnerable groups as an actor and/or governance system which enforces measure compliance, while also suggest that it is hard to be placed in such a difficult spot which on the one hand ought as part of their role to enforce measures and rules whilst on the other understand how limiting individual liberties can negatively impact citizen perceptions towards LEAs. Concluding, LEAs indicate that most of their colleagues often express their frustration towards how other societal groups would treat them due to their role and duties which would entail enforcing measures and rules.

Most if not all minority participants suggest having abided by the healthcare measures in relation to the pandemic, with the exception of one respondent who strongly opposes vaccination, mostly due to the obligatory nature the governmental response has chosen but claimed to be in favour of vaccines. Several respondents indicated that they have experienced measure conformity in their close social environment due to a vast number of issues such as a general scepticism in minority communities, ignorance, lack of education which hinders critical thinking, susceptibility to disinformation in relation

to vaccines, and lack of necessary financial resources which guarantee survival. In refugee and migrant communities, the fear of not being entitled to financial benefits or educational courses encouraged reluctant members of the aforementioned group to be vaccinated, even if some would not abide by measures such as wearing a mask properly.

“Definitely, particularly in my close environment, people are opposed to vaccinations or do not wear a mask. I have a relative that believes that vaccines have a chip and has not been vaccinated, thus I cannot let him visit us. Measure compliance has certainly impacted our social interactions. On the plane while travelling, I happen to see only two– three passengers wearing a mask besides me; therefore compliance is a constant issue. On public means of transportation such as a bus it is still compulsory to wear a mask but, on a plane, it is optional. Pandemic management and the political cost are directly relevant; I would consider obligatory to wear a mask on planes.”

“Some people didn’t want to get vaccinated; some refugees would wear their masks constantly under the chin but most would abide by the regulations. Some of them would delay the vaccination but got vaccinated so they didn’t lose the financial benefits and courses. Some would come with a rapid test, which also costed a lot so most got vaccinated due to the cost.”

In relation to expressing objections towards the imposed measures, LEAs suggest that at the beginning of the pandemic little cases of expressing objections on public were observed, whilst public negative expressions towards measures was increased gradually and escalated particularly during the second phase during which the second lockdown was implemented, during which the general public was rather exhausted psychologically and emotionally due to the impact of isolation and movement restrictions. Some LEAs suggest that towards the later phases, even LEAs participated in demonstrations against the measures, which is rather important to highlight due to the consequences that their participation may potentially have on their career. In some cases, according to LEAs, several citizens refused to continue with their vaccinations as they got COVID-19 and concluded that it would not matter if they had another round of the vaccine. Concluding, according to LEAs deductions, being unaware of all consequences of the pandemic in combination with fear towards the unknown implications, citizens did not express their objections initially, however this changed due to the psychological and emotional fatigue they experienced due to the movement restriction measures, whilst LEAs are observed to comprehend the severity of the virus, as it has claimed several lives in their personal environment and in the general society.

According to most minority group respondents the highest percentage of non-compliance to measures were experienced and can be identified during two important phases: the second curfew which was during October – November 2020 and the announcement of the mandatory vaccination. According to participants, minority group members were frustrated due to the fact that curfews had proven to have catastrophic financial consequences for the Greek society and minority groups would struggle to ensure income for their survival. In addition, several respondents indicate that the mandatory nature of the vaccination process enraged minority members due to the infringement of individual liberties. These interrelated events amplified the fear of minority members generating increased rates of non-compliance.

“When the vaccine was rolled out, I had no problem with it but only when I understood that they made it obligatory I became more and more negative as well as angry about the whole process. The period should have been between the previous September and December. The

most vivid express of my objection was my participation in the aforementioned demonstration against obligatory vaccinations.”

In certain cases, some LEAs explained that every LEA had the opportunity just like citizens to express their objections, nevertheless, not many objections were recorded particularly at the beginning of the pandemic. Despite being able to express their objections, the majority of LEAs strongly believe that it would not make a difference if they did so, due to the nature of their professional role and *modus operandi*. Moreover, several LEAs indicate that the governmental response could not have been done differently, however, in their opinion, decision and policy makers could have invested more on awareness and information raising in relation to the pandemic, measures and vaccinations. Concluding, LEAs present that their role is rather difficult whilst recognizing that personal choice in relation to the vaccination is very important and suggest that there were no instances of excessive expression of objections from themselves and their colleagues, while some LEAs would have objected to getting vaccinated, have yet to get a vaccine.

“On a personal level I tried to discuss my concerns but on a professional level, I didn’t express any concerns to my superiors because I don’t think that it would make a difference. On the other hand, I don’t think that anything could have been different in relation to how Greece managed the COVID-19 pandemic. People in some cases are very hard to change their habits and behaviour, nevertheless, policy and decision makers should have emphasized more on information and raising awareness.”

Minority participants appear to be divided in relation to whether they had the opportunity to express their objections or concerns in public. Several participants indicate they have not been able to express their concerns due to a lack of representation particularly in the Roma community on the socio-political stage. According to these participants, the Roma community are not aware of their rights and obligations towards the society, in combination with the lack of proper education and ignorance, it causes inaction. Other participants suggest having voiced their concerns towards their close environment due to the belief that they would not be heard by governmental representatives, which indicates a lack of communication between the governmental mechanism and citizens, particularly in minority groups. In one case, a respondent suggests that the role in his employment allows him to voice his concerns via publications, nevertheless, members of his close environment do not have this option. Whereas in a certain case, a respondent who voiced concerns of legality in the environment of employment, was met with anger and indifference.

“I do not consider that my voice has been heard because the Roma community does not have a proper representation, similarly to other minority groups. Since we do not have a direct democracy, someone could act as a representative for the minority group that I also belong. Minority groups such as Roma, do not have a proper representation particularly in the Greek socio-political stage. On a local level, we encounter other issues due to the lack of proper socio-political education. Most Roma members are not aware of their rights and obligations towards the society which creates a domino effect causing them to not being able to properly, politically express themselves and at the same time cannot properly claim their rights. Since there is a lack of socio-political and general education, they cannot express or represent themselves nor properly understand what rights, obligations and how to claim them really mean. This education is lacking at a local societal level leading to ignorance and inaction.”

“I would say that they haven’t had the chance to express their objections. We still observe that the Government does not take into account the objections but tend to only keep in mind the financial situation. For example, only during the summer season the government would take a more flexible stance towards COVID-19. I believe that the government should conduct empirical research utilizing questionnaires to minority groups and the general public, shared in their work places, schools among other places so they can observe their needs. We’ve observed that every European Government exercised their own strategy, and currently we are not performing good based on the infection rate.”

In relation to active steps which could facilitate open dialogue between members of the society and decision makers, participants underlined the importance of municipality centres, schools, social media which could facilitate communication efforts such as awareness and information raising campaigns, in-person meetings with concerned citizens and formal method of documenting these concerns, empirical research utilizing questionnaires to minority groups and general public. These actions seem as feasible actions which would significantly engagement and communication between decision makers, general public and minority groups.

Section 3: COVID-19 Communication and Vaccination Campaigns

Main Research Question: How communication and vaccination campaigns against COVID-19 were perceived by vulnerable groups, minorities and LEAs? How have these responses have affected people’s measure and vaccination compliance?

In general, most LEAs suggest that in relation to the sources of information, vaccination campaigns were reliable whilst the younger generations mostly use the internet and middle to elderly populations tend to utilize the TV and radio. In some cases, LEAs use all means of information whilst some LEAs have distanced themselves from relying on the TV, therefore acquiring their information mainly from the internet. Most LEAs indicate that due to conflicting information and actors whose main objective is to gain wealth via clicks in online articles, it is strongly advised to cross-reference, compare and filter the information and the sources of information. Moreover, LEAs suggest that information and communication campaigns were beneficial in awareness raising particularly with vulnerable groups such as the Roma community which has high rates of illiteracy.

“Communication and information campaigns have certainly acted beneficially on both managing COVID-19 and raising awareness on measures and vaccines. Mobile EODY units that would travel to several places and conduct vaccinations have really helped with the management of the pandemic, particularly with Roma communities, which is rather difficult for them as well to book an appointment, since most Roma members have not graduated from primary school. It’s rather difficult for these communities, whereas if a mobile EODY unit goes to these communities, it is far better for these citizens as well. I am aware of such a case, one of these units went to the community of Agia Sofia. The preference and use of information sources would depend on the age group. Most elderly use the TV as their main source of information, middle-aged people use both the internet and TV, whereas younger populations use mainly the internet. The internet has a vast number of sources and the degree of credibility varies, therefore it is each person’s responsibility to filter information as much as possible. Some people may simply keep the information that they want to hear.”

There is a general negative approach towards the acquisition of information by the Television from most minority group members, who in some cases utilize both traditional (TV) and contemporary

(social media platforms) means of information. According to most respondents, younger populations tend to use the internet more than rely solely on the TV while older populations within their communities rely mostly on the TV and to a lesser extent on the internet, mostly due to technological barriers such as lack of necessary skills to navigate online. In some cases, some respondents indicated they avoid being informed via traditional means (TV) due to the fact that in most cases discussion panels and the news are one-sided and do not encourage open dialogue, while the information from the scientific community is misinterpreted by decision makers and tailored to fit their narrative, which is presented to the general public. Most respondents are observed to favour the acquisition of information online, nevertheless, suggest that both the TV and the internet can have untrustworthy and trustworthy sources of information. Furthermore, it is suggested that presently, most minority members tend to refrain from cross-checking and verifying the validity of sources and may even use the home pages of popular social media as their main source of information without using critical thinking to examine their findings. In addition, most respondents indicated that the communication campaigns were insufficient and ineffective to a certain degree, since they were too generic, not targeted to specific sub-sections of the social structure such as minority groups and very limited. Concluding, some respondents suggest it might be more beneficial to have a more in-person approach to awareness raising campaigns even utilizing door-to-door campaigns, encourage the use of multi-polar, open dialogue discussion panels to examine a wide variety of topics and views as well as utilizing the re-direct method, which is a method that utilized targeted adds which can both inform social media end-users and more importantly, it can act as an effective method to actively combat disinformation.

“The communication campaigns didn’t function properly. Governmental spokespersons made us more confused in certain cases but they were also equally confused. On the one hand they would say this on the other hand they would say that. They didn’t know themselves what was the deal with COVID-19 and communication management of the pandemic wasn’t conducted properly. They didn’t manage this case properly. Most people use the internet but you can find almost everything. The Internet is particularly useful for business activity but in regards to COVID-19, there were a lot of sources which may not be credible, even though it has a lot of credible sources. To stay informed, I use both TV and the internet.”

“Most people that I know of at work got vaccinated, about 80%. The vaccination campaigns were really successful based on the data, however, if we examine the perception of how many people genuinely wanted to have vaccines, there were really only just a few people. In most cases that I know, they just had it because they have been forced to do it so they could work. The authorities utilized measures mostly based in fear. If people are in fear they can be controlled very easily. I happen to know people that get their information from both the TV, typically older people and the internet, which are mostly younger people. There are a lot of people that use both sources but I personally don’t use the TV at all because I can’t stand it. I don’t think the TV is trustworthy. In relation to the internet, it depends on the source as it allows us to find anything and everything, so it actually depends on you whether you feel it’s trustworthy or not.”

LEAs appear conflicted in relation to the implementation of measures and how easy they were to follow. For some LEAs they were relatively easy to follow as it was their duty to read what the measures were about, understand them and enforce these measures. However, for some LEAs they were slightly strange, unclear, were difficult to follow for themselves and other citizens while they also raised legitimate questions due to the lack of clarity, thus adaptation was challenging. Moreover, LEAs

indicate that vulnerable groups such as the elderly were more exposed due to their vulnerability, as in several cases, due to the lack of literacy or lack of tech-savviness, elderly people would frequently reach out to LEAs for assistance in order to avoid being fined and follow the regulations properly.

“They were easy to follow, but not by everyone. I found this out as a police officer. For example, we come into contact with elderly people, that did not know how to use the mobile phone to send SMS in order to get permit, that also didn't know how to write down on a piece of paper the code that we used to go out for groceries, etc., and they came many times to us and ask us the right way to do things, because they didn't want to get charged with a fine, because they were scared. So, the measures weren't clear.”

The majority of the minority respondents suggest that the measures were rather difficult to abide by, and significantly harder to follow as time progressed. Specifically, the most difficult measure to follow was isolation, albeit, several respondents indicated that some were easier to understand than other measures. The main challenges that the respondents faced were the ambiguity that was created and the rapid change of measures, based on the differentiated views scientists and decision makers would provide in short periods of time. One indicator of the confusion that ensued was the lack of a pan-European approach towards COVID-19 measures throughout the duration of the pandemic.

“The measures were rather hard to follow, particularly in the beginning as we needed some time to get used to them. They were rather confusing even though the measures could be proper in terms of prevention and protection against COVID-19, it was a messy situation. I was aware of what I had to do based on the measures.”

From the point of view of LEAs, the measures were hard to follow for most members of society, particularly for vulnerable groups such as the Roma community who would often break the rules. The public in general would abide to the measures particularly during the first pandemic phase, due to fear and lack of knowledge towards COVID-19, whereas at time progressed, according to LEAs, citizens would gradually cease abiding by the rules and regulations, particularly during and beyond the second lockdown, likely due to the impact of movement restriction such as psychological exhaustion and the rollout of the vaccine, which offered a layer of defence which did not exist previously. In addition, LEAs indicate that often citizens would have a misperception that LEAs take joy in punishing offenders, which according to LEAs is not true, while urging other citizens to adopt their point of view. Moreover, LEAs identify social isolation (lockdowns) as the worst possible measure which is accompanied by several negative implications, which is also the hardest measure to abide by. Concluding, LEAs suggest that one core element which influenced the rate of abidance to measures was fear, particularly during the first pandemic phases, which might not be the most suitable mechanism but proved to be effective.

“They were definitely a little hard to follow. At first, there was compliance. It was something new for everyone. The public found it interesting, since it was something different. But along the way they got tired, and the people objected a little, started breaking the measures, for example would go out without sending an SMS message. They started no to care. After the fear passed, it was a bit like they used to it. People were making other false certificate for permit and transportation, so they found a way to handle it somehow. Surely curfews were the hardest to follow, because this, as I said, is a deprivation of freedom, even in such a way, for just a few hours, I think it was difficult to follow.”

In general, respondents suggest that minority groups abide by the measures with a few exceptions in aforementioned cases. The most difficult measure to abide by was social isolation (curfews) for most

if not all participants, while the second curfew was the longest in duration, during which citizens began expressing their frustration and demonstrated higher degree of non-compliance. During the first phase, most participants suggest minority groups similarly to the general public were obedient mostly due to the widespread fear of COVID-19, which nevertheless changed gradually. Some respondents also indicated difficulty in abiding to wearing a mask and social distancing particularly in work environments and unavoidably crowded places such as public means of transportation.

“People in general abided to the rules. If you tell me before the pandemic that such regulations will be enforced, I’d say they wouldn’t abide them. As time went by people just weren’t afraid of COVID-19 anymore so followed them at a lesser rate. Isolation was the hardest measure for, except for a few people that liked to be isolated. This was prevalent for some people with a lot of family members in their home, for the people with a bad neighbourhood, for people that liked going outside and to their work as well as be engaged and others.”

The main role of the Law Enforcement Agencies has been more of being the enforcer of measures, making sure citizens comply with the measures. LEAs appear divided in relation to what could have been done differently, whilst simultaneously providing recommendations such as more emphasis could have been placed on raising awareness and information sharing. Some LEAs suggest that even though the main site of the Hellenic Police had information about prevention, protection and measures uploaded on the website and despite several relevant initiatives were conducted on a local level, most LEAs indicate that further initiatives would be beneficial while in certain occasions LEAs suggested that raising awareness was not part of the duties. Some LEAs suggest that their approach, which was top-down, may have been interpreted as crude, LEAs with specialized training in negotiation and a pre-established network of communication with vulnerable groups such as the Roma community, could have been utilized to achieve better compliance rate due to their familiarity with the target population, while targeted communication campaigns would also be beneficial. Overall, most LEAs suggest that the authorities managed to communicate the measures in a clear and understandable manner, however, there is also space for improvement.

“The society could have utilized people such as myself, who have received special training on negotiations and interaction with (Roma communities) minority groups as well as community representatives, and together we could reach out to these communities and explain what they had to do. It would certainly increase the compliance rate due to the network that I have established with the Roma community. They are aware that we are police officers but they are not hostile to us.”

“The approach that LEAs adopted was mostly orientated to suppression rather than raising awareness and prevention. It was direct and not as discrete as it should have been. We as police officers didn’t have raising awareness as one of our responsibilities.”

Most if not all participants indicate that the communication efforts from the authorities were insufficient. In certain cases, the authorities were non-responsive to real time interaction requests and some representatives were unsure which information to convey upon requests. Minority group members consider that LEAs in particular were simply doing their job despite the negative publicity some of their colleagues attracted in isolated incidents, nevertheless highlighting that their approach could be politer and more humane. Moreover, minority group respondents consider that it is crucial that LEAs acquire better education on social interactions and be provided with psychological support as they encounter several cases that would impact their mental health and well-being. Concluding,

during the pandemic, respondents suggested that the modus operandi was the utilization of fear, which is a wrong approach and instead suggest that there is a need for a common framework for authorities on how to implement measures and an added emphasis on the scientific community, which could also involve embassies to provide support by informing their nationals who reside or temporary stay in each country.

“To be honest, I didn’t have a response to my inquiries. I manage to acquire information from a variety of blogs and from conversing with my friends. Maybe from one side the state mechanism was not inclined to have an active information exchange and real-time interaction as they also didn’t know what would happen the next day since they adopted a reactive model instead of an approach of prevention. They didn’t manage to properly inform the public, since on several occasions, when I called the relevant state representatives, they didn’t know what was the proper information that they should provide.”

According to LEAs, information and communication campaigns have influenced the citizens’ compliance rate, whereas they suggest that vulnerable citizens would also take the initiative to stay informed at a significant high rate in order to protect themselves and their family. LEAs suggest that decision makers could have utilized specialized LEA personnel in order to bridge any potential gaps of miscommunication or interpretation. Moreover, LEAs agree that decision makers capitalized on fear which was a motivating factor for compliance, which could have been exaggerated as a method but proved effective despite the relevant implications, which have contributed to raising objections and frustration. In addition, some LEAs suggest that there were practical insufficiencies such as the lack of protective equipment (i.e., gloves) while they also observe that the information campaigns have contributed to turning good hygiene practices into daily life habits that several citizens still continue to employ in their daily lives without being obliged to do so, which can be considered as a positive outcome.

The majority of minority group respondents underlined that measure compliance and influencing citizens to be vaccinated was not due to information and communication campaigns but rather to the holistic enforcement of fines and the widespread fear on which the authorities based their approaches. According to one respondent, upon examination of data, communication and information campaigns were successful, however, most citizens were vaccinated due to fear of losing their employment. Respondents suggest that, instead of accusing the “youth” who are “irresponsible”, the authorities and media should have elaborated more on the usefulness and operating mechanisms of the vaccines as well as the potential side-effects in a clear and honest manner.

“I would suggest that fear was the most motivational factor. Those that believed in the pandemic and measures would either way comply with the measures and get vaccinated, the campaigns mostly aimed in convincing the people that objected to comply and get vaccinated. In relation to that, campaigns failed. Most of them that opposed, abided by the measures and got vaccinated due to fear of losing their jobs. In this context the State and authorities have failed. We can observe healthcare personnel that refused to be vaccinated and are unemployed, thus it is evident that they have failed. Would they be able to convince Roma communities easier than the healthcare personnel? I wouldn’t think so, thus they failed in their communication.”

In relation to motivating, influencing factors regarding citizen’s decision to be vaccinated, LEAs suggest that even though vaccination campaigns were beneficial, willingness towards vaccination is a matter

of interpretation from each citizen's point of view. According to LEAs, most citizens were vaccinated mostly due to widespread fear on the health-related consequences of the virus, some citizens made an informed decision to be vaccinated, others refused to be vaccinated due to their religious beliefs or due to the impression that being young wouldn't prevent COVID-19 from severely impacting them. Overall, some LEAs indicate that even if different means and methods were utilized, positive and negative reactions would still exist, attributing the phenomenon as part of human nature. Concluding, LEAs suggest that the refusal to be vaccinated for some citizens could have been partially due to how the vaccination was presented online and how it has been interpreted, therefore as the governmental response insisted on having citizens vaccinated, it may have worked counterproductively, as it may have intensified the sentiment of refusal.

According to some minority group participants, the vaccination campaign was successful and the awareness raising campaigns contributed in increasing the vaccination rates due to explaining how beneficial a vaccine can be against COVID-19, however, interpret the increased vaccination rate mostly due to widespread fear of getting fined and pressure.

“The fines once again contributed far more in refugees getting fined rather than vaccination information campaigns. Most of them want to leave the country, so the last thing they want is an issue with the authorities.”

Section 4: Trust in the era of COVID-19

Main Research Question: How has COVID-19 management affected people's trust towards authorities?

Most LEAs indicate that their approach and treatment of citizens, both in relation to the general population and vulnerable groups, was fair, equal and there was no discrimination. LEAs suggest that increased checks were conducted to the Roma community as this demographic group presented higher rates of non-compliance in comparison to both the general population and other vulnerable groups such as the migrant communities, who presented zeal in abiding to the measures. LEAs appear conflicted on the perceptions of the general public towards LEAs, from their side towards other social groups as well or even between Agencies. LEAs suggest that if negative pre-existing perceptions towards them existed within the general public, they were exacerbated due to their role as enforcers of order and measures, whereas some LEAs suggest that perceptions would not radically change towards them. While most LEAs agree that they have treated all societal groups fairly and equally, in some cases particularly for vulnerable groups such as the Roma community and in order to fill societal gaps as well as mitigate existing vulnerabilities, LEAs would be lenient towards Roma and would not fine but try to educate on how to better comply with the measures in order to not get fined in the future. Concluding some LEAs indicate that due to the role that the Hellenic Police had adopted, as well as the increased liberty in exercising these duties, it would potentially create a feeling of injustice among other LEAs who also contributed in the fight against the pandemic.

“Surely it wasn't equal to everyone. There were colleagues who, as I told you, were trying to educate the various social groups on how to comprehend the measures. There were other groups who tried to impose the measures on these social groups because they considered them powerless to react or do otherwise. So, it's a bit absolute in that sense. What I am trying to say is that within those groups there might be people that may not have been aware of the measures, so we turned a blind eye a bit to help explain to them what was actually occurring. There were Roma, for example, who did not know that there was a quarantine and a curfew,

because they may not have a source of information, so we did not immediately impose the measures on these people. In other words, we were giving them a second chance. We let them go without a fine (...)"

Minority group respondents appear to be divided in the issue of trust. Some respondents indicated that the treatment of minority groups was equal in all cases which could also be problematic. Some other participants highlighted that truly equal approach to all citizens is not feasible and citizens of higher socio-financial status enjoyed liberties in contrast to average and low-income citizens as well as minority groups who are considered to be more vulnerable, underlining that most citizens have lost their trust towards local, regional and national authorities in Europe. Most respondents suggest that their perceptions towards healthcare experts did not change and continue to trust them, whereas only a small percentage has been more negatively reactive towards LEAs. In general, according to some respondents, LEAs have treated minority groups fairly and equally, nevertheless, one respondent claimed that the authorities would treat migrants and refugees not as equal to native residents, who would be fined frequently during the first phase. According to this respondent's interpretation, the authorities intended to make an example out of refugees and migrants in order to demonstrate the results of their approach. The language barrier and lack of assistance from embassies, would certainly hinder the living conditions of refugees and migrants during the first phases, who were actively assisted by employees and NGO representatives who communicate with them on a daily basis. Concluding, one participant suggested that it is impossible to have an equal treatment and enforce the measures completely, if a society is unable to accommodate the needs of vulnerable people such as homeless individuals among other, whereas the COVID-19 pandemic created a falsified image of LEAs as the "enemy" who on the one hand actively work to protect citizens and their rights and on the other the implemented measures would restrict citizen liberties.

According to LEAs, pre-existing lack of trust was intensified, particularly in cases where citizens were fined due to violations of the measures. Disgruntled citizens changed their perception towards LEAs due to being fined, while LEAs suggest that in case a different course of action was adopted, reactions would still emerge. Moreover, according to LEAs, in general due to their profession, new duties and role, it would also negatively impact citizens' perceptions and trust towards LEAs. Some LEAs suggest that the minorities have treated LEAs the same way as prior to the pandemic. For the majority of LEAs, the most crucial period was during the second lockdown during which the society experienced psychological exhaustion due to the prolonged measures, therefore more violations to the measures were recorded in comparison to the first lockdown phase.

"I think what counts and what I keep telling you, is that the imposition of measures by the police on the citizens, made them see us as punishers. It's like, that you don't comply with the measures, I will punish you. That we didn't care about anything other than crime and keeping the peace in the neighbourhoods. That our issue was just how to fine someone who goes out, without a certificate. The critical time-period was during the quarantine because there was the deprivation of liberty, so the measures were more severe, and we had to enforce them."

Most minority group respondents suggest that during lockdowns and particularly during the second lockdown, people changed their approach towards LEAs due to widespread frustration, which was intensified as according to one participant, it was apparent that the social control was much stricter to lower socio-economic classes. Several participants suggested that due to the management of the pandemic and how information was conveyed, citizens tend to trust the authorities and the media less. In certain areas, particularly after cases which attracted negative attention, locals do not consider

themselves to be as much protected by the police as they should have been. Especially the high rate of frequent and daily criminal activities in comparison to how many anti-riot police personnel (MAT) would participate in a protest, can generate mistrust towards the objectives and priorities of LEAs. Concluding, participants suggest that it is very important that proper training and education should be provided to LEAs.

“I cannot trust the authorities particularly after observing the lies and propaganda that was spread through the TV and media. In relation to the vaccine, only a few people lost their trust towards the authorities overall during the pandemic.”

In relation to the pandemic being a catalyst in changing the levels of trust from vulnerable groups and minorities towards LEAs, most interviewees suggest that the pandemic would not change the levels of trust and if it did, it would be a limited change. On the contrary, some LEAs indicate that the pandemic can have a catalyst role and trust was decreased, hence LEAs present differentiated opinions. Moreover, based on official statistics of the Eurobarometer, LEAs suggest that there is a high level of trust towards LEAs and that trust would positively increase towards healthcare personnel and experts as a consequence of the pandemic. Most if not all LEAs, overall, suggest that any change in trust would mostly be attributed to systemic weaknesses, implemented measures that limit individual liberties and their role in ensuring that citizens abide by measures as well as fining the offenders. Concluding, LEAs suggest that a change in trust and perception towards LEAs is a normal consequence for minority groups such as the Roma community, because LEAs would conduct more frequent checks due to instances of non-compliance, thus it can generate a negative reaction as a result.

“Roma communities had been at the receiving end of more checks from LEAs in comparison to pre-pandemic years. It is reasonable that nobody likes to be checked upon by the police, not even me. If someone checked up on me all the time, I would be frustrated, it is completely comprehensible. On the other hand, we check up on people exactly because we want citizens to abide by the measures and contain the pandemic, thus make the pandemic management most feasible.”

Most minority group participants firmly believe that the COVID-19 pandemic had a catalyst role in relation to trust towards the authorities. More specifically, trust was influenced due to the ignorance, lack of clarity in measure and practices that were implemented. Trust can be influenced by major events such as the economic crisis. Participants suggest that active steps need to be taken in order to increase trust, such as adopting a welfare, care and assistance model, targeting the lower socio-economical groups and providing information on relevant measures and practices in a clear manner. More specifically, according to participants, minority groups such as the Roma community, trust towards LEAs has not been influenced, however they trust politicians even less. Concluding, one participant suggested that trust is influenced according to the engagement, support and accommodation of needs, also the degree that decision makers pay attention to vulnerable groups, instead of solely on an individual event that may influence them.

“I firmly believe that the trust has been shaken due to ignorance and not clear measures and practices that were implemented. This could potentially change if a model of welfare, care and assistance is adhered, targeting the base of the socio-economic pyramid as well as the provision of much more clear information on the relevant measures and practices. It will have a significantly positive effect on peoples’ perception.”

The majority of LEAs indicate that COVID-19 has caused a long-lasting impact on society and that similarly to other endemics and pandemics, society will adapt to living alongside with COVID-19 while mitigating the consequences and impact, particularly through vaccination. All LEAs suggest that citizens have incorporated specific elements in their daily lives, which are drawn from the COVID-19 regulations, measures, personal hygiene and relevant guidelines as citizens are observed to be reluctant to visit high human density places, such as avoid public means of transportation, avoid human interaction to a certain degree due to fear and awareness of how diseases can impact their lives. In some cases, COVID-19 may have fuelled conspiracy theories nevertheless, LEAs suggest that most citizens have experienced the pandemic without adopting radical opinions or ideas, while intending to continue living their lives as they did prior to COVID-19. Moreover, some LEAs strongly encourage that before citizens act based on their emotions, particularly participating in protests and being violent towards LEAs, they should try to comprehend the difficult position LEAs have been placed in. Concluding, some LEAs suggest that they would prefer a higher rate of support from the State, as they have been the tip of the spear in the fight against the pandemic, thus, also more exposed to the public's negative reactions towards the implementation of measures and pandemic management.

"(...) I noticed differences in people's attitudes and behaviour, since they are now definitely different, they have changed. People are more careful, more afraid, they choose to stay at home, than get involved in various events and activities that have to do with contact with other people. So, people's attitudes have definitely changed, yes."

The majority of minority group participants suggest that they have experienced the negative psychological, physical and socio-economic consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on a personal level. Several participants indicated the destructive effect that COVID-19 has had on the most vulnerable populations and children. These psychological impacts often make minority groups and the general public to express themselves based on the negative pressure they experienced during the pandemic, whereas several respondents indicate the importance of facilitating open dialogue between the wider social structure and the minority communities on bridging the gaps and identifying courses of action that can be beneficial for minority communities, particularly in their socio-economic and psychological wellbeing. In addition, some participants indicate the need to erase at least some of the fines that were imposed, particularly on small and medium businesses who could potentially be led to permanent closure due to the financial pressure as well as minority groups who encountered cultural and language barriers, thus, were fined. Concluding, minority group participants highlight the efforts of healthcare professionals during the pandemic and underline the need to substantially reinforce the healthcare system.

"I have been negatively impacted psychologically just like the rest of the people that I encounter. People are more frightened, they have been impacted economically, they are more secluded to themselves, and have become more pessimistic. Nowadays they are not as liberated, they are more reserved in how they live their lives. As final personal comments, I would have to add that the governmental assistance that helped businesses that have been impacted by COVID-19 is a good measure, however it is completely wrong to request half of the donated amount to be given back to the state. They need to financially assist businesses as COVID-19 had a devastating effect and erase at least some of the fines that have been issued. They need to take into account that these businesses support families, employees and based on these businesses the market is able to cope with the situation. These big fines are completely

wrong in my opinion. The state also needs to make hospitals more organized and assist businesses and civilians economically.”

2.5.6 Conclusions

This case study explored the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on Law Enforcement Agents (LEAs) and minority groups in Greece, focusing on their personal and professional lives. The **first section** of this case study focused on the Law Enforcement Agents and minority groups personal perception of COVID-19 and how it has impacted their daily life and professional environment. The **second section** of this case study examined the perceived impact of the implemented COVID-19 measures on LEAs, minority – vulnerable groups, thus, focused on perceptions, social interaction, and measure compliance. The **third section** of this case study focused on communication and interviewees’ perceptions in relation to information which may have impacted vaccination rates. The **fourth section** of this case study focused on trust and how COVID-19 has impacted trust among target populations.

Main Findings:

- **Multi-dimensional Impact:** Both LEAs and minority groups experienced changes in their social interactions, increased workload, stress levels, and a negative effect on mental well-being and financial status due to the pandemic.
- **Social Isolation:** Both groups highlighted the adverse effects of social isolation and the changes in interpersonal relations brought about by remote interactions.
- **Pandemic Response:** LEAs believed Greece had a successful pandemic response, despite both groups acknowledging that their quality of life was negatively affected.
- **Awareness of Hygiene Protocols:** The pandemic heightened the awareness of hygiene protocols, which became important in both their professional and personal lives.
- **Changes in Work Environment:** The pandemic brought about mixed reactions regarding remote work; while it hindered the process for some, others found it to be successful.
- **Adherence to Measures:** Both groups largely adhered to the pandemic measures despite facing hardships due to unclear guidelines and economic fines. LEAs considered adherence as their duty and displayed leniency wherever possible.
- **Representation in Socio-political Stage:** Minority groups felt inadequately represented in the socio-political arena, which made voicing their concerns challenging.

Lessons Learned & Recommendations:

- **Balanced Approach to Mitigation Measures:** Future policies should consider the socio-economic and mental health repercussions of non-pharmaceutical interventions like lockdowns.
- **Strengthening Healthcare System:** Governmental mechanisms should invest more in bolstering the healthcare system and facilitating community engagement, especially with minority and marginalized groups.
- **Transparent Communication:** Politicians and the media should maintain an honest, human-centered approach in communication.

- **Labor Rights Protection:** Implement mechanisms to protect the rights of employees working remotely, safeguarding them from exploitation.
- **Prepared & Post-Pandemic Response Strategy:** Development of clear, actionable strategies that address the vulnerabilities of marginalized groups for better post-pandemic recovery.
- **LEAs as Role Models:** LEAs need to be cautious and respectful while implementing measures, considering their status as role models in society.
- **Policy Adjustments:** Policy experts should learn from the pandemic and actively work to reinforce identified systemic weaknesses, including providing adequate support to businesses and individuals.
- **Vaccination Strategy:** The government should reconsider the mandatory vaccination mechanism, possibly making it optional to respect individual rights and counter misinformation through clear, science-based communication.
- **Mental Health Considerations:** Address the mental health implications of prolonged social isolation and the contributing factors leading to non-compliance with the measures.
- **Bridging Communication Gaps:** Encourage initiatives that bridge communication gaps and facilitate open dialogue between community members and decision-makers, focusing on addressing the concerns of marginalized groups.

In sum, this case study underlines the necessity for balanced pandemic responses and strategies that consider socio-economic and mental health aspects, with an emphasis on transparent communication and safeguarding the rights and well-being of all community sectors.

2.6 Italy, SAPIENZA & UCSC

2.6.1 Introduction

To date, 26,127,700 cases of confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infections have been reported in Italy, of which 484,558 were among Health Care Workers (HCWs). At the very beginning of the pandemic, in April 2020, the Italian National Institute of Health (ISS) reported that 16,991 HCWs had tested positive for SARS-CoV-2. These HCWs had a median age of 48 years, 68% were women and 32% were men, which is in line with the gender composition of HCWs in the Italian healthcare system (66.8% women and 33.2% men). The infected HCWs accounted for 10.7% of the total number of positive cases. The estimates showed that medical doctors' deaths were the majority (n=119, 57.8% of total deaths); followed by nurses 16.5% (n = 34), nurse aides 8.3% (n = 17) and dentists 5.8% (n = 12). The COVID-19-related deaths include 2 nurses who committed suicide due to unsustainable pressure at work. The number of deaths among Italian HCWs was higher as compared to that registered during the same period in other countries including China, where the epidemic began. General practitioners were the most hit among all medical specialties, registering 32% deaths (n = 66).

HCWs had earlier access to vaccines compared to most of their patients, their families, and the population at large. Despite their background, some HCWs have been reluctant to vaccinate. Additionally, Italy was the first country in Europe to make vaccination against Covid-19 mandatory for HCWs, as its government approved an emergency decree on the 1st of April 2021 to contain a third wave of the disease. HCWs who refused the vaccination had the option of being transferred to jobs

that do not risk spreading the virus or being suspended without pay for one year. The decree has been in force till the 31st of October 2022.

Overall, the Covid-19 pandemic has imposed a significant burden on Italian healthcare workers (HCWs). Italian HCWs had been through a shortage of equipment and personnel and unprecedented personal restrictions. They had to deal with the pain of losing their patients and cope with the feeling of personal isolation. This increased Italian HCWs risk of adverse psychosocial outcomes.

A large body of literature has shown that HCWs were at increased risk of infection and suffering from poor mental health during the pandemic. In addition, the daily lives of HCWs and their families have been widely disrupted by the pandemic. This may have affected the division of family labour and the gender norms that govern it. The workload for HCWs was already high before the pandemic due to public health spending cuts. Unpaid care work within the family has traditionally been performed largely by women, creating a double workload for employed women (including HCWs) already before the pandemic.

Even if HCWs did not suffer income or job losses during the pandemic, however their family members may have suffered from job or income loss. The government targeted the HCWs with some special support measures, such as the babysitter bonus or the mandatory vaccination against Covid-19. The reactions to these measures varied. For example, at first, some HCWs protested mandatory vaccination. Nowadays, almost all the HCWs are fully vaccinated. Some support measures, such as free psychological support for HCWs were never introduced or varied greatly from region to region. Moreover, the pandemic may have affected the relationship between HCWs and their employers as well as their level of trust into the organization of the health system. The public's view of HCWs changed considerably during the pandemic, from an idealised view (heroes) to stigma and back to more (perhaps?) normality.

Giving the above background considerations, our case study builds on the evidence that is important to acquire more insights on the wellbeing of Italian HCWs. More national data are needed to understand the short and long-term consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic and to inform policies. Special attention should be given to the threats of gender inequalities and family distress. Therefore, the goal of this case study is to explore the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic on physical and mental wellbeing of Italian health care workers (HCWs), as well as its impact on their daily life and family relations. To this end, using a mixed method approach, we have developed a survey based on the Policlinico Gemelli hospital located in the city of Rome. Respondents were HCWs with different types of occupation, including nurses, generalist medical doctors, specialist medical doctors, etc. In addition to infections, the focus of this case study is the analysis of the effect of the pandemic on HCWs mental health (levels of stress, burnout, resilience, vaccine hesitancy) and several well-being indicators (including time use indicators, family distress, family work conflicts). Furthermore, we have analysed health workers' attitudes towards the vaccine.

The case study is designed to better understand the impact on the health workers population of the initial levels of preparedness of the health care system, the response of central and regional authorities and the resulting adaptability of hospital facilities at the local level.

Socio-economic differences have been addressed by including health workers with different professions (e.g., nurses and doctors), education levels, income, age and gender in our study. Multilevel governance processes were considered as the Italian health system is a regionally based national health service that provides universal coverage largely free at the point of delivery.

Figure 15. SAPIENZA & UCSC, Italy – SES Framework.

2.6.2 Purpose and Research Questions

As stated in the introduction, the goal of this case study is to explore the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic on physical and mental wellbeing of Italian health care workers (HCWs), as well as its impact on their daily life and family relations. To this end, the case study has been designed and implemented to respond to the following overarching research questions:

- RQ 1: What have been the consequences of the pandemic on the well-being of health workers, both in physical and mental status? Among health professionals, which socio-demographic groups are at greatest risk of experiencing negative mental health consequences and/or family distress?
- RQ 2: In which way and to what extent have daily life and family relations changed due to the pandemic for health care workers? How have health workers, and especially parents of young children, handled their family responsibilities during the different phases of the pandemic?
- RQ 3: In which way and to what extent have working life changed due to the pandemic for health care workers? Has the pandemic in any way altered or influenced (negatively or positively) the relation between Health care workers and their employers? Has the pandemic brought greater concerns of professional liability?
- RQ 4: What aspects of healthcare workers' lives are the greatest cause for concern and how do they change over time? What are the coping strategies?
- RQ 5: What lessons or good practices can be learned from the pandemic to improve support for health practitioners in managing their work-life balance (including in emergency situations)?

2.6.3 Method

We applied a mixed methods approach, which includes both qualitative and quantitative fieldwork. Data collection methods have included a quantitative survey with HCWs and individual (semi-structured) interviews with HCWs. The growing inclination toward methodological pluralism among researchers in both quantitative and qualitative fields underscore the potential for qualitative and quantitative methods to enhance each other (e.g., Aspers & Corte 2019; Lareau 2012; Spillman 2019). Indeed, we believe that the combination of qualitative and quantitative data leads to acquiring deeper knowledge on the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic on physical and mental well-being of Italian HCWs.

Quantitative data collection:

The implementation of the survey followed several steps: first, we identified the target population, namely the HCWs working at the Policlinic Gemelli. Given that the Policlinic Gemelli currently employed 2094 nurses and 1009 physicians, we planned to include at least 100 physicians and 200 nurses.

We then planned the questionnaire, following a twofold criterion: try to limit as much as possible the fatigue of the respondents and to provide evidence for our research questions. Therefore, even if we decided to limit the number of questions, we had to get the information needed for our case study to be relevant. The questionnaire is organised in 4 main domains:

1. Socio-demographic information

2. The effects of the pandemic on work life
3. The effects of the pandemic on family life
4. Perceptions of pandemic management

The total number of questions is 53 (including filter questions) and it is available in Annex I. The questions considered different periods of the pandemic, namely phase 1: 2020; phase 2: 2021-2022; phase 3: November-December 2022. Between mid-October and the first decade of November 2022, we conducted a small-scale pilot survey to test the clarity of the questions and the questionnaire completion time. The questionnaire was slightly adapted after the pilot phase. The completion time ranged between 15 and 20 minutes.

As for the method of data collection, we decided to use an online survey (self-compiled questionnaire) to guarantee anonymity and to leave the respondents the choice about the time to fill-in the questionnaire.

EUSurvey was chosen as the hosting platform for the survey based on several criteria. First and foremost, its selection was driven by its adherence to the ethical standards of the COVINFORM project. EUSurvey's "template privacy statement" assured that all online survey responses are securely recorded in a protected database managed by the Data Centre of the European Commission. The Commission's strict security protocols and provisions, as established by the Directorate of Security for such servers and services, ensure that the database remains inaccessible from outside the Commission. Only authorized personnel with a specific User Id/Password can access the database within the Commission.

Furthermore, the decision to use EUSurvey was influenced by its extensive language support, catering to a wide range of languages. Additionally, being a free service for EU citizens made it an attractive option. Moreover, the platform offered a mobile-friendly version of surveys, which proved beneficial for users with low-processing power devices.

The survey involved the collection of personal data, which necessitated providing participants with an overview of their data protection rights. To accomplish this, in the survey introduction were included details about Italian legislation on data protection.

The questionnaire was sent via email on the 11th of November 2022, providing the potential respondents with information about the data collection, the aim of the survey and the relevant privacy information. To access the questionnaire, the respondent had to click on a link in the email. The response rate was very high in the first 10 days after the opening of the questionnaire, we had already collected 500 responses. A reminder to the potential respondents was sent via email at the end of December 2022. In January 2023 we closed the possibility to reply to the questionnaire. The total number of collected questionnaires is 725, which is well beyond our initial planning of the interviews. This demonstrates the significant interest in the topic under investigation.

Qualitative data collection:

Once the data collection ended, we proceeded with data cleaning and data analysis. At first, we performed descriptive statistics on the four main domains. According to the results of the descriptive statistics, we planned the follow-up qualitative survey, based on semi-structured interviews, using a convenience sampling.

We included professional workers (nurses, physicians, and midwives) working at the Policlinic Gemelli of Rome who had already replied to the quantitative questionnaire. For the recruitment for semi-structured interviews: the participants were identified with the support of the head physicians and nurse coordinators, who informed them of the study aims and will provide them with the personal contact of one of the investigators. Those who were willing to participate, spontaneously contacted through mail or telephone call the investigators. A copy of the consensus form and a demographic form to fill has been provided to each participant. To be considered eligible the HCWs should (i) have been actively working at the Policlinic since the first wave of Covid-19 (March 2020); (ii) be a professional worker, as per World Health Organization definition (2006); (iii) be able to provide written consent. We excluded residences or nursing students and administrative staff.

We collected 10 semi-structured interviews, 8 women and 2 men, mean age 49, all Italian citizens born in Italy. The questions revolved around the same domains used for the quantitative survey according to the thematic block script.

2.6.4 Results: Data reporting

General demographic characteristics

Quantitative survey: The data were collected between September 2022 and December 2022/ January 2023 in the Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS in Rome.

There were 725 participants, 573 of them were women and 152 were men.

Most of the women were between the ages of 40 and 49 (29.0%) and 50 and 59 (36.3%). Only 11.9% and 16.2%, respectively, were in their 20s and 30s. 6.6% of the women workers were only 60 or older. Men's age groups also tended to fall into the ranges of 40-49 (29.0%) and 50-59 (36.3%), while 24.3% were between 30-39 years old and just 6.6% of men were between 20 and 29 years old. The remaining 13.2% were men who were 60 or older.

Only 5 participants did not have Italian citizenship and they were all women.

A major part of the women were nurses (67.2%) and only 11.9% reported being doctors, while for the men only 34.9% worked as nurses and, instead, 34.2% declared to be doctors. The other 20.9% of the women and 30.1% of the men were doing other jobs as Auxiliary healthcare assistants, midwives, Rehabilitation health professionals, Radiology technicians and Others.

Qualitative interviews: We performed 10 semi-structured interviews, 8 women and 2 men, mean age 49, all Italian citizens born in Italy. 7 out of 10 were in a couple, 3 singles. 8 out of 10 (all the women) were nurses, while the 2 men were doctors. Only 2 out of 10 had children.

2.6.5 Results: Analysis and Interpretation

The data analysis followed different steps: it started with descriptive statistics of the sample, by gender, age and profession (see Appendix B, Annex 6.1), then it was performed a multivariate linear regression (see Appendix B, Annex 6.2) and finally it was complemented by the analysis of the transcript of the qualitative fieldwork.

Overall, the pandemic has largely affected the daily lives of HCWs of Policlinico Gemelli hospital, especially from the point of view of stress (mental health-RQ1). More specifically the results of our survey show that during the phase 1 of the pandemic, the daily life has changed of HCWs as they had to devote more time to work (24.27%), family (29.93%) and children (21.11%), in comparison with

before the pandemic. Their resting time has lowered a lot (52.83% declared to sleep less than before the pandemic) together with their free time (79.45% declared to have less free time than before the pandemic).

Furthermore, focusing on the family lives of HCWs (RQ2), most of the family responsibilities were left to women (33.5%) who were also working as nurses (33.11%). While most of the men declared that their partner was responsible for the family duties (26.97%) together with most of the doctors (30%). Despite this, it seems that in general, satisfaction with the division of household tasks with the partner is the same as before the pandemic. After phase 1 the domestic workload has remained stable, or it has increased for the large majority of HCWs.

In general, the relationship with cohabitants is not easy for HCWs: 49% report a very bad relationship with the partner, 42.86% with children. However, the relationship with partners in most of the cases was the same before the pandemic (64.79%) and in 19.06% of the cases it has improved after the COVID-19 pandemic. The same is true also for the relationship with children.

Roughly half of the HCWs (48.41%) had to isolate themselves from their family during phase 1.

As far as RQ3 and RQ4 are concerned, work is considered by both men and women as the main source of stress (39.72%), followed by the general situation (16.55%), the management of the daily life (16.55%) and the economic situation (10.76%). The younger HCWs (20-29 years old) are those most stressed by work (55.13%). Interestingly stress caused by work decreases with age, those aged more than 50 years being the least stressed (34.82%). Anyway, notwithstanding with age, work is the first source of stress for HCWs. The youngest are more concerned with the economic situation, while the older (50 and more) with the general situation with the management of daily life and with health. Work is the main source of stress by most doctors (55%) and nurses (38.36%). Moreover, the large majority of HCWs attributed the score 3 (30.62%), 4 (33.24%) and 5 (20%) to their stress situation on a scale from 1 to 5. HCWs are generally highly satisfied with their job (77.59%).

The pandemic has implied major changes for most of the HCWs in terms of work duties and on the stress caused by work. Half of our sample has worked (35.86%) or works at present (13.79) in a COVID-19 unit. Among those HCWs who have worked or who work at present in a COVID-19 unit 56.5% are nurses and 37.5% doctors. Furthermore 20% of nurses and 7.5% of doctors worked or currently work in intensive care units (ICU). The large majority of HCWs has worked or currently works with COVID-19 patients (74.34%). During phase 1 of COVID-19 most of the HCWs had to deal with longer working hours: 77.65% of them declared to have worked extra hours daily, several times per week or at least once per week. Even if they worked extra hours and they were under pressure, they declared to be quite satisfied of their duties (68.41%) and that the relationship and the communication with their superiors was good (48.38%), however, they think that the planning of work could have been better (32.27%). The relationship with colleagues, considered overall good (58.62%), was only partially affected by COVID-19, 67.59% of HCWs declared that the relationship did not change, while 13% declared that it has improved and 13% that it has worsened.

The vast majority of HCWs were infected by COVID-19 (67%) and 38.9% reported consequences of COVID-19 on their health after one month from the contagion.

During phase 1 most of the HCWs reported high levels of fatigue: to have to face another working day (75.18%), to be emotionally exhausted (76.41%).

Overall, the stress was increased by being a woman, and by the type of occupation, auxiliary health care assistant and rehabilitation health professionals, being the most exposed to stress, followed by medical doctors and nurses (Appendix B, Annex 6.2).

This result is coherent with previous studies on HCWs and the pandemic: according to a recent meta-analysis conducted by De Souza et al. in 2021, the pandemic has led to a significant increase in the prevalence of mental health issues from 20% to 36% in the general population. However, it was observed that healthcare workers (HCWs) faced even higher rates of anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) compared to the general population.

Additionally, HCWs showed elevated levels of sleep disorders, stress, and burnout syndrome, which are classified as psychophysiological stress conditions (De Souza et al., 2021). Scholars like Fernandez et al. (2021), Abraham et al. (2021), and Lenzo et al. (2021) have delved into the rising rates of anxiety and depression among HCWs. It is important to note that these figures might be underestimated due to cultural norms discouraging complaints or the fear of being stigmatized as unstable.

Coping strategies were particularly important for HCWs during the first phase of the pandemic: most of them declared to have found creative or alternative ways to handle difficult situations (71%), thought that the pandemic could be an opportunity for professional growth (56%), and has actively seek ways to fill the losses caused by the pandemic (57%). Women and younger HCWs were more proactive than men in adopting coping strategies during the first phase of the pandemic, while no major differences were found among different professional profiles of HCWs.

Finally, as far as the communication strategies about the contagion and the vaccination campaign during Phase 1 of the pandemic, the HCWs are globally satisfied by the information provided by their employer, while they are strongly critical about the information provided by the media. Governmental, regional govern and ministry of health communication was judged sufficient, but it could have been better.

2.6.6 Conclusions

The case study has analysed the impact of the pandemic on health workers and their families. The responses have been analysed in terms of physical and mental discomfort related to work pressure, and difficulties in reconciling work and family life, and has provided useful information for policy makers to increase the well-being of health care workers and their families.

Our study helps to identify risks and vulnerabilities for health care workers belonging to different socio-economic groups, and we have developed a set of proposals to improve their wellbeing and work-life balance.

First, as in previous studies we have found an increase of stress in HCWs caused by increased working hours and lack of sleep. Indeed, like in other context, at Policlinico Gemelli, the pandemic has significantly impacted HCWs' daily lives and sleep quality (De Souza et al., 2021), with insomnia disorders being common during peak periods (McCall et al., 2021), affecting their ability to provide care. To address this situation, it is crucial for institutions and stakeholders to regularly screen HCWs for insomnia levels and psychological disorders (Sahebi et al., 2021). By implementing appropriate supportive measures and timely interventions, the incidence of more severe psychological issues can be reduced, thereby improving the long-term work efficiency of HCWs (Sahebi et al., 2021).

Moreover, the pandemic has particularly affected young and women HCWs both from the professional and from the family life point of view. Not surprisingly those who were most vulnerable were also the

most resilient: they adopted different coping strategies to face the new situation at work. They were proactive in finding creative or alternative ways to handle difficult situations, they believed that the pandemic could be an opportunity for professional growth, and they were actively seeking ways to fill the losses caused by the pandemic. Also, the personal lives of HCWs have been largely affected by the pandemic: also, in this case women bore the more responsibilities in performing domestic tasks, witnessing a great increase with respect to the period before the pandemic.

Phase 1 was undoubtedly full of new challenges for HCWs both for their professional and for their family life. However, once the vaccination rollout started and till the end of the emergency phase, they did not come back to “normal” pre-pandemic life. It seems that changes occurred during Phase 1 in professional and family life were quite permanent.

Surprisingly, even if the workload and the stress were enormous, the HCWs were generally satisfied with their jobs, with the interactions with their colleagues and employers and with the information received about the pandemic by their employers. Much more critical is their position toward the mass media and the Government, especially in terms of communication about the pandemic and the vaccines.

Overall, one of the primary challenges in responding to the Covid-19 pandemic is supporting the mental health of healthcare workers (HCWs). A recent systematic review conducted by Buselli et al. in 2021 revealed that many hospitals have developed supportive care programs using a multidisciplinary approach. These programs aim to provide emotional support through counselling and motivational interventions. Various strategies, such as team training, peer support, and institutional assistance, are employed in these interventions. The overarching goal of all these supportive care programs is to manage the psychosocial impact of Covid-19 on HCWs and prevent long-term mental health issues.

Despite our awareness of the impact of Covid-19 on HCWs' mental health, it appears that we still lack cohesive policies and a standardized approach to addressing these problems. In another systematic review by Drissi et al. in 2021, it was found that most mental health programs delivered by institutions to support HCWs are delivered digitally. The use of technology offers several solutions in managing psychological problems, and over the past years, there has been an increase in the delivery of e-health interventions. Despite the heterogeneity in their core elements, e-health interventions have demonstrated effectiveness in reducing stress and burnout among HCWs (Drissi et al., 2021). These digital interventions seem to be well-suited to meet the restrictions imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic and the support needs of HCWs.

To inform policies and decision-making, further research should be conducted to compare the cost-benefit of digital psychological interventions with standard supportive care programs. This will help us gain a better understanding of the most effective and efficient ways to support the mental well-being of HCWs during the ongoing pandemic.

2.7 Portugal, FS

2.7.1 Introduction

Resilience in long term care facilities (LTCFs) of different socio-economic status: COVID-19 structural and psychosocial impacts on elderly residents in Évora, Portugal

Évora city is part of the largest region of Portugal (Alentejo), which has a population density of 22.3 (PORDATA, 2021) and 704.707 inhabitants (INE, 2021). The city of Évora is the 5th largest in Portugal with a population density of 41 (PORDATA, 2021) and 53.591 inhabitants (INE, 2021). Évora city presents an age index of 33.7% and an elderly dependency index of 178.3% (PORDATA, 2021). Moreover, Évora's population aged 65 or over (12,633 people in total) accounts for 6.81% of Portugal's elderly population (INE, 2021) and of that total, 2,941 people were flagged by the law enforcement authorities (GNR) due to their high vulnerability risk, poor life conditions, lack of social support or for being under health threats, even before the pandemic. Since January 2020, Alentejo is the Portuguese region with the highest fatality rate. As of November 2021, Évora was one of the cities with the most high-risk parishes/neighbourhoods (ENSP, 2021). By the 12th of December 2021, 4,784 cases and 72 deaths by COVID-19 were reported. In April 2021, about 40% of total deaths reported in Portugal were stemming from LTCF (Mamede, Pereira & Simões, 2020). Thus, these data represent the strong challenges faced in trying to control the COVID-19 pandemic in elderly LTCF in Portugal.

Portugal's case study focuses on the resilience of 2 types of LTCFs, as well as their elderly residents' resilience, located in Évora city. Elderly Long Term Care Facilities (LTCFs) - the systems under analysis – are social response structures aimed at collective housing, for temporary or permanent use of elderly people, where social support activities are developed and basic health care is provided, contributing to the well-being and social integration of its users, as well as stabilizing, empowering and stimulating active ageing, and improving the quality of life of these people. Although they share the same goals, LTCFs differ from each other in terms of accommodation type (e.g., rooms/homes); density (e.g., of residents and staff); activities provided (e.g., entertainment); amenities owned (e.g., articulated beds); health care services provided (e.g., physiotherapy); and price (low/high ranks). Nursing homes can be considered systems that are basically characterized to belong, in Portugal, to one of three categories, i.e., a) public Social Security institutions managed and operated with connection with municipalities, b) non-governmental institutions mainly connected with the church (i.e., IPSS – Social Solidarity Particular Institution) and c) private (for profit). However, for analysis purposes, we divide them into IPSS institutions and private (for profit) institutions.

The 2 types of LTCFs considered here are linked to different levels of governance (e.g., national norms and policies – Portugal -, regional measures – Alentejo region -, local implementation – Évora city, and resources within each type of LTCF). These levels of governance entail different entities to be considered (e.g., National Health Directorate (DGS), Social Security (SS), Local Authorities/City Council, Churches/Religious structures, Civil Society Organizations, Private investors). The technical management of the residential structure is ensured by a technician with a degree in social and behavioural sciences, health or social services and, preferably, with professional experience to perform the duties (MSSS, 2012, Article 11). It is incumbent upon the technical director to assume responsibility for the programming of activities and the coordination and supervision of all staff, considering the need to establish a technical management model appropriate to the proper functioning of the establishment. The residential structure must have personnel to ensure the provision of services 24 hours a day (MSSS, 2012, Article 12, see Table 4). The residential structure can count on the collaboration of volunteers, duly qualified, and these cannot be considered for the purposes of the provisions of previous numbers. It must have internal regulations, which define the specific rules and principles of operation. The functioning of the residential structure is subject to monitoring, evaluation and supervision by the Social Security Institute (MSSS, 2012, Article 19, a fundamental component of the Social Security Ministry).

The identification of the encompassing socio-ecological systems where nursing homes are integrated is of outmost importance. The case study conducted in Portugal focuses on people living and working in different LTCF structures as the vulnerable target population (i.e., elderly residents/users, staff and administration, in private and social solidarity institutions). The elderly users will be the main focus, especially in terms of vulnerability, but we also gather information/data from the governance body (e.g., administration of LTCFs) and staff working in LTCFs (e.g., professional health workers, cleaning staff) in order to compare the experiences of these different groups and capture their different perspectives regarding the COVID-19 pandemic. We were mostly interested in analysing their perceptions, behaviours, and psychosocial well-being while adopting a systemic and comparative perspective. We analysed multiple factors (e.g., social support networks), their interaction, and their impact on the different groups of the target population and their vulnerabilities, through different time-points.

Figure 16. FS, Portugal - SES Framework.

2.7.2 Purpose and Research Questions

This case study systematically explores the way different LTCF structures and contexts impact and/or interact with the perceptions, behaviours and psychosocial well-being of elderly users in LTCFs during the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on cumulative and synergic vulnerabilities.

Main research aims:

- To test and apply a systemic methodology of analysis of the diverse nursing homes systems functioning; Compare the internal and external driven responses to the pandemic across time and identify the systems factors that predict a better performance
- To identify the turning points, phases and resilience main factors and isolating the adaptive cycles that the nursing homes have been through
- To identify the attitudes and mental models to, and of, the COVID-19 pandemic from the different stakeholders of those systems (leaders, staff, users and families)
- To study a specific region of the country (Alentejo) where is hypothesized that some of intervening factors are more clearly identifiable
- To analyse how general communication strategies and behavioural rules were adapted and had timely changes within the nursing homes systems
- To identify the main protective factors and risk factors of resilience of elderly living in LTCFs.

Research Questions:

- **RQ1:** What are the socio-ecological system characteristics of each type of LTCF (for profit and private non-profit IPSS)? Which were more successful in mitigating Covid-19 impacts, and why? How has this changed over time?
- **RQ2:** How has COVID-19 and responses to COVID-19 affected residents' shared attitudes, beliefs, and practices? How has this changed throughout time, particularly regarding resilience levels across different types of LTCF?
- **RQ3:** Did specific structural features of local social networks and governments' systems and norms aggravate or mitigate residents' vulnerabilities? How has this changed throughout time and across different types of LTCF?
- **RQ4:** In what way have COVID-19 information communications been accessible, actionable, relevant, timely, and understandable? How has this changed throughout time and across different types of LTCF?
- **RQ5:** How well have communication strategies and vaccination plans addressed the specific needs and attributes of the LTCF? How has this changed throughout time and across different types of LTCF?
- **RQ6:** What are the main structural causes and socio-psychological consequences of the impacts of COVID-19 in LTCF?

2.7.3 Method

The Portuguese case study analyses reports from three different groups of participants pertaining to two different types of LTCFs. The two types of institution are non-profit and profit. The participants

are under administration of the LTCFs, different levels of staff (from the auxiliary to the technical and medical workers), and users (the elderly residents of LTCFs).

Table 3. Participant Sample (Portugal Case Study).

Sample (N)		Group			
		Elderly Users	Administration	Workers	Total
Type of Institution	3 rd Sector	12	5	7	24
	Private	8	6	5	19
	Total	20	11	12	43

Sociodemographic data of the Elderly Residents:

- 14 female; 6 male; $N=20$ Elderly Residents.
- Age: $M=81.26$; $DP=8.95$ (ranging from 65 to 94 years old).
- 15 widowed; Number of offspring: $M= 1.26$ (< 3 children); 6 don't have any offspring.
- Time living in the nursing home: $M=3.40$ years (ranging from 3 months to 14 years);
- Years of schooling: $M=2.42$ (ranging from 0 to 15 years)

In Phase 1, desk research was used to describe to distinguish the different types of nursing homes and choose the most adequate Alentejo zone where the different variables are most extreme (i.e., density and type of management) and collect information on national guidelines. Information was gathered through dashboards, existing datasets, official documentation, national reports, surveys/studies, etc. In Phase 2, concerning primary data, semi-structured interviews were conducted (from May 2022 to August 2022) to allow for applying a retrospective and intersectional approach. The recruitment of institutions (i.e., sample for data collection) was conducted through Santa Casa da Misericórdia (SCM), Carta Social, ALI Association and various online sites. The interviews were organized following a constructionist paradigm, with a mixed approach (top-down and bottom-up) and according to the rules of the mental maps approach (Morgan, 2002). The idea behind the method is a very specific “general to particular” concept induction where the concepts are probed to understand the respondent's intuitive framework. The questions revolved around the domains described on the thematic block script (i.e., different time-points of the COVID-19 pandemic, information and communication, life in the LTCF, prophylactic isolation and vaccination, health perception, best practices, etc.). Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) was the chosen method for analysing the data, using the software NVivo 12 with both themes identified in advance and derived from the data. For more information, refer to FS COREQ Checklist (Appendix A, Annex 8).

2.7.4 Results: Data Reporting

Figure 17. FS, Portugal – Coding Tree (1), Elderly Residents of LTCFs.

Figure 18. FS, Portugal – Coding Tree (2), Administration and Workers of LTCFs.

Word Clouds depicting the word frequency from the interviews with administration members, workers and elderly users of LTCFs in Appendix B (Annex 7.1).

2.7.5 Results: Analysis and Interpretation

Throughout the present section, the numbers in brackets included in the text represent either the number of interviews where the theme emerged, the number of references/mentions of that theme, or both, when separated by a slash (*Number of interviews where theme emerged/Number of references of that theme*).

Pandemic Communication: Practices and Vulnerabilities (RQ2, RQ4, RQ5)

Elderly Residents' interviews: Most elderly users had frequent information consuming habits (12), and the most mentioned communication channel was television (10), from which many seem to have formed their perceptions about COVID-19. Evaluations of the pandemic communication are majorly associated with negative feelings: it was described as excessive in quantity and too scary, shocking and/or alarming in quality. In elderly's descriptions, these adjectives appear especially related to the beginning of the pandemic. There were mentions of the excessive focus on the numbers of cases and deaths. On a more positive note, the users started to be less negatively affected by the news as time passed. There were also mentions of pandemic communication by LTCFs workers and directors (8); there was an effort on the part of staff and/or administration members to communicate and explain information about the pandemic to the elderly despite all the communication difficulties they faced.

"Some of them, poor people, didn't know well. They didn't know what it was. They said: this is a bug, but we don't see it. Nobody could explain very well what it was." (User25)

Administration and Workers' interviews: The elderly wanted to be informed and willingly watched the news, but that also led to more fear and negative feelings. While there were mentions of television being a good vehicle for disseminating information, negative aspects dominated these reports; the view transmitted by the news was often negative and catastrophic, leaving everyone alarmed, taking things out of proportion, and creating anxiety, fear and confusion.

In general, administration members and workers share the opinion that communication was not adapted to the elderly population. The fact that the news frequently reported numbers of COVID-19 cases and deaths, allied to the fact that most affected age group were the elderly, led to more anxiety and fear. Besides that, this population is more vulnerable to misinformation in the sense that the information was not always adapted, adequate and properly explained, and they are at times more gullible/not in their full cognitive capacity, and therefore are more prone to confusion and misinterpretation. Additionally, there was a lack of communication in the sense that the elders deserved more targeted attention, for example, in terms of explaining to them what was happening, how the vaccines work, how they would make them feel, etc.

Regarding news about LTCFs and their response to the pandemic, administration members mentioned that they always focused on the negative and never shared cases of success or good practices, resulting in a general sentiment of distrust in nursing homes, which put an extra pressure and responsibility on top of these institutions and created additional stress.

"The media always projected for the worse. Of course, there were very bad moments, for sure, but when there were positive things, nobody talked about it, it was never focused. This was also reflected in the elderly because the elderly had group activities that had to stop being done. So, what did they focus on: television. What did the television show: midday or one o'clock news"

that ended at half past two and only talked about Covid and dead people. The same at night. The television programmes that were used to distract us also talked about Covid only. We even have an elderly woman whose hobby was to keep a record of the number of cases and deaths. Every day she kept a record, she had a little notebook with her record. Then it was so infiltrated in her head... Some people were scared because they saw the numbers and most of the people who died were old people.” (Admin10)

“To our Minister of Health and colleagues: don't forget that the elderly are people too, they need to understand information too, and they need to be looked after too. It's not just "the old people are the first to be vaccinated", that's not all. Maybe they don't really understand why they must be vaccinated or what it will do in the future. Someone needs to explain to them what will happen.” (Worker32)

Communication with users, by administration: Administration members reported having communicated with the users about the pandemic; they explained them the situation and why certain procedures were being adopted (e.g., why staff had to use PPE, why users had to stay in their rooms, why they could not see their families, etc.). This communication was majorly carried out without external help, leaving it up to the administration members to decide how to deal with this task. Another difficulty concerns the fact that communication has to be adapted to different users; while some are in good mental health states, seek and understand information, many other users suffer from illnesses like dementia, which make them more prone to confusion and creates additional challenges for communication.

Communication with users, by workers: Workers also engaged in pandemic communication with the users and identified some of the same difficulties, namely, adapting their communication to the elderly population and dealing with differences in comprehension abilities. The cognitive health aspect was, once again, mentioned as a factor that influenced comprehension and cooperation. Regarding users that can understand this kind of information, workers refer that there was a constant effort to keep them updated, not only to make everything clear for them, but also to raise awareness and gain their cooperation (e.g., towards mask use, hand sanitizing, vaccination, etc.). Besides, workers mentioned having to clarify certain information the elderly got through the media. Even though users were kept informed, there was also a very present concern on the part of workers to not let the amount of pandemic information consumption and exposure be excessive, to avoid creating more anxiety or fear. They would often reassure the elderly that they were doing their best to protect them and that the situation would get better. In general, workers feel that there should have been a more concise communication plan. This plan should have included the provision of an expert or health professional that would come to the institution to adequately communicate the information, instead of it being done by the staff of the LTCFs since they don't always have the necessary skills and knowledge to do so.

Communication with the staff was another important role of the administration. Guidelines were transmitted through meetings, informal conversations, and printed flyers and brochures that were updated as new guidelines came out, given out to the workers and displayed at the facilities. Workers confirmed this and said that the administration always communicated with them; they had training and meetings to learn the new procedures, as well as written/visual information available for consultation. Every time new guidelines were put out workers were updated through meetings.

Communication with the families: Both workers and administration members often took on the role of communicating about the pandemic with the families of the users. On one hand, there were cases of success, with family members trusting the staff, seeing the protective measures as what was best for the elderly users, following all the rules and even wanting to help the staff. The staff always tried to be open with the families regarding the measures, the state of the elderly, and procedures like isolation and vaccination (e.g., updates were sent through text messages). However, interviewees also describe the communication with the families as a very challenging task. Some family members did not accept the rules, felt outraged towards LTCFs' staff, demanded explanations and even instigated conflict. The reasons were often related to their contact with the users (e.g., cancelation of visits, not being able to take them home, etc.). In this sense, family members often took their indignation out on the staff and did not always comply with the necessary measures (e.g., keep the mask on during the visit). LTCFs staff wished families had trusted/helped them more instead of creating additional stress for workers who were already overwhelmed with work and concerns.

"We had the carer go just occasionally to see if everything was okay or if they needed anything (during the visit). And what we saw was that we would just turn our backs and they would take the mask off, try to touch the elderly.... This issue I think was one of the most difficult to control. Revolting for us, because we were allowing the visits and they were still abusing it, undoing our work..." (Worker11)

Communication with LTCF administration, by the national authorities: Administration members constantly received information from the health authorities with the guidelines, norms and procedures they had to implement, flyers and posters they had to print and display, etc. However, there were mentions of emails containing decree-laws or guidelines with more than one hundred pages – which did not facilitate the assimilation/application of the guidelines by the LTCFs. In this sense, the administration expressed that the communication should have been simpler and clearer.

- Private vs 3rd sector: Based on the directors' reports, communication seems to have been relatively more successful in non-profit institutions, compared to private LTCFs. There were mentions of efficient communication happening between the institution and the health authorities (e.g., for vaccination), guidelines coming from DGS and Social Security, and the opportunity for clarification of doubts and two-way communication with staff from Social Security. On the other hand, the reports from private institutions assume a more negative tone overall; they referred to having felt lost and having no one to rely on. While they also received information from the health authorities and Social Security, there seems to have been a more distant relationship, with no clear identification of how they could ask questions or who exactly they should contact, and they felt like the information received was often contradictory, reflecting a lack of coordination between actors. It should be mentioned that the private non-profit institutions (IPSS) that are usually organized nationally through its national federation and the church.

Vulnerabilities and Negative Impacts (RQ1, RQ3, RQ6)

Elderly Users' Interviews: In terms of areas of vulnerability – both pre-existent and related to impacts of the pandemic – the most mentioned area was physical health (70), followed by relational impacts and social support vulnerabilities (45) and mental health (43). Elderly users said their vulnerabilities were related to not being able to go out/leave the care facility (14), as well as missing their personal homes (12).

Administration's Interviews: The most common theme was mental health (77), followed by lack of support from the government and/or health authorities (69) and lack of resources (51), both human and material, as the most significant vulnerability factors for LTCFs during the pandemic. Lack of social and relational support/contact was referred to as both a vulnerability factor and a negative consequence of the pandemic (60). Themes like communication vulnerability (36; presented in the section about communication), physical health vulnerability (23), economic vulnerability (15) and lack of recognition of the social sector and its workers (6) were also mentioned, but less frequently.

Workers' Interviews: Once again, the most common theme was mental health (70), but this time it was followed by the lack of social support/contact (57) and physical health vulnerabilities and impacts (38). Communication vulnerabilities (25) were mentioned as well. For workers, lack of support from the government/health authorities (21), lack of resources (6) and economic vulnerability (2) were less relevant fragilities (compared to what was reported by administration). A specific vulnerability mentioned by the workers is related to the impact of the PPE the workers had to wear on the elderly users (8): users often found the protective suits frightening, and the whole equipment made interaction on an interpersonal level much more difficult.

Health-related Vulnerabilities: Physical Health

Regarding physical health, most users report pre-existent health problems and conditions. The lack of autonomy emerged as a relevant theme related to these health problems, with many elderly users referring to needing help to move and being dependent on the staff to take care of their hygiene, which represents extra vulnerability during a pandemic situation, when physical touch represents a risk and is to be avoided. Additionally, some users had their visits to the hospital and usual medical services limited or completely suspended; many health problems stopped being screened and medications were not being adjusted, which worsened the health conditions of some. The suspension of usual health services together with the allocation of all services and resources to the COVID-19 response was given even more emphasis by the administration members. In the interviews with administration and staff members, advanced age and fragility were indicated as significant vulnerability factors, as well as previous diseases and health problems, in the sense that they could become comorbidities and increase the risk of negative health consequences in the case of Covid-19 infection. The lack of mobility was described as a common problem that was aggravated by the pandemic, creating great dependencies and losses of autonomy and motor capacities.

A minor theme was the impact on the physical health of the staff, with mentions of long-term health consequences from being infected with COVID-19 and physical exhaustion from the augmented workload and stress they were under working in a LTCF throughout the pandemic.

Health-related Vulnerabilities: Mental Health

Different degrees of dementia and similar diseases were referred by the users as being common in the LTCFs they live in. In terms of less disruptive mental issues and concerns, there were mentions of depression, anxiety, sadness, loneliness, lack of energy, enthusiasm, and interest in life, etc. While some of these issues were triggered by negative life events and personal situations, for many of the users, mental issues emerged because of the pandemic. For them, being "closed" in the home and unable to be with their relatives contributed to the development of new vulnerabilities and aggravation of the existent ones. As the main mental health consequences of the pandemic, the elderly referred to feeling down, tired, and having lost interest in their hobbies. Administration and staff members reinforced these impacts on the well-being of the elderly users; there were several mentions

of the fear they felt, and the impossibility of physical touch made it difficult for workers to comfort users. Not seeing their families, not being able to leave the facilities, the lack of affection and seeing their peers get sick or die were points referred to as factors that the elderly had a difficult time coping with. Furthermore, workers noticed a great decline in cognitive abilities. Many of the users felt extremely lost and confused when people they didn't know had to come and take care of them, as well as when they had to be moved to different spaces; some never understood why their families stopped coming to visit them and some were sad and angry because they thought that the workers were afraid of being infected by them; there were also some degrees of temporal confusion. In sum, these drastic changes in the users' environment had several negative impacts on them.

Besides the impact on the users, there were several mentions of negative impacts on administration and workers' mental health (e.g., anxiety, feelings of blame, burn out, depression, despair, confusion, neglect, etc.). These people also felt a lot of fear, both for themselves, their families, and the elderly users, but had to be in control of their emotions and reassure the elderly. There was also the added weight and responsibility of working with a vulnerable group; many of these workers lived in fear of taking the virus into the institution and being responsible for infecting elderly users. They suffered a lot due to the public opinion and media; all eyes were on them and LTCF workers were under a lot of pressure. The work at a LTCF was described as both mentally and physically demanding, becoming even more exhausting during the pandemic, with changes in schedules, increased workload and personal sacrifices. The workers were tired from the long shifts (e.g., 12 hours a day for 10-15 days), and in some cases they had to live at the institutions, which implied not seeing their families for days/weeks at a time. The work itself was difficult and emotionally challenging, even leading some employees to quit their jobs. It was distressful seeing the elderly around them get sick or pass away, feeling powerless and dealing with the families' despair.

They share the opinion that mental health was not a focus of the pandemic response, and that all the efforts were all concentrated on physical health. There was a lack of mental health support, both for the users and themselves; it is an area that needs to be rethought and invested in. Namely, workers report not being able to help their users to the extent that they need because they don't have the training nor the number of staff necessary. At last, directors and workers wish they had been offered some kind of support in that sense – in particular, by the national health authorities.

"I think we must rethink mental health. It is an issue that is really arising and, as in everything, we are responding to the situations that arise, but we are not preventing anything, we are just being firefighters solving situations, the means are scarce, we have few reception centres for people, we have few psychiatrists, we have few... And then we treat mental health issues with drugs to make them prostrate, unresponsive, without activity, and that is how we treat mental health? I don't think that's the way to go." (Admin14)

Relational Impacts and Support System Vulnerabilities

Regarding this form of vulnerability – which reflects lack of social support and/or isolation from social networks and relational consequences of the pandemic –, the suspension of visits was, by far, the most mentioned topic. The elderly point out not being able to see their families as one of the most difficult aspects of the pandemic, as well as the one that had possibly the most negative impact on their well-being. As a matter of fact, mental health vulnerability and relational/social vulnerability are two very related themes. While the cancellation of visits was the major reason behind the elderly's isolation from their social networks, there were also mentions of their relatives living far away from the LTCF or

not visiting as a voluntary protective measure. While less common, there were also some users (4) that did not have visitors even before the pandemic since they don't have significant social support networks, either because their relatives passed away already, or they don't have good relationships with their family. While these users are more vulnerable due to the lack of social support, they were also less impacted by the pandemic in the sense that they did not feel the suspension of visits was a loss for themselves. Additionally, a very small minority has also mentioned not having any friends/not getting along with any of the other users at their LTCF.

Administration further pointed out being prevented from seeing their families, as well as the lack of physical touch and affection, as something that deeply affected this population. Some directors said that, as people who are on the final stage of their lives, the elderly felt wronged since they were not asked if they wanted to be protected or if they minded having COVID-19. Some of them would have liked to be with their families until the end, even if they were to be infected or die. In this sense, some administration members feel like the suspension of visits was a bit "in vain" and they refer with certainty that many elderly did not die from COVID-19, but from grief and heartbreak.

"I have a lady here who turned 99, and we used to have a visit from her children or grandchildren every day. When she realised that they weren't coming, I explained why but she didn't want to understand/accept it, she died within a month. She was my first victim, so to speak, because she simply gave up living, because she didn't want to live like that, but her children couldn't take her home, because they couldn't take care of her anymore and I was so angry about this... Did anyone ask people if they minded having COVID? Maybe a lot of them didn't mind, maybe they would have got COVID and died... But they would have lived happily until the last day because they were with their family. So, they died anyway without being with their family (...) We were practically protecting them for a year, protecting them, closing them, and they got covid and 10 of them died. And of those 10 who died, they hadn't been with their families for almost a year. Did that make any sense? It didn't to me." (Admin3)

Furthermore, the experience of isolation when infected, together with not being able to recognize the staff because of the PPE, impacted the elderly greatly, leaving them feeling lonely at times. Additionally, directors confirmed that some elderly are completely unseen and unprotected, with no social support outside the LTCF (e.g., have been abandoned, robbed or mistreated by their families).

For the staff, there were also vulnerabilities at a social level; they had to make personal sacrifices and put their life on hold, felt like they had to avoid physical touch in between shifts, spent more time working and sleeping at the LTCF leaving their families for long periods of time, avoided contact with the "outside world" and their social circles, and had their interactions and dislocations very limited to the ones strictly necessary, for fear of becoming infected and contaminating the elderly at the LTCFs.

Lack of Support from the Government and Health Authorities

Administration (9/69) and workers (5/17) often characterized the support from the government and health authorities as insufficient or non-existent. This vulnerability factor was more prevalent in the interviews with the administration from private (6/58) than from non-profit institutions (3/12).

In fact, administration from private facilities referred to not receiving any funding from the government and feeling a great lack of support in many ways, which made them feel abandoned. Every expense was supported by the owners, having received no financial aid or help in the form of resources from anyone. Social Security and the Health Directorate were in contact with these institutions and

visited the facilities often to do inspections, supervise their work conditions, and check if everything was according to the norms, creating pressure on the administration for them to comply with the demands – but they never offered help to the institutions or their more vulnerable elderly residents. Social Security was described by directors and workers as a very strict and bureaucratic entity that only came to evaluate, criticize and demand alterations, without providing proper assistance, support, cooperation, or any consideration of their needs. It was difficult for these institutions to manage their expenses, especially with the rising prices. Some institutions applied for programs but were never selected to benefit from the aid. A few institutions stated that they did not even receive visits from the health delegate and from medical staff for testing or vaccination, having developed contingency plans alone and tested the users themselves. Furthermore, lack of information, not knowing where to turn for clarification and the lack of response to their calls for help was mentioned as a difficulty.

Administration and workers from non-profit social solidarity institutions refer that there were medical teams from SNS that were to provide support to LTCFs during outbreaks; however, these teams weren't enough in number, considering the high demand due to the existence of outbreaks in the whole district of Évora at a certain point. Despite receiving funds from Social Security, these are not nearly enough in the face of the rising expenses. There were mentions of the lack of training and information support in practical questions like how to dispose of the PPE and medical waste, and where to turn for specific services. Public health was, at certain points, inefficient in terms of responding to institutions and their needs (e.g., testing/screening of cases), and responses took too long, leading to worse outcomes (e.g., delays in testing, delayed isolation, creating outbreaks). Overall, this type of service was inconsistent (e.g., functioning well when health professionals were displaced to assist LTCF and worse around holidays and at later stages of the pandemic).

“The elderly people are completely unprotected (...) What I think is important - and I'm tired of saying this - is to talk to the elderly. The DGS came every 2 months, so why didn't they talk to the elderly? Why didn't they ask them what they were feeling? Nothing. They didn't even go into their lounge. And so, this doesn't work, neither with pandemics nor without pandemics, they don't work well (...) If Social Security supervises the homes, why can't they talk to the elderly? Give support? See what is going on in society, a protection, even if it is just legal protection... They (elderly) become invisible from a certain point on, these people... It is sad, but this is only seen here in our country.” (Admin24)

Resources Vulnerability

Very related to the previous topic is the lack of enough human and/or material resources and the lack of help received in that sense. Accordingly, this form of vulnerability was mostly mentioned by administration members (9/51). Despite administration from private institutions having mentioned the lack of support way more than the administration from non-profit institutions, here, the prevalence of vulnerability related to resources was similar for private (5/22) and non-profit institutions (4/23).

Administration from private institutions stated that they did not have public help with material and having to buy everything themselves from face masks, gloves, disinfectant, hand sanitizer, protective suits, etc. Others – both from profit and non-profit institutions – refer having received only a negligible amount of material (e.g., 5 boxes of masks; 50 suits during an outbreak, etc.), which was not nearly enough, especially since material and equipment were out of stock at times and being sold at much

higher prices due to the high demand. In terms of facilities and infrastructures, they were also not sufficient, specifically when having to separate the positive and negative cases from each other.

Lack of human resources and the difficulty in contracting new workers was also mentioned, especially related to times when workers were infected or quit their jobs. In fact, one of the most salient problems for directors of non-profit institutions was the sudden lack of staff when there were outbreaks and most of the workers were infected. There were mentions of norms being strict and (e.g., asymptomatic infected workers being sent home), which made managing the few human resources challenging. Institutions were left with less than the necessary means to take care of the users and there was no more staff available to come from the outside and help.

“From the moment you open the suit you have to discard it and there were no suits for sale, everything was sold out. We opened the suit, and at that time we were immediately subject to the virus entering, so if everyone became infected, who would take care of the elderly? It’s that question... To go to the bathroom, sometimes it’s the whole day without going, if it must be. I heard stories of doctors here at Évora’s hospital who even put diapers on to avoid going to the bathroom and having to constantly discard (the protective equipment)” (Admin10)

“Every day the staff would test positive and go home. I got to a point where I found myself with the nursing home turned upside down, with no staff, with the positive users, with families calling all the time and I couldn’t answer. They were annoyed that no one answered the phone; I wasn’t able to be everywhere and do everything. My right hand tested positive; I was on my own. The animator was coming to help me, but I was very afraid that she would catch it, because she is an older person and I was trying to keep her protected, more in the back ground. My nurse was on leave, she was pregnant. We had a nurse who came to help, but because she worked in the hospital, so it was only during the times when she wasn’t working. And I got to a day when I didn’t know what else to do (...) It was something that really, really, really struck me. The desperation of not knowing. At that moment, I had to do something, but I felt blocked: “Who do I ask for help? What do I do?”. Then I was able react and things got done, but it was very bad.” (Admin3)

Economic Vulnerability

Administration members (5/13) also referred to the aspect of economic vulnerability as something closely related to the topic of lack of support from the government and lack of resources. Administration from non-profit institutions (3/9) mentioned that the social sector workers are underpaid; the funding they receive from the government is very low and, together with the very little money the users pay with their pensions, the money is not enough to support the cost each user represents. While users from non-profit institutions are more economically vulnerable because they have relatively low pensions, users from private institutions are usually wealthier and have means to pay for a more expensive LTCF; however, during the pandemic, some of these users and their families became more economically vulnerable (2/4). Regarding costs associated with the pandemic, institutions said that a lot of money was spent on products and services that could not be done internally (e.g., laundry and food preparation), as well as expenses required to comply with the safety measures imposed; these necessary investments affected institutions financially.

Covid-19 Pandemic Direct and Structural Impacts (RQ1, RQ3, RQ6)

The Biggest Challenges

Administration (6/28) and staff members (8/26) highlighted what was more difficult for them and their institutions to deal with during the pandemic. The challenges most emphasized were: 1) adaptation to the rapidly changing norms and rules; 2) the lack of time to apply all the measures required; the logistics of outbreaks; 3) isolating all the positive cases, especially at smaller facilities; 4) creating habits like using masks and hand sanitizer; avoid contamination through incorrect use of the PPE; 5) long shifts with several hours without eating or going to the bathroom; disposal and collection of medical waste; 6) managing testing, visits and all the pandemic related procedures; the uncertainty and complexity of the situation; 7) avoiding physical touch; dealing with the complaints and emotions of the users; and 8) the possibility of “taking the virus” into the LTCF, etc.

Experience of Isolation

Isolation of the positive cases was a challenge for the managers of LTCFs and they describe the experience as extremely harmful for the users who were left alone, closed in rooms, many times feeling confused and lost. Users also talked about their experience with isolation (13/27); it was described as something very difficult they had to go through and, despite having been well cared for, they felt very lonely, and it made them more lethargic. Not being able to leave the institution, even when not infected, greatly impacted their well-being too.

Services and Activities

The impact of the pandemic on services and activities was mentioned by most of the administration (9/35) and workers (8/18), as well as some users (8/17). Most activities were suspended inside and outside the homes, specifically when measures were tighter during lockdowns and outbreaks. Inside the facilities, sociocultural and recreational activities were the most affected, as well as cosmetic services and services like psychomotricity, physiotherapy and psychotherapy. While some institutions completely suspended these services and the respective external professionals (e.g., sociocultural animators, psychologists, physiotherapists) would not even go to the facilities, other institutions were able to maintain a few activities to the minimum and adapted – especially one non-profit institution who mentioned having an internal team of professionals. Some services were done remotely, and then individually or even in smaller groups when the situation allowed. Users could not go outside for a long time, so their usual activities (e.g., go to the café, take walks, church, etc.) were also suspended and then resumed gradually. Lastly, services less directly related to the users like food preparation and laundry were also affected.

Positive Impacts

Not everything was negative; in fact, workers mentioned some positive consequences of the pandemic (7/22). They discovered new ways of doing things that are sometimes better than the old ways and choose to keep some of the things they adapted during the pandemic. Additionally, many workers preferred their new work schedules. Human relations between workers inside the LTCF have also gained a lot with the pandemic, thanks to the mutual help, collective effort and identification with each other's struggles that came from their experiences during the pandemic. Workers became the users' families and were able to improve their intervention once they got closer to the elderly and got to know their needs better. Managers also mentioned better preparedness for future events and better hygiene practices as positive aspects.

Resilience and Protective Factors (RQ1, RQ3)

“And I think that, well, our team, the multidisciplinary team, is essential in the lives of these people, and I think that there is a huge need in institutions for teams capable of developing... For example, to counteract passivity a little, as I said earlier, the useful occupation of time, promoting socialization, dialogue between peers... Because it's very important, people come here without any reference, if they don't have someone who stimulates and promotes dialogue with other people, they won't do it... And what happens? They will tend to isolate themselves - that's what we don't want. So, I think this work is fundamental.” (Worker1)

Support from the Government and Health Authorities

The most mentioned form of support received from the state and public health authorities was the non-material support in the form of measures, visits, information and accompaniment/assistance referred by a few workers (4/6) but, especially, by administration (9/43). In this category, some directors from non-profit institutions (4/31) referred the information and orientations DGS sent them, all the visits made by state employees and health professionals to check if the measures were being applied correctly, map the existent difficulties, give recommendations, conduct testing and vaccination, as well as all the contact to check how the institution was doing, to help create the contingency plans and clarify any doubts. A few workers (3/5) mentioned these very same aspects.

“The state created teams that came periodically to help us, they were multidisciplinary teams made up of social security, civil protection and health professionals that helped us and taught us how to create the circuits, the separation of waste, the prophylactic isolations and a series of procedures that we had to implement over these months, all had a checklist ... They helped us improve.” (Admin10)

Some directors from private institutions (5/12) also mentioned receiving updated orientations from DGS and Social Security, as well as the periodic visits to check the working conditions. However, the contact between private institutions and the state/health authorities seems to have been more distanced and scarcer, compared to the contact with 3rd sector LTCFs.

Regarding material forms of support, some directors from non-profit LTCFs (4/14) mentioned human resources support like: the multidisciplinary teams that went to the institutions to help; a Social Security brigade; opening of human resources vacancies through Social Security; governmental initiatives to increase the number of staff at LTCFs through recruitment (e.g., the MAREESS initiative (Support Measure for Emergency Reinforcement of Social and Health Equipment)). Support in the form of material resources like PPE provided by Social Security and Civil Protection was also mentioned, while direct economic support was only mentioned by one non-profit institution manager regarding the funding coming from Social Security and the APOIAR program. Managers from private LTCFs mentioned much less resources support (3/3), referring only to the presence of public doctors/nurses and the provision of a few masks and gloves, and no economic support.

Community Support

According to both some managers (5/10) and workers (3/8), the communities the LTCFs are inserted in showed them support during the pandemic. People like the users' families, groups of local firefighters, the priest, neighbours and friends of the institution's managers came to help and show their support any way they could (e.g., from transportation and cleaning to helping take care of the

elderly). There were also non-governmental volunteer initiatives (e.g., Portugal ComVidas) that contributed greatly to tackle the lack of human resources.

“The director of the pharmacy we work with arranged for a number of friends to come, I would give them the suits and they would come in. They'd come to feed the elderly, to help put them to bed, they'd come to wash the floor... They came to do whatever. The parish priest did the same thing, he sent some friends (...) And the volunteers brought their guitars and besides helping with the day-to-day tasks, hygiene, food, cleaning, they tried to cheer them up and played their guitars and that brought some relief. You could see it on the faces of the elderly, it distracted them a little from that stress and they felt a little lighter and it was very good that they came. There were 12 volunteers, plus 2 from Social Security, plus the employees who, in the meantime, started to return because they were discharged (from prophylactic isolation).”
(Admin3)

Social Support

As forms of social support, workers (7/25) and administration (8/13) mentioned the remote contact with the families as well as the contact between users promoted by the LTCF internal activities. All elders (19/59) mentioned some form of social support, referring mostly visits and contact with their children, grandchildren, siblings, nephews and friends; positive interactions with the other users living at the LTCF were also mentioned (e.g., talk to each other about their pandemic related fears).

Some specific aspects related to social support and resilience highlighted were:

- **Relationships Inside the LTCFs** – The pandemic contributed to strengthening relationships; workers and managers got much closer to the users and became like a second family to them, which became a protective factor. Workers feel connected to the elderly and get along well with their coworkers. Users get along well with each other, despite sometimes not socializing as much as the workers would like and preferring to be on their own.
- **Proximity to the Users** – Some directors (5/11) mentioned a close relationship with the users as an important protective factor and something that allowed them to bridge the gaps the pandemic created. When the workers know each user personally, they are better able to identify their strengths and fragilities, and are more apt to respond, adapt to each user and promote their well-being, as well as tackle their lack of affection/social contact. In sum, the care provided is more humanized, which promotes resilience and protects the elderly.
- **Unity and Collaboration** – The joint effort and collaborative work dynamic between staff at LTCFs was emphasized by the workers (8/29) both as a positive consequence of the pandemic – workers got closer because of the shared experiences and challenges they faced – and a resilience factor that helped institutions overcome their hardships. Workers said that they had to be strong and do what was necessary to keep things afloat; they did their best to protect the elderly, worked together towards a common goal despite the difficulties and the fatigue, and felt like that sense of unity between them was essential to “survive”.

Elderly’s Resilience Factors

- Besides the social support mentioned above, the elderly users mentioned a few other topics that reflect protective factors that contributed to their well-being and resilience, namely:

- Well-being markers related to health and autonomy (16/47) (e.g., taking care of their own hygiene, good mobility, feeling energetic and optimistic, etc.);
- Good relationship with the workers, feeling well cared for and “in good hands” (15/21);
- Liking the LTCF, feeling good and protected while living there (13/31);
- Entertainment and individual strategies (12/32) – the users have their own personal hobbies to entertain themselves as well as personal strategies that contribute to their well-being (e.g., sewing, playing games, walking, farming, watching tv, praying, writing, reading, etc.);
- Trust in workers and in the pandemic information disseminated (12/14) – users did not always trust the government but tended to trust the workers and health professionals;
- Other positive factors identified were not feeling too much worry or fear, feeling like their will was considered, and talking to a mental health specialist/going to therapy.

Part of Resilience: Ability to Adapt

“The result I really see is that we institutions have an enormous capacity to adapt to the difficulties and circumstances we are experiencing and that we only now have that realisation when we have gone through these difficulties... We have had to change spaces, we had to create isolation zones...” (Admin13)

“I have a colleague of mine who says that we are essentially creative. We sometimes have to think very hard to come up with strategies; how to solve problems of lack of staff, how to solve the problem of doctors not coming here... We always must invent something, look for solutions.” (Admin3)

“And I think that's it, we really managed - despite the fears, and some weaknesses of course, because nobody is made of iron, and we were all working under some pressure - I think we managed to withstand everything.” (Worker1)

Responding to challenges: In general, institutions and their members are revealed to be very capable of adapting. Administration (9/47) and workers (8/51) mentioned having to be creative and adapt the way things are done considering the restrictions and emergent needs. They adapted their schedules considering the lack of staff; everyone did a little bit of everything; changed dispositions, created circuits and spaces for isolation; found ways to make the isolation more bearable; found new ways to show affection to the users; adapted the activities to different formats; sociocultural animators adapted their work to fit individual and remote formats and promoted new opportunities for socializing and internal events for the users, among many other changes. Institutions also had to adapt the management of their financial resources and integrate suggestions from all the staff. There's a general feeling that they did their best and it was worth it, and that they would do it all over again for the well-being of their users. They share the opinion that users were also able to adapt and get used to the situation. Some users (5/8) also referred to this point, mentioning their ability to adapt and accept their reality – many times because it must be done and there is no other way.

Ways in which Institutions showed ability to adapt:

- **Change of schedules** – mentioned both by administration (9/22) and workers (9/34). Because of the pandemic, they started working in shifts of 12 hours a day for usually 3 to 5 days and then went home for another 3 to 5 days. Other institutions mentioned doing one or two weeks

in a row. It was very difficult for the staff to adapt at first to this type of schedule and most recognize that it was stressful, especially considering the increased workload.

- **Contact with the families** – administration (9/34) and workers (9/33) described how contact with the families was adapted to the new situation to tackle the impact of the distance. Technology was extremely helpful; they relied more on phone and video calls, sending photos/videos of the users, updating the relatives about the user's health condition, sharing their activities on social media, etc. Visits were done less frequently with strict rules (e.g., tests, masks, separated by a barrier) and were adapted according to orientations. New forms of contact (e.g., through the window, near the gate, etc.) were also tried out as strategies for the users to feel closer to their families. The elders (7/13) also mentioned phone and video calls as something positive that allowed them to be in contact with their loved ones.
- **Training for Workers** – some staff members (5/11) mentioned receiving training at the LTCF before the pandemic and specific training related to the Covid-19 safety procedures (e.g., sanitization, correct use of the PPE), which was confirmed by administration (4/7). One of the non-profit institutions mentioned having participated in sessions promoted by the Social Security for clarification, while others mentioned having resorted to the internal nursing team or doctor for educational purposes. However, one manager from a private institution mentioned not having training during the pandemic and only recently paying to receive training at the institution because Social Security demanded it. It is possible that this reflects differences between institutions in terms of training opportunities.
- **Services and Activities:** As mentioned before, a few workers (4/10) mentioned adapting the way they practice their usual activities to avoid suspending them and promote users' well-being (e.g., cognitive stimulation, other forms of practicing gymnastic and visual arts, video consultations, making up new games and forms of entertainment, etc.).

Contingency Plans: Elaboration and Compliance (RQ1, RQ3)

Regarding the pre-existence of contingency plans, directors from both types of institutions (6/9) stated that they were insufficiently prepared. They already had resilience, emergency and evacuation plans, but only for occurrences like fires or earthquakes. Both types of institutions elaborated their own contingency plans according to the official orientations and adapted to the attributes of each facility. However, while administration from non-profits mentioned receiving help from Social Security to elaborate and update their contingency plans, administration from private LTCFs made internal plans on their own, based on their knowledge and understanding of the orientations disseminated, and imposed each measure autonomously. While most of the orientations were followed, managers shared the opinion that not all of them are good or applicable; some are impossible to implement given the characteristics of the facilities, while others do more damage than good. Non-profit institutions always tried to the best of their ability to implement every rule. On the contrary, despite private institutions also being guided by official orientations, there seems to exist more disagreement when it comes to how wise those orientations are and, therefore, there's less compliance. Directors were more independent and autonomous in their decision-making, complying with some requirements (e.g., hygiene procedures) but not others (e.g., rules for prophylactic isolation or visits) according to their own judgement. Contributing to this relative non-compliance on the part of private institutions (compared to 3rd sector IPSS), there's the fact that private institutions seem to have received less and/or less frequent visits by government/health representatives, which meant less

control. This more distanced and scarcer monitoring gave these institutions more freedom to make their rules and assume responsibility for the consequences on their own.

Elderly's Covid-19 Mental Models (RQ2)

A mental model is an internal representation of external reality; it shapes the way we see the world and gives it meaning. In this sense, it is important to consider the elderly users' mental models regarding the pandemic to better comprehend their experiences, risk and protective factors.

In terms of the pandemic in general, we find a variety of mental representations and risk perceptions. Some elders have lower risk perceptions and more positive perceptions of the pandemic: they think it could be a good thing to be infected if they do not have severe consequences, imagine they won't be infected, and see the situation as proof of our great ability to adapt as humans and to adopt a mentality of mutual protection. Some even see the pandemic as just one more disease that should be seen as a flu, and think the restrictive measures are exaggerated. On the other hand, other users have higher risk perceptions and are way less optimistic: they mention how the pandemic represents the unknown – which increases the subjective risk perception – and refer how many people have died/will die because of it; a few users expressed how some people have been irresponsible, how there should have been a bigger avoidance of risk behaviours, and praised the institutions and entities for adopting preventive measures as soon as it was possible.

However, despite this great diversity of opinions, there is a general feeling that all representations were more negative at the beginning of the pandemic, with higher risk perceptions associated with the unknown/uncertainty factors and aggravated in part caused by the big media coverage and the usually negative framing of risk information. With time, as more was known about the pandemic and restrictive measures and vaccination produced good results, mental representations evolved.

“I would perceive it as even worse than it was. My idea was that everyone would die and, after all, those who had to die, died, but it wasn't that bad as I thought at first... It wasn't as bad as the news made it seem.” (User4)

At a more advanced stage of the pandemic, despite users feeling less scared, not perceiving as much risk and feeling more protected, a few users share the opinion that restrictive measures were relaxed too soon, giving people excessive freedom and resulting in the of worsening the country's situation again – especially at the time of the new variants of concern. In this sense, a few users urged people to be vaccinated and continue wearing face masks. In fact, many (8/13) see the use of masks as an important protective and preventive measure that is effective and not difficult to comply with.

“I'm going to tell you something, honestly, I don't know much about these things because we don't have that much education, but they implemented and imposed things, and there are people who are against it, but they shouldn't be, because it's to safeguard all of us (...) I think that everyone should protect themselves, for us and for everyone, but people put themselves at ease even before the government took away this obligation of the masks, I already saw people on television without a mask, that I think is something that should protect us when we are around each other (...) It is necessary to be careful, wear a mask. The measures have been well put and all of it is to protect everything and everyone.” (User16)

Concerning the end of the pandemic, most believe it will never truly end, not because it will always be characterized as a pandemic, but in the sense that Covid-19 will become like a flu; the situation is

getting better and will continue to get better, but people will still have COVID and take vaccines for it throughout the years and it will be like a regular cold – it will become our new normal.

Time-Points (all RQs)

“I felt many changes throughout the various phases here. In the beginning, it was more frightening, they (elderly) didn't understand, we weren't sure about anything yet and we had more measures.... Over time, some were withdrawn... And then there was the question of it all being very tiring and going on over time.... And not knowing when it would end. At the beginning we thought it was going to be a phase, a few months, and then this lasted two years and so on.” (Worker11)

T0. Before the Covid-19 pandemic onset (baseline/control, 2019)

Before the pandemic, staff worked in shorter shifts, with higher rotation; they had trainings every once in a while; the visits had a set day and hour, but relatives would spend hours with the users, sometimes several days in a row; many elderly users were quite discerning, in full control of their motor and cognitive abilities, with great time and space awareness, and some had several hobbies at their disposition, some promoted by the nursing homes. LTCFs offered a variety of services and activities to promote the well-being of their users, namely: access to a psychologist, a psychomotor therapist, physiotherapy, gymnastics, sociocultural animation, swimming, activities with the community, cultural trips and tours, farming/gardening, walking, etc. The day-to-day of the elderly users was fuller; while some already had a bigger tendency to not interact or participate as much, others were much more active and entertained themselves both by participating in the activities promoted by the LTCFs and autonomously. However, many of these activities and services were suspended when the pandemic started, especially those involving physical/close contact, social interaction, being outdoors, and the facilitation of professionals external to the LTCFs.

T1. Beginning of the Pandemic: During initial outbreak and lockdown (2020)

The beginning of the pandemic is one of the time periods most associated with negative feelings and appraisals. Workers remember feeling scared, especially because they were dealing with the unknown. People expected the lockdown to be over soon; to be something more temporary. It was described as awful; everything changed abruptly, and fear took over the lives of these people. The elderly users stress the fact that everything was closed suddenly and that they were closed inside the institutions without being able to leave as what they remember the most from the beginning of the pandemic. In terms of negative feelings, the users felt the most scared at the beginning, both for their health and the health of their relatives, and because of what they saw on the news.

“The unknown. There is no vaccine; there is no cure; there is no treatment; there is nothing... And it affects the elderly more; in nursing homes it was like that... And we have the case of Reguengos, where many people died, Alcáçovas, which was horrible...” (Worker9)

T2. Vaccination rollout (December 2020 to April 2021 and onwards)

Institutions received support from the NHS since the vaccination process was conducted at the LTCFs, therefore requiring no need for transportation and increased risk exposure. Despite this happening for both kinds of institutions and the process being generally successful, administration from private institutions made some negative evaluations. A couple of managers mentioned some disorganization on the part of the vaccination teams; the fact that in some cases not all doses being administered at the LTCF; negative beliefs regarding the effects of the vaccines both by managers and users (e.g., “do

more harm than good”, “are a scam”, etc.) and feelings of distrust and disagreement (e.g., felt pressured or obliged to do so). However, in general, the vaccination process went well; managers and workers got the users’ written consent to be vaccinated and families were kept informed. The elderly users (20/59) also talked about vaccination and expressed very positive attitudes and evaluations. While a few of them state that they were not asked for their preference and a few others seem to be indifferent, most of them see the vaccines optimistically, as something that is good for them and the people around them, and as an experience that was easy to go through. Even those who referred not having been asked for their opinion expressed willingness to be vaccinated.

T3. Detection of variants of concern (October 2021 to February 2022)

Workers and administration described their experiences with outbreaks at LTCFs throughout the evolution of the pandemic and detection of new variants. Most institutions dealt with at least one outbreak, and others even had 2-3 outbreaks at different points in time. In general, the first outbreaks were more difficult to deal with, more aggressive and damaging to the institutions, resulting in more infected, more severe symptoms and more deaths. In comparison, outbreaks of new variants (e.g., Omicron) happening around the end of 2021 and the first months of 2022 were described as more peaceful, easy to manage, and less worrying; they led to fewer negative consequences, despite being highly contagious, with most infected being asymptomatic or having very light symptoms and a lower number of deaths. Much of this improvement is attributed to the benefits of vaccination, since the users and workers were already vaccinated.

“We had positive cases, but the vaccines came and did their job here, because in February 2021 we had an outbreak with 14 cases, and we had an outbreak in February this year (2022) and it was completely different. In February 2021 we had 14 cases, but we were afraid of death, there was fear of serious situations occurring... Thank God, with the vaccine, now in February 2022 we had most of the nursing homes with COVID, but they were asymptomatic, most people did not even understand why they had to be isolated.” (Admin14)

T4. Current Situation: at the time of the interviews (March 2022 to July 2022)

Workers (11/35) mentioned how things were starting to return to normal at the time of the interview: there were less restrictions, families could visit the residents and take them outside the LTCF, activities restarted, and the elderly started being more cognitively and socially stimulated again. The general feeling is that the COVID-19 pandemic was essentially a matter of adaptation, something that will never fully go away but life must go on. A few users (3/6) also mentioned the lifting of restrictions as a positive factor; they were already starting to do the activities they used to do before.

2.7.6 Conclusions

Using the SES Framework (Figure 16) as a general scaffold for the conclusions it can be proposed:

1. In terms of the **Interaction Area (I)**, regarding **pandemic and risk communication**, each LTCF had to organize their own communication practices towards their staff, users and families since there was a lack of specific external support and guidelines. LTCFs were not always able to adapt their communication to more vulnerable users (e.g., dementia patients) due to the existence of different levels of cognitive capacities. Information put out by the government, health authorities and media were not adapted to the elderly, which contributed to more fear and confusion. Additionally, the excessive dissemination of the number of cases and deaths created more anxiety, panic and fear, not only for the elderly, but also the staff. Also, it made

communication with the families more difficult for the staff, and families confronted the workers with what they heard – and mainly perceived – from the news. In sum, there's a general feeling that risk communication failed for the Covid-19 pandemic and that a lot could have been done better, as documented in the literature (Palma-Oliveira, Trump & Linkov, 2021).

2. At the level of the **Governance Systems (GS)**, there is the shared opinion that the guidelines disseminated to the LTCFs were too complex and extensive at times so, in the future, information should be simplified to facilitate the implementation and adherence to the measures. More importantly, the structures of the governance systems were not prepared for a situation like this – a compound crisis – and were slow to adapt and respond to all the needs.
3. At the level of the **Actor Systems (A)**, social support networks were extremely important during the Covid-19 pandemic; contact with the families, even if remote, and a close relationship between staff and users were essential to mitigate the negative impacts of the pandemic.
4. In terms of **Resource Systems and Units (RSU)**, IPSS (private non-profit) institutions had a privileged access and availability of resources – human and material – compared to the private institutions due to the closer proximity to Social Security, to aid measures and other governmental initiatives. Non-material support in the form of visits, assistance and clarification was also a big differentiator between types of institutions, resulting in differences in the way directors and staff dealt with uncertainty and ambiguity in their decision-making as well as differences in their evaluations of the pandemic management. However, the help provided was often not enough and the health teams were not prepared to the volume of help requests, which resulted in insufficient responses for both types of institutions. Furthermore, facilities with more space/rooms were better able to isolate positive cases during outbreaks, and having outdoor spaces (e.g., vegetable gardens or backyards) was an important protective factor for users' well-being. Additionally, those institutions with internal specialized professionals and health care services (e.g., medical staff, physiotherapist, sociocultural animator, etc.), were able to maintain some of their services, benefiting their elderly residents.
5. At the level of **Outcomes (O)**, specifically regarding **protective and aggravating factors of risk and resilience**: Changes in the routines was one of the main structural causes of negative impacts on the mental and physical health of elderly residents of LTCFs, due to the restrictions imposed by quarantine and isolation, like the suspension of medical consultations and treatments, cultural activities, physical activity or any activities involving movement, and social events. Restrictions on family visits is one of the main risk factors for elderly's resilience. Feeling of abandonment, perception of cognitive decline and loss of autonomy are some of the main socio-psychological consequences in elderly residents of LTCFs. In fact, restrictive measures and distancing requirements increased isolation and feelings of loneliness, lack of emotional support, and reduced motivation (Eghtesadi, 2020; Fallon et al., 2020). Discouragement to participate in activities, resignation with life, health comorbidities and being away from their loved ones are aggravating effects on the level of resilience, representing vulnerabilities. Belief in vaccination, relationship with LTCF workers and remote contact are the main protective factors of the level of resilience of the elderly. In general, **adaptation was gradual and difficult, but the institutions feel like they succeeded and were able to adapt to the circumstances**, to the best of their abilities and despite all the obstacles.

Lessons learned and recommendations for the future

Workers and directors mentioned several aspects, namely:

- **The need for more recognition of the social sector and its needs.** Workers are underpaid and the work these professionals do is no longer limited to simpler services like hygiene and feeding, involving now almost taking on the role of a nurse due to the health conditions of the users (e.g., many users with dementia). Additionally, the funding non-profit institutions receive is not enough to face the costs and provide quality of life, especially considering the users are generally of lower socioeconomic status. In this sense, it was added that legislation should be reviewed, and funding should be supervised to ensure all needs are met.
- **The need to humanize the services provided.** See individuals instead of numbers; focus more on the well-being, life quality, assistance of the users, and less on the spaces and infrastructures (i.e., in terms of inspections and investments).
- **The need to consider mental health a priority and provide psychological support.** The elderly users are already a vulnerable population, but they became especially vulnerable during the pandemic and there was a clear lack of psychological support. In general, the pandemic deepened mental health concerns and created new fragilities (e.g., depression, anxiety, etc.) that did not receive the appropriate attention – both on the side of the residents and the workers. Furthermore, there's the need to capacitate and give tools to the LTCFs so they can deal with aspects regarding user's mental health in a way that is tailored for the elderly population and for the specific concerns of each crisis/situation.
- **The need to adapt** the measures and restrictions to the characteristics of each institution (e.g., size of the facilities, existence of outdoor spaces, etc.) and the needs of the elderly (e.g., not being closed inside the institution without social contact, movement or opportunities to be outdoors).
- **The need for communication practices to be directed and adapted to the elderly population.** *“The elderly are people too; they also need to understand information”*; having experts/health professionals talking to this population, directly explaining and clarifying any doubts the elderly might have regarding the crisis should be a bigger concern.
- **The need to work together.** Work as a partnership both between different public entities and between the entities and the people working in the field (e.g., directors of LTCFs).
- **Public entities' responses** in the face of emergencies/requests for help (e.g., from Social Security, the National Health System) need to be **swifter and timelier**; national structures and systems must be better prepared to deal with a compound crisis.

2.8 Spain, URJC

2.8.1 Introduction

The case study defined in the Spanish case study explores **the experience of COVID-19 among migrants of Latin American and Moroccan origin in Madrid**. Research conducted in the framework of this grant suggested that migrants were one of the most affected communities by the pandemic due to the syndemic nature of the crises unleashed by the pandemic. These communities are two of the most numerous communities in Madrid, according to national statistics (INE 2021). Further information about the profile of this population can be found in Deliverable 3.4. As it was previously

described, this population, on average, is younger than the regional average and mostly of working age. Describing one of our researched groups as people from Latin American origin leads to including a heterogeneous group of citizens from almost every Spanish-speaking country in Latin America and different situations. For instance, in the last few years there has been a wave of migration from the upper classes in Venezuela, who have come to Spain fleeing the political and economic instability in their country. We focus on migrants from a low socioeconomic status, who are the ones who have found themselves in vulnerable situations during the pandemic.

In line with other working packages in the project, we have focused on migrants and how the pandemic has had an effect not only on their health outcomes, but more generally on their overall levels of wellbeing and life course (Settersten et al., 2020). This is the case because we expect them to be in generally good health at the early stages of the pandemic and, even if their physical wellbeing may have not resented after COVID-19, there are many other dimensions that have, and that could shape health outcomes in the future for this population group. In addition, there is an interest in this population group because this group had particularly high levels of exposure to the pandemic due to their socioeconomic conditions: occupational profiles, characteristics of their households, etc. The final motivation to choose this group is the lack of access to these groups in other studies that focus on the general population. These groups are hard to reach and an experience of COVID-19 that can provide relevant lessons for future crises.

This case study intended to explore differences between two communities of migrants in Madrid. Our initial expectation was that those who spoke Spanish as mother tongue would have dealt more easily with the disturbances derived from the COVID-19 pandemic (Smith et al., 2021). The analysis of the interviews shows otherwise. The relations with the actor system were strained, particularly regarding vaccination. At the same time, the crisis was an opportunity for the creation of solidarity networks, the introduction of new policies regarding the provision of social services and the digitalization and streamlining of procedures. The more complex interactions occurred around crisis communication. Increasingly fragmented information has created challenges for those conveying information and those receiving it. Contrary to our initial expectation, there are no significant differences between the responses of both communities in terms of how challenging the pandemic was. This may be explained by the characteristics of the interviewees that were recruited: they had built a life in Spain (they have all spent more than five years) and were fluent enough to conduct the interview without an interpreter. This suggests that the differences between communities may be more significant amongst those who have lived for a short period of time but, if they are able to build a life project in Madrid, these differences fade and difficulties are tied to other dimensions of the migratory experience (precarity, xenophobia, etc.).

Figure 19. URJC, Spain – SES Framework.

2.8.2 Purpose and Research Questions

The case study defined for Spain explores the experience of COVID-19 amongst migrants of Latin American and Moroccan origin in Madrid from a systems socioeconomic framework. The main objective is to better understand how a multi-staged crisis can affect citizens of migrant origin. We are interested in these groups because they are usually the ones with weaker networks to pull them through difficult periods and higher contagion risks (Settersten et al., 2020). In this regard, these individuals were on the verge of vulnerability, but they were not considered as vulnerable, and they were not recurring to social aid on a regular basis. Until the outbreak of the pandemic, these migrants were able to make ends meet and provide aid to families in their countries of origin. However, this income was unstable and strongly reliant on the capacity of these individuals to move around and find work in the informal economy. The lack of contractual relationships led to a sudden stop in this income as employers could not apply for safeguards and employees could not benefit from furlough schemes. This research intends to document these experiences and explore which mechanisms were put in place, both by citizens and the actor systems involved to overcome these disruptions.

To do so, we have developed a series of research questions that not only look at the experience of migrants but also to the larger actor system involved. In this regard, this case study attempts to answer the following research questions: What strategies, if any, did the local government put in place to tackle the COVID-19 pandemic regarding migrant communities? To what extent have social services and other institutional actors adapted to provide for the needs created by the pandemic? What strategies, if any, did they implement? How have members of the studied migrant communities gathered and shared information about the pandemic? How was information adapted to these communities in case there was any adaptation? What solidarity strategies and social aids seek members of these communities to fare through the pandemic? How have they experienced the disruptions linked to the COVID-19 pandemic? These research questions are the same ones included in previous deliverables.

2.8.3 Method

The original methodology of this case study envisioned a mixed methods approach that combined survey analysis with in-depth interviews. However, research needs to focus solely on the qualitative part of the research. The surveys we intended to use as further triangulation are a series of survey studies commissioned by the local government during the pandemic. These studies were supposed to be a household panel study that allowed for tracking of participants during the pandemic. When we started exploring the dataset there are some reasons why we have chosen to drop this side of the research. First, the household identifiers are not consistent across waves which meant that the panel dimension could not be used. Second, the question regarding nationality was not coded using all the categories. Instead, there were three response options (Spanish, EU nationals and Third-Country nationals) that did not allow us to identify the specific groups we were interested in.

Turning to the interviews, as was described in the COREQ requirements, we also applied the socioeconomic framework to define the interviews conducted. The resulting sample of interviews can be divided into two groups: institutional actors and citizen interviews. The first interviews conducted were selected using a purposive sample of members of the local government that were involved in the provision of social services during the pandemic. Taking advantage of previous contacts with the local government of the lead researcher we managed to reach decision-makers in the local government (response rate amongst this group 80%). This allowed us to gain direct insight into how the government

system reacted to the new issues that emerged during this period, whether they were able to detect them quickly and whether any measures were put in place. After, a second round of interviews was launched focused on those who were responsible for providing such services on the ground and with CSOs. Regarding access, some contacts were facilitated by the members of the local government and by acquaintances of another colleague, such as contacts with police or firemen (response rate 100%, every contact made resulted in an interview). Turning to the CSOs, we received a list of organizations that work with the city council, and we selected a convenience sample that allowed us to gain some perspective of how they had managed through the pandemic (response rate of 71%). The translated questionnaire administered in the interviews with citizens can be found in Appendix B (Annex 8.1). The original questionnaire is in Spanish. The translated questionnaire administered in the interviews with institutional actors – from decision makers to practitioners and CSOs – can be found in Appendix B (Annex 8.2). It is similar to the previous one insofar as it explores the same topics. The main difference is that it shifts the attention from the personal experience to how their organizational activity was affected by COVID-19. The original questionnaire is also in Spanish.

Once the first round of interviews was completed and after several exchanges with the lead researchers of the working package, the third round of analyses was launched. The characteristics of the citizens to be interviewed were identified: men and women, country of origin (Latin American or Moroccan), length of stay in Spain (at least 5 years prior to the pandemic). There has been an ongoing discussion amongst members of the project to find the ideal entry point to contact individuals with these characteristics that are one of the main examples of how vulnerability was embodied during the pandemic. In this regard, three of the organizations interviewed in the previous round were contacted but only two of them offered to forward the information about the interviews to their members and beneficiaries. This led to 17 candidates who were willing to participate and were contacted to schedule interviews. Between non-response and problems in the scheduling, finally 13 interviews were conducted. One of the weaknesses in this regard is that response rates are distributed unevenly. As can be seen in the COREQ Requirements Table in Appendix A (Annex 9), Latin American respondents were more willing to participate than Moroccan respondents. Furthermore, there was one interview with a Moroccan woman that could not be conducted because she did not feel confident enough in Spanish to be able to participate and there were no resources available to fund a translator. The interviews were conducted in cafeterias in places that were convenient for the interviewees to minimize disturbances due to participating in this research.

Once the interviews were conducted, they were transcribed by a transcription company following GDPR guidelines. Transcripts can be made available if needed. The transcripts have been analysed according to the topics mentioned by respondents. The original block script focused on the main topics of interest of this project: vulnerability linked to socioeconomic conditions (mainly due to the characteristics of their occupational profile or their housing arrangement), disturbances of their social relations due to the pandemic, their experience of the pandemic (including health consequences), and information consumption patterns during the pandemic. In addition, three further elements have been considered in the analyses due to evolving interests within the project and those topics coming up repeatedly without any specific prompting on behalf of the interviewers. The first topic added was attitudes towards vaccines and vaccination programmes. Given that the project was designed well before vaccines were available and vaccination programmes unrolled, it was not included in the initial considerations. However, the interviews were carried out during the vaccination campaign, which allowed interviewers to ask about this issue. Second, many interviewees have talked about trust in

different institutions. Trust has been found to be a significant factor in predicting mortality outcomes during the pandemic (Charron et al., 2023). Finally, respondents repeatedly discussed how they and their family members felt during the pandemic. Given that they were not asked specifically, the fact that they felt the need to discuss their feelings seems a relevant addition to the analyses that will be conducted in the following section.

2.8.4 Results: Data Reporting

Figure 20. URJC, Spain – Coding Tree.

Word Cloud depicting the word frequency when describing the experience of COVID-19 from the interviews with the participants in Appendix B (Annex 8.3).

2.8.5 Results: Analysis and Interpretation

The Spanish case explores comprehensively the SES framework within which two migrant groups found themselves during the pandemic. As mentioned in the previous paragraph, to conduct this research, interviews were conducted both with institutional actors and with citizens from these two communities. In this section, we intend to outline the main results of the analyses of these interviews. First, the main issues regarding the institutional interviews will be discussed. Second, the results from the citizen interviews will be discussed considering what was said among the members of the actor system and the extent to which there was a match between the perceptions of the different groups.

Interviews with members of the actor system

Before the crisis, the local government in its II Madrid Plan for Social and Intercultural Coexistence (Ayuntamiento de Madrid, 2016) detailed its competencies regarding migration. This allowed them to develop devolved competencies that different national regulations have attributed to them. First, Spanish legislation on the rights of migrant citizens attributes specific functions to municipalities in terms of registration (Articles 42.2 e) and 45.2 b) of the Regulation for the Development of Organic Law 4/2000), social services and integration (Arts. 25 and 26 of the Law regulating municipalities) and Madrid's city council is attributed subsidiary functions due to its exceptional condition as the capital city of the country. Besides this general framework, additional regional legislation attributes municipalities to broad competencies in migration management.

One of the key findings regarding the pandemic, replicating in the citizen interviews, is the adaptability of those involved in its management. When they were asked about the pandemic, what came to their minds was mainly the first stage, the lockdown that lasted until May-June 2020. After this, they seem to get used to it and since people were allowed out of their homes again, COVID-19 became one of the many challenges they dealt with. Those first months of the pandemic left a mark on those practitioners who recall feelings of solitude, but also gratitude towards those working with them.

"We were not ready for any of this, so we had to take many decisions. [...] This was an impressive rollout of means, people had to come here for their computers, in many cases so that computers could be distributed to those who could not come... In many many cases, and, of course it is my Directorate, almost everyone came for their computer and took it home. That is, the staff working at the Directorate reacted admirably because people did not stop working a single day." (Decision-maker 03)

Communication strategies

Communication, particularly crisis communication is a task that governments perform in which they need to balance providing worrisome information, the crisis, and tranquilizing information, what is being done to tackle it and what citizens need to do to protect themselves. During the COVID-19 pandemic this was no exception. What has changed regarding previous crises is the fragmenting of the media landscape. The flourishing of social media and the contamination between traditional media outlets and social media has opened new opportunities for misinformation to be presented as veracious and travel faster than rumours or other forms of fake news did before.

Governments have tried during the pandemic to provide updated and accurate information. However, fighting misinformation often requires extra effort. In this regard, the interviews show there are two

positions: those who believed that they only needed to provide information as accurate as possible and those who claim to have taken this step further by refuting misinformation. Firstly, some of the interviewees deny having to fight against misinformation. In Spain, we see high levels of acceptance of the measures implemented during the pandemic, with fewer significant opposition movements compared to other countries. This could explain why, in general, most entities did not face serious problems regarding the fight against misinformation. Instead, there were continuous information campaigns that aimed to explain to the citizens what was happening in the clearest possible way.

"We have had many communication strategies that we had before, but that we have redoubled... we redoubled communication efforts to the population [...] through all media, I think [...] we used different sources [...] We did not have a feeling of fake news during the pandemic, fake news, no, there might have been different interpretations." (Practitioner 04, Police)

"We have our own online newspaper where we posted everything that happened, all the rules if we had to restrict personnel, go back, etc., we published it so that when you opened your computer, you could inform yourself." (CSO 02)

Amongst those who claim to take a stance against information, they identify vaccination campaigns as one of the main sources of concern. Different entities (both public and CSOs) provided information and guidance, which, on top of the information about how every procedure was being fast-tracked to make it available as soon as possible, created considerable confusion amongst the population. Interviews with migrants from both communities show how some of the information regarding the fight against COVID-19 was easily perceived as fake (for instance, one of the interviewees mentions Trump's suggestion of drinking bleach), but with the vaccine, there was more reluctance.

"The vaccine. The issue of confinement, no, people had it clear, and people demanded it. The issue of the vaccine [...] we met with them, explained what it was, and they understood that it didn't mean they would be tracked or lost... etc., etc. So, that was the only moment when we had to address misinformation." (Practitioner 05)

"We had to provide a lot of information, but there were moments when we didn't have government information either because the vaccine arrived, and no one was clear about what it was, if it was really effective, if it was going to be a single vaccine [...] it has been through dialogue, explaining the guidelines given by the government [...] we put the information on the table, everything is on TV, in the news, and the media." (CSO 01)

The confusion around the information being provided was also perceived as a by-product of polarization and politicization of the pandemic. At the beginning, it was a valence issue and almost every administration cooperated. As the crisis extended over time, tensions started to emerge as some political actors made it an issue over which they could compete. For instance, no one denied COVID-19 but there were strong differences on how protective measures and economic performance should be balanced. The regional government in Madrid (conservative) was one of the most vocal against restrictions proposed by the national government (socialist). Given that the municipality is also held by the conservative party, the local government saw itself dragged into these highly polarized conflict dynamics.

"We have not faced post-truth [...] if I had to say something, [...] I had the feeling that politics came into play because there were criticisms in the Madrid City Council that, from my

perspective, didn't match what I saw happening in the day-to-day work of those people here in the social centre. I think politics [...] came in to distort things." (Decision-maker 02)

Within this struggle, providing information for vulnerable groups, particularly migrants, became an additional challenge, as they lack the skills to easily apprehend the information provided. The interviews conducted show that this was not done by designing specific information campaigns. Instead, they coordinated with third-sector organizations in formal and informal channels. Formally, all the information is published online so that these organizations could make it available to their beneficiaries.

"Because you look for it, and you don't find it, you know? Maybe they have it, but it's hidden there on the page." (CSO 01)

However, the information was so vast that they also scheduled meetings with social workers and third-sector professionals and other actors relevant to these groups to segment the information and provide the highlights they wanted communicated to these groups.

"That's a topic that is complicated, we have a formal way, and then what we are implementing more informally to reach people. In the formal way, you know that the Administration publishes everything, and they have to do it for transparency, and everything is public on the website, which is so dense due to numerous publications [...] even in search engines, it's difficult to find something because if you don't use the exact word... [...] So what we did first is inform all the professionals, I mean, it's not a practice that can be done regularly, what we did is inform all the social workers from all the centres, all the staff, [...] about this procedure, how to operate it, in which cases it can be used, and in which cases it cannot be used." (Decision-maker 01)

Public institutions also tried to reinforce their capacity to communicate directly through channels that compensated for the loss of direct attention to the public. In this regard, many online procedures that were being piloted or developed were fast-tracked, information was posted online, appointments were set up for telephone assistance with procedures and telephone information lines were reinforced.

"Much of the contact has been, well, over the phone, through telematics, and everything has also been posted on the City Council's website so that people knew where the resources were, but there has been a lot of direct contact, you know? It has been a lot through direct contact with the resources. Yes, we do have the need, and this is something we believe we should do, and it's a task we have on our hands, to establish catalogues of benefits and services that we provide." (Decision-maker 03)

"So, starting from September 2020, we began to set up booths because the Regional government asked for them, and we have always responded to the Regional government on these matters, and the City Council itself also asked for them. 'Hey, we need to start setting up awareness booths for the COVID issue.'" (Practitioner 02)

In summary, the provision of information was a difficult task because in-person contact was lost and measures had to be put in place of this information, mainly online or by telephone. Despite this, some of the members of the public administration were aware that this was not enough, and they developed additional strategies to contact significant community members that could act as information transmitters to these communities that were out of reach of an administration that was already swamped. Turning to the information itself, the fragmentation of media landscapes and the flourishing

of social media has opened a breach that allows for misinformation to become widespread. The degree to which this is considered an issue varies, as some consider that they should take an active role, while others consider that their role is to provide truthful information and that media outlets should act as filters for fake information.

Vulnerabilities and resilience within the organizations

The second research question regarding the role of those in the actor system was related to the appearance of vulnerabilities in the organizations that had to provide support and how they were addressed. The outbreak of the pandemic created a crisis for which the different actors composing the actor system were unprepared. In the first moments of the pandemic, as the disease spread, most of these institutions found themselves in uncharted territory for which they needed to develop new protocols to be able to provide their services in a safe manner for their workers and for beneficiaries. Several factors were key in defining the pace at which this adaptation process occurred. Differences between organizations concerning nature (public vs private), size and competencies are among the key factors identified. First, private organizations usually have regulations that allow them to shift practices and adapt faster than public ones, whose regulation intends to guarantee fairness and the rule of law. Second, larger organizations with more members have usually less capacity to adapt than smaller ones that need to put to work a smaller amount of people and where communication is more fluid. Finally, those organizations (be it CSOs or public institutions) who are used to protecting themselves, such as firefighters or police, could adapt their protocols faster than those who had different competencies. As knowledge about the virus advanced, they just needed to adapt existing protocols, whereas other institutions had to design and implement new ones. Despite the differences, all the interviews share a similar description of what happened with the first months as extremely chaotic and disorganized, and later they managed to develop protocols and get the work done. Indeed, it is a common finding across the interviews with different actors how administrators were surprised by how the members of these organizations stepped up and contributed to the adaptation to the new circumstances and developing an unforeseen resilience.

“At the beginning, a response had to be given and the response was not very organised, I think that everyone tried to respond. Here I always divide it into three, on the one hand there was the Public Administration; on the other hand there was the Third Sector, or Organised Civil Society, which already had experience in this; and then in third place there was the unorganised private initiative, which at that moment was organised to do it, or which has a function and adopted another function at that moment.” (Decision-maker 01)

“The quickest to act were the neighbourhood associations, food distribution points and so on, which did it in a very unstructured way, but very quickly, they had those two things. This was good at first, because what it generated was that families could be provided with a very basic need for food and so on, but it was soon very counterproductive. Why? Because the fact that they were not organised, not coordinated, caused [...] hoarding; in other words, situations began to arise that were not the best. So, around the month of June-July, I think that all this response began to be organised between social services and the more organised third sector, [...] the other initiatives began to disappear, because they were no longer necessary, [...] I think they played a very important role at the beginning.” (Decision-maker 01)

Due to this unforeseen situation, most of the interviewees state that they had to change their mentality, functions and programmes to adapt to the new social reality imposed by the health crisis.

Thus, they put aside their usual tasks to focus on measures, on the one hand, to protect their own resources, their own workers as part of the identified essential services.

“The first thing is to attend to the population and to attend to our own resources, it was clear to us that if we did not control the pandemic in the operation we would run out of firefighters, and if we ran out of firefighters we were not going to attend either to the population or to the activities that were going to take place, and we said: well let's see, let's think about what could happen [...], we said: [...] risk analysis.” (Practitioner 01)

“You couldn't eradicate the disease, you had to take care of logistics, hygiene, protection, distance, hand washing, disinfectants [...] so that the doctor, the health personnel could do their job without being distracted by anything.” (CSO 02)

This also meant undergoing processes of digitalization, as many of these institutions relied on personal contact and paper rather than computers and the Internet. In this regard, the pandemic became an opportunity to accelerate existing modernization plans and a way to improve efficiency in how these organizations worked.

“In terms of efficiency we have improved a lot, and the quality of our services I think are better now than before the pandemic, and I think the pandemic forced us to do that, it forced us to be more productive from a social point of view, to improve all our methodologies and processes, to review them. We have reviewed, that's why I was telling you about the digital part, we have reviewed all our processes and all the processes have been adapted, and I believe that today we are undoubtedly much better prepared to face a new challenge.” (CSO 03)

On the other hand, organizations were rendered vulnerable because the rate at which their services were demanded increased exponentially in a matter of days. The lockdown meant that new profiles of vulnerable families, without buffer nets to substitute the loss of income due to the closures, emerged and had dire needs that needed response. Public institutions could not adapt fast enough to digital environments, so governments relied on CSOs to take over and fill this gap despite the mobility restrictions.

“We adjusted to covering basic needs, that's it, because without food and without that, we adjusted to that. Then if there was something special from the lawyers or whatever, they were called, but what we kept and never missed was the basic needs coverage.” (CSO 04)

Coordination through the City Council's Municipal Emergency Territorial Plan (PEMAM) was also identified as a key strategy to identify challenges but also solutions that adapted to the mobility restrictions, particularly during the first lockdown:

“There have been many good practices here. Look, I think that the issue of coordination, for example, has been something that has allowed us to set many things in motion. Good practices would be coordination, we were able to set up a project to distribute food to families who could not go out on the street to collect it [...] we had to set up a coordination project [...] we were able to bring together the fire brigade, the local police, Madrid Salud and ourselves.” (Decision-maker 01)

“We had very effective coordination with the social services, we had coordination with the whole framework of the Community of Madrid in terms of civil protection and we also carried out many campaigns through the government delegation and the Community of Madrid.” (Practitioner 04)

Addressing vulnerability amongst migrant communities

In line with the results in working packages 4 and 5, public officials at the regional and national level were under such pressure to tackle the pandemic that measures were targeted at the general population. Measures were not tailored to the specific needs migrant communities may experience. Prior to conducting the interviews, the expectation was that local governments, as the level of government in direct contact with these citizens, may have undertaken some specific adaptations. However, given existing findings from other levels of government, it could also be the case that they had not. The interviews conducted show that communication strategies tried to simplify the message so that it was comprehensible to every citizen but there were no specific strategies targeted at migrants:

“I think that hunger has affected many people, perhaps more immigrants than natives, because their relative situation of vulnerability is greater, that is to say, there are more people in worse conditions among those with an immigrant background than among those without, but vulnerability ends up affecting everyone in the same way [...]” (Decision-maker 01)

Decision makers in the local government considered that the COVID-19 pandemic had not created differentiated needs amongst migrants, because it was an exceptional situation where other characteristics marked the emergence of unmet necessities:

“What I tried to do was to break the positive discrimination that existed towards certain groups that I understand that in an ordinary period they might deserve it because being an immigrant and not having social support networks puts you in a particular situation in life, but when the Madrid City Council provides you with emergency food in an emergency situation of economic closure, your hunger is the same as the hunger of the person who has social networks, because no one could move from their home, the activity of the underground economy was paralysed, we know that many cases, particularly the most vulnerable ones, work economically in the underground economy, that is to say; it seemed to me that it was unnecessary to privilege any group.” (Decision-maker 02)

This approach stems from two considerations. First, the local government tried to avoid identifying migrants as specially deserving to avoid making those collectives the target of xenophobic attacks. The Chinese community was already trying to avoid being pointed at and the uncertainty of the situation could lead to an increase in racism and xenophobia. As shown in the citizen interviews, this fear was matched amongst the migrant communities. This logic also stems from the fact that, at least in Madrid, thanks to the registration policy, undocumented migrants can be protected by the city council, without the need to establish any kind of differentiation.

“People who do not have documentation, a valid residence and work permit, have difficulty accessing a minimum income, a Ingreso Mínimo Vital (minimum vital income) or a housing benefit. In the case of the Madrid City Council we do not have this limit, any person who is registered on the census, which is the requirement, can access any type of assistance.” (Decision-maker 02)

Amongst practitioners there was also this view that migrants did not pose specific challenges and policies had to be targeted based on other characteristics that led to vulnerable situations:

“Specific measures were applied, but based on the characteristics of the people, what we said before, if we had problems with alcoholism disorders and we had to lock them up, the centres

were adapted to respond to that profile. But [...] it was more based on their needs and their problems than on any other series of conditions, so, no. For example, we had to adapt to the foreign population in terms of communication by producing documents in different languages” (Practitioner 03)

Finally, the third sector also perceives a broad aid framework, which factors vulnerable groups, but without making specific mention of migrants, for example, an interviewee gives this response when asked about recommendations to the authorities:

“It is necessary [...] to strengthen protection systems for vulnerable people, for the elderly, for women especially victims of gender-based violence, for migrants, for refugees, for children and for the homeless.” (CSO 02)

Therefore, the results of the interviews conducted have provided relevant information that articulates our case study. Both policy makers at the local level and representatives of the third sector have described a similar reality. The different interventions that were carried out, in any social and health care field, both by public institutions and third sector entities were not targeted at specific ethnic characteristics, rather they tried to respond as best as they could to the growing needs triggered by the pandemic. Services were put in place to address economic and social vulnerability, but these were not specifically targeted at migrants. Moreover, private-public collaboration during the first months of the pandemic was increased to respond to an exponential growth in the demand for social services. In the city of Madrid, hunger became a widespread problem affecting multiple households. In this sense, a network of services was built to deliver not only food but also services to households whose savings, if there were any, were rapidly depleting and could not guarantee new income.

Interviews with members of the migrant communities

In this section, the interviewees were less articulate than those in the preceding section. For this reason, quotes will be translated to English and the original in Spanish is made available as a footnote in case it can further clarify what they are saying.

Citizens’ interviews started with a prompt in which respondents were asked to remember three key moments from the pandemic. The first finding in this regard is that they all start recalling how they spent the first lockdown. They soon get carried away in this memory and they do not mention the other two moments. It seems as if the first lockdown left a very strong mark but afterwards, COVID-19 and the disturbances attached become part of their daily routine and they lose the sense of exceptionality. This does not mean that there is a loss of awareness of the risk of contagion or that they feel that their life has gone back to how it was before the pandemic. For instance, some of the interviewees do speak about other measures implemented in further stages as the interview advances but they do not give this sense of significance that the first lockdown does have. For example, one of the women interviewed talks about how the closures that happened in Madrid during the fall of 2020 were very hard to understand because they corresponded with administrative delimitations that are never used by citizens:

“There were measures that I did not understand, but as I did not understand I remained like this, without understanding why they said that you could not go out from this zone to this other, but I said that I passed through that area and the people in that area were passing to this one. I can’t understand. That is, I said to myself: does this make any sense?” (Citizen 04, Latin American woman)

One of the main research questions of this case study is articulated around communication practices and habits of migrant communities during the pandemic. Our initial expectation was that for those who did not have Spanish as their mother tongue, information consumption should have been more challenging than for those whose mother tongue was Spanish. As mentioned in the methodological section, the interviewees have a length of stay that has allowed them to learn the language with quite some fluency. In addition, the lack of translators led to not having interviews with people who did not feel comfortable expressing themselves in Spanish.

The interviews show that media consumption patterns are not only linked to language proficiency but to skills in a broader sense and to trust. Gendered patterns emerge both in terms of how much information was consumed and the trust they placed in this information. For instance, male interviewees speak about how they consumed much less information than the women interviewed. Furthermore, the men talk about how they consumed information on television, but they resorted to the women around them to provide the information, telling them about what they were watching in the news and what happened to their acquaintances:

“Yes, my mother kept up with the information and a little bit my father. Indeed, she kept us more or less informed at home about all this. But, as I was telling you, was like repetitive, very repetitive” (Citizen 03, Latin American man)

This same interview illustrated the mood of respondents with similar sociodemographic characteristics:

“In general, during 2020 and a bit during 2021, but there was a lot of information running around because that was what we were going through. Daily, almost 25 out of 24 hours a day there was only information about COVID. This was a bit tedious because they repeated the same things over and over. People in my house and acquaintances were saturated with information that we did not really know whether it was truthful or not, because there was so much speculation and so many things that one said, look, we are not going to listen to the news anymore. We started reading sporadic news or listening to specific broadcasts, but we no longer listened to everything because it was practically all talking about the same, going over the same contents, and it was almost nonsense. Everything was nonsense because other news came out refuting the first. Then, you are left wondering: what for? Are they disinforming the population or are they providing false information to the population?” (Citizen 03, Latin American Man)

Younger men from both communities also discuss their preference for social media as a significant source of information to learn about what happened in their countries of origin. In contrast, women talk about how social media helped them make sense of information on media outlets when they were not fully able to understand what was happening:

“As I told you before I tried what I listen to, I do not have to understand and then I go on and watch it from those youtubers who were saying that they explained it as it was and so on.” (Latin American woman)

Despite this recourse to social media, most of the interviewees consider that the quality of the information they were fed on traditional media outlets was satisfactory. Some of them suggest that the information could have been translated to other languages and some adaptations could have been made to account for some residents' lack of proficiency in Spanish to fully understand official

information. Turning to fake news, those who identify fake news received them through Whatsapp groups they had with family and friends or Youtube:

“Indeed because, see, I received many many messages from Colombia, from my country, with this story on Youtube from the same doctors, from the police there in Colombia, from what they were saying, what they were living there. And the dishonesty, there in Colombia were discussing the lies under which citizens in Europe were living. In the US, closer to Colombia, the same, look at that crazy man Trump. Then, if you watch it, you are bombarded with news that you cannot really tell. Are they true? Are they lies? And then comes YouTube, true doctors and fake doctors talking. Look at what happened with vaccines” (Citizen 13, Latin American woman)

Along with patterns of media consumption, interviewees also described their trust in the information being provided and their trust in different actors within the actor system. Overall, interviewees seem to trust the actor system and the institutions involved in decision making. Some of the responses mention the lack of agreement between different levels of government as something they disliked but not as a major issue. At the same time, respondents also acknowledged the fact that COVID-19 was a new disease about which there were few certainties. Although there are no precise excerpts to illustrate differences in trust between the two communities, reading both groups of interviews suggests that there are some mild differences. While Moroccan interviewees tended to rely on networks of people with whom they had family connections and CSOs, South American were more open to include as well other people they met or recur to public administrations. Nonetheless, the young men interviewees also expressed views of mistrust regarding public administrations. Rather than nationality, people with lower levels of trust (whatever their origin) seem to be the ones that were recurring more to social media to make sense of the information they received, where they received a variety of information with varying degrees of truthfulness.

In terms of trust, the women interviewed tend to be more trusting than the men. However, amongst the more religious women identifying as evangelical, pastors have been a key heuristic to understand the information provided but also opening the door to some of the “conspiracy beliefs”, particularly regarding vaccination campaigns.

“Interviewee: With the vaccine, I said I would not get vaccinated, I said, because I am catholic and Christian evangelical, and they were telling us about the chip.

Interviewer: The chips, I see. And how did you change your mind?

Interviewee: I did not, I got the shot because I had to go to Ecuador.

Interviewer: So it was because you needed to go to Ecuador. Had it not been the case, you would not have gotten vaccinated? Why?

Interviewee: Because I did not believe that the vaccine was necessary. Because I was saying, will it be true that they are giving us the vaccine or what are they giving to us? And as some were saying that they were putting water into the shots, I said, why should I get water? I already have water I said” (Citizen 07, Latin American woman)

In this regard, despite respondents being generally satisfied with the quality of the information, these answers suggest that more could be done in terms of crisis communication to provide the information in a way in which uncertainties are acknowledged and information is presented in a way that makes sense of contradictions and changes.

Vaccines against COVID-19 have provided ample opportunities for fake news to circulate. Out of the full sample of interviews, two have not taken the vaccine and three have done it reluctantly. That is, 85% of the people recruited for the interview have taken the vaccine, a slightly lower rate of vaccination compared to the general population. In terms of vaccine hesitancy, the rates are closer to those of the general population considering the small number of interviews conducted (Borga et al., 2022). What is remarkable in this case is that all the hesitant recipients had been fully vaccinated and even those who had not taken the shot were considering it, as they were thinking about travelling to their countries of origin and without the vaccine it would be much more difficult and expensive (need to take additional tests, difficulties to receive travelling authorizations, etc). In terms of their profile, those who had not been vaccinated were young men, whereas vaccine hesitancy emerged amongst middle-aged women with high levels of religiosity. These interviewees argue that, despite the lack of trust, they took the shot to avoid the negative consequences of not doing so, which included travel difficulties, but also job loss. The existence of these constraints, combined with a comprehensive vaccination scheme may be one of the key drivers of the high levels of coverage achieved in Spain.

“Then you cannot travel. Without getting the vaccine you cannot travel, nor work, nor go out and about to do your usual things like shopping or going to the doctor’s or to the library. That was what they were saying at the beginning.” (Citizen 01, Moroccan woman)

Migrant populations have been counted amongst the most vulnerable to the pandemic (Molenaar & Van Praag, 2022; Smith et al., 2021). Nonetheless, its members are usually young and in generally good physical condition, thus, their risk of contagion is not derived from pre-existing ailments, rather from their housing arrangements and occupational profile. In fact, only 3 out of the 13 interviewees mention having some form of physical impairment and all of them are linked to muscular or bone issues derived from their occupation. A fourth interviewee (see Citizen03’s interview) mentions that in his family, his mother and brother have significant disabilities that rendered them in need for special protection, and still, when they became sick with COVID-19 they only suffered a mild version of the infection.

During the first lockdown (details can be found in the deliverables in working package 4), the national government implemented a generous furlough scheme for every company that had to interrupt or reduce their activity due to the closure measures. This measure, which reached many citizens, was insufficient to cover the needs of many whose income relied on the gig economy. These furlough schemes were linked to social contributions that those in the informal economy had not paid. The income of every interviewee relied to some extent on these gigs, although the level of exposure was different. For some it was a top up of their income which allowed them to live more comfortably than just with their main salary. There are two interviewees who discuss how they did not feel this reduction of income as much because they maintained other sources of income. For others, it was their main source of income or even the only one. It is for these citizens, mainly women who work in the care sector, for whom the closure produced a sudden loss of their whole income, and they lacked the savings to buffer the impact. Similarly, men working in construction found themselves without a contract that could back their applications for passes to move around and look for work. As a result, they suddenly found themselves in need of applying for social help, unable to pay for rent, utilities or food.

“Before the lockdown everything was fine. I was working, although not generally [he means not with a legal contract] but with people I knew, people you search for on the Internet and you go to work and we made ends meet. When the lockdown arrived, with everyone at home, there

were moments when we were left without food, without money to buy.” (Citizen 06, Moroccan man)

In addition to their occupational profile, their accommodation was also a source of vulnerability as they often live in crowded accommodations. There are two main profiles within those interviewed: families who have their own flat and those who live in some form of shared accommodation. All the interviewees were recruited through organizations that have provided social aid during the pandemic. They have all had to ask for social assistance, be it in the form of pre-paid cards that they could use to buy in supermarkets or food packages. However, compared to the latter, those families that lived in their own flats were slightly better off. They experienced difficulties and sometimes had to cut some utilities or refrain from providing support to other family members in their countries of origin but, at the time the interviews were being conducted, they had been more or less able to bounce back. Despite asking for help, these interviewees did not have the feeling that the pandemic had caused them large financial turmoil. Out of the 5 interviewees in this group, only one family had moved, downsizing to a smaller apartment and she argues that this decision was made to cut the cost and to increase the resources available to help the organization with whom she was working:

“I was living in a three-bedroom apartment, with my son and another person and I had to leave. [...] For the reason I was describing, because of affordability, and also, at the same time, to be able to contribute a bit more to the social aid for other comrades. That is, to help others and myself, because of the demand and because we did not know what the length of the lockdown would be.” (Citizen 12, Latin American woman)

Those who were living in shared flats narrate more extreme experiences, although there are differences within them. Most of them (5 interviewees out of a total of 8 sharing flats with other families) live in flats where two or three rooms are allocated to different families and the kitchen and bathroom are shared. These interviewees were either single or in a couple sharing with other adults in a similar situation. Amongst them, some had children who were living in their countries of origin, being taken care of by other family members, and others had adult children. The loss of income derived from lockdowns and the reduction of activity had a cascade effect. On the one hand, they could not afford to pay rent, they had to cut on expenses (postpone payment of utilities, switch to cheaper telephone/Internet plans, change eating habits) and they had to apply for social aid from private organizations like Caritas or the Red Cross because they did not meet the criteria to receive aid from public institutions or they were overflown with applications that they could not reply fast enough. However, within this group there are three who endured even tougher circumstances. Two of them spent the pandemic in supervised accommodation (shelter or foster homes). After the lockdown was substituted by other measures, they transitioned to shared flats with multiple families where they complain about the cleanliness and the difficulties to maintain some of the measures. The last interview within this case started the pandemic in a house shared with his wife’s family but they could not afford it anymore in the summer, so they occupied a house while he tried to get back to working. These three cases share an overlap of problems which resulted in them moving to very poor-quality housing. For instance, during the first months of the lockdown the police cancelled appointments to renew work and residence permits. Documents were issued extending the validity of those expired, but some did not trust these extensions, which led to subsequent job loss and eviction.

The last two sources of vulnerability to be discussed are less tangible, although they are equally important to individuals’ welfare: social interactions and mental well-being. Most of the interviewees are very religious, which led to their social interactions being articulated around attendance to

religious services. During the lockdown and the months immediately afterwards, attendance was reduced or completely cut, resulting in them often feeling lonely. This reduction of social life persisted for months for some women who work caring for old or sick people and they were involved in shielding their employers. Even those who shared flats with other families shared feelings of solitude as the usage of shared places became a source of conflict for fear of contagion. Yet, not everyone felt this solitude and there were about four interviewees who either did not have an active social life prior to the pandemic, thus, they did not feel a huge change, or they felt the pause as a relief rather than a nuisance.

“No, no. It is because before the pandemic we were not meeting either. I arrived in Madrid and said that I would not meet with people here because I am not into alcohol, smoking... I am not into being loud, I am like that. So then the pandemic started and for me it was the usual. Better for me, of course” (Citizen 05, Latin American woman)

Sharing emotions and discussing wellbeing has become more widespread in recent years, although there is a persistent gender divide that reflects in the interviews. The men interviewed talk about the feelings of the people around them, mainly women, who felt scared and/or anxious:

“Yes, when we were locked up at home, after two months more or less. She lived next door to us, she came home and spent the day with us. The next day she went to her sister’s where she always went and it was that day or the next when she spoke to us on Whatsapp, on video call. She was in IFEMA [field hospital set up in Madrid to host the less severe cases of COVID], so, of course, if you are in IFEMA it is because it has something to do with COVID, alright? At the time my wife was pregnant, she was crying. So was her aunt, poor thing, because she said that we may become sick with COVID as well, because that takes a few days to develop symptoms. At that moment we had a really tough time, each one with their own paranoia, each one sanitizing the whole apartment, each thing that she touched was cleaned in the washing machine. We did many things at that time.” (Citizen 06, Moroccan man)

In contrast, women provide a personal account of what happened, discussing how they were scared for their future, anxious about becoming sick and constantly worried about how they would fare through the many challenges the pandemic put their families through. Some of these feelings were already there before the pandemic but the lockdown magnified them and created new sources of concern.

“The first moment was exactly in March of that year, 2020. I had the appointment to provide my fingerprint for the second permit, which I was renewing, and they cancelled the appointment because of the pandemic. I had a job, and I lost the job because I was [inaudible]. It was terrible for me; they were very distressing moments. The truth is that I had never seen myself so sad, so stressed, so desperate because I was living in a shelter, and they moved me to another one. They were very delicate moments. A couple of months later I contracted the virus.” (Citizen 04, Latin American woman)

The scholarly literature has criticized the concept of vulnerability as it often entails a loss of agency of individuals, focusing on their weakness and inadequacy to provide for themselves (Brown, 2011; Virokannas et al., 2020). One of the main results of these interviews is the resilience shown by these individuals and their adaptive capacity. When asked about the three main moments they remembered from the pandemic, all of them just mentioned the first lockdown, as if afterwards they were slowly returning to their routine. This routine was by no means like their previous one, but it factored the

pandemic into a sort of “new normality” where COVID-19 was part of the landscape. Interviews were conducted in the spring of 2022 and no follow-ups have been arranged more recently, so it cannot be known how their situations have evolved in the months after COVID-related measures were lifted.

One of the main measures adopted within the governance system was a comprehensive furlough scheme that tried to avoid layoffs. However, as mentioned above, most of the interviewees work in the care or construction sector where the rates of participation in the informal economy are significant. This meant that when the lockdown occurred, they did not qualify to benefit from this income substitution, and they found themselves without savings to help them transition the period. Institutional actors showed an awareness to this situation that was unleashed by the pandemic. Buffer mechanisms were reinforced to try and give a response to these emergent needs. Social services would have been the usual mechanism through which these demands were channeled but their offices were swamped during the first months of the pandemic as they tried to find materials and protocols to protect themselves. In their place, the funding of CSOs was also increased so that they could set up networks of food distribution or provide pre-paid cards with some money to pay for this shopping. All the respondents mention that they used these services. There is some variation in the length of time they had to recur to these services depending on how long they took to return to the labor market.

Another set of measures that were put in place were related to rent payment. Roughly every interviewee had difficulties facing rent payment, particularly during the first months of the pandemic. The government passed measures that encouraged private arrangements to delay and reschedule payments to avoid a large increase in evictions. Ultimately, for about a year a temporary moratorium of evictions was passed. One of the interviewees benefitted from this measure, as she recalls that her landlord was reluctant to defer payment and she was able to force his hand and reach an agreement:

“They annoyed me, they were really complaining but in the end they accepted. In the end, I adopted a tone, not rude but arrogant. I told them that if they wanted they could have it this way [deferring rent payments]. If not, they talk to the authorities to kick me out. In fact, there was a law that forbade... That is, it established a moratorium of payments so that one paid a little but they did not allow it [eviction]. They did not allow it. So I told them, then kick me out. In spite of this, they accepted it [the deferral of payment]. When we got back on, my roommate started working again and I told him to remember that we owed rent.” (Citizen 13, Latin American Woman)

Existing solidarity networks were reinforced and expanded so that help was shared amongst those who were receiving social aid. It is a common expectation that those who find themselves in dire situations such as the ones experienced by these interviewees, they have enough on their plate helping themselves. This is not the case in most of the interviews. These individuals were already providing help, mainly financial support to family members in their countries of origin. These remittances were cut during the pandemic because they could not afford to keep sending them, and some even had to ask for remittances for themselves. Nonetheless, roughly half of the sample, mostly Latin American respondents, describe how food parcels were often shared and redistributed between families to compensate for needs or they tried to provide what little money they could to members of their cult that were worse off than them:

“We, well, we had a lot of macaroni, a lot of spaghetti, beans, chickpeas... Both in bags and pre-cooked ones in jars. So those who needed them, she gave them away. I told her to gather

this, take this other thing to the church so that it can be given to someone who needs it.” (Citizen 02, Latin American Man)

“A sister from church, she... In the Christian church we call it a blessing. She blessed me with sixty dollars, euros. She blessed me. [...] She is from Colombia, she also goes to church. [...] She gave me a blessing that one time. After, the pastor also wanted to give us money, but my husband refused, he told the pastor that there were people in a worse situation than us, he should give it to them” (Citizen 07, Latin American woman)

Following the scheme of the sources of vulnerability, the last elements that became a source of resilience were religious beliefs and the media broadly understood. And sometimes both were intertwined. For those with strong religious beliefs, which are a good two thirds of those interviewed, despite the negative feelings they accounted for, they talk about how the pandemic is God-sent and their faith sustained them through these months, providing them with certainty that the pandemic would pass at some point. Some of the older respondents, who did not feel comfortable or lacked the skills to use the Internet used the phone to stay in touch with their pastor and receive this comfort from them:

“Interviewer: Did you have to stop attending church?”

Interviewee: [She whispers, inaudible] And I called the pastor, and told him that I could not come. And he said it was fine, and we could pray” (Citizen 07, Latin American woman)

For the rest of them, who were already Internet and social media users, having to cut their access to the Internet was a huge sacrifice as it had become a crucial tool to keep them connected. As it became usual with the general population, social media and video call applications became a common tool to stay in touch with friends and family members. They already used them with members of their families in their countries of origin, but they also used them now with their acquaintances in Madrid.

“Just some months before I had returned to my church, with the activities of the weekend and during the week. We had a very nice and strong friendship bond. And all of a sudden all this. With physical contact being so necessary, and everything was bounded, that is, it was cancelled. Then everything returned on Zoom” (Citizen 04, Latin American woman)

In addition, social media became a source of information complementary to Spanish media outlets. They gathered information about the situation in their countries of origin and they searched for further explanations for what they could not understand or make sense of. This usage underlines the potential social media have, despite its risk of becoming a spreader of fake news.

2.8.6 Conclusions

Main findings:

In terms of the **vulnerability of organizations**, there is a general agreement that organizations were largely unprepared for a crisis this size.

- **Adaptative capacity:** Members of these organizations stepped up and went beyond their job descriptions to respond to an explosion in the demand for social aid.
- **Resilience:** This crisis became an opportunity for large institutions to become more agile in their procedures and deepen their digitalization.

In terms of the **profiles of vulnerability**, new profiles emerged during the pandemic due to income instability. Those working in the gig economy experienced a sudden and massive loss of income. This situation was particularly prevalent amongst migrant communities, who are more likely to work informally.

- The actor system acknowledged this new demand and tried to respond by reinforcing social services. However, social services collapsed during the first months of the pandemic. CSOs' funding was increased to allow them to step in on the provision of food packages. Pre-paid cards substituted existing processes of financial aid that consisted of reimbursement of shopping tickets.
- Citizens also showed a strong capacity to adapt. Those who were interviewed seldom met the criteria to receive social aid from public institutions. Instead, they resorted to private actors (Red Cross, Caritas) to receive help. They also created solidarity networks with their acquaintances, sharing food packages and what little money they received. Many of the interviewees mention that their situation was hard but not the hardest.

During the first months of the pandemic, public action focused on solving health issues and providing for the most basic needs as there were many who could not afford even their most basic needs. This has led to **overseeing emotional and mental wellbeing**. Before the pandemic mental health was already poorly addressed by the health system but the pandemic has only aggravated the situation. The reduction of social interactions, including cult attendance, together with the uncertainty and the precarity amongst these communities triggered and exacerbated feelings of fear, anxiety and stress. Interviewees describe they had a hard time coping and little to no assistance was provided (a problem that is also present amongst the general population, particularly young people, whose mental health deteriorated heavily during this period).

- Social media and telephones were very useful as they helped interviewees to stay in touch with friends and loved ones during the lockdown. Many women were still having limited social interactions to protect their jobs and shield the vulnerable people they worked for.

Information management was one of the trickiest issues during this crisis and it is the interaction area in which there is more heterogeneity in positions. Information fragmentation due to the diversification of sources facilitated by social media has also opened a breach for misinformation to disseminate.

- Institutional actors differ between those who consider that it was not an issue and those who do. The first consider the diversity of information was a by-product of the politicization of the pandemic. The latter are most interviewees although amongst them there is no agreement regarding how to deal with this. Some argue that institutions should act proactively and engage with misinformation and fake news, whereas others consider that this engagement should be left to journalists and institutions should focus on transparency and providing truthful and accessible information.
- Amongst citizens, they consider that the information conveyed in traditional media outlets was understandable and trustworthy. Nonetheless, many went into social media for further clarification or to inform themselves about their countries of origin. Information also circulated through Whatsapp groups. It was through these channels that misinformation slipped. Some of the stories they received were considered as purely bizarre, others were able to plant the seed of mistrust and create reluctance to comply, particularly when it comes to vaccination.

- Within information consumption, pastors and other religious leaders have played a significant role as cognitive shortcuts to make sense of what was happening. These pastors have also contributed to the dissemination of misinformation. Although they are hard to identify due to the low levels of institutionalization of these cults, future crises should try to work with them more intensely.

Institutional trust: Citizens were largely trusting of the measures and decisions adopted by governments. Not the most trusting, but they consider that governments did the best they could with the information available. There was some confusion in the variety of measures implemented and some of the interviewees felt that some of the mistrust was linked to the politicization of the issue and the polarization within political elites.

Main limitations:

- Few interviews of a community that is very hard to trace and reach. Those interviewed have spent quite some time in Spain. They have learnt the language and they have asked for help in navigating how to apply for social aid. There is less information about those who did not ask for help – although it may not be possible to gather it easily.
- There is a nuanced difference between Moroccan and Latin American migrants. The first seemed to trust less institutions than the latter. The first seemed to rely on their family members, while the latter built larger networks with friends and acquaintances from their cult. Further research could try to disentangle what drives this difference, whether it is linked to political socialization and the type of regime in which it occurs, whether it is due to other factors such as the distance from the country of origin or the family composition.

Lessons learned:

- Organizations, despite being largely unprepared for the crisis, showed that they were more resilient and capacity. It could be criticized that there were no protocols in place for these adaptations and it all relied on the good will of those working in the organizations (both public administrations and CSOs).
- The crisis was a problem because demand for social aid experienced a sudden increase, but it was also an opportunity to introduce institutional innovations that had been piloting for some time but they were reluctant to fully implement (i.e.: digitalization of procedures, teleworking or home offices and switching from a refund system of aids to one with pre-paid cards).
- Existing channels of public-private cooperation were expanded, allowing for institutions to reach citizens that otherwise they cannot identify and provide support.
- Migrant communities showed, in line with Brown (2011), that vulnerability is a temporary circumstance and should not be used as an excuse to reduce individuals' agency. Most of those interviewed shared the help they received with other families and when the interviews were conducted they were already developing plans to bounce back.
- Information should be curated more carefully: availability in different languages even if they are not the official language in the country; collaboration with significant community members to engage them in the diffusion of truthful information; presenting information in a way that enhances the sturdiness of leaders by acknowledging the existence of the crisis, but also of the uncertainties around what is still unknown.

2.9 Wales, SU

2.9.1 Introduction

Since COVID-19 emerged in December 2019, it has had an unprecedented global social, behavioural and economic impact. Socio-cultural factors remained largely underappreciated in the pandemic measures that shaped the experiences of COVID-19 among migrant nurse populations. Dimensions that are part of this case study include different kinds of exposure to COVID-19, intersected with different forms of vulnerabilities and resilience that stem from, ethnicity and racialisation, gender, living conditions, daily activities, organisation of protective measures at work in healthcare setting and in public, legal allowances related to (a lack of) residency and citizenship for non-British nationals, and accessibility to various forms of care and support prior to, during, and after infection with COVID-19. Vulnerability is the acknowledgement of the openness to the unchosen and unforeseen (Harrison 2008) that in the pandemic has helped differentiate how for some social groups the consequences “increase the severity and mortality of COVID- 19” (Bambra et al 2021: 8, Braidotti 2020). Whilst vulnerability to the effects of living in the pandemic has largely been understood and managed as a biological phenomenon that prioritised infection, illness, death, the effects of COVID-19 have gone far beyond physical health, impacting on “everyday life” and well-being, mental health, education, employment, and political stability. In addition to biological aspects, these other elements differentiated ways in which different social groups – ethnicity – and groups that are shaped by practice – healthcare workers.

This case study report focuses on the intersectional vulnerabilities of a social group that is both marginalised for being migrants from a minority ethnic background and working in healthcare during the pandemic. This report unearths the various ways in which predominantly qualified, but low-ranking nurses from African countries have experienced the pandemic working in and around COVID wards in Swansea-based hospitals, and how their circumstances have rendered them vulnerable. Focusing on this group allows understanding better how the state-issued pandemic policies and protective measures in healthcare settings have had effects on BAME migrant nurses.

Welsh healthcare and the COVID-19 pandemic

Set up of the healthcare system in Wales

The basic model of the Welsh healthcare system can be characterized as the so-called Beveridge or national healthcare model, based on universal health care coverage for all citizens provided by the Government (Kulesher & Forrestal, 2014). This national healthcare model is funded through taxation with a small proportion raised through national insurance contributions, and the Government has ownership of most of the delivery of health services (ibid.). Healthcare is therefore primarily provided through the publicly funded NHS Wales for all people in Wales, although the growing private sector also provides healthcare (Yar et al., 2006).

Since the devolution of Wales in 1999, the country has been responsible for healthcare provision and the National Health Service Wales (NHS Wales) takes responsibility for healthcare in Wales. NHS Wales was reorganised in 2009 and seven local Health Boards are responsible for delivering all healthcare services within a geographical area. The Health Boards are supported by three specialist NHS trusts: the Welsh Ambulance Services Trust offers emergency services, the Velindre NHS Trust offers specialist cancer care and a range of national support services, and Public Health Wales (PHW) is the national public health agency in Wales. One of PHW’s roles is to protect the public from infection and to provide

advice on epidemiology (the incidence and prevalence of disease). Although operationally independent of the Welsh Government, it acts at the Welsh Government's direction.

Statistically, the NHS in the UK employs 1.3 million staff in 2023, and staff with a Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic (BAME) background amounts to 25.7% (UK Government 2023). Nonetheless, in 2020, 64% of staff who passed away from COVID-19 had BAME background (Chaudhry et al. 2020). In 2020, this group only represented 15% of people in managerial level positions, and only 11.3% in senior managerial positions (UK Government 2023).

Recruitment of BAME overseas qualified nurses

Many countries do not produce and retain enough midwife and nurse graduates to meet health service demands (WHO, 2021). Before and during the pandemic, BAME overseas qualified nurses had been recruited to make up for the shortage of nurses that have been educated in the United Kingdom. Also, the UK is committed to adhering to a WHO code of practice for international recruitment of health personnel (2023). NHS Wales recruits foreign born, overseas qualified nurses in particular countries in which the infrastructure has proven to be worth the investment. Besides Eastern European nurses, countries that nurses are successfully recruited from into NHS Wales are predominantly India and Nigeria. The seven health boards are responsible for their own organisation of the recruitment and facilitation of administrative, practical, and clinical quality levels for integration in hospitals.

Upon passing an online interview with dedicated health board recruiters in their home country, nurses require a working visa, which the health boards assist with obtaining, they are provided with free travel to Wales, and are housed in shared accommodation with colleagues overseas recruited nurses. Before being allowed to work as a nurse in a Welsh hospital, overseas qualified nurses need to requalify after successful completion of the Objective Structured Clinical Examination (OSCE). They receive special training to prepare them for passing the exam that is organised by health boards Wales. In adapted form, these trainings continued during the pandemic. In 2023 the Swansea Bay University Health Board that covers the Swansea metropolitan region, is estimated to recruit 30-40 overseas qualified nurses according to a clinical educator interviewed for this study.

Figure 21. SU, Wales – SES Framework.

2.9.2 Purpose and Research Questions

The report is led by the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** What structural issues (mobility, opportunity, access) affect the pandemic experiences of BAME overseas qualified nurses who work in South Wales hospitals?
- **RQ2:** What organisational issues (management, spatial arrangements, institutional regulations) affect the pandemic experiences of BAME overseas qualified nurses who work in South Wales hospitals?
- **RQ3:** What can we learn about COVID-19 politics (containment, immunization and biopolitics) and the regulations of BAME overseas qualified nurses who work in South Wales hospitals?
- **RQ4:** What are the dominant rationalities (goals) in governing populations during the pandemic and techniques (means) of ensuring productivity, efficiency, and resilience of BAME overseas qualified nurses who work in South Wales hospitals?
- **RQ5:** How do government policies encourage beneficial forms of movement (money, goods) and limit harmful forms of circulation (disease) with reference to the Swansea Metropolitan Area?

In Section 2, the report expands on the healthcare system in Wales and how foreign-born nurses are educated and employed in this system that has been adapted to cope with the pandemic situations. Section 3 sets out the methodology, and Section 4 formulates answers to the research questions. Following Section 5 which concludes the study, Section 6 formulates recommendations.

2.9.3. Method

This section explains the methodology and methods of the study. As the research seeks to uncover circumstances of BAME migrant nurses during the pandemic and as shaped by the pandemic measures, the methodology is rooted in experience and its contextualisation in broader terms of ethnicity in the Swansea region. Therefore, the answers to the research questions are based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative research. This methodology ensures that the insights and recommendations can be related to vulnerable groups (e.g. BAME people, migrants, and healthcare workers) in other European countries. Ethical approval has been obtained at the Swansea University College of Science and the NHS Health Research Authority (HRA).

Qualitative semi-structured interviews have been conducted with 8 Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic overseas qualified nurses who have been working in a South Wales hospital during the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, 7 healthcare managers were interviewed who have varied decision-making authority over different aspects of the Wales-based lives and careers of the nurses. These interviews provide a more specialised context about the nurses' recruitment, their training, their work circumstances, and the support they are offered. See Table 4 for a description of the interviewees. The interviews were audio recorded and conducted over a video conferencing platform, such as Zoom, Teams, or over the phone. The interviews were transcribed and coded in NVIVO v13 (see Figure 22 for the coding tree). All transcripts were anonymised, and recognisable aspects of the interviewees and their background were omitted.

The interviews were combined with insights into Swansea Metropolitan Area-based BAME populations from a survey conducted between November 2021 and March 2022 via the SurveyMonkey platform and in person. It registered the pandemic experiences and opinions from 171 BAME residents of

different ethnic and national backgrounds in the Swansea Metropolitan Area. Consisting of 50 open and closed questions, the themes included vulnerability, wellbeing, opinions about the pandemic measures, accessibility of healthcare, racism, and changes of life circumstances. 85% Of the respondents were ethnic minorities including mixed and multiple ethnicity and 15% are white (Welsh, British, and other white backgrounds). The minority groups include Black people (with African or Caribbean heritage), Bangladeshi, and/or Pakistani, Indian, and East Asian people (including Chinese and South-East Asian). All non-white ethnic group categories include mixed heritage; for example, a mixed Black and White background is counted towards the category of Black people. Although this survey is considered as a relatively large cohort, the survey results are not statistically representative of the areas. Therefore, as always in survey-based research, caution should be taken not to extrapolate and generalise the findings.

Table 4. Interviewee Characteristics (Wales Case Study)

Interviewee specialism / job role	
Nurses	Nurse managers
Nursing specialism (ward)	Job role
medical & surgery ward	Senior nursing manager
Respiratory ward	Clinical educator
Theatre & A&E ward	Former Chief Officer for Nursing for Wales
Acute medical ward	Chief Officer for Nursing for Wales
Emergency ward	Healthcare manager in a residential care home
Medical ward 1	BAME foreign nurse manager
ITU ward	Recruitment manager
Medical ward 2	

2.9.4 Results: Data reporting

Figure 22. SU, Wales – Coding Tree.

2.9.5 Results: Analysis and Interpretation

“It was very hard for a lot of nurses, very hard. We all did it in our own ways, but it's not something I'd want to revisit.”
 - Clinical educator, Swansea hospital

This section elucidates how public health policy that underpins the pandemic responses (at the Welsh national level and the local Swansea) and that informs healthcare organisation (Swansea Bay University Health Board) and policies in care institutions (hospitals in particular) (re)produces social and health inequalities with reference to ethnicity and working in healthcare. This results section uncovers aspects of life lived as a vulnerable person that have remained unconsidered in social policies, institutional organisation, and behavioural regulations. These emerge from the social, civic, and spatial organisation of the lives of BAME overseas qualified nurses onto which these policies and regulations do not map well compared to the lives of less vulnerable others.

Previous research has pointed out how BAME overseas qualified nurses in Wales have experienced a tremendous amount of stress during the pandemic both at the workplace and outside it (Public Health Wales 2020, Welsh Government 2020, Kabasinguzi et al. 2023). These studies' outcomes have been in line with the outcomes of the survey with people from largely minority ethnic backgrounds. The survey points out how minority ethnic groups tended to suffer a higher deterioration in mental health during the pandemic compared to British White groups (Beljaars & Shubin, 2022). Survey responses highlighted not only the increased awareness of the inescapability and nearness of death and indicated that the pandemic produced a heightened sense of social responsibility towards close family members and other loved ones. It also suggested the persistence of a gender gap in mental health deterioration during the pandemic. Women and non-binary survey participants reported suffering a higher increase in mental distress than men taking part in the survey. Other studies from before and during the pandemic demonstrate that this is in part due to the inequalities they have been facing at the workplace (i.e., lower wages, more precarious work contracts, and fewer migrant nurses in managerial positions) and differences in workplace regulation per health board area and hospitals.

The Welsh pandemic in the hospital

“In a more general context, vulnerability is the ability of humans naturally to show our emotions and weaknesses by having no restriction to express how you feel.”
 - BAME overseas qualified nurse working on a COVID ward

Both nurses who had worked in Welsh hospitals before the pandemic and during the pandemic remark on differences in the way the provision of care in hospitals is organised. Such differences are important for these nurses' working in potentially dangerous virus-filled spaces, their wellbeing, and their career progression. Ultimately, these differences are important for the smooth running of the wards on which these nurses work, and how effective hospitals can respond to crises such as pandemics. The following subsections answer Research Questions 4 and 5.

The interviewed nurses were generally content with the choice to work in the Welsh NHS in Swansea hospitals. All mentioned that the wages are a large factor in their reasons, as many suffered poverty in their home country. An ITU nurse illustrated:

“The fact that my son [with cerebral palsy] is getting all these things that I dreamt of him getting and couldn't get, and he's now getting them, is far more important than me being well taken care of at work.”

As such, on the one hand, all saw their work as a great opportunity and were very committed to their job. On the other hand, they felt that they had to be grateful for what they were granted and accept what was demanded of them. Their circumstances shaped by the pandemic had specific effects on the vulnerability of their situation.

During the pandemic, nurses felt largely vulnerable to the COVID-19 virus. These feelings were mostly based on them seeing so many different patients being so critically ill and so many colleagues being ill. That everyone was vulnerable to the virus seems to be the strongest held opinion amongst the nurses, immediately followed by the clinical hierarchy of vulnerability used in the pandemic measures. However, BAME overseas qualified nurses did generally not feel more vulnerable to COVID illness than their white British colleagues. Some argued that to work in a hospital, particularly in emergency care or ITU, or to work with patients with communicable diseases was just part of the job they accepted when they chose the profession: in other words, to run the risk of catching COVID was no different than other dangers they were exposed to, and which rendered them no different than their non-black and non-brown colleagues. Aligned with biomedical – as opposed to epidemiological and sociological – approaches to the virus, which encouraged a more individualist consideration of risk – rather than a shared or collective consideration – the nurses agreed on the importance of ‘keeping themselves safe’. They accepted that parts of the hospital were unsafe to be in: the COVID wards in particular, but that safety could mostly be granted if they adhered to the PPE rules and protocols. Ethnicity, living conditions, and other personal circumstances were considered of diminishable relevance.

Cultural differences in work and training

Particularly evident are differences in the usage of technology, the specialisation of nursing work, and documentation of illness progression and care provided. A nurse working on an emergency ward remarks that in the Welsh hospital that he works in *“everything seems automated”*. His experience of using technology in his African home country's hospital contexts is that computers are involved for particular tasks but not for everything. Him and other nurses are more used to relying on prior knowledge of patients' illnesses and making connections between clinical phenomena on their own. His experience is echoed by an ITU nurse who shared that she *“realized that here you are more worried about litigation than anything. People would rather document than do the work.”* The more intense focus on documenting and fear of litigation influences the role nurses have in the organisation of care provision in hospitals. The ITU nurse explained:

“I realized that the way nurses are educated here and the way we are educated is totally different. Because we are taught to be having done ITU as well, you are taught to not to have blinkers on as a nurse and to be open-minded to deal with situations as they arise.”

As such, the overseas qualified nurses thus considered having more capacity for thinking creatively about possibilities for care provision, being less afraid of being sued, and dealing with rapidly changing circumstances. In addition, in their home countries, the roles in wards, such as ITU, tend to be much less specialised as the roles they have been recruited for in Wales, which means that these nurses are experienced in more facets of delivering care. Overseas qualified ITU nurses therefore judged themselves more versatile acute care nurses than their Welsh counterparts. Nonetheless, they did not feel like their qualities were considered important, as demonstrated by an incident with the ITU nurse:

“I’ve done intensive care nursing, so when I got the job here, I was told about going to a surgical ward, which I wasn’t really pleased with, because I was used to ITU. But anyway, I thought, ‘Oh, well, it’s alright. I will learn all the systems and all that’. So when we’re doing OSCE, and then they say they’re giving us temporary teams, I received a call now. They wanted me to work in ITU. And I refused. Not because I don’t want to work in ITU, I want to work in ITU, but I felt like an end to a means. Like, I felt like ‘oh, now that will suits you on because we are short staffed in ITU, now you need ICU nurses, now you want me to work in ITU. But you didn’t trust that I could work in ITU before you had this need for ICU nurses’, which really, which I didn’t really like, which for me was like a sign for the future, that it’s not as rosy as I thought it would be.”

Such treatment by management, in which their wishes were not considered despite clear arguments for the benefit of their wishes, contributed to feelings of being undervalued and not considered beyond their capacity to fill gaps in the hospital staffing organisation.

Another, pandemic related aspect of cultural difference to play a role in the pandemic was the alteration of the training for the OSCE exam. A clinical educator working with foreign nurses explained that the lack of face-to-face training had significant consequences:

“Speaking as a teacher, generally, I do not think [teaching via Microsoft] Teams work. (...) I’ve had to do extra teaching with these guys to make sure they’re up to speed when they come under warranty, because they were extremely vulnerable, in respect and lacking in knowledge, because they hadn’t had the teaching. (...) I realized that there is no substitute for face to face. (...) It takes motivation, and it takes somebody passionate to be able to install those skills, shall we say, into the next nurse. But if that nurse is just looking at a screen, yeah, and that passion is not necessarily going to happen the same way the fund is not going to be there. (...) And that’s hard to be relearned (...) I think we’ve also got to realize the necessity of getting back to basics again. (...) Of course in in nursing school, they would have had classes where you basically get around a dummy and do simulated training. And because that never happened, and if it didn’t happen on the boards, because of both staff and etc, then they never got that experience. So hence, you know, we’ve had to pick up the pieces on that a lot to try and make sure our nurses are confident and yeah, able to do the job effectively.”

Not only did the adapted training to prioritise COVID safety during the sessions deprive the BAME overseas qualified nurses of particular hand-on experiences, but the clinical educator also points out the importance of enthusiasm and passion as vital elements of being a nurse in a South Wales hospital. Accordingly, working without such passion would make working life more difficult in healthcare situations. This does not mean that the foreign nurses would lack passion, but it does imply that the nurses did not necessarily learn what enthusiasm and confidence looks like in these Welsh hospital workplaces, which could be important for displaying when seeking promotion opportunities. Furthermore, not having the patient interactions with actual people or patients in their training puts these nurses at a disadvantage for not learning cultural sensitivities around the provision of care for white Welsh patients and communications with white Welsh colleagues. Indeed, nurses working in Welsh hospitals with the pre-pandemic level of face-to-face contact with colleagues and patients spoke of this time in much more positive terms when recalling the early stages of their immigration:

“It was a good learning experience, you get to learn other people’s culture. So for me, it was quite good. I enjoyed every bit of it. I wanted to learn more. And it helped me to adapt quickly so it was a good learning experience for me.”

Staffing

Staffing was one of the elements that greatly contributed to BAME overseas qualified nurses' exposure to the COVID-19 and sense of safety and wellbeing in hospitals. Understaffing in the Welsh NHS has been a long-standing problem that the pandemic compounded in myriad ways, and which created particular issues for BAME overseas qualified nurses. This section discusses the various organisational aspects of staffing during the pandemic.

During the pandemic, the practice of hiring so-called 'agency nurses' to fill in gaps in staff schedules became normalised. Agency nurses are employed by agencies rather than hospitals and are hired by hospitals for their specialism through the agencies to cover gaps in the shift schedule for hospital contract nurses. The better pay, more flexible working opportunities, better access to training opportunities, and "less requirement to respond to managerial pressures" proved attractive to many nurses from Wales or other UK nations (RCN 2022). Foreign nurses from African and Asian countries cannot switch to agency work as their working VISA is linked to their contract is NHS-based and with the hospital. Nonetheless, agency nurse hire did increase which meant that they often worked with agency nurses. Accordingly, agency nurses "were being choosy" and would not accept being allocated to a COVID ward, as a nurse working on a medical and surgery ward argued: "*they will come over and say, 'I'm not working with the COVID patients. And if you don't try to accommodate their ground, [these agency nurses] will tell you that they are going home*". Therefore, she and other foreign nurses were more exposed to the virus as they covered COVID wards disproportionately often, and they had to work in severely understaffed conditions. This nurse recalled having 6 to 7 patients to care for on an ITU ward, where she should have 1-2 with a maximum of 3: a staffing level that was confirmed by other nurse interviewees. This risked not only the quality of care for patients on these wards, but also the welfare of these nurses. However, hospital management responded to take some pressures of these nurses. COVID patients on COVID wards could deteriorate severely rapidly, which required the nurses to do many time-consuming checks of oxygen saturation and blood pressure and diminished the reliability of the previous check. Supporting the nurses' clinical decision making around the kind of care such patients required, the hospital applied continuous monitoring. This was strongly welcomed by the nurses.

On non-COVID wards, the ratio of contract staff to agency staff was also sub-optimal because of some agency staff refusing to work on COVID wards. This led to extra work pressure for contract nurses on the non-COVID wards, because as medical ward nurse 2 attested, agency staff needed constant help as they did not know their way around the ward. Helping these agency nurses organise themselves consequently fell on the shoulders of the contract nurses.

BAME overseas qualified nurses also recalled the considerations management had around staffing the newly set-up COVID wards. At the beginning, a medical and surgery ward nurse argued that management prioritised risks of understaffing over the health and safety of a small group of medical personnel. Instead of rotating the nurses so that the exposure to the virus was limited in time and spread out across the group to limit a potentially large group of staff going off sick and infecting patients on non-COVID wards, it was decided that a smaller group would have to work in the COVID wards for an extended period. She, as one of the nurses chosen to stay on the COVID ward, sets out the debate that followed when she and other nurses resisted:

"The fact that we want to curtail the spread doesn't mean [management] should expose us more, because the duration also influenced the risk of contractility. So the fact that

[management] wants to manage staff, [management] wants to reduce the number of staff that might tend to go off sick due to COVID doesn't mean we need to always face it. So the argument came up. And at the end of the day, they do have to review this. I never knew whether it's like a formal policy then, or whether it was just something that was limited to my ward. I wasn't quite sure. But then it came up as a debate, because we started contesting it that 'Oh, no, I was there all last week, you can't put me back there: there are other people'. (...)"

The debate then changed to other ways of deciding who would have to work on the COVID wards, as medical and support staff would bring up living with children and elderly people. The nurse quoted above points out how what she called 'excuses' "*put people who have kids in another country at a disadvantage*". In response, the hospital management chose for fairness around exposure time of staff, regardless of other potential effects. Doing so reduced the potential for BAME overseas qualified nurses to disproportionately run the risk of becoming ill with COVID-19.

Another aspect of working in a South Wales hospital during the pandemic as a BAME overseas nurse has been the difference in attitude to work that these nurses remarked on. The following quotation from a nurse who worked on theatre and A&E wards explains how knowledge of the system and being very familiar with cultural sensitivities around illness, vulnerability, and working in the NHS puts BAME overseas qualified nurses behind on their Welsh/British colleagues:

"What I find is that the British know how to play the games. So, for example, during the pandemic, they will say they're positive, and yet, they are not positive, they use that as, you know, to stay home. (...) I'm not saying they don't like to work, but they know how to play with the money : just to sort of give excuse not to be at work. And that is what we've had in this pandemic, lots of people were ringing to say, in the morning. 'Oh, I've got COVID, I think I'm coughing, I think I have a fever'. (...) Oh, 10 days don't come to work is another: 'Oh, my sister has got it. Okay, isolate me with my family for days'. So then that person is off work for how many (...) And that is where I find that managers, they know we will come to where they know, we the foreigners we will come, they know we do most of the work. That is everywhere, not only Wales, everywhere, we do most of the work. And they understand we're not here to play, we're here to work. You know, we're here to look after patients, so we're not going to complain so much, because I have come myself to work to look after the patient."

In 2022, when the Welsh government had lifted the legal necessity for people to stay at home when infected with COVID-19, the Swansea area-based hospital restarted with registering and counting COVID-19 illness as regular sick days that are limited within a year. Discussing the consequences, a medical ward nurse elaborated: "and then we realized. We were like, 'Oh, I said I can't take sick time off. I'm coughing, but yeah, it doesn't matter.'" This decision thus seemed to allow potentially infectious nurses to staff non-COVID hospital spaces and contaminate staff break room if they had already been off ill earlier in that year, regardless of people being able to get reinfected with the different strands of the COVID-19 virus within months, such as what happened with the different versions of Omicron.

Racialisation and racism

"When things are happening, it's all sugar-coated and nicely presented to you or in a way that you don't realize it at the moment. But when you reflect on certain events, you realize it's them"
- BAME overseas qualified ITU nurse

The experiences of being racialised in the healthcare system differ amongst the nurses that were interviewed. Some shared that they had not had any instances in which their non-white ethnicity played a role in interactions with colleagues, patients, or the healthcare system at large. However, that is questioned by an emergency ward nurse who pointed out the forms of racism he had encountered:

“Maybe if I'm talking to you, somebody will tell me some racial slur, and I'll feel like okay, yes, this is racism. So I have not seen that. For me, personally, I've never experienced that. (...) What I feel like what we can have now, I think the word has actually moved on, we have like always the same rights like everywhere. But now we have maybe some subtle racism, in which maybe if people from black and an ethnic minority background demand an opportunity, they don't have the opportunities. Those reasons might be even, maybe a deep form of racism. And that one is actually difficult to fight. Because you're not seeing it to your face. Yeah. So you just like maybe like, we'll put it like, institutional racism lies embedded in a way.”

He continued to explain how it is impossible to tell if being denied opportunities is related to his ethnicity, but he and others have felt that it did play a role. His experience with racism thus seems to be the more insidious and institutionalised kind that strays from the obvious kind of racism that involves slurs and direct racist language. Racism as a lack or a negative is, as he argued, “difficult to fight”.

In direct relation to the pandemic, nurses reported having been offered different possibilities for them to remain off COVID wards and working away from COVID-positive patients in the hospital, as it was clear that BAME people had a higher chance to fall severely ill or die. The former Chief Nursing Officer for Wales explained that this social inequity required more management through calculations of vulnerability:

“Lots of people went out of their way to do this public response. Yet, as we found with the evidence coming through over who was higher risk, we had to actually develop a tool to stop them dying by putting themselves at risk. (...) At the beginning, the only plan we had to work on was the Flu plan. This was a new bug, so we had to chuck the rules away.”

Those who were offered to be treated with more caution on work placement for their higher potential to fall severely ill or die during the first wave felt that clinically it might be a correct solution. Nonetheless, the more dominant feeling was being singled out, where their ethnicity had not been a reason for different treatment from management before, and they felt that they would not be able to contribute to the hospital's and their colleagues' handling of the patient deluge. That reason became the dominant response from many BAME overseas qualified nurses as they declined the offer to stay home or work in hospital-designated safe spaces.

Most nurses did report such an openly and unbound kind of racism. When the racist incident was instigated by patients, they explained they deal with it in different ways. Often nurses brushed off the incident as part of the illness which led patients to display delirious behaviour. Stated by nurse 1 who worked on a medical ward: “you can't really be angry at them”. As such, she had found a way of coping with being racialised at work that worked in her mind to reduce the energy she had to spend on dealing with this.

A nurse who worked on a medical ward has made complaints to management in the past. She elaborates on her disappointment:

“The managerial system, I don't think they're fully equipped to, like, undo racism, they just tell you to report, it's to edit six reports, but that doesn't change how I'm feeling on the inside. And obviously, they ask you how you are, alright and all that. But there's never really a follow up on how you feel afterwards. And for me, I'm the kind of person that because I'm having a difficult time with you, I'm not going to avoid you. So for some people that would rather not work on that section, they'll choose to go to another section, but I'm like, ‘Why should I run away from you? That kind of person’. So I'd rather stay there and just walk around, and we still interact until my shift is over. It's not easy on the inside, especially when you're trying to help someone when you are faced with this.”

Both nurses who have and nurses who have not made complaints to the managers responsible for the ward have learned to cope with it on their own as complaining, and learning how others had complained about it did not trigger an adequate response. A BAME nurse manager emphasized with more junior BAME overseas qualified nurses who she had worked with and noticed how her team BAME members dealt with the instances:

“I saw that people have different ways of dealing with people, even things that you normally wouldn't accept to be said or done to you. Sometimes we give them a blind eye and say, ‘Oh, I'll decide not to focus on that. And focus on what I need to do and focus on the bigger picture’.”

Whilst the situation was found to be managed alright in the moment, there was often no sufficient follow up. For the foreign nurses it seemed to become clear rapidly that these instances were treated as unacceptable but also unavoidable. The BAME nurse manager explains how she knew that them being racialised would not necessarily be best thought of as mistakes, but as reflections of deep-seated dispositions and ignorant misconceptions. She explores what leads to BAME nurses having to defend their knowledgeability and capabilities as coming from abroad; from African countries in particular:

“Different people have a perception of Africa that they want to believe. So coming in, and them knowing that I came from Africa they make you feel useless. Because in their minds when we are nursing patients in Africa, we will be nursing patients close to lions. And they're watching us when we are asking questions. (...) And all your years of experience are sort of thrown away, which is not true, because when push comes to shove, your experience just kicks in. You do what needs to be done. But at the moment, we are restricted to what we can do, because of being new. But students who were qualified like maybe last month are treated differently to you with all your years of experience, which I honestly didn't appreciate. (...) And they are not as knowledgeable as you would anticipate that they are. (...) You have to work with these students, and you ask them questions; they're in their final year. They don't know simple pharmacology, drug classes and things like that. Then I asked myself, so ‘how come someone who qualified last month is considered better than me, but they lack all this?’ I fail to understand that.”

This manager, having had first-hand experience of having her capabilities questioned and being treated as underqualified at times, demonstrates how asking questions about processes that are taken for granted by Welsh or British nurse students and nurse colleagues can easily be construed at best as lacking skills and knowledge at a more advanced level, and at worst unreliable with correct care provision for patients. This can affect foreign nurses in major ways. Because of being racialised on many occasions, an acute medical ward nurse dreaded going to work. She stated the following: *“I'll just say that 60% of people I've worked with kind of let me know that being black or not being white is*

a huge thing for [them] and make you feel less of yourself sometimes.” She stated that having been racialised had affected her mental health so profoundly that she was seriously considering returning to her home country. As the anticipation of coping with racialisation can take up significant ‘mind space’, the level of care that she and nurses like her can provide therefore comes into question.

In conclusion, whilst ethnicity and race are not categories that have a specific place in the organisation of Welsh hospitals, including not during the pandemic, it seems like not being white British does put people at a disadvantage. Such disadvantages may not be clear in the severity of racial confrontation by patients or colleagues, the heaviness of the accumulation of being ignored in social situations or rejected in career prospects, nor in the betrayal of being left to work through the incidents themselves. However, they may lead to situations that render BAME overseas qualified nurses unsafe in the pandemic for social reasons in the hospital workplace.

Territorialisation of the virus

Hospital management employed an understanding of the virus response within the hospital based on biomedical and life scientific understandings of viruses. These understandings are materialistic and see bodies and viruses as distinct entities that can be separated. Based on these understandings hospitals employed spatial tactics to keep the virus as potentially attached to objects and residing in contagious bodies away from bodies that are not affected: i.e. through territorialisation. Territorialisation worked through differences of PPE required in hospital spaces, which was an extension of the system that had already been in place in parts of the hospital before the pandemic, as a theatre & A&E ward nurse explained:

“We always had to do all different things, so we have the red, amber, and green. So when I'm back red, then that's the danger, so if we are going there, you definitely have to put your complete protective gear on. And for amber it depends on what case it is either complete, or it's up to the individual, but then you've been advised. I even wear glasses, I make sure I clean my glasses before I come out, or I dropped my glasses in a case and somebody will pass it back to me. We try not to, you know, impact other places, so that everywhere was red, green, red, yellow, green.

Interviewer: Was it confusing to have all these different zones?

But because we had the training, the initial start, which I thought was very good, it helped all of us, because we were even taught how to take it up. We do it but because it's a different way of wearing it: how to take it up, so that you don't even shake the virus around you and others.”

As such, the hospital became a pattern of red, orange, and green spaces that medical staff had to navigate. The primary difference from other earlier practices around infection control was the practice of donning and doffing the PPE as the virus could be ‘shaken’ off clothes and onto bodies and other clothes, reflecting the fear for virus’ airborne transmission.

The amber category, as this nurse described, allowed for individuals to make their own decisions about how to use protective equipment. Whilst this rule demonstrates sensitivity for difference in opinion around how to protect oneself around the virus, it also demonstrates the introduction of ambiguity in the hospital.

This territorial pattern had disadvantages for medical staff working in the red zones over staff working in orange and green zones aside from the increased exposure to the virus through bodily interactions with contagious patients. Red zones held patients with COVID, and whereas green-zoned nurses were

allowed in and out of green and orange zones (when donning appropriately), red-zoned nurses were contained within their red zones. Movement of people and objects alike were curbed for fear of bringing COVID-19 into non-COVID zones. The strict boundaries put up between COVID and non-COVID wards challenged the normal way of working for the nurses on the COVID wards. As explained, the BAME overseas nurses had a higher chance to be working on these wards. On top of the understaffing, a medical and surgery nurse explained the disruption to her workflow as she had no longer access to a 'runner':

"A runner is somebody that will stay by the reception. Because when you are fully donned in your PPE and then you remember, 'oh, I need this pair of scissors'. You don't want to come out of the bay, remove all your gadgets, make excuses, come back again and don everything because at that point, you are even at risk of contaminating other things. So you don't want to keep popping in and out. If you have somebody like that, but the fact that we're never, like, we never had like good stuff, and it was difficult to keep up with that pace of not having a runner. (...) I would say, 1 in 10 times, you have a runner, the other nine times you would never."

As expressed by her and others, not having access to a runner to accommodate the care provision increased workload stress with the nurses and it increased chances of contamination of the nurse having to go in and out of their PPE and those around them on other wards. Whilst this did not single out BAME nurses, they may have had to deal with this lack more often, given that they seemed more likely to work on COVID wards

Another way in which the virus created ambiguity in the hospital was the ill-recognition of the manifestation of the virus. As in Western medicine, disease, including COVID-19, is proclaimed and described from an objective, *outside* point of view, and as the illness has a varied presentation, healthcare workers equally struggled with recognising bodily phenomena as symptoms from their own experience. A nurse who worked on a critical care ward explained her confusion at an unknown moment in the pandemic, but during which they had access to lateral flow tests:

"So I came to work. I think I was running late. So I had to hurry by running. So when I came, I was breathless. So I was trying to catch my breath in between coughing, so I thought it was because of that. But when COVID came, everybody had this paranoia going on. So if you cough, your colleagues would look at you a certain way. Because I kept coughing intermittently, I didn't think it was anything. I thought it was just because I was trying to catch my breath. So when we went on break, my colleague said, they should just check my temperature that I never noticed, I was like 'No, I'm very sure I don't have COVID so I haven't lost my sense of taste. I don't feel this way'. So she was like 'you never know, just to be sure to protect yourself. Just check your temperature'. So I checked my temperature. My temperature was okay. But I started having chills after going home. And the cough continued, though. And then a headache was creeping in. So I decided to give the occupational department a call. They scheduled me to come and swap at one of their centres. So I didn't I was very sure I didn't have COVID. So I was very much taken aback when the results came out. I was I was positive COVID. I was like, 'Are you really sure this is my results? So after the results came in, that's when I started feeling the symptoms."

The virus' disguise as exertion symptoms was therefore brought into the different spaces in which this nurse worked, as the hospital regulations aimed at early detection of staff infection had not been sufficient in recognising her body as infectious. Hence, even in a space that was highly regulated, and

in which highly trained clinical professionals who were familiar with the virus and its symptomatology, the virus could not be kept from spreading. As such, the territorialised approach to contain the virus as adopted in the hospital and as reflected in the Welsh government's regulations, seemed to have allowed for multiple kinds of ambiguity that permitted the healthcare workers and patients alike to be exposed to COVID illness.

The Welsh pandemic in the hospital: Conclusions

This section uncovered aspects of the life lived by a Swansea-based BAME overseas qualified nurse within the hospital and how they were rendered vulnerable through the circumstances they were put in. The organisation of healthcare provision, predominantly in hospitals, was an important factor in the ways in which nurses were vulnerable during the pandemic. Lacking the development of cultural competencies in adapted training rendered the foreign nurses socially vulnerable after qualifying, which may have compounded anxieties around being racially accosted by patients or colleagues. Staffing issues also played an important role in the organisation of hospitals during the pandemic, which created challenging circumstances for the BAME overseas qualified nurses. Furthermore, the territorialised approach, and the partially inadequate scrutiny of bodies coming into the hospital through reliance on symptoms, to avoid the spread of COVID-19 introduced new ambiguities into the hospital. As such, this rendered healthcare workers, and especially minority ethnic healthcare workers vulnerable.

The Welsh pandemic beyond the hospital

Nurses felt largely safe outside the hospital and welcomed the government mandated behavioural pandemic measures. A theatre and A&E ward nurse put emphasis on "all kinds of systems that made it safe", in drawing attention to mask wearing that was made compulsory. She and most others were positive about the Welsh government's response to the pandemic in Wales. However, whilst the everyday situations of the nurses outside the hospital seemed equitable in terms of vulnerability to pandemic effects, their position in Welsh society and situation in legislation did open up disadvantages as minority ethnic healthcare workers with a migration background. The following subsections answer Research Questions 4 and 5.

Whilst the pandemic measures worldwide severely restricted the flow of travellers between countries, qualified nurses were actively made exceptions for. European countries, including the UK, restricted travel from African countries and other parts of the world that are considered to be developing regions from a Western point of view by categorising them as 'red countries' for large periods during the pandemic. A recruitment manager for the Swansea Bay University health board illustrated:

"Through the pandemic, we were obviously still keen to recruit overseas nurses, and the overseas nurses was still as keen to come for the opportunities and come to work for us in in, you know, in Wales, but to that led to, you know, obviously, significant delays in different processes, etc. And that was, I suppose, the biggest impact that we had from COVID, in terms of us actually getting the nurses to come, once the nurses were here, then, you know, we were able to support, etc, and care for them."

Once the nurses had arrived, many argued that family members who were due to reunite with them in Wales also faced significant delays; both in acquiring the right documentation to travel at the embassies in their home country, and in receiving the right documentation that proved their right to remain in the UK. This created many uncertainties as the dysregulated foreign document processing

capacity of the UK government put their life on hold in their home country as one foreign nurse manager explained how a colleague nurse from India heard nothing from the UK embassy for months and was then expected to be on a flight two days later. Also, family reunions took much longer than had been expected and had the case prior to the pandemic with Biometric Residence Permit (BRP) provision being delayed for the husband of a medical ward nurse who then had to wait for his BRP, which had major consequences:

“He didn't get the card [until] after six weeks, but after four weeks we go into the post office every week. They keep telling us ‘Oh, it's not here yet. It's not here yet’. And at some point, it does become frustrating for him because without the BRP you can't open a [bank] account. Yeah, without the VRP, you can prove to employers that you are legal immigrants so you can get a job. So it was like a, like a pause for him. They've always justified the delay with COVID pandemic. That's due to the pandemic, they are having loads of backlog and began – they couldn't do anything about it for us to just wait. But when do we wait for an answer that they couldn't provide? So at some point, it had a strain on my marriage? Because my husband was very, very emotionally downcast then was like, no, because coming from an African perspective, the men always feel their pride and their ego lies in their ability to provide.”

As such, the bureaucratic functions of the Welsh and UK governments during the pandemic faltered, which created a series of problems at different aspects of the lives of BAME overseas qualified nurses.

Living arrangements and everyday life

Living arrangements are vital in the organisation and possibility for rest and deployment of other aspects of personality. If such arrangements are not in line with people's needs, this can create new vulnerabilities in pandemic lives. Higher levels of anxiety and mental distress as well as large households characterised the lives of other BAME people in the Swansea Metropolitan area. The survey outcomes suggest that BAME women particularly struggled, scoring a 52 on the happiness scale, which was 10% less than men. Thibaut and Van Wijngaarden-Cremers (2020: np) argue that the gender gap in mental health deterioration during the pandemic exists because of “the specific psychological and psychiatric risks faced by women both as patients and as workers in the health sector, the increased risk of violence against women at home and at workplace and, finally the risk run by children within their families.” Recent research in the Welsh context by women's labour organisation Chwara Teg (2020) found that during the pandemic women largely lost their support networks and saw alterations in childcare expectations, which negatively affected their mental health. The pandemic lives of the BAME overseas qualified nurses illustrates how mental pressures and living situations made them vulnerable.

When the BAME overseas qualified nurses first arrived in the UK they were not provided with accommodation somewhere in the Swansea region, but at the hospital. A programme manager overseeing the recruitment of foreign nurses explained:

“So the accommodation at that time during the pandemic changed. Not because we've increased our numbers and they've got an external provider for accommodation, but they will go into our hospital accommodation that we've got for staff. So they would be met as soon as they arrived out of quarantine. Someone – I've met the nurses myself and taken them to the [surgical] theatre accommodation, whatever or, you know, different people within the team do that. Help them settle in, welcome them, give them information, etcetera.”

Hence, the nurses who arrived during the pandemic were immediately embedded into the hospital setting, whereas before they would have been living in shared accommodation in a residential area. This pre-pandemic placement would allow easier contact with Welsh people, which would have helped them settle in the country quicker. During the pandemic, in the beginning stages of their move to Wales their lives were entirely dominated by the hospital.

Many BAME overseas qualified nurses experienced anxieties around how to feel safe in working with the virus at such close proximity. Most nurses linked these anxieties to the waves in 2020 and 2021 through feelings of not having any control and until the vaccines were considered to reduce the number of hospitalisations. A theatre & A&E ward nurse attempted to keep her home as a virus-free space that felt safe:

“I didn't feel safe because there were some theories going on that the virus tends to stick to your uniform. So there was a lot of anxiety on my own part, where once I come back from work, I'd try to like, take my dirty clothes, right? Right at the entrance of the house if I can.”

Despite following all the rules precisely, she still caught the virus. She also lived with a friend who she had met during their shared OSCE training upon arrival. As they are both nurses, it became virtually impossible to keep the virus out of their home. However, whilst her feelings of safety were not helped by the insufficient measures that she adhered to, she felt better for living with a friend:

“Yeah I live with my friend. She's also a nurse, so we're able to relate our experiences and we have similar experiences, so it makes it easier. When you are having a difficult day, you have someone to share it with, and somehow laugh alright in the end.”

The comradery between nurses who share living arrangements was therefore of particular importance during the pandemic: not just to relay experiences with and consider challenges at work, but also to keep each other's mental health in check and have each other for emotional support. However, sharing accommodation, which is common for foreign nurses and medical staff in training (e.g. junior doctors on rotation) has also led to an intensification of pandemic anxieties for BAME overseas qualified nurses. As a ITU nurse [NUSM] explained:

“It was made obvious that we were at risk. We [foreign nurses] were more at risk than the other groups. So just interacting with my colleagues and my housemates in the house who were working in COVID wards made me anxious because I thought 'I'm very much as exposed as they are, because they are going to work in a COVID ward and we are coming back to interact together'. And sometimes you tend to isolate yourself, but this is like the only family you have. And you want that social interaction and it made it so difficult. So yeah, I'll say there was a time I felt really vulnerable and at risk of just contracting COVID.”

Whilst hospitals were so tightly regulated through the zoning and the many rules that aimed to prohibit the spread of COVID-19, the lives outside of the hospital did not offer a continuation, despite being organised by the institution. Living arrangements could thus increase the exposure to the virus outside the hospital.

As part of their lives in shared accommodation or as living with family, BAME overseas qualified people spent time in public places. A medical and surgical ward nurse explained how their job in healthcare created new anxieties in these spaces:

“I felt it was during the height of the of the pandemic, when everybody were using their mask, and all these restrictions were in place – I would say I feel safe, I felt more protected then. But

over time, when they started opening up the places and the restrictions were lifted, one after the other. At some point, I was like, 'oh, I hope we aren't going back to this awful time, I don't want it to be crazy again, okay. (...) At some point, I was finding it difficult to wear my mask. Despite the fact that they've taken it off the public places like the supermarkets and all that it became quiet. It was more of a suggestion than a law. So it was up to individuals. So at that point, I was still stuck to my mask that at some point, there was even my husband that will tell me 'you are home now, take that off'. I hadn't forgotten. I was quite used to it, because I felt more protected having it on. But over time, when I could see that nine in 10, people were not having the mask on. So gradually, I just felt it's I don't even think is quite reasonable. Because there are nine people surrounding me and I'm the only one using this mask."

She feels very uncomfortable noticing the juxtaposition between the call for civic liberties entailing not taking OVID precautions by not wearing masks, and still having fresh memories of the COVID patient deluge and the many people she saw passing away from the illness. Also, other nurses raised the awkwardness of seeing people actively putting themselves in jeopardy and the nurse having to care for people like this when they would be brought into the hospital days later.

Migration and the pandemic regulations

BAME overseas qualified nurses working in hospitals in South Wales were also rendered vulnerable by virtue of their migrant status in the UK-based and Welsh pandemic regulations. In addition to travel and work documents having been delayed in many cases, coming from red-listed countries, they also had to quarantine for 10 or 14 days. A respiratory ward nurse who did not see her VISA application and approval delayed, recalled her quarantine experience as such:

"That was fantastic. Brilliant, yeah. Two weeks of not doing anything getting your meals, right. Yeah. (...) It is the mind that was free, so I had my things working out; watched movies, called for food, eat, sleep."

Whilst the isolation of the quarantine can be a difficult period for a migrant who has just left their familiar life and has built no familiarity with the new country yet, such a period can be very difficult. However, it seems like the health board and hospital management recognised the potential for nurses' mental health to decline. As a nurse later working on a medical ward explained, they had coping mechanisms:

"We had to isolate ourselves in the hotel. And we could not see each other. If I could remember correctly it was until the last day that we saw each other. But during the isolation we had video calls together just to see each other like 'Oh, I'm fine. I'm okay'. Then also our coordinator in Swansea, she called us every day as well to keep in touch, which was really helpful."

As such, hospital management had very well anticipated the mental pressures of moving to another country on your own and the extra pressures the loneliness of quarantine could bring.

Governance of flows: the embedding of BAME overseas qualified nurses

Wales as a Western capitalist state governs at the population level through political strategies that interfere with the biological processes of this population to achieve a balance in economic growth stability that is measured in the life and death of its subjects (Foucault 1976). According to Deleuze and Guattari (2004: 260) states exert control over the population by mediating the stabilising and destabilising oscillations between the poles of rigidity and chaos. Adapting to the incessant changes in circumstances that threaten the balance these mediations attempt to introduce and maintain, the

state continually introduces new regulations. As the pandemic was such an anomalous event that disrupted the balance to such a strong extent, the severe measures reflected this profound disruption. States can, however, only interfere with the biological processes that government officials find important, can measure, and that are embedded in its governance structures. Ethnic minorities with and without migration background in Wales are an historically disadvantaged group for whom services have not been set up as accessible as for the white British majority group.

Provided with investment (as seen in 'Shared Prosperity Funds' from Swansea Council and the 'Strategic Equality Plan 2020-2024' from Neath Port Talbot Council) to create opportunities, provide additional support, and offer special funding and project-based investment. As the terms suggest, the provisions for many ethnic minorities were *additional* elements; not aspects of the foundations of the governmental system that would suggest full integration of their lives. Nonetheless, a Chief Nursing Officer for Wales who was active during the pandemic ensured that all policies relevant to healthcare workers, and nurses in particular, went through equality impact assessment. She recalled being questioned about this in meetings with other CNOs and senior civil servant colleagues in other UK nations and of the UK government:

"They all went, 'What's that? What have you done with that? Why? Why do we need it?' And as I said, 'because it has to be for the populations that we are serving, actually, it won't be the same, this mask won't work the same as it will for somebody who's very much further at risk based on ethnicity or genetic definition than someone else'. So we did that. But did it move enough? I don't think it has, I think they don't focus on this in all governments, but even my [Welsh] government now is very much on inequalities as the thread and the lens through which we write all our policies. But it does need – it takes time and doesn't instigate a shift change. People don't do it just because the government says it, doesn't mean everyone's going to think that's the right thing to do."

The BAME overseas qualified nurses included in this research did not recall their ethnicity to be of major importance in staffing decisions. A foreign medical ward nurse stated that her management served them a risk assessment to determine in what spaces they could be scheduled to work.

BAME overseas qualified nurses who are recruited into NHS Wales do so for a variety of reasons, but, as mentioned before, the primary reason is to be able to better support one's family financially. This is a known fact as this is what makes recruitment so successful for the Welsh health boards. However, this financial dependency of people in the nurses' home country on average disadvantages foreign nurses in comparison to Welsh or British nurses who are less likely to have many people depend on their salary. A nurse who worked on a medical ward explained the consequences for her:

"I haven't been in my country since I came here for 15 years, and I just went. I know! I put my whole life in the British and the Welsh. Yeah, I just went back in April. Yeah. So that's what I'm saying we work and work, work and it is all we do, most of us at least, you know. We work and send the money home. And then sometimes you go [check your account] and it's empty. There's nothing there for you."

The statement demonstrates how the already low wages for most BAME overseas qualified nurses could not fully be enjoyed by the nurses themselves as it funded their family and community in their home country or family brought over to Wales. Not only did having little access to money disallow doing activities and purchasing enjoyable items to relieve work stress and anxieties, it also kept these nurses living in shared accommodations. Whilst the latter had distinct advantages regarding emotional

support and possibly some cultural familiarity, it also disallowed privacy and peacefulness and retained a high level of exposure to the virus from – or possibility to infect – nurse colleagues who (also) worked in COVID wards. These mechanisms keep these foreign nurses in their job and accept the unsafe conditions without complaining too much as they are too dependent on their job in the Welsh NHS. Consequently, this workforce becomes a cheap and reliable element in the management of the healthcare system in Wales.

The Welsh pandemic beyond the hospital: Conclusions

BAME overseas qualified nurses were rendered vulnerable outside the hospital and as part of Welsh society in several ways. Not only did the tightly regulated and relatively clear and equal management of the pandemic conditions for nurses in hospitals not necessarily extend to spaces outside the hospital. The foreign nurses also had little flexibility on shaping their living situation as line with their need to stay safe from the virus and benefit from community and care networks is the absence of (the majority of) their family in Wales. The first stages of the move towards integrating in the hospital training system during the pandemic was appreciated by the nurses. The dependency mechanisms that lock nurse into their low-paid hospital job keep these foreign nurses in their job and accept the unsafe conditions without complaining too much. Consequently, this workforce becomes a cheap and reliable element in the management of the healthcare system in Wales.

2.9.6 Conclusions

This section provides new indications of pandemic policies and regulations in Wales (re)produced inequities between social groups with reference to healthcare workers, migrants, and ethnic minorities. It will also provide suggestions for pre-empting the formation of these inequities and reducing some of those that have pervaded and exist today.

From the beginning of the pandemic onward, there has been clear evidence that BAME people seemed to have a higher chance for severe illness and death, which had been established already in April 2020 (Kirby 2020). The clinical indication of vulnerability in the pandemic context of not specifying ethnicity as a factor thus did little to structurally protect BAME overseas qualified nurses in their job. Therefore, this allowed an unequal situation for these nurses to go unnoticed in healthcare spaces. Vulnerabilities over BAME healthcare workers in Wales can be attributed to the following:

The structural unequal embedding of BAME overseas qualified nurses in the Welsh healthcare system emerged as unrecognised vulnerability that could arise because of ill-recognition of compounding processes and exclusions that singled out BAME overseas qualified nurses.

Government's responses to the pandemic operated based on separation of the ill (contagious) and healthy, segregating individuals based on risk and vulnerability in relation to specific territories (Toscano, 2020). Territorialisation of the virus in the pandemic measures added extra pressure on the BAME nurses, limited their everyday contacts and support networks, which increased their vulnerability.

The organisation of ward staffing and the eventual rotation-based schedule balanced the exposure to COVID-19 between nursing staff. However, the hospital's choice to hire agency nurses and their refusal to work on COVID wards did seem to disproportionately put the BAME overseas qualified nurses at risk of contracting COVID-19. The organisation of staffing combined with the zoning of the hospital according to the need for patients' treatment specifically for COVID-19 exacerbated the already challenging circumstances for foreign nurses. A perceived lack of opportunities for their career made

it extra difficult to retain the motivation to put oneself in danger at the request of the hospital, all the while seeing how white nurses seemed to be offered more opportunities from earlier on in their career, got away with excuses to avoid working at points in the pandemic, and seemed unable to appropriately reconcile ethnic differences.

Simultaneously, BAME overseas qualified nurses often faced continuing exposure due to the financial dependability of their family and community.

Recommendations

This section develops recommendations for the Welsh Government, the local Swansea and Neath Port Talbot councils, Public Health Wales, Swansea Bay University Health Board, Swansea-based hospitals, civic society organisations, and media. Answering to research question 3, the following recommendations can be made:

- The structural organisation of the nurses' employment in hospitals, the Visa-related restrictions placed on foreigners, and state-issued pandemic measures locked them in a bounded and disadvantaged place in Wales.
- Hospitals can improve the organisation of labour in which BAME overseas qualified nurses' function to make better use of their creative and solution-based capacities – predominantly in emergency care – and their time providing care instead of managing agency nurses.
- Acknowledgement of hospital management that hospitals could have run the risk of collapse if management had not been so effective in arguing that COVID safety was attainable through individual protective behaviour, rather than manage it as a collective responsibility.
- Developing mindfulness of racism emerging as limitation in career development possibilities, by patronising behaviour from other staff and colleagues, abuse of grateful attitude and accepting the foreign nurses' tolerance of dismissive behaviour, and lacking insight and action on preventing the accumulation of circumstances that lead to disproportionate exposure to the virus and mental pressures through uncertainty.
- Mental health support in pandemic and perhaps also other crisis and high-pressure situations, needs to be designed and organised to target ethnic groups differently and with great sensitivity to gender difference.
- Living arrangements as shared between hospital staff need to be considered following similar scrutiny to infection as hospital spaces to avoid infections and the infection anxieties that these arrangements can create.
- Better attention to the social structures and social pressures that minority ethnic people and healthcare workers are enclaved in in the institutions they work for.

3. Cross-analysis of Case Studies

Section 3 provides a global analysis across the COVINFORM case studies, synthesizing findings by system, target population, outcomes, timeline, and other factors. Additionally, it summarizes key methodological insights from the COREQ analysis.

Analysing across systems reveals how governance responses, public health measures, community networks, and communication strategies intersected to shape pandemic experiences. National policy differences produced varied impacts, with more restrictive lockdowns exacerbating vulnerabilities for migrants and minorities. Healthcare systems demonstrated adaptability but require better mental health services. Local organizations filled gaps, yet fragmentation posed barriers. Communication practices relied on community channels to reach marginalized groups.

Examining across target populations shows healthcare workers suffered immense stress, anxiety, and burnout. Migrants and ethnic minorities faced social isolation, discrimination, and digital exclusion. Low-income and precarious workers lost income and housing access. Women disproportionately shouldered childcare and domestic duties. Each population experienced distinct challenges reflecting their positioning.

In terms of outcomes, mental health emerged as an overarching impact across groups, along with economic precarity. Groups and individuals also demonstrated remarkable resilience through community organizing and mutual aid. Coping strategies provide solidarity, but support systems remain inadequate. Across pandemic timelines, the initial lockdown phases provoked the most disruption as uncertainty and restrictions peaked. Later waves brought “normalized routines” yet persistence of problems as policies oscillated. Long-term consequences include entrenched inequalities and lingering psychological distress.

While the case studies focused on different vulnerable populations in varying contexts, several common themes and experiences emerged. Mental health impacts were widely reported, though specific groups like healthcare workers and migrants appeared especially affected. Both frontline workers and minorities encountered heightened stress, anxiety, depression, and burnout. Similarly, economic precarity arose as a shared challenge, with income loss and housing access difficulties noted across low-wage precarious workers, migrants, and marginalized communities. Trust and information issues also recurred across cases, though manifesting somewhat differently for health workers versus minority groups. The Austria and Italy cases revealed similar mental health impacts for healthcare workers and women in socially assisted housing, with both studies finding increased psychological distress. However, the coping mechanisms differed, with Austria emphasizing alcohol consumption and Italy focusing on employer-provided mental health resources.

Divergences arose regarding social impacts and coping strategies. Cases focusing on migrants and ethnic minorities emphasized social isolation and loneliness due to lockdowns and mobility restrictions. In contrast, healthcare workers faced work overload and family conflicts but maintained workplace social connections. Resilience responses also varied, with minority groups exhibiting self-organization while health workers relied more on employer-provided mental health resources. Additionally, the prominence of racial discrimination differed, being central for minority group cases but less examined in healthcare worker studies. The Belgium and England cases highlighted social isolation as a key theme among migrants and ethnic minorities. Yet the community organizing responses varied, with self-organized aid in England versus reliance on local organizations in Belgium.

Racial discrimination was also more central in England. Likewise, Economic precarity spanned the Spain and Wales cases, though the populations differed. Spain examined migrant workers losing income while Wales focused on the financial constraints keeping migrant nurses in unsafe hospital jobs. Both revealed housing access issues but more digital divide concerns in Spain.

Timelines revealed both shared and unique patterns. Initial lockdown phases represented peak disruption across cases, giving way to “normalized routines” later on. However, some populations like migrants experienced cumulative economic problems over time, while healthcare workers reported persisting burnout and psychological distress. Communication practices also evolved, with misinformation featuring early on and trust declining in later pandemic stages. Trust and communication challenges recurred in Germany/Sweden, Portugal, and Greece. However, Germany/Sweden found high institutional trust while Greece emphasized declining trust in authorities over time. The Portuguese case study indicated an initial and worsening trend of adherence to risk communication guidelines in long-term care facilities – fear messaging contributed to extreme risk aversion for some (residents, workers), and ignoring of guidelines for others. Germany/Sweden also noted greater misinformation exposure compared to inconsistent government messaging in Greece. Timeline patterns diverged between Greece and Italy. Greece saw compliance declining and frustrations escalating in later phases, while Italy pointed to persistent mental health problems after lockdown periods subsided. Communication evolutions also differed, with Italy showing improving employer relations over time unlike Greece.

The COREQ analysis offers methodological insights. Sample sizes ranged considerably, with most relying on small qualitative samples. Interviewer characteristics were seldom reported. Interview guides focused on pandemic experiences and vulnerabilities. Techniques to analyse the data included thematic coding. In conclusion, cross-case analysis reveals both specific and overarching pandemic impacts on diverse vulnerable populations. It highlights priorities like mental health services, economic aid, and resilience-building. A complex systems perspective elucidates synergistic effects across domains. The COREQ review demonstrates inconsistent reporting but overall methodological rigor. These global insights strengthen the project's capacity to inform effective, equitable policies.

4. Conclusions

The Phase 2 case studies presented in this section provide invaluable insights into the experiences of diverse vulnerable groups during the COVID-19 pandemic across European contexts. By adopting complex systems and intersectionality approaches, the studies uncover the syndemic nature of COVID-19 impacts on physical, mental, social, and economic wellbeing. Several key themes emerge that demonstrate how pre-existing inequities and exclusions were exacerbated by the pandemic.

First, the studies reveal a detrimental impact on mental health across almost all groups, with heightened stress, anxiety, loneliness, and depression. Frontline healthcare workers faced immense pressures leading to burnout, while lockdowns and isolation severely affected migrants and minorities. Second, digital divides emerged as a key factor reinforcing inequalities in access to information, services, and opportunities. Third, loss of income due to pandemic restrictions pushed many vulnerable groups into economic precarity, especially those reliant on gig economy jobs. Fourth, inadequate and overcrowded housing amplified risks for contagion and adverse outcomes. Finally, complex dynamics surrounding trust in government institutions influenced information consumption and adherence to protective behaviours.

These insights will directly inform the risk assessment framework and dashboard developed in Work Package 2. The dashboard synthesizes findings across work packages into systems map, visualizing vulnerabilities and interlinked pandemic impacts. The case studies provide crucial empirical evidence from Phase 2 to populate the dashboard. In particular, the mental health, economic, and digital divide impacts identified can indicate priority areas for risk assessment.

Methodologically, the case studies demonstrate the value of complex systems and intersectionality approaches for understanding COVID-19. Applying these frameworks illuminates how vulnerabilities intersect and interact to produce uneven pandemic experiences. This perspective is essential for elucidating the structural roots of syndemic impacts. The methodologies and conceptual tools used in these studies can inform research on future health crises and shocks to enhance preparedness and response.

Several recommendations emerge from the case studies:

- Targeted mental health services should be made available for frontline healthcare workers and minority/migrant groups to address the psychological toll of pandemics.
- Digital divide interventions (e.g., skills training, subsidized broadband access) are needed to ensure equitable access to critical information and services.
- Social protection schemes and unemployment benefits must cover the gig economy and informal workers to mitigate income loss during crises.
- Public health communication should utilize community partners to disseminate messaging in culturally and linguistically appropriate ways.
- Housing policies should expand access to affordable, adequate, and safe accommodation options.
- Trust-building between institutions and citizens requires transparency, acknowledgement of uncertainties, and inclusive participation.

One aspect that should be underlined is the fact that all people and organizations have a latitude of adaptation that relates to their resilience. All the case studies showed resilience indicating that the factors of disequilibrium in a pandemic are the ones that exist before its appearance. Thus, besides the specific adaptation in a pandemic framework of certain procedures (for example developing tailor made risk communications) what is more important is put in place supporting measures like extension of mental health networks, for example.

This reinforcement of measures during the normal function of society is the only way that a pandemic does not become a syndemic.

In conclusion, the COVINFORM case studies provide invaluable, context-specific insights into pandemic impacts on diverse vulnerable populations. By elucidating complex systems dynamics and intersecting vulnerabilities, they strengthen preparedness for future shocks and crises. The findings reinforce the scientific value of systems and intersectionality approaches while also informing more ethical, effective policy responses.

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Appendices

Appendix A. COREQ Checklists

1. SYNYO COREQ Checklist

Item	Consideration
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	<i>Which author/s conducted the interview or focus group?</i> Viktoria Adler (VA), Rojin Bagheri (RB)
2. Credentials	<i>What were the researcher's credentials?</i> PhD in Anthropology (VA) MA in Sociology (RB)
3. Occupation	<i>What was their occupation at the time of the study?</i> Post-doctoral researcher & project coordinator (VA) Prae-doctoral researcher (RB)
4. Gender	<i>Was the researcher male or female?</i> All two researchers identify as women.
5. Experience and training	<i>What experience or training did the researcher have?</i> VA is trained in qualitative methodologies and has extensive experience in conducting ethnographic research including narrative and semi-structured interviews as well as participant observations. RB is trained in both qualitative and quantitative methods. She has experience in conducting narrative and problem-centered interviews and in various qualitative data analysis methods.
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	<i>Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?</i> No, the research team did not have any pre-existing relationship with their interlocutors or the management of the residency.
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	<i>What did the participants know about the researchers</i> The management of the residency introduced us to the interlocutors in our absence. They also recruited the participants. We introduced us with our names and told them that we are the researchers for the COVINFORM project.

8. Interviewer characteristics	<p><i>What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator?</i></p> <p>Based on the conversations we had and our overall interactions the participants knew that VA is from Austria and RB is from Germany and that both are women.</p>
Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	<p><i>What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study? e.g. grounded theory, discourse analysis, ethnography, phenomenology, content analysis</i></p> <p>We are conducting phenomenological research as we aim to understand the experience of low SES women of the pandemic crisis communication and how it affected their feelings of safety and risk. For that we are using a theoretical framework that is based on an intersectional approaches and theories on sense making. For the analysis of the interview data, we will be conducting a thematic analysis (Braun & Clark 2006).</p>
<i>Participant selection</i>	
10. Sampling	<p><i>How were participants selected? e.g. purposive, convenience, consecutive, snowball</i></p> <p>Residency manager recruited and selected the interlocutors for us based on their willingness to be interviewed. Some interlocutors were suggested based on their interesting stories (again by the management).</p>
11. Method of approach	<p><i>How were participants approached? e.g. face-to-face, telephone, mail, email</i></p> <p>The researchers approached the management of the residency who then spread the information and info material and recruited participants for us. As incentive we offered a 20 Euro voucher for a popular discount supermarket.</p>
12. Sample size	<p><i>How many participants were in the study?</i></p> <p><i>Include also total number of planned interviews per target group and number of interviews conducted so far per target group</i></p> <p>So far, we conducted five interviews with residents</p>
13. Non-participation	<p>How many people refused to participate or dropped out?</p> <p>-</p>
<i>Setting</i>	

14. Setting of data collection	<p><i>Where was the data collected?</i></p> <p>Data was collected in the cafeteria (which was closed and empty during the interviews), as well as in the garden of the residency.</p>
15. Presence of non-participants	<p><i>Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers?</i></p> <p>-</p>
16. Description of sample	<p><i>What are the important characteristics of the sample?</i></p> <p>Women living in the Hannah Arendt House run by one of the big social economy providers in Austria. This is an assisted and stationary home for homeless people. They are provided with (semi-) permanent flats with very low rent and social workers supporting them in their daily lives if needed.</p>
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	<p><i>Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested?</i></p> <p>For our case study we used the resident interview guide and focused on the section on communication.</p>
18. Repeat interviews	<p><i>Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many?</i></p> <p>No repeat interviews are planned.</p>
19. Audio/visual recording	<p><i>Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?</i></p> <p>We audio-recorded the interviews which we also transcribed.</p>
20. Field notes	<p><i>Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group?</i></p> <p>We wrote short notes on the context of the interviews.</p>
21. Duration	<p><i>What was the duration of the interviews or focus group?</i></p> <p>The interviews we conducted so far took between 20 and 60 minutes</p>
22. Data saturation	<p><i>Was data saturation discussed?</i></p> <p>Yes, are aiming for a sample of eight interviews with the residents. As we are interested in perceptions and sense making and we are using qualitative methods to investigate these issues data saturation is hard to reach. However, we expect that new information gained after eight interviews will decrease with each following interview. Additionally, we aim for two interviews with staff/management of the Hannah Arendt House</p>
23. Transcripts returned	<p><i>Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction?</i></p>

	No
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	
24. Number of data coders	<i>How many data coders coded the data?</i> One, although the codes were reviewed by another researcher and checked for reliability.
25. Description of the coding tree	<i>Did authors provide a description of the coding tree?</i> Yes
26. Derivation of themes	<i>Were themes identified in advance or derived from the data?</i> Major themes were identified beforehand, subthemes were derived from the data.
27. Software	<i>What software, if applicable, was used to manage the data?</i> Nvivo.
28. Participant checking	<i>Did participants provide feedback on the findings?</i> No.
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	<i>Were participant quotations presented to illustrate the themes / findings?</i> Yes, in the analytical chapter findings are illustrated by quotations. All quotations can be found in German as well as English in the annex.
30. Data and findings consistent	<i>Was there consistency between the data presented and the findings?</i> Data analysis showed consistency with the current state of the art, however one of the consistencies is also the great individuality and heterogeneity of the interviewees. The interviewees varied greatly in respect to their life trajectories and thus also in their experiences during the pandemic. However, these differences are discussed thoroughly.
31. Clarity of major themes	<i>Were major themes clearly presented in the findings?</i> Major themes are presented in the findings, in line with the research lines identified in the SES framework.
32. Clarity of minor themes	<i>Is there a description of diverse cases or discussion of minor themes?</i>

	As discussed under point 30, the studied group in itself is already very heterogenous which is consistent with existing literature. Therefore, variations concerning minor themes exist and are discussed in the analysis chapter as well as the conclusion.
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2. UANTWERPEN COREQ Checklist

<i>Item</i>	<i>Consideration</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	Hannah Robinson Jil Molenaar
2. Credentials	Bachelor History and Politics, Master International Development Bachelor Human Sciences, Master Global Health
3. Occupation	Researcher
4. Gender	Female
5. Experience and training	Qualitative research experience
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	None
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	Researcher at the UA
8. Interviewer characteristics	Introduced ourselves as researchers at the UA, working on an EU funded research project looking at the impact of the pandemic on different groups of people.
Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	

<i>Participant selection</i>	
10. Sampling	Recruited through organisations or actors working with migrants in Antwerpen Noord/Borgerhout. Snowball sampling.
11. Method of approach	Personal contacts (via-via) or to organisations through text or email. Rest contact face to face at organisation walk-in moments, or through community health workers.
12. Sample size	19 interviews with migrants 13 interviews with experts
13. Non-participation	Difficult to measure rates of non-participation, as many were approached face-to-face.
<i>Setting</i>	
14. Setting of data collection	At various organisations 'walk in' moments, such as SAAMO or Elegast. Or at cafes when recruited in other ways. Experts mainly interviewed through video-call or in their office space.
15. Presence of non-participants	Sometimes workers from organisation or community health worker to help with translation.
16. Description of sample	Members of migrant communities in Borgerhout and Antwerpen Noord, specifically migrants that arrived in Belgium more than 5 years ago. Representatives from local-level govt and decision makers (Stad Antwerpen), professionals working in mental health services (GPs, psychologists), representatives from community level initiatives and services (Coronababbels, Atlas vzw)
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	Interview guide included questions to guide interviews as well as prompts during the interview. It was not pilot tested but after a few interviews with migrants we realized that language barriers meant some of the questions were not properly understood. Also we received feedback from migrants interviewed at the beginning that questions were too specialist/technical and a bit too abstract. So we adapted the interview guide after this.
18. Repeat interviews	None
19. Audio/visual recording	A phone was used to record interviews, or Teams/Skype if the interview took place online.
20. Field notes	No

21. Duration	Between 30 mins and 1 hour.
22. Data saturation	Not yet
23. Transcripts returned	No
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	
24. Number of data coders	Two
25. Description of the coding tree	<p>The coding tree was partly created using themes derived from before conducting the case study. Specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Key drivers of mental health ● Role of community-based organisations <p>The coding tree was expanded using codes derived from analysis, specifically the codes below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Key drivers of mental health (health concerns, social network, work and finances, digitalisation, built environment, public space, care responsibilities (Gendered)) ● Role of community-based organisations - unique value and fragmentation and fragility (awareness local needs, addressing bottlenecks/filling gaps, responding to broad spectrum of needs, culturally sensitive care, workload and capacity constraints, physical accessibility, fragmentation and lack of oversight))
26. Derivation of themes	Themes were partly derived in advance (when reading literature) and partly derived when analysing the data.
27. Software	NVivo was used
28. Participant checking	No
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	Quotations were used to illustrate the findings.

30. Data and findings consistent	There is consistency between data presented and findings.
31. Clarity of major themes	Major themes were clearly presented in the findings, in answering the research questions.
32. Clarity of minor themes	Minor themes were presented when analysing the data and creating sub-codes.

3. MDI COREQ Checklist

<i>Item</i>	<i>Consideration</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	Paresh Solanki
2. Credentials	Paresh Solanki is an international award-winning producer/director and media executive with a passion for social development. He was a senior executive at the BBC till 2007. Solanki was awarded the Fellowship of the Royal Television Society in 2005, and the Fellowship of the Institute of Leadership and Development in 2011. He has worked as Media Expert for the Council of Europe and is a trustee for the Media Diversity Institute.
3. Occupation	Director of Media Empowered Social Innovation.
4. Gender	Male.
5. Experience and training	Solanki is an experienced journalist and media expert.
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	The interviewer had some relationships established prior to the interviews.
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	Not all interviewees knew the interviewer prior to the data-gathering process.
8. Interviewer characteristics	Paresh Solanki has extensive experience as producer/director and as media executive, in these roles he gained knowledge about data-gathering, interviewing, and media production at a professional level. He was a senior executive at the BBC till 2007, has worked as Media Expert for the Council of Europe, and is a trustee for the Media Diversity Institute.

Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	Ethnography, qualitative interviewing, document analysis. In terms of theory, the work was underpinned by systems theory and intersectional media use.
<i>Participant selection</i>	
10. Sampling	Non-random, purposive.
11. Method of approach	Telephone, email, face-to-face.
12. Sample size	The original plan was to conduct around 20 interviews, but we carried out 31 in-depth semi-structured interviews in total.
13. Non-participation	Two people dropped out of the interviewing process because they could not make the proposed time and place.
<i>Setting</i>	
14. Setting of data collection	England, United Kingdom.
15. Presence of non-participants	The only people present in the interviews were the interviewer and the cameraman, Bhasker Solanki. For one of the interviews, the interviewer's mother came with him.
16. Description of sample	Used variables of gender, religion, ethnicity, age, and community role within minoritized ("hard-to-reach communities") in England, UK.
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	Questions were refined by members of the research team, based on the expert or scholarly literature reviewed.
18. Repeat interviews	None.
19. Audio/visual recording	Every interview was video recorded.
20. Field notes	Field notes were taken.
21. Duration	Interviews lasted approximately one hour per interviewee.
22. Data saturation	Saturation of themes was reached.

23. Transcripts returned	The interviewees were not interested in reading the transcript. Some were interested in seeing the short videos, and MDI will provide these to them.
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	
24. Number of data coders	Three professionals participated in the data coding and elaboration of the thematic blocks.
25. Description of the coding tree	<p>The authors provided a description of the coding tree, and the coding tree was elaborated using the following thematic blocks or qualitative codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Time points of the pandemic, ● Vulnerability, ● Protective factors, ● Strategies used (Referential, Predicational, Argumentation strategies), ● Communication channels, ● Trust in media.
26. Derivation of themes	Qualitative coding themes were partly identified in advance of the interviewing process, guided by scholarly/expert literature; yet these were also partly derived from the data gathered, especially after the first set of pilot interviews.
27. Software	NVivo software was used. Yet, the data gathered was also coded manually.
28. Participant checking	So far participants/interviewees have not received feedback, yet this will be arranged at a later stage for those who provided their contact details.
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	Some participants/interviewees' quotations were used to illustrate the themes or aspects of the latter.
30. Data and findings consistent	There is consistency between the data presented and the findings.
31. Clarity of major themes	Major themes were clearly presented in the findings (See Section 25 of this form).

32. Clarity of minor themes	There is description of the diversity of cases and discussion of both the broader and the tributary/minor themes identified. Together, these generated thematic blocks.
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4. SINUS COREQ Checklist

<i>Item</i>	<i>Consideration</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	Annette Schiffmann, Rusanna Gaber, James Edwards
2. Credentials	Recruiting: small civil society organisation (CSO) based in the Heidelberg area specialising in consulting and arranging support for vulnerable women. Interviewers: 1) PhD in political science; 2) MA in European studies. Analysis: PhD in sociology of music/culture, with a focus on mixed-methods data analysis.
3. Occupation	Recruiting: CSO director. Interviewing: 1) senior researcher; 2) researcher. Analysis: senior researcher.
4. Gender	Recruiting: women-identifying. Interviewing: 1) women-identifying; 2) male-identifying. Analysis: male-identifying.
5. Experience and training	Recruiting: over 20 years of field experience working with vulnerable women. Interviewing: 1) ca. 15 years experience working on public health projects with vulnerable populations; 2) ca. five years experience working on public health projects. Analysis: ca. 6 years working on European Commission-funded studies in fields related to sociology of culture.
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	The participants were provided with extensive project information and asked to provide informed consent in writing. The participants were furthermore given several opportunities to ask questions about the project, research institution, and/or researchers (e.g., at the time of first contact, at the time the

	informed consent form was returned, and before and after the interview itself).
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	Participants were provided with the interviewer's professional credentials such as occupation, name, and experience, and given several opportunities to ask questions.
8. Interviewer characteristics	The interviewers introduced themselves as professionals who were conducting a European compared research across different countries within the pandemic context.
Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	<p>The questionnaire and the data collection techniques for the interviews consider the research questions and, therefore, the theoretical-conceptual framework of this research, specifically socio-ecological systems framework.</p> <p>The analysis and processing of the data collected will also be carried out using methodological tools such as discourse analysis and content analysis.</p>
<i>Participant selection</i>	
10. Sampling	Purposive sample combined with snowballing.
11. Method of approach	Depending on the interviewee, face-to-face, by telephone, or by email.
12. Sample size	<p>Civil society organisation representatives: N=5.</p> <p>Public health practitioners: N=5.</p> <p>Governmental organisation representatives: N=5.</p> <p>Journalists: N=2.</p> <p>Governmental communicators: N=3.</p> <p>N=6 low-SES women without migration background.</p> <p>N=8 low-SES women with migration background.</p> <p>N=4 low-SES men with migration background</p>

13. Non-participation	Several participants ended up declining or no-showing due to personal reasons. However, we did not find any systematic patterns of non-response.
<i>Setting</i>	
14. Setting of data collection	Municipality of Mannheim, Germany.
15. Presence of non-participants	No
16. Description of sample	Inclusion criteria were: 1) gender, as determined via self-identification; 2) low socioeconomic status, as determined by receipt of social assistance; 3) for some respondents, migration background, defined as at least one parent having been born outside Germany.
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	Interview guides were designed including questions to guide the interviews. Different guides were used for interviews with citizens and institutional actors. Each guide contains a beginning section with a brief explanation of the project to be provided to the interviewee prior to the interview, without going into details so as to not bias their answers. Official consent forms and project's info sheets were also administered.
18. Repeat interviews	No
19. Audio/visual recording	Audio devices: mobile, tape recorder, recording software provided by meeting platforms (SINUS Digital Salon online qualitative research platform: https://www.sinus-institut.de/en/research/solutions/digital-salon).
20. Field notes	Field notes were made by the interviewer upon consent by the interviewee.
21. Duration	Between 30 and 90 minutes.
22. Data saturation	Yes
23. Transcripts returned	Interviewees were offered the opportunity to access their data, however, no interviewees have chosen to do so as of the time of reporting.
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	

24. Number of data coders	Two
25. Description of the coding tree	Yes
26. Derivation of themes	Both: structural codes were applied in accordance with the interview guide flow, while thematic codes were applied based on the interview contents.
27. Software	QDA Miner v5.0.35
28. Participant checking	Interviewees were offered the opportunity to access their data, however, no interviewees have chosen to do so as of the time of reporting.
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	Yes, in pseudonymised form, except in cases in which participants refused consent to be cited.
30. Data and findings consistent	Yes.
31. Clarity of major themes	Yes.
32. Clarity of minor themes	Yes.

5. UGOT COREQ Checklist

<i>Item</i>	<i>Consideration</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	Which author/s conducted the interview or focus group? Julia Ekman Marina Ghersetti Wilhelm Golinski Sofia Johansson Petter Myrenberg Erika Stacke Elias Åhlander
2. Credentials	What were the researcher's credentials? Julia Ekman – Master student Marina Ghersetti – Professor Wilhelm Golinski – Master student

	<p>Sofia Johansson – Ph.D. student</p> <p>Petter Myrenberg – Journalist student</p> <p>Erika Stacke – Master student</p> <p>Elias Åhlander – Journalist student</p> <p>The main selection criterion for all interviewers was previous experience of interviewing. The Master students and the Ph.D. student that conducted interviews were also well acquainted with central theories and literature in risk and crisis communication. The journalist students were at the time studying a course in journalism research and writing their Bachelor Thesis.</p>
3. Occupation	<p>What was their occupation at the time of the study?</p> <p>See above, form field no. 2</p>
4. Gender	<p>Was the researcher male or female?</p> <p>Julia Ekman – female</p> <p>Marina Ghersetti – female</p> <p>Wilhelm Golinski – male</p> <p>Sofia Johansson – female</p> <p>Petter Myrenberg – male</p> <p>Erika Stacke – female</p> <p>Elias Åhlander – male</p>
5. Experience and training	<p>What experience or training did the researcher have?</p> <p>All researchers and students had experience from interviewing. The Professor and Master Students had already conducted research interviews in previous research projects and/or when writing Bachelor and Master Thesis. For journalism students, interviewing is a very central part of their education and a skill they acquire and practice repeatedly during their training. The journalism students involved in the COVINFORM project are in their third semester.</p>
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	<p>Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?</p> <p>No.</p>
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	<p>What did the participants know about the researcher?</p> <p>Most of the participants of the case study were contacted through intermediaries, usually supervisors/contact persons of study circles, childcare centres, or homework help organisations. The supervisors very briefly introduced the project and the interviewees to the participants. When</p>

	meeting the interviewee (participant), the interviewer would present both the project and her-/himself more in detail (orally and by handing over a written presentation of the project).
8. Interviewer characteristics	What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator?
Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	<p>What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study? e.g., grounded theory, discourse analysis, ethnography, phenomenology, content analysis</p> <p>The case study departs from theory of sensemaking in analysing information seeking and communicative behaviour within a social constructivist framework, i.e., in recognition of the embeddedness of individual behaviour and the dialectic of agency and structure. The study has a comparative approach; data from Sweden and Germany are compared and analysed.</p>
<i>Participant selection</i>	
10. Sampling	<p>How were participants selected? e.g. purposive, convenience, consecutive, snowball</p> <p>All participants were selected from ethnical minority groups living primarily in one specific migrant dense suburb in the outskirts of Gothenburg, Hjällbo. A snowball recruitment approach was used. Only individual interviews were conducted, with one exception when two participants were interviewed at the same time. No focus group interviews were conducted.</p>
11. Method of approach	<p>How were participants approached? e.g. face-to-face, telephone, mail, email</p> <p>The participants were usually contacted face-to-face by an intermediary, usually a person in charge of some form of interest organization/group operating within the geographically defined recruitment area (see also form field no 7). All interviews were conducted face-to-face.</p>
12. Sample size	<p>How many participants were in the study?</p> <p><i>Include also total number of planned interviews per target group and number of interviews conducted so far per target group</i></p> <p>The established number of interviews was 12, 6 women and 6 men living in the two pre-defined areas. However, all in all 15 interviews were conducted since three were of rather pure</p>

	quality, due mainly to language issues, and will not be included in the sample.
13. Non-participation	How many people refused to participate or dropped out? N/A
<i>Setting</i>	
14. Setting of data collection	Where was the data collected? All interviews were conducted in the area where the interviewees lived, in the premises made available by the organization that mediated the recruitment. No interview was conducted in the interviewee's home. All interviews were conducted in separate rooms or in separate parts of a large room, in most cases with two interviewers present, one responsible for following the interview guidelines, and one responsible for relevant ad-hoc follow-up questions. In some cases, two people were interviewed at the same time.
15. Presence of non-participants	Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers? When the interview was conducted in a separate space of a large room, other people may have been present. However none close enough to interfere with/overhear the interview. Also, in some cases a translator was present.
16. Description of sample	What are the important characteristics of the sample? The sample consists of persons that have migrated to Sweden, some early in life when they were infants, other later as adults. Knowledge of the Swedish language varied a lot, some of the interviewees spoke it fluently why others had difficulties in understanding and making themselves understood. Interviews were mainly conducted in Swedish, but also in English if needed.
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested? An interview guide was provided by SINUS and UGOT in collaboration with other partners in the project. The guide was thoroughly elaborated, and several adjustments were made. The first interview set out to be a pilot, but since the guide worked well the interview was included in the sample.
18. Repeat interviews	Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many? No.
19. Audio/visual recording	Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?

	Yes, all interviews were recorded in consent with the interviewee.
20. Field notes	Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group? Yes, field notes were in some cases made during the interview.
21. Duration	What was the duration of the interviews or focus group? The duration of the interviews was around 30 minutes (ranging between 18 minutes and 44 minutes).
22. Data saturation	Was data saturation discussed? No.
23. Transcripts returned	Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction? No.
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	
24. Number of data coders	How many data coders coded the data? One
25. Description of the coding tree	Did authors provide a description of the coding tree? Yes
26. Derivation of themes	Were themes identified in advance or derived from the data? Both, using the SES framework, theories of crisis communication but also attention to dimensions in the data not foreseen.
27. Software	What software, if applicable, was used to manage the data? QDA Miner
28. Participant checking	Did participants provide feedback on the findings? No
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	Were participant quotations presented to illustrate the themes / findings? Yes
30. Data and findings consistent	Was there consistency between the data presented and the findings?

	Yes
31. Clarity of major themes	Were major themes clearly presented in the findings? Yes
32. Clarity of minor themes	Is there a description of diverse cases or discussion of minor themes? No

6. KEMEA COREQ Checklist

<i>Item</i>	<i>Consideration</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	Multidisciplinary team with experience in social research, including the application of qualitative and quantitative data collection tools.
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	Effrosyni Dima, Ioannis Bagkatzounis, Ioannis Konstantopoulos, Anna Tsekoura
2. Credentials	<p>Effrosyni: Participation in the EU projects COVINFORM.</p> <p>Ioannis Bagkatzounis: Participation in the EU projects COVINFORM, PERCEPTIONS, ERADICATING. Graduate of History and Ethnology (DUTH), MSc in International Security and Law.</p> <p>Ioannis Konstantopoulos: Participation in the EU projects COVINFORM, MEDEA, IRIS. National & Kapodistrian University of Athens: Master of Arts - MA Geopolitics, 2016-2018, London Metropolitan University: Master of Laws - LLM International Law, 2011-2012, Ecole Supérieure de Commerce et Gestion de Yaounde: Master in Business Administration - MBA Global Marketing Management, 207-2010, London Metropolitan University: Bachelor of Laws - LLB Law, 2003-2005.</p> <p>Anna Tsekoura: Participation in the EU projects COVINFORM. National & Kapodistrian University of Athens: Masters degree Crisis emergency disaster management, Health Emergency Management and Civil Protection Expert, Certified Adult Trainer Health Emergency Management and Civil Protection Expert, Certified Adult Trainer (Euro-Mediterranean Institute for Quality and Safety in Health Services (EIQSH), National School of Public Administration National School of Public Administration - Master's degree, Health/Health Care Administration/Management, Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences - Bachelor's degree, Sociology</p>

3. Occupation	Research Associates
4. Gender	Effrosyni: Female Ioannis B.: Male Ioannis K.: Male Anna: Female
5. Experience and training	<p>Effrosyni: Bachelors in Philosophy, Pedagogy and Psychology - University of Ioannina, Master in Multicultural education – University of Ioannina, Master in Primary school education – University of Munich. Several years working in qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods research. Professional experience in project management at national and international level.</p> <p>Ioannis B.: Graduate of History and Ethnology (DUTH), MSc in International Security and Law. Several years working in qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods research. Professional experience in project management at national and international level.</p> <p>Ioannis K.: National & Kapodistrian University of Athens: Master of Arts - MA Geopolitics, 2016-2018, London Metropolitan University: Master of Laws - LLM International Law, 2011-2012, Ecole Supérieure de Commerce et Gestion de Yaounde: Master in Business Administration - MBA Global Marketing Management, 2007-2010, London Metropolitan University: Bachelor of Laws - LLB Law, 2003-2005. Several years working in qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods research. Professional experience in project management at national and international level.</p> <p>Anna: National & Kapodistrian University of Athens: Masters degree Crisis emergency disaster management, Health Emergency Management and Civil Protection Expert, Certified Adult Trainer Health Emergency Management and Civil Protection Expert, Certified Adult Trainer (Euro-Mediterranean Institute for Quality and Safety in Health Services (EIQSH), National School of Public Administration National School of Public Administration - Master's degree, Health/Health Care Administration/Management, Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences - Bachelor's degree, Sociology. Several years working in qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods research. Professional experience in project management at national and international level.</p>
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	No previous relationship was established.

7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	None. With the cooperation of third sector organizations (CSOs) and utilizing the network that has been established between KEMEA with third party entites, we have contacted migrant, refugee and members of the Roma community as well as Law Enforcement Agents. In both interview pools, thematic areas revolved around perceptions, trust and interaction with each target group in a pre-covid-19 and during-COVID-19 phase along with health-related uncertainties, economic activity, administrative situation and household issues.
8. Interviewer characteristics	Introduced themselves as a professional who was conducting European comparative research across different countries within the pandemic context.
Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	<p>The questionnaire and the data collection techniques for the interviews consider the research questions and, therefore, the theoretical-conceptual framework of this research, specifically socio-economical systems framework, emphasized in perceptions and trust.</p> <p>The analysis and processing of the data collected will also be carried out using methodological tools such as Discourse analysis and content analysis. We also take into consideration the ethnographical methodological elements due to our target groups' characteristics.</p>
<i>Participant selection</i>	
10. Sampling	Purposive sample combined with snowballing.
11. Method of approach	Face-to-face, Telephone and email
12. Sample size	<p>How many participants were in the study?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5 Law Enforcement Agents - 5 individuals with the following characteristics: members of the Roma community and/or Refugees and/or Migrants and/or representatives of the aforementioned target groups.
13. Non-participation	<p>We did not find any patterns of non-response.</p> <p>For Roma and LEAs, the response rate reached 100%.</p>

<i>Setting</i>	
14. Setting of data collection	We contacted the aforementioned target groups as potential interviewees, and those who finally agreed were generally interviewed (on-site) in meeting rooms of CSOs, the HQ of KEMEA, or exceptionally in cafés in the neighbourhoods where the interviewees lived. The familiarity of these spaces for the interviewees facilitated their trust and openness to talk. Remote interviews were conducted by utilizing platforms such as Skype, Microsoft teams, Webex and Zoom. All interviews were conducted in Greece.
15. Presence of non-participants	None of the interviewees were accompanied during the interviews.
16. Description of sample	For minority groups and LEAs, the main characteristics were origin, employment, role, frequency and interaction with other relevant groups, socio-demographic status.
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	Interview guides were designed including research questions to guide the interviews. Different guides were used for interviews with each target group. Each guide contains a beginning section with a brief explanation of the project to be provided to the interviewee prior to the interview, without going into details so as to not bias their answers. Official consent forms and project's info sheets were also administered. Interviews were GDPR compliant and abided to all national and European legal framework ethical considerations, particularly in relation to conducting empirical research.
18. Repeat interviews	None.
19. Audio/visual recording	Audio devices: mobile, tape recorder, recording software provided by meeting platforms (webex, microsoft teams, skype and zoom).
20. Field notes	Interviews were carried out by at least two interviewers so that one carried out the interviews and another one took notes and recorded the session.
21. Duration	The duration of each interview varied, nevertheless they ranged between 40 minutes to 1 hour.
22. Data saturation	Yes.
23. Transcripts returned	Interviewees were given the opportunity to access them if they wanted to.

Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	
24. Number of data coders	How many data coders coded the data? One researcher
25. Description of the coding tree	Did authors provide a description of the coding tree? Yes
26. Derivation of themes	Public Trust, perception of risk and threat, accountability and self awareness, governmental responses: practical and psychological impact - challenges, evaluation of governmental responses
27. Software	None. The coding and analysis were conducted manually.
28. Participant checking	No
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	Yes
30. Data and findings consistent	Yes
31. Clarity of major themes	Yes
32. Clarity of minor themes	Yes

7. SAPIENZA&UCSC COREQ Checklist

<i>Item</i>	<i>Consideration</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	<i>Which author/s conducted the interview or focus group?</i> Chieffo Daniela (CD), Valentina Delle Donne (VDD), Monia Pellizzari (MP)
2. Credentials	<i>What were the researcher's credentials?</i>

	PhD in Psychology (DC), Phd in Clinical Cellular and Molecular Research (VDD), Phd in Social Psychology of Development and Educational Research (MP)
3. Occupation	<i>What was their occupation at the time of the study?</i> Assistant Professor (DC), Research Psychologist (VDD), Research Psychologist (MP)
4. Gender	<i>Was the researcher male or female?</i> All three researchers identify as women.
5. Experience and training	<i>What experience or training did the researcher have?</i> All researchers are trained in qualitative methods, DC have several years of experience of fieldwork using qualitative methods
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	<i>Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?</i> We had already contacted the interviewees during the quantitative survey. Therefore they knew the objective of the case study and more generally of the COVINFORM project.
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	<i>What did the participants know about the researcher?</i> Background, credentials, work position.
8. Interviewer characteristics	<i>What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator?</i> We introduced ourselves, our position and our organisation, as well as the project and its objectives.
Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	<i>What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study? e.g. grounded theory, discourse analysis, ethnography, phenomenology, content analysis</i> Ethnography, content analysis, anthropological demography, psychology.
<i>Participant selection</i>	

10. Sampling	<i>How were participants selected? e.g. purposive, convenience, consecutive, snowball</i> Snowball
11. Method of approach	<i>How were participants approached? e.g. face-to-face, telephone, mail, email</i> Email, face-to-face
12. Sample size	<i>How many participants were in the study?</i> <i>Include also total number of planned interviews per target group and number of interviews conducted so far per target group</i> We planned to interview 14 people
13. Non-participation	<i>How many people refused to participate or dropped out?</i> 4 people, among those contacted by e-mail and who had indicated their willingness to participate, did not carry out the interview
<i>Setting</i>	
14. Setting of data collection	<i>Where was the data collected?</i> Data was collected at the hospital where HCWs work
15. Presence of non-participants	<i>Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers?</i> -
16. Description of sample	What are the important characteristics of the sample?
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	<i>Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested?</i> Yes, questions we refined by members of research team
18. Repeat interviews	<i>Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many?</i> None
19. Audio/visual recording	<i>Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?</i> Yes video and audio recorded
20. Field notes	<i>Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group?</i> Yes
21. Duration	<i>What was the duration of the interviews or focus group?</i>

	Approximately 40 minutes
22. Data saturation	<i>Was data saturation discussed?</i> Not yet
23. Transcripts returned	<i>Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction?</i> No
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	
24. Number of data coders	<i>How many data coders coded the data?</i> Two
25. Description of the coding tree	<i>Did authors provide a description of the coding tree?</i> No
26. Derivation of themes	<i>Were themes identified in advance or derived from the data?</i> They were identified in advance from the quantitative survey
27. Software	<i>What software, if applicable, was used to manage the data?</i> None
28. Participant checking	<i>Did participants provide feedback on the findings?</i> Not yet
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	<i>Were participant quotations presented to illustrate the themes / findings?</i> Yes
30. Data and findings consistent	<i>Was there consistency between the data presented and the findings?</i> Yes
31. Clarity of major themes	<i>Were major themes clearly presented in the findings?</i> Yes
32. Clarity of minor themes	<i>Is there a description of diverse cases or discussion of minor themes?</i> No

8. FS COREQ CHECKLIST

<i>Item</i>	<i>Consideration</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	<i>Which author/s conducted the interview or focus group?</i> Joana Melo Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto
2. Credentials	<i>What were the researcher's credentials?</i> Joana Melo: Clinical psychologist (master's degree) Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto: Junior social psychologist (master's degree)
3. Occupation	<i>What was their occupation at the time of the study?</i> Joana Melo: Researcher at FS Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto: Project manager and principal researcher at FS
4. Gender	<i>Was the researcher male or female?</i> Joana Melo: Female Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto: Female
5. Experience and training	<i>What experience or training did the researcher have?</i> Joana Melo: Curricular training and approximately 15 interviews done previously for the same project. Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto: Curricular training, interviews conducted for previous research, and interviews conducted for the current project
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	<i>Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?</i> No
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	<i>What did the participants know about the researcher?</i> Name, gender, and qualifications
8. Interviewer characteristics	<i>What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator?</i>

	Condition of low vision.
Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	<p><i>What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study? e.g. grounded theory, discourse analysis, ethnography, phenomenology, content analysis</i></p> <p>Socio-ecological systems as theoretical and methodological framework; Thematic analysis to address data analysis through a mixed approach: Bottom-up and top-down</p>
<i>Participant selection</i>	
10. Sampling	<p><i>How were participants selected? e.g. purposive, convenience, consecutive, snowball</i></p> <p>Mainly non-probability sample. Extensive list of contacts from statal websites and private websites. Visits to close by LTCFs upon conducting field work at the site.</p>
11. Method of approach	<p><i>How were participants approached? e.g. face-to-face, telephone, mail, email</i></p> <p>Via email and telephone to reach out, explain project and arrange for time to interview participants; Most were approached in person once at the site due to lack of response in previous method. All interviews were conducted face-to-face</p>
12. Sample size	<p><i>How many participants were in the study?</i></p> <p><i>Include also total number of planned interviews per target group and number of interviews conducted so far per target group</i></p> <p>Total interviews conducted: 43 (34 women);</p> <p>Total participating LTCFs: 13</p> <p>LTCF administration: 11 (10 women)</p> <p>LTCF workers: 12 (10 women)</p> <p>LTCF elderly residents: 20 (14 women)</p>
13. Non-participation	<p><i>How many people refused to participate or dropped out?</i></p> <p>Total LTCFs contacted (phone, email and in-person): around 45.</p> <p>Total LTCFs contacted via phone and email: around 28.</p>

	<p>Total LTCFs contacted in-person: around 17.</p> <p>Once at the institution, after acceptance of participation from LTCFs administration, no participant (worker, elderly, administration) refused to participate or dropped out.</p>
<i>Setting</i>	
14. Setting of data collection	<p><i>Where was the data collected?</i></p> <p>City of Évora in the Alentejo Region of Portugal.</p>
15. Presence of non-participants	<p>Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers?</p> <p>Sometimes, there was no other space to conduct the interview besides the room the elderly was on, so there were other LTCFs residents in the same room, but with no capacity to understand due to degenerated abilities.</p>
16. Description of sample	<p><i>What are the important characteristics of the sample?</i></p> <p>Elderly residents in long-term care facilities, as well as LTCFs' workers who provide for elderly on a daily basis and administration staff who are decision-makers regarding their LTCF.</p>
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	<p><i>Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested?</i></p> <p>The scripts were carefully elaborated given the goals, research questions, and indicators previously established.</p> <p>The first interviews of administration and worker target groups were considered pilots and included in the sample given their success. Upon the first interview of elderly, adjustments had to be made as they were not able to answer some questions designed with rating-scales. The script ended up being less structured than planned, but after adjustments were made, it worked out well.</p>
18. Repeat interviews	<p><i>Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many?</i></p> <p>No</p>
19. Audio/visual recording	<p><i>Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?</i></p> <p>Audio. Participants consented to this, given that their audio would be erased after successful transcription.</p>

20. Field notes	<p><i>Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group?</i></p> <p>Regarding the space, amenities, and observed relationship between staff and elderly available to elderly.</p>
21. Duration	<p><i>What was the duration of the interviews or focus group?</i></p> <p>LTCF administration: between 40min-1h LTCF workers: between 30-45min LTCF elderly residents: between 15-30min</p>
22. Data saturation	<p><i>Was data saturation discussed?</i></p> <p>We planned for at least: 1 private LTCF; 1 public LTCF; 1 third sector LTCF; 2 elderly from each LTCF type (both genders); 1 worker from each LTCF type; 1 admin from each LTCF type = minimum acceptable: 12 interviews.</p>
23. Transcripts returned	<p><i>Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction?</i></p> <p>No. It was not planned, and no participant asked for this.</p>
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	
24. Number of data coders	<p><i>How many data coders coded the data?</i></p> <p>3 (Beatriz Rosa, Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto, Rebeca Chaby)</p>
25. Description of the coding tree	<p><i>Did authors provide a description of the coding tree?</i></p> <p>Coding trees for elderly users and administration/workers can be found in the data reporting section.</p>
26. Derivation of themes	<p><i>Were themes identified in advance or derived from the data?</i></p> <p>Both. Some codes were created based on the interview guide, and new thematic codes were created based on the interview contents.</p>
27. Software	<p><i>What software, if applicable, was used to manage the data?</i></p> <p>NVivo</p>
28. Participant checking	<p><i>Did participants provide feedback on the findings?</i></p> <p>No</p>

<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	<p><i>Were participant quotations presented to illustrate the themes / findings?</i></p> <p>Yes. Quotations following the themes described in the analysis chapter can be found in annex 6.3. of the case study report.</p>
30. Data and findings consistent	<p><i>Was there consistency between the data presented and the findings?</i></p> <p>Yes. Despite the diversity of experiences, the data is consistent with the outcomes and indicators expected based on psychological theory and the SES framework, as well as with the findings discussed in the analysis (e.g., vulnerabilities, risk factors, protective factors, etc.).</p>
31. Clarity of major themes	<p><i>Were major themes clearly presented in the findings?</i></p> <p>Yes. Major themes were presented in the analysis section in line with the SES framework and associated with the research questions.</p>
32. Clarity of minor themes	<p><i>Is there a description of diverse cases or discussion of minor themes?</i></p> <p>Yes. Besides the descriptions that represent the majority of the sample, there were descriptions of diverse cases and experiences shared by only a minority of the sample integrated in the descriptions of the major themes.</p>

9. URJC COREQ CHECKLIST

<i>Item</i>	<i>Consideration</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	Multidisciplinary team with experience in social research, including the application of qualitative and quantitative data collection tools.
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	Manuel Tamayo Irene Sánchez-Vitores Javier Lorente Diego Castellanos Roraima Estaba
2. Credentials	Manuel Tamayo: PhD in Political Science, lead researcher of URJC team in COVINFORM

	<p>Irene Sánchez-Vítores: PhD in Social and Political Sciences</p> <p>Javier Lorente: PhD in Law and Political Science</p> <p>Diego Castellanos: Graduated in Political Science and Sociology. Master's degree in applied Sociology to Social Problems.</p> <p>Roraima Estaba: PhD in Political Science (obtained over the course of the project, not as an outcome of the project).</p>
3. Occupation	<p>Manuel Tamayo: Associate Professor at URJC</p> <p>Irene Sánchez-Vítores: Assistant Professor at URJC</p> <p>Javier Lorente: Assistant Professor at URJC</p> <p>Diego Castellanos: Research Assistant at URJC</p> <p>Roraima Estaba: Research Assistant at URJC</p>
4. Gender	<p>Manuel Tamayo: Male</p> <p>Irene Sánchez-Vítores: Female</p> <p>Javier Lorente: Male</p> <p>Diego Castellanos: Male</p> <p>Roraima Estaba: Female</p>
5. Experience and training	<p>Manuel Tamayo: is a lecturer at different degrees at URJC.. In addition, he is a lecturer in Strategic Management Degree of Public Security (URJC-Ministry of the Interior), and in Master in Public Administration (Menéndez Pelayo University-IUIOG). Specialized in public administration, analysis and evaluation of public policies, welfare policies, urban policies and public opinion on public policies and services. He has participated and participates in different European projects financed by the European Commission and in national projects financed by the Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness. He has been a consultant for different national and foreign institutions in matters related to governance and policy evaluation: Madrid City Hall, Madrid Regional Government, Valencian Regional Government, Castilla la Mancha Regional Government, Ministry of Defense, Ministry of the Interior, Ministry of Social Security and Social Services, Ministry of Housing and Public Infrastructure, Government of the Republic of Cuba, Government of the Dominican Republic, Government of the Republic of Colombia, etc.</p> <p>Irene Sánchez-Vítores: curricular training. She has done methodological training during the PhD although her research has been mainly quantitative during this period. Currently she has done interviews for different COVINFORM WPs.</p> <p>Javier Lorente: curricular training. He has done methodological training during the PhD although his research has been mainly</p>

	<p>quantitative. He has interviewed for COVINFORM, but also for previous H2020 Projects like Perceptions.</p> <p>Diego Castellanos: experience workin in qualitative projects with institutions like Housing First, Fresno Servicios Sociales S.L.. Previous interviews done for COVINFORM.</p> <p>Roraima Estaba: graduated in Political Science. Master degree in Political Science. Master degree in International Cooperation. Postgraduate course in Applied Social Research. Several years working in qualitative research. Professional experience in social project management at national and international level.</p>
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	No previous relationship was established.
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	<p>No previous knowledge. During interviews they were told that interviewers were working for a research project at the University. They were not told details about their interviewers, but they could identify gender, ethnicity and, broadly, age of interviewers.</p> <p>CSOs that acted as entry points to contact interviewees were given more information about the project and the characteristics of the people to be recruited. No information was provided about how much information the CSOs may have provided to possible interview candidates.</p>
8. Interviewer characteristics	Interviewers introduced themselves as researchers doing work for a European research project fielded across several countries.
Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	<p>Grounded theory on social welfare provision and public policy analysis, discourse analyses, content analysis.</p> <p>Socio-ecological systems have also become an overarching methodological approach, guiding the selection of interviewees (institutional actors and citizens).</p>
<i>Participant selection</i>	
10. Sampling	Purposive sample combined with snowballing, both for institutional actors and citizens.
11. Method of approach	Email and telephone to reach out and arrange the interviews.
12. Sample size	- 13 migrants. The sample is composed of thirteen respondents from the two largest migrant communities in Madrid, that is, the Latin American community and the Moroccan community, and

	<p>is divided into 9 (69%) Latin American respondents and 4 (31%) Moroccan respondents. In terms of gender, of the thirteen interviewees, eight are women (62%) and five are men (38%).</p> <p>In addition, interviews were conducted with institutional actors to get a better understanding of the system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 4 policy makers with responsibilities associated with health, social services, and family issues. - 5 practitioners working on these same issues - 5 CSOs working with vulnerable and/or migrant populations.
<p>13. Non-participation</p>	<p>Response rates finally distribute as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resident interviews. The overall response rate is 76%. 17 contacts were made but only 13 agreed to be interviewed. Among Latin American respondents, out of 10 contacts, 9 interviews were recorded (response rate – 90%). Among Moroccan respondents, rates are lower because some contacts did not feel confident enough in their language skills to be interviewed and there were no resources to hire a translator. 7 contacts were made and only 4 interviews recorded (response rate – 57%). - For Decision-makers respondents, the response rate reached 80% (5 contacts, 4 interviews). - For Practitioners, the response rate was 100% (5 contacts, all interviewed). <p>For CSOs, the response rate reached 71% (7 contacts, 5 interviews).</p>
<p><i>Setting</i></p>	
<p>14. Setting of data collection</p>	<p>Through the CSOs that became our entry points, we contacted migrant individuals as potential interviewees, and those who finally agreed were generally interviewed in meeting rooms of these CSOs or exceptionally in cafés of their choice, close to their places of residence or work. The familiarity of these spaces for the interviewees facilitated their trust and openness to talk.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All interviews were conducted in the city of Madrid between February and May 2022.
<p>15. Presence of non-participants</p>	<p>None of the interviewees were accompanied during the interviews.</p>
<p>16. Description of sample</p>	<p>For the citizen sample, main selection criteria were nationality of origin, length of stay in the country (more than 5 years), gender, and income.</p>

	The interviews with institutional actors were based on a convenience sample. Policymakers interviewed are the heads of their services (social services, family affairs, etc.). They pointed to different practitioners that we could interview to learn how the service provision was done during the pandemic. In terms of the CSOs, the institutional actors provided a list of collaborators and we chose from that list a sample out of which contacts were made.
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	<p>Interview guides were designed considering research questions and research interests discussed in previous deliverables. There were two main guides that adapted the same topics to the different actors involved. For instance, when asking about crisis communication, policy makers were asked about how they produced the information, whereas citizens and CSOs were asked about the reception to gather a better understanding of how interactions took place.</p> <p>Each guide contains a beginning section with a brief explanation of the project to be provided to the interviewee prior to the interview, without going into details so as to not bias their answers. Official consent forms and project's info sheets were also administered.</p>
18. Repeat interviews	None.
19. Audio/visual recording	Audio devices: mobile, tape recorder
20. Field notes	Interviews were carried out by two interviewers so that one carried out the interviews and another one took notes and recorded the session.
21. Duration	Between 30-90 minutes.
22. Data saturation	Yes.
23. Transcripts returned	It was not planned. Participants were offered the possibility but they did not ask to do so.
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	
24. Number of data coders	One, although codes have been tested with members of the research team to guarantee validity of codes.
25. Description of the coding tree	Table 1, presented below, describes the themes and subthemes

26. Derivation of themes	Some themes were identified during the design of questionnaires (for instance, those linked to household composition).
27. Software	NVivo
28. Participant checking	It was not planned for participants in the interviews to engage with the findings.
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	In the report to be delivered we will illustrate themes and findings with quotations from the participant interviews. Given that those interviews were conducted in Spanish, the main text will contain a translation of the quotation. Originals will be provided as a footnote; in case it is necessary to use the original.
30. Data and findings consistent	Data analysis shows some consistency with the initial expectations regarding how migrants navigated difficulties during the pandemic. Contrary to expected difficulties to understand the information provided was not only linked to speaking Spanish but also to the cognitive skills and resources available. This may be a product of the sample interviewed, who were all fluent enough in Spanish to answer our questions. But it also provides insight into how communication should be conducted in future crises.
31. Clarity of major themes	Major themes are presented in the findings, in line with the research lines identified in the SES framework.
32. Clarity of minor themes	There was some diversity within the cases but not as much as could have been originally expected.

10. SWANSEA COREQ Checklist

<i>Item</i>	<i>Consideration</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	
Personal Characteristics	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	Which author/s conducted the interview or focus group? Diana Beljaars (Sergei Shubin sometimes joined)
2. Credentials	What were the researcher's credentials? PhD, 10 years of experience in qualitative interviewing of medicalised topics with people socially (not formally ethically) considered vulnerable in that context.

3. Occupation	<p>What was their occupation at the time of the study?</p> <p>Postdoctoral researcher</p>
4. Gender	<p>Was the researcher male or female?</p> <p>Gender: Woman</p> <p>Sex: Female</p>
5. Experience and training	<p>What experience or training did the researcher have?</p> <p>PhD in Human Geography</p>
Relationship with participants	
6. Relationship established	<p>Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?</p> <p>Nurses: Briefly through email contact, although some participants had had a chat with Louise Condon, who has been a nurse: all were offered to have a chat with Louise or Diana.</p> <p>Healthcare managers: On some occasions, a prior connection had been established during a reading group and through gatekeepers</p> <p>Survey respondents: none</p>
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	<p>What did the participants know about the researcher?</p> <p>Interviews: Very little: role in the research, experience with the method, some knew some of my further research background beyond COVINFORM</p> <p>Survey respondents: nothing</p>
8. Interviewer characteristics	<p>What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator?</p> <p>Interviews: My gender, my status as immigrant to Wales, having English as my second language, my education (specialism and doctorate achieved), employment as postdoctoral researcher on this project, and some of my personal pandemic experiences that relate to their experiences</p> <p>Survey respondents: nothing</p>
Domain 2: study design	
Theoretical framework	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	<p>What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study? e.g. grounded theory, discourse analysis, ethnography, phenomenology, content analysis</p>

	Interviews: Phenomenology, discourse analysis Survey: discourse analysis, content analysis
Participant selection	
10. Sampling	How were participants selected? e.g. purposive, convenience, consecutive, snowball Interviews: Purposive sampling via a set of eligibility criteria and distributed via a professional network. Also snowball sampling. Survey: purposive and convenience sampling
11. Method of approach	How were participants approached? e.g. face-to-face, telephone, mail, email Interviews: Via email and face-to-face at events and at the hospital (Louise) Survey: via organisations, personal networks of a collaborator, and in person at shops the sample population was known to frequent.
12. Sample size	How many participants were in the study? (Include also total number of planned interviews per target group and number of interviews conducted so far per target group) 174 in the questionnaire (complete) 16 for the interviews (planned: partially achieved)
13. Non-participation	How many people refused to participate or dropped out? Interviews: 2 Survey respondents: 4
Setting	
14. Setting of data collection	Where was the data collected? Online (interviews and survey) and in the street (survey)
15. Presence of non-participants	Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers? No
16. Description of sample	What are the important characteristics of the sample? Nurses: BAME background, qualified as nurse overseas, having worked in a Swansea hospital during the pandemic, mostly since January 2019 Healthcare managers: White or BAME background, in senior positions in clinical and social care settings in Swansea, having

	<p>worked in these settings in Swansea during the pandemic, mostly since January 2019</p> <p>Survey respondents: BAME background, living in Swansea, Neath, or Port Talbot</p>
Data collection	
17. Interview guide	<p>Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested?</p> <p>Provided to interview participants on request. The list of questions was not pilot tested.</p>
18. Repeat interviews	<p>Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many?</p> <p>no</p>
19. Audio/visual recording	<p>Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?</p> <p>Audio recording of the interviews</p>
20. Field notes	<p>Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group?</p> <p>Yes, sometimes at the interviews</p>
21. Duration	<p>What was the duration of the interviews or focus group?</p> <p>Interviews: 45-90 minutes</p>
22. Data saturation	<p>Was data saturation discussed?</p> <p>Not with participants. Yes amongst researchers</p>
23. Transcripts returned	<p>Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction?</p> <p>No (emission of remarks offered before commencing with the interview)</p>
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
Data analysis	
24. Number of data coders	<p>How many data coders coded the data?</p> <p>1 (Diana)</p>
25. Description of the coding tree	<p>Did authors provide a description of the coding tree?</p> <p>Yes (see coding tree)</p>
26. Derivation of themes	<p>Were themes identified in advance or derived from the data?</p>

	Both (primarily conceptual with adaptations caused by the interview data)
27. Software	What software, if applicable, was used to manage the data? NVIVO
28. Participant checking	Did participants provide feedback on the findings? No
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	Were participant quotations presented to illustrate the themes / findings? Yes
30. Data and findings consistent	Was there consistency between the data presented and the findings? Yes
31. Clarity of major themes	Were major themes clearly presented in the findings? Yes
32. Clarity of minor themes	Is there a description of diverse cases or discussion of minor themes? Both are included in the report

1. SYNYO, Austria

1.1 Translated Citations

Original (German) ¹	English
<p>Es ist quasi wirklich so gedacht, dass die Leute hier ihren eigenen individuell gestaltbaren Wohnraum haben. Ähm, die Grenzen ist halt quasi die Hausordnung, die Hausregeln, also das heißt, was natürlich nicht geht ist Ruhestörung nach 10 Uhr, ähm Gewalt, Diskriminierung, Rassismus, das sind Dinge, die wir im Haus nicht dulden. Das kann reichen von einer Verwarnung bis~, je nach Schwere des Vorfalls, bis hin zu ähm Hausverbot oder sogar Wohnplatzverlust. Wenn es wirklich ganz, also bei Gewaltvorfällen ähm, ist es normalerweise so, dass Wohnplatzverlust im Raum steht (Staff 1).</p>	<p>It is really thought of in such a way that the people here have their own individually designable living space. Um, the limits to this are the house rules, so what that means is that it is not possible to disturb the peace after 10 o'clock p.m., um violence, discrimination, racism, these are things that we do not tolerate in the house. That can range from a warning to~, depending on the severity of the incident, to um a ban from the house or even loss of residence. If it's really~, so in the case of incidents of violence, um, it's usually the case that loss of living space is possible (Staff 1).</p>
<p>[...] Finanziell, also um die materielle Grundsicherung, wie das so schön heißt. Das heißt, wir schauen, dass die Leute auch das Geld kriegen, was ihnen auch zusteht (Staff 1).</p>	<p>[...] Financially, also the basic material security, as it is called. That means, we make sure the people receive the money that they are entitled to (Staff 1).</p>
<p>Genau, also das, was schon auffällig ist, wie viele Leute hier~ also in der Wohnungslosigkeit generell gesundheitliche Probleme haben, sei es jetzt psychisch oder physisch (Staff 1).</p>	<p>Exactly, so what's already striking is how many people here~ so in homelessness in general have health problems, whether it's mentally or physically (Staff 1).</p>
<p>Und was für uns die große Sorge war, ist, dass es ebenso viele vulnerable Personengruppen im Haus gibt und, da die Befürchtung war, dass wenn wir uns anstecken und das ins Haus tragen, dass dann halt viele Infektionen und vielleicht sogar viele Todesfälle gibt. Das war so die Befürchtung am Anfang. Und, wenn man das sich jetzt im Nachhinein anschaut, hat das aber eben erstaunlich gut funktioniert, dass das nicht passiert ist. Ähm, das was eher problematisch war und jetzt auch noch immer ist, sind die Folgen der sozialen Isolation (Staff 1)</p>	<p>And the biggest concern for us was that there are just so many vulnerable groups of people in the house, and the fear was that if we become infected and spread it in the house, there will be many infections and perhaps even many deaths. So that was the fear at the beginning. And, if you look at it now in retrospect, it worked amazingly well, that it [the spread of the virus] didn't happen. Um, what was rather problematic, and still is, are the consequences of social isolation (Staff 1).</p>
<p>I: Aber von welcher Stelle kamen die dann? B: Teilweise intern, teilweise war es ganz klar, dass es über die Regelungen passiert ist, die von der Regierung vorgegeben wurde äh und teilweise haben wir ja noch strengere Regelungen gehabt, als die Regierung vorgegeben hat. Aber das war auch von Phase zu Phase unterschiedlich. Aber, zum Beispiel, als die Maskenpflicht schon aufgehoben war zum Schluss, haben wir sie im Haus noch getragen, zum Beispiel. I: Ah, wirklich? B: Also wir haben das noch hinausgezögert, dieses Ende, und das war dann eine organisationsinterne interne Regel, dann, zum Beispiel (Staff 1).</p>	<p>I: But from where did they [the measures, rules and regulations] come then? B: Partly internally, partly it was quite clear that it happened through the regulations that were given by the government and partly we had even stricter regulations than the government had given. But that also varied from phase to phase. But, for example, when the obligation to wear masks was lifted at the end, we still wore them in the house, for example. I: Ah, really? B: Well, we delayed the end of it, and that was an internal rule of the organisation, for example (Staff 1).</p>
<p>Es war~, da war auch ein großer Denkprozess dahinter wie man das gestalten können, damit es möglichst sicher ist für</p>	<p>It was~, there was also a big though process behind how this [the regulations] could be realized, so that it would be</p>

¹ Citations are listed in the order they appear in.

<p>alle und vor allem, als es noch gar keine Masken und keine Sichtschutz oder sonst was gegeben hat. Ähm, Desinfektionsmittel war schwierig, das ist an die Rettung gegangen, die erste Zeit. Haben wir haushalten müssen. Und es war einfach die Angst, die überall war, weil ich bin ja genauso ein Mensch, der davon noch nie etwas gehört hat, so wie alle anderen. Ähm, und du gehst dann halt arbeiten so wie immer, aber es ist nicht wie immer, du denkst dir: "Ich habe auch furchtbare Angst davor. Vielleicht sterbe ich und was ist wenn es sich im Haus verbreitet?" Das war die größte Angst von uns, dass sich das~, im Haus wenn es ins Rollen kommt, dass es unstopppable ist. Ist aber nicht passiert (Staff 2).</p>	<p>as safe as possible for everyone and this especially when there were no masks at all and no privacy screens or anything. Um, disinfectant was difficult, it went to the rescue service at the beginning. So we had to economize it. And it was simply the fear that was everywhere, because I am just as much a person who has never heard of it, like everyone else. Um, and then you just go to work like always, but it's not like always, you think to yourself: "I'm also terribly afraid of it. Maybe I'll die and what if it spreads in the house?" That was the biggest fear of ours, that it~, in the house when it gains momentum, that it's unstoppable. But it did not happen (Staff 2).</p>
<p>Nein, das Einzige, was mit dazu einfällt ist, ganz am Anfang von der Pandemie, habe wir alle geglaubt, dass es da drinnen sofort ausbrechen wird. Und wir waren eines der letzten Häuser, wo die Leute COVID gehabt haben. Das war im letzten Jahr. Also, so super hat das ganze Haus darauf geachtet, jetzt nicht nur die Betreuer, sondern auch teilweise die Bewohner, dass das nicht~ sogar die Heimhilfen haben Angst gehabt, dass das gleich ausbrechen wird und so, weil es sind halt ein paar Leute hier drinnen, die haben keine Maske getragen und keinen Abstand gehalten. Die sind am Praterstern zu den Freunden gefahren oder dorthin oder so. Und da haben wir geglaubt, dann wird das da gleich drinnen sein (Inhabitant 3).</p>	<p>No, the only thing that comes to my mind is, at the very beginning of the pandemic, we all believed that it was going to break out right away in there. And we were one of the last houses where people had COVID. That only happened last year. So, the whole house paid attention to it, not only the staff, but also partly the residents, so that~ even the home helpers were afraid that it would break out immediately and so, because there are a few people in here, who did not wear a mask and didn't keep distance. They went to their friends at Praterstern or somewhere or so. And we believed that it would spread in here immediately (Inhabitant 3).</p>
<p>Ähm, es war schwierig den Leuten die Maskenpflicht, die dann gekommen ist, also das durchzusetzen. Da hat sich auch immer wieder die Frage gestellt [...] wie soll man es durchsetzen, es ist im Grunde, ich bin nicht die Polizei, ich bin nicht ein Richter, aber es ist halt im Sinne von allen da im Haus, wenn da alle mitziehen. Dann hat es die Verschwörungstheorien gegeben, dass das alles nur n Schaß ist, und das ist ja nur ein Schnupfen und eine Grippe und das war~, das war eine Ultrahauptbeschäftigung, eine Zeit lang diese Maskenpflicht durchzusetzen. (Staff 2)</p>	<p>Um, it was difficult to enforce, among the people, the obligation to wear a mask, which then came- There was always the question [...] how to enforce it, it's basically, I'm not the police, I'm not a judge, but it's just in the interest of everybody in the house, if everyone goes along with it. Then there were the conspiracy theories that it's [Covid-19] all just bullshit and it's just a cold and a flu and that was~, that was extremely time consuming, to enforce this mask requirement for a while (Staff 2).</p>
<p>Ich meine bei gewissen Sachen trage ich es auch, ist eh klar. Wenn zu viele Leute sind oder wenn du weißt die sind jetzt nicht sauber oder so irgendwas. Da trage ich sie ja auch. Aber ansonsten möchte ich mich frei fühlen, ich will Mensch sein (Inhabitant 5).</p>	<p>I mean at certain times I wear it [the mask] too, it's obvious. When there are too many people or when you know they're not clean or something. Then I wear it too. But otherwise I want to feel free, I want to be human (Inhabitant 5).</p>
<p>[...] weil es sind halt ein paar Leute hier drinnen, die haben keine Maske getragen und keinen Abstand gehalten (Inhabitant 3).</p>	<p>[...] but there are some people in here that didn't wear mask and didn't keep distance (Inhabitant 3).</p>
<p>Es waren eher so die Sachen, die dann verhängt wurden vom Staat oder so, Ausgangssperre und so weiter, das kannst du halt mit schwer psychiatrischen Menschen nicht umsetzen, das spielt es nicht (Staff 2).</p>	<p>It was rather the things that were imposed by the state or so, mandatory confinement and so on, you just can't implement that with severely mentally ill people, that doesn't work (Staff 2).</p>
<p>12: Gibt es irgendwas für das Sie besonders dankbar sind</p>	<p>12: Is there something that you are especially thankful for,</p>

<p>hier im Haus? Während der Pandemie so quasi?</p> <p>IP: Ich bin sehr dankbar, dass ich da bin (Inhabitant 5).</p>	<p>here in the house? During the pandemic and so?</p> <p>B: I am very thankful to be here (Inhabitant 5).</p>
<p>Naja, da habe ich viel zum dankbar sein. Ich bin dankbar, dass ich da sein darf, dass ich da wirklich gut aufgenommen bin. Und dass die Betreuer so hinter mir stehen, dass ich weiß, wenn irgendwelche Probleme sind, sind das die Ersten, die da sind (Inhabitant 4).</p>	<p>Well, I have a lot to be thankful for. I am thankful for being allowed to be here, that I am really well received. And that the caregivers are so supportive that I know that if I have any problems, they will be the first ones there (Inhabitant 4)</p>
<p>I: Also haben Sie~. Wie ist Ihr Verhältnis mit Ihrer Betreuerin? Gut?</p> <p>B: Ja. [...] Es war sogar eine Ärztin im Haus, Psychiaterin war da wegen meinen Depressionen, Medikamente und so. [...]</p> <p>I: Und geht es Ihnen dann jetzt schon wieder besser?</p> <p>B: Ja, jetzt ist ok. Bisschen, aber manchmal kommt die Traurigkeit, ich weiß nicht warum. Aber als die Corona-Zeit war, das war für mich sehr traurig, sehr schlecht (Inhabitant 8).</p>	<p>I: How is your relationship with your supervisor? Good?</p> <p>B: Yes. [...] There was even a doctor in the house, a psychiatrist was here because of my depression, medicine and so on. [...]</p> <p>I: And now you are feeling better already?</p> <p>B: Yes, now it's ok. A bit, but sometimes the sadness comes back, I don't know why. But during the Covid-time, it was very sad for me, very bad (Inhabitant 8).</p>
<p>I: Und also, Sie haben gesagt, Sie vertrauen den Mitarbeiter*innen vom Haus eigentlich sehr?</p> <p>B: Ja, die Angestelltengruppe, also da gibt es überhaupt keine Probleme, die sind sehr höflich und sehr nett und sie verstehen~. [...]</p> <p>I: Eine Frage noch, warum vertrauen Sie den Leuten, den Angestellten hier? Also, das frage ich nicht, warum, aber was haben die Gutes gemacht, dass sie sich Ihr Vertrauen gewonnen haben?</p> <p>B: Erstens einmal, das Vertrauen kommt einmal auf einer Basis rüber, wie man mit den Leuten umgeht (Inhabitant 6).</p>	<p>I: And so, you said that you trust the staff of the house a lot?</p> <p>B: Yes, the staff, so there are actually no problems, they are really friendly and very nice and they understand~. [...]</p> <p>I: One more question, why do you trust the people, the staff here? [...] so, what good did they do that they gained your trust?</p> <p>B: First of all, trust comes across on a basis of how you deal with people (Inhabitant 6).</p>
<p>B: Erstens einmal, das Vertrauen kommt einmal auf einer Basis rüber, wie man mit den Leuten umgeht.</p> <p>I: Mhm, ok.</p> <p>B: Der kommt nicht und, der redet halt ume, redet auf Augenhöhe, was einmal schon viel ist. Wenn einer umme: "Ich bin Sozialarbeiter, ich bin das." Nein, komm auf Augenhöhe den Leuten entgegen und du redest, es kommt ganz anders umme.</p>	<p>First of all, the trust comes from how you treat people. [...] He [the social worker] talks with you as if you be equal to him, which is already a lot (Inhabitant 6).</p>
<p>[...] ewiges eingesperrt sein. Das allein sein. Und ja, wenn man nicht wirklich~ am Anfang hat man halt wirklich Angst gehabt, wie das ausgebrochen ist. Ob das wirklich so extrem ansteckend ist, ob wirklich so viele sterben [...] (Inhabitant 5).</p>	<p>[...] being eternally locked-in. Being alone. And yes, if you don't really~ at the beginning you were just really afraid, after it had broken out. Whether it's really so extremely contagious, whether really so many people will die [...] (Inhabitant 5).</p>

Und auf Deutsch gesagt, haben wir uns meistens niedergesoffen (Inhabitant 3).	And to be honest, we just drank a lot most of the time (Inhabitant 3).
Viele sind verstorben. Weggezogen. Der eine, der Liebe ist nach Deutschland mit seiner neuen Freundin. Einer sitzt im Hefn, weil er einen schweren Raub begangen hat. Trafikraub (Inhabitant 5).	Many died. Moved away. This one, the nice one moved to Germany with his new girlfriend. One is in prison because he committed an aggravated robbery (Inhabitant 5).
Und dann war das Corona für mich sehr, wie soll ich sagen, sehr schwer, weil ich konnte nicht zu meinen Kindern gehen [...] (Inhabitant 8).	And then Corona was for me, how should I say, very difficult, because I couldn't go to my children [...] (Inhabitant 8).
I: Sie haben sich auch nicht allein gefühlt? IP: Nein (Inhabitant 1).	I: You didn't feel alone? B: No (Inhabitant 1).
Ich gehe ja sowieso nicht viel hinaus, wegen meiner Psyche. Und für mich war der Lockdown jetzt nicht das Schlimmste (Inhabitant 3).	I don't go outside that much anyway, because of my mental state. And for me the lockdown wasn't the worst thing (Inhabitant 3).
Ich habe alles gehabt, was Gott verboten hat. Den vollen Verlauf. Ich bin eine Woche gelegen und ich habe nicht einmal mehr gewusst, ob ich ein Männchen oder ein Weibchen bin, teilweise. Das Einzige, was mich bewogen hat mich irgendwie zu bewegen, waren die Katzen, weil die haben ja Futter gebraucht. Gut ich habe immer viel daheim, ich habe es nicht einkaufen gehen müssen, aber trotzdem muss ich sie füttern, frisches Wasser, Kiste vollmachen. Das war für mich Schwerarbeit, das, was ich normalerweise aus dem FF gemacht habe.	I have had everything that God has forbidden. The full course. I lay down for a week and I didn't even know anymore if I was a male or a female, partly. The only thing that made me move in any way were the cats, because they needed food. Well, I always have a lot at home, I didn't have to go shopping, but still I have to feed them, fresh wa-ter, fill up the box. That was hard work for me (Inhabitant 3).
I: Und das heißt, wie ging es Ihnen? Haben Sie sich allein oder einsam gefühlt? B: Nein. Nur als ich eingesperrt war, zehn Tage. Aber da muss ich auch sagen, da ist mir eigentlich gut gegangen, weil ich bin ja da in dieser Gruppe so drinnen, ja. Der XXXX hat mich jeden Tag angerufen, hat gefragt „XXXX, brauchst du was? Soll ich dir was bringen?“ Also ich war nicht allein (Inhabitant 4).	I: And that means, how were you? Did you feel alone or lonely? B: No. Just when I was locked in ten days. But I also have to say that I was actually fine, because I'm in this group, yes. XXXX called me every day, asked "XXXX, do you need anything? Do you want me to bring you something?" So I was not alone (Inhabitant 4).
Wir haben definitiv niemanden gezwungen, wir haben Infos bereits gestellt, wir haben~, ja wir haben Infos bereitgestellt und was das bedeutet und wo du halt hingehen kannst und den Rest muss jeder selber für sich entscheiden. Also wir haben niemanden gezwungen (Staff 2).	We definitely didn't force anybody, we provided the information, we did, yes we provided information like where you can go and regarding the rest everybody has to decide for themselves. So we didn't force anybody (Staff 2).
Oder der Chef des Hauses. Wenn der irgendwas gesagt hat, das war für mich auch Sache, ja. Weil das ist ein sehr bedachter Mensch und dem kann man auch das glauben, was er erzählt. Zu 100 Prozent (Inhabitant 3).	Or the manager of the house. If he said something, that was also a matter for me, yes. Because he is a very thoughtful person and you can believe what he says. 100 percent (Inhabitant 3).
Ja, wir wurden ewig informiert [von der Organisation]. Immer wieder was Neues. Maske tragen, kommt ein neuer Virus, komm ein alter Virus, Maske tragen, Hände waschen, nicht zusammensitzen. Das hat das Haus gemacht. Die haben uns gesagt was los ist, was wir wie machen sollen (Inhabitant_4).	Yes, we were informed constantly [by the organisation]. Always something new. To wear the mask, that a new virus is spreading, an old virus is spreading, to wear a mask, to wash your hands, to not sit together. That's what the house did. They told us what was going on, what we should do and how (Inhabitant 4).

<p>Nein, da fragt man sich schon, wenn du über das nachdenkst, was hat das für einen Sinn, wenn du beim Billa eine Maske aufsetzt, dann gehst du zwei Geschäfte weiter, weil du in den DM einkaufen gehst und dort brauchst du keine Maske. Ich muss in der Apotheke eine Maske aufsetzen. Ein Geschäft weiter ist der Frick, die Buchhandlung, da kaufe ich meine Kreuzworträtsel und dort brauche ich keine Maske. Also, das COVID-Virus, weiß ganz genau, wo es reindarf und wo nicht. Ja, ist ja unlogisch (Inhabitant 4).</p>	<p>No, but you do ask yourself, if you think about it, what's the point, if you put on a mask at the Billa [local supermarket chain], then you go two stores further because you're shopping at the DM and you don't need a mask there. I have to put on a mask at the pharmacy. The store next to it is the Frick, the bookstore, that's where I buy my crossword puzzles and I don't need a mask there. So, the COVID virus, it knows exactly where to go in and where not to go in. Yes, it's illogical (Inhabitant 4).</p>
<p>Obwohl das zu 90 Prozent gestimmt hat, wie er das weitererzählt hat. Er hat halt immer ein bisschen was dazu gedichtet, weil er eben ein Leugner ist. Aber sonst hat es gepasst</p>	<p>Although what he told us was 90 percent true. He just always added somethings [that were not true], because he's a denier. But otherwise it was fine... (Inhabitant_3).</p>
<p>Für mich war das jetzt zum Beispiel egal, ob das Virus jetzt so oder so heißt, weil da hat es ja jetzt noch eins gegeben. Ich weiß jetzt nicht wie das heißt. Eine Zeit lang habe ich es gewusst, aber dann habe ich gesagt, ich beschäftige mich nicht mehr damit. Und mir war das egal, wie das heißt. Für mich war das nur eins, es ist gefährlich. Und da brauche ich nicht, das heißt jetzt dann Lieselotte oder Aaron oder weiß ich nicht wie. Das interessiert mich dann nicht. Also was das anrichtet, das ist für mich relevant, sage ich jetzt einmal (Inhabitant 3).</p>	<p>For me, for example, it didn't matter whether the virus is called one thing or another, because there's been another one now. I don't know what it's called. For a while, I knew, but then I said I'm not going to engage with it anymore. And I didn't care what it's called. To me, it's just one thing, it's dangerous. And I don't need it to be named Lieselotte or Aaron or whatever. That doesn't interest me. So, what it's causing, that's what's relevant to me, I would say. (Inhabitant 3)</p>

2. UANTWERPEN, Belgium

No additional annexes.

3. MDI, England

No additional annexes.

4. SINUS, Germany & UGOT, Sweden

4.1 Codebook: Impact of the pandemic and protective measures

Communication

Activities

Under this category coding of concrete measures related to communication are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

Mentions of using classical media

Avoiding news

Communication with friends and family

Communication with CSOs

Communication with HCWs

Communication with public sector institutions

ICT - Active (WhatsApp, Zoom, etc.)

ICT - Passive (Google, etc.)

Foreign media
Misinformation other

Communication

Perceptions

Under this category coding of perceptions related to communication are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

Conspiracy theories
Confusion about measures, risks, etc.
Trust / distrust in official information
Differences in information
Feeling sufficiently informed
Feeling insufficiently informed
Lack of information in other languages (Other than domestic language)
Lack of information in general

Social

Activities

Under this category coding of concrete measures related to social activities are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

Arts and culture
Communal activities
Cease contact with friends, family
Maintain contact with friends, family
Conflicts with authorities
Hobbies / other activities
Mutual support
Volunteering
School closures (children or self)

Social

Perceptions

Under this category, coding of perceptions related to social activities are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

Coexisting crises / social problems
Feeling of abnormality / normality
Feeling of communal responsibility
Feeling of paternalism / lack of participation
Feeling of loneliness / isolation
Feeling of social division
Perceptions living space (Apartment, house)

Perceptions of neighbourhood / city

Perceptions of vaccine rejectors, conspiracy supporters, etc.

Economic *Activities*

Under this category, coding of concrete measures related to the economy are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

Missing / losing work / education

Overwork

Working / studying from home

Unable to work from home

Economic *Perceptions*

Under this category coding of perceptions related to economy are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

Impact on local businesses, etc.

Impact on personal finances

Health *Activities*

Under this category coding of concrete measures related to health are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

Hygiene

Mask wearing

Testing

Social distancing

Unable / unwilling to follow regulations

Health *Perceptions*

Under this category coding of perceptions related to health are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

Belief / disbelief in severity of pandemic

Perceived risk to self / others

Role models

Perceptions about vaccine

Perceptions about immunity

Other *Vulnerabilities*

Under this category coding of other recurring themes related to vulnerabilities of self or others are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

COVID illness - friends, family, others

COVID illness - self

Discrimination / inequality – age

Discrimination / inequality - ethnic

Discrimination / inequality - gender

Discrimination / inequality - SES

Feeling worried / scared

Feeling of indifference

Health vulnerability

Mental health

Perceptions of measures

Perceptions of vulnerability

Pregnancy

Preparedness

Other *Support*

Under this category coding of other recurring themes related to giving or receiving support are coded.

The following subcategories have been coded under this section:

Need for support

Support measures - CSOs

Support measures - HCWs

Support measures - municipal

Support measures - mutual aid

4.2 SES Framework & Codes

Under this section coding the SES framework has been compared and integrated with the codes from the previous categories.

Code	Count	Cases	% Cases	Second-tier	(ECO)	(S)	(RS) & (RU)	(GS)	(A)	(I)	(O)
Activities - Communications											
Avoiding news	7	2	7,1%	A8					x		
Classical media	113	27	96,4%	RS1, I9			x				

This is the socio-demographic and COVID-19 status questionnaire research findings, completed by ten (10) participants of KEMEA’s case study within the context of the COVINFORM project. No personal identifiers are being reported on this form (i.e., name or date of birth) whereas all information acquired, is conducted in consideration with GDPR and ethical rules.

The participants in this study were informed that the information collected will be reported at group level to describe the overall study population. Personal details will not be presented with in interview transcripts and findings. The participants retain the right to refuse to answer any questions with no consequence on their participation in the study, and are indicated as N/A.

Study ID: KEMEA Case Study

▪ SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION																													
<p>1. Age at time of interview (years) – In the case study of KEMEA, five (5) members of Minority groups and five (5) Law Enforcement Agents participate. The average rate in relation to the minority sample is 34,8 while 39 is the average rate for the LEA participants. Concluding, the average age for both groups in relation to their age is 36,9 years.</p>																													
<p>Age of participants at the time of the interview</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Data for Age of participants at the time of the interview</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Participant 1</th> <th>Participant 2</th> <th>Participant 3</th> <th>Participant 4</th> <th>Participant 5</th> <th>Average Rate</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Minorities</td> <td>30</td> <td>36</td> <td>34</td> <td>26</td> <td>48</td> <td>34.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Law Enforcement Agents</td> <td>46</td> <td>45</td> <td>38</td> <td>35</td> <td>31</td> <td>39</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td colspan="5"></td> <td>36.9</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Category	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4	Participant 5	Average Rate	Minorities	30	36	34	26	48	34.8	Law Enforcement Agents	46	45	38	35	31	39	Total						36.9
Category	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4	Participant 5	Average Rate																							
Minorities	30	36	34	26	48	34.8																							
Law Enforcement Agents	46	45	38	35	31	39																							
Total						36.9																							
<p>2. Gender – In this case study, 9 participants identified as Male and 1 participant identified as female.</p>																													
<table border="1"> <caption>Data for Gender Distribution</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Group</th> <th>Identifies as Male</th> <th>Identifies as Female</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>90%</td> <td>10%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Minorities</td> <td>80%</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Law Enforcement Agents</td> <td>100%</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Group	Identifies as Male	Identifies as Female	Total	90%	10%	Minorities	80%	20%	Law Enforcement Agents	100%	0%																
Group	Identifies as Male	Identifies as Female																											
Total	90%	10%																											
Minorities	80%	20%																											
Law Enforcement Agents	100%	0%																											
<p>3. Place of Birth – In total, all LEA participants have been born in Greece whereas, similar to 60% of Minority group members. Only 20% of the total participants have been born in a different country, specifically Germany and Albania.</p>																													

HOUSEHOLD AND MARITAL STATUS

4. Where do you currently live? – In this case study, participants were inquired to indicate their current resident. In total, 60% of the participants live in Athens, the capital city of Greece while 40% live in Thessaloniki, which is the second biggest city in Greece.

5. How long have you lived in Greece (years)? – The research findings based on the acquired socio-demographic data and in comparison to *Age at time of interview (years)* indicate that Law Enforcement Agents have resided in Greece the majority of their lives, whereas some Minority group members have spent a considerable amount of time living abroad.

6. What is your first language (mother tongue)? – All Law Enforcement Agents present a homogenous sample regarding their native language. Most of the participants in Minority groups have Greek as their first language, while some participants also indicated German and Albanian.

7. Do you speak any other languages? – Based on the following data, the participants of the minority groups, in total and as a group, are able to communicate in an additional six (7) languages, namely: English, German, Greek, French, Serbian, Spanish, Roma-Romani. On the contrary, the group of Law Enforcement agents that participate in this study are able to communicate in three (3) languages, besides their native language, namely: English, French, Italian.

8. How would you describe your living arrangement? – Most of the minority group participants indicated that they have no fixed address and/or have a temporary residence (60%), while only 40% have a private household (20%) or share accommodation (20%). In contrast, the vast majority of the Law Enforcement Agents in our study suggest to live in a private household (80%) while only 20% share their accommodation. In general, half of the participants own a private household whereas 30% have no fixed address and 20% live in a shared accommodation.

9. How many people, including children, live in your household? – The rate of 1,8 residents is observed in the households of minority group members and 3,75 in Law Enforcement Agents' households. The average in relation to the residents in all of the participants' households is 2,67.

10. (A) Do you have children? (B) If yes, how many children do you have and (C) how many live at home? – In our study, most Minority group participants are observed to not have children (80%) while one participant suggested that none of his 4 children live at his household. On the other hand, most Law Enforcement Agents (60%) suggested to have between 1 and 3 children while all of them still live at home.

11. What is your Marital Status? – Most of the minority members in our sample are identified to not be married and/or single (80%) while only 20% declared to be married. On the other hand, 60% of our LEA participants suggested to be married while 40% have never been married. The total responses appear to be balanced between the married participants and individuals that have never been married.

• EDUCATION STATUS

12. Highest level of education completed? – There is a high number of Master degree graduates in the minority group sample in our case study, while a 20% (one of five) respondent suggested to have completed a Secondary level of education. On the other hand, Law Enforcement Agents appear to have completed Post-secondary education (40%), possess one or more Bachelor degree(s) (40%) and at least one respondent has a Master Degree (20%).

• EMPLOYMENT STATUS

13. What is your employment status? – All participants in our study are identified to be employed.

14. What is/was the name or title of your main job? – As expected, the main title of employment for LEAs is police officer, whereas 40% of minority participants suggested to be working in the field of education, 20% suggested to be engaged in research, while 40% declared to be working in Sales industry (20%) and/or own his/her own business (20%).

15. How would you describe your work environment? – All of the Law Enforcement Agent respondents suggested to work on-site, similarly to 60% of minority participants while the remaining respondents (40%) indicated a hybrid form of working which combines both remote and on-site employment.

16. What type of employment do you currently have? – It can be observed that in our case study, all Law Enforcement Agents have permanent employment while 40% of minority participants are on a fixed term contract, 40% on a non-fixed term contract while 20% are on self-employment status.

17. During the COVID-19 pandemic, would you suggest that your type and role of employment can be considered as “essential employment”? (i.e. healthcare workers such as pharmacists, healthcare experts such as doctors, Supermarket employees etc). – The vast majority of the Law Enforcement Agents (80%) consider themselves to be essential workers during the pandemic, particularly in persevering peace and order whereas 60% of the minority groups consider their role as “essential”, particularly participants working in educational institutions. Minority groups underlined the significance of educators during COVID-19 and the negative psychological consequences on children’s well-being, as a result of the pandemic.

18. What is your main source of income? – The majority of the respondents in both groups (100% LEAs and 80% Minority group participants) suggested that their main income derives from monthly salary, while only 20% (one of five) Minority respondents suggested their income is generated from self-employment activities.

COVID-19 STATUS

19. Are you vaccinated against COVID-19? – All of the Law Enforcement Agents that participate in this study have declared to be fully vaccinated in comparison to 60% of the minority group participants. 20% of the minority participants suggested to have been partially vaccinated and 20% of the same group suggested to be unvaccinated.

20. Have you been infected by the coronavirus? – The vast majority of the respondents in both groups suggested to have been infected by COVID-19 at some period during the pandemic, with the exception of a single respondent in the LEA group of participants (10% of the overall responses).

• SOCIAL STATUS (TRUST & INTERACTION)

21. Do you consider yourself a member of “vulnerable groups” regarding COVID-19? – Based on the responses, the majority of (60%) minority group participants identify themselves as members of vulnerable groups in relation to COVID-19, while on the contrary, the majority of Law Enforcement Agents (80%) do not consider themselves as vulnerable during the COVID-19 pandemic.

22. If yes, how would you define your vulnerability? – 40% the participants in the *Minority group* determined this question is not applicable in their case (N/A). One respondent of the same group suggested to experience mental vulnerability, whereas another experiences a combination of social and physical. The last participant suggested to experience both social, economic and physical vulnerability as he is identified as a Low Socio-economic status citizen who is challenged by long-term heart disease. In relation to *Law Enforcement Agents*, 75% of the participants suggested this question is not applicable in their case (N/A) while 25% indicated social vulnerability. (Kindly note: 3 of 5 *Minority participants* define themselves as vulnerable in comparison to 1 of 5 *LEAs*. 2 of 5 *Minority* suggested N/A, while 1 of 5 *LEA* does not define himself as vulnerable and 3 of 5 *LEAs* suggested this question is not applicable in his case).

23. Do you work in different geographical locations? – 40% of the minority participants in this study and 60% of the LEAs work in more than one geographical location. Specifically, several respondents suggested to be working in a combination of geographical locations (i.e. On respondent from the minorities group on local & regional level, another on national & international level, a LEA on local & national level) while the vast majority of both groups indicated to be working on a local geographical level, 60% for Minority participants and 80% for LEA participants respectively.

24. Do you usually travel to your place of employment? – In both samples, 60% of the participants travel to their place of work while 40% do not.

25. If yes, how? Did it change during the pandemic? – In relation to the means of transport, most participants in both groups utilize private means. Minorities still continue to use public transport, several respondents from both groups demonstrated reluctance in responding to this question.

26. Do you consider yourself to be in a physical and/or mental state that hinders you to conduct daily your activities? (“WHODAS 2.0” covers 6 Domains of Functioning) – Based on the responses from all participants, only 10% (one of 10 participants – 20% in the Minorities group) suggests to be defined with a disability (Mobility) that hinders his every day activities.

27. Do you consider that your level of social interactions and trust towards Minority groups (i.e. Roma, refugees, migrants etc), healthcare professionals (i.e. doctors), governmental representatives and/or Law Enforcement Agents (politicians, police officers etc) have changed during COVID-19? If yes, with which socio-demographic group and to what degree? – More than half of the minority groups participants (60%) indicate that their social interactions and trust has not changed in contrast with 60% of LEA that adopt the exact opposite views. Moreover, despite the fact that at least half of the total participants in both groups are observed to be reluctant in specifying with which socio-demographic group, social interactions and trust have been impacted (particularly 60% participants from Minority groups and 40% participants from Law Enforcement Agencies), LEAs and Minorities indicate positive and negative impacts with all three socio-demographic groups (namely: Governmental representatives

& LEAs, Minorities, Healthcare experts). Most LEAs (60%) indicate a significant impact in their social interactions and trust with the aforementioned groups. On the contrary, 40% minority participants suggest a high level of change while 60% indicate zero to minimum changes. From the minority participants' perspective, social interactions and trust with (40%) Governmental representatives & LEAs and (20%) healthcare professionals, are negatively impacted. Only 20% of the minority respondents suggest their interactions are more positively impacted with healthcare professionals during the pandemic. On the other hand, from a Law Enforcement Agent perspective, their social interactions with minorities were negatively impacted on a 60% rate, while on a smaller percentage their interactions and trust towards governmental representatives & fellow colleagues as well as healthcare professionals was impacted by a 20% rate for each group respectively.

Degree of change in social interactions and trust

Minority participants' perception changes in their level of social interaction and trust with other socio-demographic groups

Law Enforcement Agents' perception changes in their level of social interaction and trust with other socio-demographic groups

6. SAPIENZA & UCSC, Italy

6.1 Descriptives

6.1.1 Descriptive for Gender

Age class

Age class	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
20-29years old	11.87	6.58	10.76
30-39years old	16.23	24.34	17.93
40-49years old	28.97	30.26	29.24
50-59years old	36.30	25.66	34.07
60and plus	6.63	13.16	8.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Partner

Do you have a Partner	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	42.58	32.89	40.55
Yes	57.42	67.11	59.45
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Citizenship

Citizenship	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Italian	99.12	100.00	99.31
Foreign	0.88	0.00	0.69
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Education level

Education level	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Elementary school	1.93	3.29	2.21
High school	22.94	17.11	21.72
Bachelor	46.23	33.55	43.57
Master	12.26	10.53	11.89
Post-graduate	16.64	35.53	20.61
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

N inhabitants

Inhabitants	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
1	18.15	19.08	18.34
2	22.51	25.00	23.03
3	24.26	19.08	23.17
4	24.78	26.32	25.10

5	7.16	8.55	7.45
6	2.44	0.66	2.07
7	0.52	0.66	0.55
9	0.17	0.00	0.14
10	0.00	0.66	0.14
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Family member care

Currently taking care of a disabled/dependent family member (cohabiting or not).	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	76.76	78.29	77.08
Yes, rarely	4.40	4.61	4.44
Yes, at least once a week	7.04	9.21	7.50
Yes, every day	11.80	7.89	10.97
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Currently care elderly

Currently caring for an elderly family member (cohabiting or non-cohabiting)	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	63.40	62.50	63.21
Yes, rarely	8.23	11.84	8.99
Yes, at least once a week	15.94	17.11	16.18
Yes, every day	12.43	8.55	11.62
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Healthcare profession

Actual Healthcare profession	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Other	9.60	9.21	9.52
Healthcare assistant	3.49	7.89	4.41
Nurse	67.19	34.87	60.41
Doctor	11.87	34.21	16.55
Midwife	2.97	0.00	2.34
Other sanitary profession	4.54	6.58	4.97
Radiology technician	0.35	7.24	1.79
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Average hours worked per week

On average, how many hours do you work per week?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Less than 36h	8.73	1.99	7.32
36-39h	68.06	56.29	65.61
40-48h	17.45	29.14	19.89
More than 48h	5.76	12.58	7.18
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Different Job Phase 1

Phase 1: You were employed in a different service.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	75.83	75.33	75.73
Yes	24.17	24.67	24.27
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Emotionally finished Phase 1

Phase 1: Emotionally exhausted between 1-5.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
1	8.14	14.09	9.38
2	11.86	17.45	13.03
3	25.84	30.87	26.89
4	29.38	22.15	27.87
5	24.78	15.44	22.83
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Tired day work Phase 1

Phase 1: Tired of having to face another working day in 1-5.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
1	8.60	18.00	10.59
2	12.37	12.67	12.43
3	25.45	25.33	25.42
4	29.93	28.00	29.52
5	23.66	16.00	22.03
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Patients as objects Phase 1

Phase 1: I seemed to treat patients as objects between 1-5.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
1	58.23	55.48	57.65
2	13.38	15.75	13.88
3	13.20	14.38	13.45
4	6.69	9.59	7.30
5	8.50	4.79	7.73
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Work department Covid

Do you work/have you worked in a Covid-19 department?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	48.95	54.61	50.14
Yes, now	12.63	18.42	13.85
Yes, in the past not now	38.42	26.97	36.01
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Work department Covid spec

Please specify whether you work/have worked in (during Covid-19):	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Outpatient	6.94	7.46	7.04
Ordinary/sub-intensive care	58.33	52.24	57.18
Intensive care/critical care	34.72	40.30	35.77
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Asthenia Covid-19

If you had Covid-19, did you have as a consequence: Asthenia	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	70.86	81.58	73.10
Yes	29.14	18.42	26.90
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Consequence mental Covid-19

If you had Covid-19, did you have as a consequence mental confusion	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	83.25	94.74	85.66
Yes	16.75	5.26	14.34
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Muscular pains Covid-19

If you had Covid-19, did you have as a consequence Muscular pains	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	80.28	90.13	82.34
Yes	19.72	9.87	17.66
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Paraesthesia Covid-19

If you had Covid-19, did you have as a consequence Paraesthesia	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	94.59	96.71	95.03
Yes	5.41	3.29	4.97
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Consequences Covid-19

Consequences of Covid on your health for more than one month after testing posit	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	43.66	55.26	46.18
Yes	56.34	44.74	53.82

Total	100.00	100.00	100.00
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Stress

How stressed from 1 to 5	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
1	2.62	5.92	3.31
2	11.01	19.08	12.71
3	30.94	29.61	30.66
4	33.22	33.55	33.29
5	22.20	11.84	20.03
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source of stress

What is your main source of stress?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Other	3.33	5.92	3.87
Work	40.11	38.82	39.83
Family relationship	1.75	1.32	1.66
Child relationship	1.75	0.66	1.52
Daily life management	16.99	15.13	16.60
Health	4.73	1.97	4.15
Economic situation	10.16	13.16	10.79
General situation	17.51	13.16	16.60
Couple life	1.05	3.29	1.52
None	1.58	4.61	2.21
Don't know	1.05	1.97	1.24
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time home Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Housework/home management.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Much less	8.56	4.64	7.72
Less	14.80	13.91	14.61
Equal	45.45	47.68	45.93
More	17.11	24.50	18.68
Much more	12.66	8.61	11.80
Not applicable	1.43	0.66	1.26
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time Children Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your time use changed?: Children care.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Much less	8.22	7.75	8.12
Less	7.84	7.04	7.67
Equal	33.46	34.51	33.68
More	13.19	13.38	13.23

Much more	9.94	9.15	9.77
Not applicable	27.34	28.17	27.52
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time care family Phase 1

Phase 1: How did your time use change?: Care of family members.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Much less	8.53	8.16	8.45
Less	12.89	12.93	12.89
Equal	42.29	39.46	41.69
More	13.79	17.69	14.61
Much more	9.26	8.16	9.03
Not applicable	13.25	13.61	13.32
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time Sleep Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Sleep.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Much less	18.29	11.26	16.81
Less	36.94	36.42	36.83
Equal	35.52	43.71	37.25
More	4.62	5.96	4.90
Much more	3.20	2.65	3.08
Not applicable	1.42	0.00	1.12
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Personal care time Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Personal care.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Much less	4.08	2.67	3.78
Less	13.65	10.00	12.89
Equal	63.65	66.00	64.15
More	9.57	12.67	10.22
Much more	7.80	8.67	7.98
Not applicable	1.24	0.00	0.98
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Leisure time Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Leisure activities/leisure time.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Much less	59.29	49.34	57.18
Less	22.65	25.00	23.15
Equal	11.50	15.79	12.41
More	2.83	3.29	2.93
Much more	1.77	5.26	2.51
Not applicable	1.95	1.32	1.81

Total	100.00	100.00	100.00
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Overtime Phase 1

Phase 1: how often overtime hours	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
At most once a week	33.39	32.24	33.15
Never	24.48	13.82	22.24
Every day	10.31	15.13	11.33
Several times a week	31.82	38.82	33.29
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Dissatisfaction Phase 1

Phase 1: I am dissatisfied with the performance/work I delivered/performed.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Totally disagree	31.44	32.67	31.70
Disagree	38.37	36.00	37.87
Agree	12.79	11.33	12.48
Completely agree	4.97	7.33	5.47
Not sure	12.43	12.67	12.48
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Communication Superiors Phase 1

Phase 1: here was good communication between me and my superiors.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Totally disagree	8.08	10.00	8.49
Disagree	19.03	21.33	19.52
Agree	36.98	32.67	36.07
Completely agree	13.29	14.67	13.58
Not sure	22.62	21.33	22.35
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Good work planning Phase 1

Phase 1: Good work planning was ensured.	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Totally disagree	10.71	13.25	11.25
Disagree	21.43	22.52	21.66
Agree	30.54	35.10	31.50
Completely agree	11.43	8.61	10.83
Not sure	25.89	20.53	24.75
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Got Covid

Did you have Covid-19?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total

No	27.67	24.50	27.01
Yes, more than once	17.34	12.58	16.34
Yes, just once	54.99	62.91	56.65
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Cohabitants Covid-19

Have any of your cohabitants had COVID-19?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	16.52	20.49	17.35
Yes, more than once and/or more familiar	23.82	27.05	24.49
Yes, only once	59.66	52.46	58.16
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Hospitalization Covid-19

Have you ever been hospitalised for Covid -19?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	98.55	99.12	98.67
Yes, not in intensive care	1.45	0.88	1.33
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Work with Covid-19 patient

Do you work/have you worked closely with Covid-19 patients?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
No	26.63	19.08	25.03
Yes, currently	26.10	38.82	28.79
Yes, in the past but not currently	47.27	42.11	46.18
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Colleagues' relation today

How would you define your relations with your colleagues today overall?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Very bad	1.05	0.66	0.97
Bad	1.75	0.00	1.38
Neither good nor bad	16.58	23.03	17.93
Good	58.46	59.21	58.62
Not applicable	22.16	17.11	21.10
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Comparison relation preCovid-19 colleagues

Comparison of relationships immediately before the pandemic with colleagues	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Better	13.81	11.84	13.40
Don't know	5.94	1.97	5.11
Worse	13.81	13.82	13.81

Equal	66.43	72.37	67.68
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Actual satisfaction job/home

How satisfied are you with the division of domestic work between you and your partner	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Not at all	7.29	1.00	5.83
A little	22.80	11.00	20.05
Quite a lot	51.98	55.00	52.68
Very much	17.93	33.00	21.45
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Isolation Phase 1

Phase 1: Did you have to move/isolate yourself from your family for fear of infection	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Mai	37.77	49.59	40.20
More than once	44.64	33.88	42.42
Just once	17.60	16.53	17.38
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Load weight appliance Phase 1

Phase 1: Who did most of the housework/care in the household?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Another person	1.29	0.83	1.20
Partner	12.28	34.17	16.78
Children	1.94	0.00	1.54
Parents	5.60	5.83	5.65
I	41.38	13.33	35.62
A little of everyone, no one in particular	37.50	45.83	39.21
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Load between home and family work

Load between home and family work:	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Not at all difficult	2.28	3.33	2.50
A little difficult	10.51	13.33	11.10
Somewhat difficult	63.40	72.67	65.33
Very difficult	23.82	10.67	21.08
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Satisfaction during pandemic

Phase 1: More or less satisfied with household/domestic work division	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Much less	5.20	0.00	3.99

Less	11.31	5.05	9.86
Equal	72.17	77.78	73.47
More	7.65	13.13	8.92
Much more	3.67	4.04	3.76
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Change labour load

Has your workload changed or remained the same since Phase 1?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
It is less	11.23	9.27	10.82
It is more	40.53	39.74	40.36
It is the same	48.25	50.99	48.82
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Contacts friends Phase 1

Phase 1: have you heard by phone/video calls/via internet seen relatives/friends?	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Several times a day	34.33	32.45	33.93
Once a day	27.15	21.85	26.04
A few times a week	24.17	31.13	25.62
Once a week	5.95	5.96	5.96
More rarely	7.01	7.95	7.20
Never	1.40	0.66	1.25
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Relation today partner.

Relationship with partner today?: Partner/spouse	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Very bad	48.05	52.54	49.01
Bad	1.15	0.00	0.90
Neither good nor bad	9.66	6.78	9.04
Good	32.87	35.59	33.45
Not applicable	8.28	5.08	7.59
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Current relation children

Relationships with cohabittees today?: Child(ren)	Gender		
	Female	Male	Total
Very bad	41.57	47.75	42.86
Bad	0.00	2.70	0.56
Neither good nor bad	6.65	2.70	5.83
Good	32.07	26.13	30.83
Not applicable	19.71	20.72	19.92
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Citizenship

Citizenship	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
Italian	98.72	98.46	100.00	99.18	100.00	99.31
Foreign	1.28	1.54	0.00	0.82	0.00	0.69
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Education level

Education level	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
Elementary school	0.00	0.77	1.42	4.08	3.45	2.21
High school	8.97	7.69	10.38	40.82	31.03	21.72
Bachelor	78.21	54.62	49.06	27.76	18.97	43.57
Master	2.56	10.00	12.26	15.10	13.79	11.89
Postgraduate	10.26	26.92	26.89	12.24	32.76	20.61
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

N inhabitants

How many people live in your household (or family)	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
1	17.95	20.77	13.68	18.62	29.31	18.34
2	28.21	30.77	15.09	23.08	27.59	23.03
3	15.38	23.08	26.42	23.48	20.69	23.17
4	25.64	20.00	29.72	25.91	15.52	25.10
5	8.97	3.85	10.85	6.48	5.17	7.45
6	2.56	0.77	3.77	1.21	1.72	2.07
7	0.00	0.77	0.00	1.21	0.00	0.55
9	0.00	0.00	0.47	0.00	0.00	0.14
10	1.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Family member care

Currently taking care of a disabled/dependent family member (cohabiting or not).	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
No	83.33	83.72	78.20	72.13	70.69	77.08
Yes, rarely	6.41	6.98	1.90	5.33	1.72	4.44
Yes, at least once a week	7.69	4.65	6.64	9.43	8.62	7.50
Yes, every day	2.56	4.65	13.27	13.11	18.97	10.97
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Currently care elderly

Tired day work during Phase 1

Phase 1: Tired of having to face another working day in 1 5.	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
1	3.95	6.40	10.85	13.39	16.07	10.59
2	10.53	13.60	9.43	15.06	12.50	12.43
3	26.32	25.60	27.36	23.43	25.00	25.42
4	44.74	28.80	27.36	28.03	25.00	29.52
5	14.47	25.60	25.00	20.08	21.43	22.03
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Patients objects Phase 1

Phase 1: I seemed to treat patients as objects between 1 5.	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
1	30.26	55.04	57.35	66.81	64.81	57.65
2	18.42	14.73	13.74	13.10	9.26	13.88
3	28.95	13.18	13.27	8.30	14.81	13.45
4	10.53	8.53	6.16	6.99	5.56	7.30
5	11.84	8.53	9.48	4.80	5.56	7.73
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Work department Covid-19

Do you work/have you worked in a Covid-19 department?	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
No	25.64	44.62	50.48	55.87	70.18	50.14
Yes, currently	20.51	12.31	16.19	11.34	10.53	13.85
Yes, in the past but not now	53.85	43.08	33.33	32.79	19.30	36.01
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Work department Covid-19 spec

Please specify whether you work/have worked in:	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Outpatient	0.00	7.04	9.71	7.41	12.50	7.04
Ordinary/sub-intensive care	42.11	54.93	51.46	73.15	50.00	57.18
Intensive care/critical care	57.89	38.03	38.83	19.44	37.50	35.77
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Asthenia Covid-19

If you had Covid 19, did you have as a consequence Asthenia	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
No	75.64	74.62	71.70	73.68	68.97	73.10
Yes	24.36	25.38	28.30	26.32	31.03	26.90
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Mental confusion Covid-19

If you had Covid 19, did you have as a consequence mental confusion	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
No	88.46	85.38	87.74	82.59	87.93	85.66
Yes	11.54	14.62	12.26	17.41	12.07	14.34
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Muscular pain Covid-19

If you had Covid-19, did you have as a consequence muscular pains	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
No	85.90	87.69	81.13	80.16	79.31	82.34
Yes	14.10	12.31	18.87	19.84	20.69	17.66
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Paraesthesia Covid

If you had Covid-19, did you have as a consequence paraesthesia	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
No	97.44	98.46	95.28	93.12	91.38	95.03
Yes	2.56	1.54	4.72	6.88	8.62	4.97
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Consequences Covid-19

Consequences of Covid-19 on your health for more than one month after testing posit	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
No	51.72	54.37	41.25	42.59	51.22	46.18
Yes	48.28	45.63	58.75	57.41	48.78	53.82
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Stress

How stressed from 1 to 5	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
1	0.00	3.88	3.30	4.05	3.45	3.31
2	10.26	10.08	12.26	13.77	18.97	12.71
3	44.87	29.46	24.53	30.77	36.21	30.66
4	33.33	34.88	35.38	33.60	20.69	33.29
5	11.54	21.71	24.53	17.81	20.69	20.03
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source stress

What is your main source of stress?	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
Other	2.56	6.98	3.30	3.64	1.75	3.87
Work	55.13	44.19	38.21	34.82	36.84	39.83
Family relationship	0.00	1.55	1.42	2.83	0.00	1.66
Child relationship	0.00	1.55	1.89	1.62	1.75	1.52

Daily life management	8.97	16.28	22.64	13.36	19.30	16.60
Health	1.28	3.10	2.36	5.67	10.53	4.15
Economic situation	14.10	12.40	8.02	12.55	5.26	10.79
General situation	12.82	7.75	17.45	21.46	17.54	16.60
Couple life	3.85	1.55	1.89	0.40	1.75	1.52
None	0.00	2.33	2.36	2.43	3.51	2.21
Don't know	1.28	2.33	0.47	1.21	1.75	1.24
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time home Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Housework/home management.	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Much less	3.85	9.45	8.02	7.92	7.27	7.72
Less	26.92	15.75	11.32	12.92	14.55	14.61
Equal	42.31	40.16	45.75	49.17	50.91	45.93
More	17.95	22.83	18.87	15.83	21.82	18.68
Much more	6.41	11.02	15.57	12.08	5.45	11.80
Not applicable	2.56	0.79	0.47	2.08	0.00	1.26
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time Children Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your time use changed?: Children care.	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Much less	9.09	10.00	8.54	6.58	7.69	8.12
Less	3.03	5.83	9.05	9.21	5.77	7.67
Equal	12.12	22.50	31.66	44.30	48.08	33.68
More	1.52	12.50	16.58	14.91	9.62	13.23
Much more	3.03	7.50	17.59	6.58	7.69	9.77
Not applicable	71.21	41.67	16.58	18.42	21.15	27.52
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time care family Phase 1

Phase 1: How did your time use change?: Care of family members.	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Much less	8.45	9.45	9.05	7.56	7.69	8.45
Less	22.54	11.81	11.43	13.03	7.69	12.89
Equal	29.58	41.73	42.38	45.38	38.46	41.69
More	11.27	11.81	15.24	15.55	19.23	14.61
Much more	4.23	5.51	12.38	10.08	5.77	9.03
Not applicable	23.94	19.69	9.52	8.40	21.15	13.32
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time Sleep Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Sleep.	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Much less	8.97	17.32	17.92	19.42	10.91	16.81

Less	37.18	40.94	34.91	34.71	43.64	36.83
Equal	24.36	29.92	42.45	40.91	36.36	37.25
More	14.10	5.51	2.36	3.31	7.27	4.90
Much more	14.10	3.94	1.89	0.41	1.82	3.08
Not applicable	1.28	2.36	0.47	1.24	0.00	1.12
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Personal care time Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Personal care.	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
Much less	5.13	2.34	4.78	3.29	3.57	3.78
Less	16.67	17.19	13.40	11.11	3.57	12.89
Equal	47.44	60.16	65.55	67.08	78.57	64.15
More	23.08	10.94	7.66	8.23	8.93	10.22
Much more	6.41	8.59	8.13	8.64	5.36	7.98
Not applicable	1.28	0.78	0.48	1.65	0.00	0.98
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Leisure time Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Leisure activities/leisure time.	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
Much less	50.00	58.14	59.72	58.44	50.00	57.18
Less	33.33	19.38	24.17	19.75	28.57	23.15
Equal	7.69	9.30	12.32	14.81	16.07	12.41
More	5.13	4.65	1.42	2.47	3.57	2.93
Much more	2.56	6.20	1.42	1.65	1.79	2.51
Not applicable	1.28	2.33	0.95	2.88	0.00	1.81
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Overtime Phase 1

Phase 1: how often overtime hours	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
At most once a week	44.16	35.38	30.19	32.39	27.59	33.15
Never	18.18	13.08	24.06	25.91	25.86	22.24
Every day	3.90	13.85	11.79	10.53	17.24	11.33
Several times a week	33.77	37.69	33.96	31.17	29.31	33.29
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Dissatisfaction Phase 1

Phase 1: I am dissatisfied with the performance/work delivered/performed.	Age class					
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	Total
Totally disagree	19.48	34.88	32.38	34.02	28.57	31.70
Disagree	48.05	27.91	38.10	40.25	35.71	37.87
Agree	12.99	12.40	12.38	12.45	12.50	12.48
Completely agree	3.90	6.20	6.19	4.15	8.93	5.47

Not sure	15.58	18.60	10.95	9.13	14.29	12.48
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Communication Superiors Phase 1

Phase 1: here was effective communication between me and my superiors.	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Totally disagree	5.19	9.30	10.29	9.17	1.75	8.49
Disagree	20.78	21.71	22.55	17.50	10.53	19.52
Agree	31.17	34.11	35.29	37.50	43.86	36.07
Completely agree	10.39	15.50	13.73	12.08	19.30	13.58
Not sure	32.47	19.38	18.14	23.75	24.56	22.35
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Planning work activities Phase 1

Phase 1: Good work planning was ensured.	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Totally disagree	9.09	11.63	15.69	10.66	0.00	11.25
Disagree	28.57	25.58	18.63	20.49	19.30	21.66
Agree	25.97	31.78	31.37	30.33	43.86	31.50
Completely agree	7.79	8.53	9.80	11.89	19.30	10.83
Not sure	28.57	22.48	24.51	26.64	17.54	24.75
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Got Covid-19

Did you contract the virus from COVID-19?	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
No	25.64	19.38	24.53	33.74	26.32	27.01
Yes, more than once	28.21	13.18	19.34	14.63	3.51	16.34
Yes, just once	46.15	67.44	56.13	51.63	70.18	56.65
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Cohabitants Covid-19

Have any of your cohabitants had Covid-19?	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
No	15.63	12.62	17.03	20.71	17.07	17.35
Yes, more than once and/or more familiar	29.69	23.30	26.92	21.72	21.95	24.49
Yes, just once	54.69	64.08	56.04	57.58	60.98	58.16
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Hospitalisation Covid-19

Have you ever been hospitalised for Covid-19?	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
No	98.28	100.00	98.13	98.16	100.00	98.67
Yes, not in intensive care	1.72	0.00	1.88	1.84	0.00	1.33

Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
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Work Covid patient

Do you work/have you worked closely with Covid-19 patients?	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
No	3.85	14.06	22.27	35.25	44.83	25.03
Yes, now	38.46	36.72	30.81	22.54	17.24	28.79
Yes, in the past but not now	57.69	49.22	46.92	42.21	37.93	46.18
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Colleagues' relation today

How would you define your relations with your colleagues today overall?	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Very bad	0.00	0.00	2.36	0.81	0.00	0.97
Bad	1.28	2.31	0.94	1.21	1.72	1.38
Neither good nor bad	16.67	18.46	18.87	17.41	17.24	17.93
Good	62.82	60.00	57.08	57.89	58.62	58.62
Not applicable	19.23	19.23	20.75	22.67	22.41	21.10
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Comparison relation preCovid-19 colleagues

Comparison of relationships immediately before the pandemic with colleagues	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Better	20.78	16.92	12.74	9.72	13.79	13.40
Don't know	20.78	4.62	3.77	2.43	1.72	5.11
Worse	12.99	14.62	16.51	12.15	10.34	13.81
Equal	45.45	63.85	66.98	75.71	74.14	67.68
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Actual satisfaction job/home

How satisfied are you with the division of domestic work between you and your partner	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Not at all	0.00	2.35	8.11	6.34	6.45	5.83
A little	26.09	15.29	19.59	24.65	9.68	20.05
Quite a lot	52.17	56.47	53.38	51.41	45.16	52.68
Very much	21.74	25.88	18.92	17.61	38.71	21.45
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Isolation Phase 1

Phase 1: Did you have to move/isolate yourself from your family for fear of infection	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Mai	28.13	36.89	39.01	42.21	64.10	40.20
More than once	59.38	44.66	45.60	37.69	17.95	42.42

Just one time	12.50	18.45	15.38	20.10	17.95	17.38
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Load weight appliance Phase 1

Phase 1: Who did most of the housework/care in the household?	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Another person	1.59	0.98	1.10	1.01	2.56	1.20
Partner	4.76	18.63	21.55	14.57	20.51	16.78
Children	0.00	0.00	0.55	3.52	2.56	1.54
Parents	25.40	5.88	2.21	2.51	5.13	5.65
I	19.05	33.33	41.44	36.68	35.90	35.62
A little bit of everyone, no one in particular	49.21	41.18	33.15	41.71	33.33	39.21
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Load job/domestic work

Load between home and family work:	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Not at all difficult	2.56	0.78	1.90	3.25	5.26	2.50
A little difficult	17.95	15.50	7.11	8.54	17.54	11.10
Difficult	64.10	62.79	57.35	74.80	61.40	65.33
Very difficult	15.38	20.93	33.65	13.41	15.79	21.08
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Satisfaction during pandemic

Phase 1: More or less satisfied with household/domestic work division	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
Much less	8.70	3.53	4.76	2.86	3.23	3.99
Less	13.04	3.53	17.01	7.14	3.23	9.86
Equal	73.91	75.29	65.31	79.29	80.65	73.47
More	0.00	12.94	7.48	8.57	12.90	8.92
Much more	4.35	4.71	5.44	2.14	0.00	3.76
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Change job load

Has your workload changed or remained the same since Phase 1?	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	
It has decreased	16.67	10.16	13.74	6.91	10.34	10.82
It has become more	35.90	33.59	42.65	41.46	48.28	40.36
It has remained equal	47.44	56.25	43.60	51.63	41.38	48.82
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Contacts friends Phase 1

Phase 1: have you heard by phone/video calls/via internet seen relatives/friends?	Age class					Total
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 & +	

Education level

Education level	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Elementary school	15.63	0.46	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	13.04	2.21
High school	78.13	24.94	0.00	0.00	2.78	15.38	28.99	21.72
Bachelor	3.13	57.89	0.00	82.35	55.56	69.23	26.09	43.57
Master	3.13	12.81	6.72	5.88	27.78	15.38	11.59	11.89
Post-graduate	0.00	3.89	93.28	11.76	13.89	0.00	20.29	20.61
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

N inhabitants

How many people live in your household (or family) including	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
1	28.13	15.07	21.67	5.88	22.22	7.69	31.88	18.34
2	25.00	23.52	26.67	11.76	11.11	15.38	23.19	23.03
3	12.50	23.06	19.17	29.41	50.00	23.08	20.29	23.17
4	34.38	26.94	17.50	35.29	13.89	53.85	20.29	25.10
5	0.00	7.99	11.67	11.76	2.78	0.00	2.90	7.45
6	0.00	2.28	2.50	5.88	0.00	0.00	1.45	2.07
7	0.00	0.68	0.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.55
9	0.00	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
10	0.00	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Family member care

Currently taking care of a disabled/dependent family member (cohabiting or not).	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	71.88	73.39	86.55	76.47	77.78	92.31	83.58	77.08
Yes, rarely	6.25	5.28	5.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.49	4.44
Yes, at least once a week	3.13	8.72	4.20	5.88	13.89	7.69	4.48	7.50
Yes, every day	18.75	12.61	4.20	17.65	8.33	0.00	10.45	10.97
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Currently care elderly

Currently caring for an elderly	Current health profession
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family member (cohabiting or non-cohabiting)	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	59.38	60.64	70.59	58.82	69.44	69.23	65.22	63.21
Yes, rarely	15.63	8.92	7.56	11.76	5.56	0.00	11.59	8.99
Yes, at least once a week	9.38	17.39	18.49	5.88	8.33	30.77	11.59	16.18
Yes, every day	15.63	13.04	3.36	23.53	16.67	0.00	11.59	11.62
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Average hours worked week

On average, how many hours do you work per week?	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Less than 36h	6.25	9.13	1.67	5.88	14.29	0.00	4.35	7.32
36-39h	87.50	76.03	20.00	76.47	51.43	61.54	73.91	65.61
40-48h	6.25	13.70	43.33	17.65	31.43	38.46	15.94	19.89
More than 48h	0.00	1.14	35.00	0.00	2.86	0.00	5.80	7.18
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Different Job Phase 1

Phase 1: You were employed in a different service.	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	71.88	73.10	78.99	64.71	77.78	92.31	86.96	75.73
Yes	28.13	26.90	21.01	35.29	22.22	7.69	13.04	24.27
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Emotionally finished Phase 1

Phase 1: Emotionally exhausted between 1-5.	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
1	6.45	6.91	12.71	5.88	14.29	7.69	19.70	9.38
2	6.45	11.75	20.34	11.76	17.14	7.69	10.61	13.03
3	35.48	26.04	27.97	11.76	20.00	46.15	30.30	26.89
4	25.81	29.26	26.27	52.94	34.29	0.00	18.18	27.87
5	25.81	26.04	12.71	17.65	14.29	38.46	21.21	22.83

Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
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Tired day work Phase 1

	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Phase 1: Tired of having to face another working day in 1-5.								
1	9.38	7.04	17.09	5.88	16.67	7.69	20.90	10.59
2	18.75	11.97	11.97	11.76	16.67	7.69	11.94	12.43
3	9.38	25.59	29.91	17.65	30.56	15.38	25.37	25.42
4	28.13	29.81	28.21	52.94	27.78	38.46	23.88	29.52
5	34.38	25.59	12.82	11.76	8.33	30.77	17.91	22.03
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Patients objects Phase 1

	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Phase 1: I seemed to treat patients as objects between 1-5.								
1	64.52	52.72	60.00	58.82	58.82	46.15	83.33	57.65
2	9.68	15.60	13.91	5.88	14.71	15.38	6.06	13.88
3	12.90	15.60	13.04	11.76	5.88	23.08	3.03	13.45
4	9.68	7.09	6.96	17.65	11.76	0.00	4.55	7.30
5	3.23	8.98	6.09	5.88	8.82	15.38	3.03	7.73
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Work department Covid-19

	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Do you work/have you worked in a Covid-19 department?								
No	28.13	44.62	62.50	43.75	63.89	53.85	67.65	50.14
Yes, now	15.63	14.87	10.00	31.25	11.11	38.46	5.88	13.85
Yes, in the past but not currently	56.25	40.50	27.50	25.00	25.00	7.69	26.47	36.01
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Work department Covid-19 spec

Please specify whether you	Current health profession
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work/have worked in:	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Outpatient	0.00	7.50	9.09	0.00	16.67	16.67	0.00	7.04
Ordinary/sub-intensive care	56.52	55.83	70.45	55.56	41.67	0.00	71.43	57.18
Intensive care/critical care	43.48	36.67	20.45	44.44	41.67	83.33	28.57	35.77
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Asthenia Covid-19

If you had Covid-19, did you have as a consequence Asthenia	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	62.50	71.23	77.50	70.59	75.00	84.62	79.71	73.10
Yes	37.50	28.77	22.50	29.41	25.00	15.38	20.29	26.90
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Mental confusion Covid-19

If you had Covid-19, did you have as a consequence mental confusion	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	71.88	85.16	92.50	88.24	83.33	76.92	85.51	85.66
Yes	28.13	14.84	7.50	11.76	16.67	23.08	14.49	14.34
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Muscular pains Covid-19

If you had Covid-19, did you have as a consequence muscular pains	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	71.88	81.74	88.33	88.24	83.33	84.62	78.26	82.34
Yes	28.13	18.26	11.67	11.76	16.67	15.38	21.74	17.66
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Paresthesia Covid-19

If you had Covid-19, did you have	Current health profession
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as a consequence paresthesia	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	93.75	94.52	97.50	100.00	100.00	92.31	91.30	95.03
Yes	6.25	5.48	2.50	0.00	0.00	7.69	8.70	4.97
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Consequences Covid-19

Consequences of Covid on your health for more than one month after testing positive	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	41.38	42.57	59.57	41.67	51.72	70.00	38.89	46.18
Yes	58.62	57.43	40.43	58.33	48.28	30.00	61.11	53.82
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Stress

How stressed from 1 to 5	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
1	0.00	2.28	3.36	0.00	5.56	7.69	10.14	3.31
2	9.38	11.87	15.97	11.76	11.11	15.38	14.49	12.71
3	28.13	31.28	30.25	41.18	27.78	15.38	30.43	30.66
4	40.63	33.56	32.77	17.65	36.11	46.15	28.99	33.29
5	21.88	21.00	17.65	29.41	19.44	15.38	15.94	20.03
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source of stress

What is your main source of stress?	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Other	3.13	4.79	3.36	0.00	2.86	0.00	1.45	3.87
Work	31.25	38.36	55.46	35.29	37.14	23.08	31.88	39.83
Family relationship	3.13	1.37	2.52	11.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.66
Child relationship	0.00	2.05	0.84	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.45	1.52
Daily life management	12.50	15.53	17.65	35.29	20.00	15.38	17.39	16.60

Health	9.38	5.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.25	4.15
Economic situation	9.38	12.56	3.36	0.00	11.43	30.77	11.59	10.79
General situation	25.00	17.35	7.56	17.65	20.00	23.08	20.29	16.60
Couple life	3.13	0.46	5.04	0.00	5.71	0.00	0.00	1.52
None	0.00	1.37	2.52	0.00	2.86	7.69	7.25	2.21
Don't know	3.13	1.14	1.68	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.45	1.24
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time home Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Housework/home management.	Current health profession							Total
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	
Much less	6.67	6.51	12.71	5.88	2.86	7.69	10.14	7.72
Less	16.67	15.81	13.56	11.76	17.14	23.08	5.80	14.61
Equal	43.33	48.60	43.22	47.06	28.57	38.46	44.93	45.93
More	10.00	16.28	21.19	17.65	42.86	23.08	20.29	18.68
Much more	23.33	11.40	9.32	11.76	8.57	7.69	15.94	11.80
Not applicable	0.00	1.40	0.00	5.88	0.00	0.00	2.90	1.26
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time Children Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your time use changed?: Children care.	Current health profession							Total
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	
Much less	3.85	7.67	9.91	5.88	2.86	23.08	10.17	8.12
Less	11.54	7.67	9.91	5.88	0.00	15.38	5.08	7.67
Equal	34.62	37.38	27.03	23.53	31.43	23.08	27.12	33.68
More	19.23	11.63	11.71	23.53	11.43	7.69	23.73	13.23
Much more	7.69	9.65	8.11	5.88	25.71	7.69	6.78	9.77
Not applicable	23.08	25.99	33.33	35.29	28.57	23.08	27.12	27.52
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time care family Phase 1

Phase 1: How did your time use change?: Care of family members.	Current health profession							Total
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	
Much less	6.90	7.84	10.92	11.76	2.86	23.08	7.81	8.45

Less	6.90	14.01	13.45	11.76	5.71	23.08	9.38	12.89
Equal	41.38	44.18	35.29	35.29	42.86	38.46	39.06	41.69
More	24.14	13.06	12.61	23.53	14.29	7.69	23.44	14.61
Much more	6.90	10.21	4.20	5.88	17.14	0.00	9.38	9.03
Not applicable	13.79	10.69	23.53	11.76	17.14	7.69	10.94	13.32
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Time Sleep Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Sleep.	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Much less	12.50	18.65	9.32	11.76	13.89	30.77	20.29	16.81
Less	46.88	35.43	37.29	47.06	33.33	38.46	39.13	36.83
Equal	31.25	36.13	45.76	29.41	44.44	15.38	34.78	37.25
More	9.38	4.43	5.08	11.76	8.33	7.69	1.45	4.90
Much more	0.00	3.96	1.69	0.00	0.00	7.69	2.90	3.08
Not applicable	0.00	1.40	0.85	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.45	1.12
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Personal care time Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Personal care.	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Much less	0.00	4.21	5.88	5.88	0.00	0.00	1.45	3.78
Less	15.63	12.85	13.45	11.76	11.11	23.08	10.14	12.89
Equal	68.75	62.62	65.55	64.71	72.22	53.85	66.67	64.15
More	6.25	10.51	5.88	17.65	11.11	15.38	14.49	10.22
Much more	9.38	8.64	9.24	0.00	5.56	7.69	4.35	7.98
Not applicable	0.00	1.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.90	0.98
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Leisure time Phase 1

Phase 1: How has your use of time changed?: Leisure activities/leisure time.	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Much less	46.88	55.92	61.34	64.71	72.22	61.54	52.17	57.18
Less	31.25	23.43	23.53	35.29	13.89	7.69	21.74	23.15
Equal	18.75	12.99	9.24	0.00	11.11	15.38	14.49	12.41

Planning work Phase 1

Phase 1: Good work planning was ensured.	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Totally disagree	15.63	10.21	12.61	12.50	16.67	25.00	7.69	11.25
Disagree	28.13	23.43	13.45	31.25	30.56	25.00	13.85	21.66
Agree	31.25	30.16	41.18	31.25	30.56	16.67	26.15	31.50
Completely agree	15.63	11.14	7.56	0.00	2.78	0.00	21.54	10.83
Not sure	9.38	25.06	25.21	25.00	19.44	33.33	30.77	24.75
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Got Covid

Did you contract the virus from COVID-19?	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	9.38	31.65	20.17	29.41	19.44	23.08	21.74	27.01
Yes, more than once	21.88	15.14	19.33	23.53	13.89	23.08	14.49	16.34
Yes, just once	68.75	53.21	60.50	47.06	66.67	53.85	63.77	56.65
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Cohabitants Covid

Have any of your cohabitants had COVID-19?	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	30.43	15.99	21.28	25.00	14.29	16.67	13.04	17.35
Yes, more than once and/or more familiar	17.39	24.66	20.21	18.75	28.57	58.33	26.09	24.49
Yes, only once	52.17	59.35	58.51	56.25	57.14	25.00	60.87	58.16
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Hospitalization Covid

Have you ever been hospitalised	Current health profession							
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for COVID-19?	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	100.00	98.66	97.87	100.00	100.00	100.00	98.15	98.67
Yes, not in intensive care	0.00	1.34	2.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.85	1.33
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Work Covid patient

Do you work/have you worked closely with COVID patients?	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
No	12.50	21.84	22.03	12.50	44.44	7.69	52.17	25.03
Yes, now	25.00	28.74	36.44	43.75	13.89	38.46	20.29	28.79
Yes, in the past but not currently	62.50	49.43	41.53	43.75	41.67	53.85	27.54	46.18
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Colleagues relation today

How would you define your relations with your colleagues today overall?	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Very bad	6.25	0.46	0.83	0.00	2.78	0.00	1.45	0.97
Bad	0.00	0.68	1.67	5.88	2.78	0.00	4.35	1.38
Neither good nor bad	15.63	18.95	14.17	17.65	11.11	30.77	20.29	17.93
Good	62.50	59.82	62.50	52.94	63.89	46.15	43.48	58.62
Not applicable	15.63	20.09	20.83	23.53	19.44	23.08	30.43	21.10
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Comparison relation preCovid-19 colleagues

Comparison of relationships immediately before the pandemic with colleagues	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Better	12.50	14.42	12.50	0.00	13.89	7.69	13.04	13.40
Doesn't know	3.13	6.86	2.50	11.76	0.00	0.00	1.45	5.11
Worse	18.75	12.59	15.83	5.88	16.67	15.38	15.94	13.81

Equals	65.63	66.13	69.17	82.35	69.44	76.92	69.57	67.68
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Actual satisfaction job home

How satisfied are you with the division of domestic work between you and your partner.	Current health profession							Total
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	
Not at all	10.00	6.02	1.23	0.00	10.53	10.00	12.12	5.83
A little	10.00	22.93	14.81	10.00	26.32	10.00	15.15	20.05
Quite a lot	40.00	52.63	53.09	70.00	52.63	40.00	54.55	52.68
Very much	40.00	18.42	30.86	20.00	10.53	40.00	18.18	21.45
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Isolation Phase 1

Phase 1: Did you have to move/isolate yourself from your family for fear of infection.	Current health profession							Total
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	
Never	43.48	38.48	47.31	43.75	46.43	33.33	34.78	40.20
More than once	47.83	43.63	37.63	56.25	32.14	50.00	39.13	42.42
Only once	8.70	17.89	15.05	0.00	21.43	16.67	26.09	17.38
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Load weight appliance Phase 1

Phase 1: Who did most of the housework/care in the household?	Current health profession							Total
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	
Another person	0.00	0.82	4.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.20
Spouse/partner	13.04	11.20	39.13	18.75	10.71	41.67	14.89	16.78
Children	4.35	1.64	1.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.13	1.54
Parents	13.04	6.01	3.26	12.50	3.57	0.00	4.26	5.65
I	30.43	39.62	26.09	18.75	39.29	16.67	34.04	35.62
Everyone, no one in particular	39.13	40.71	26.09	50.00	46.43	41.67	44.68	39.21
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Load home /family work

Load between home and family	Current health profession						
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work:	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Not at all difficult	3.13	1.83	1.69	0.00	2.78	0.00	8.70	2.50
A little difficult	6.25	12.39	9.32	11.76	2.78	7.69	13.04	11.10
Somewhat difficult	78.13	63.53	65.25	58.82	69.44	69.23	69.57	65.33
Very difficult	12.50	22.25	23.73	29.41	25.00	23.08	8.70	21.08
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Satisfaction during pandemic

	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Phase 1: More or less satisfied with household/domestic work division								
Much less	10.00	4.17	0.00	0.00	10.53	0.00	9.09	3.99
Less	20.00	10.98	6.25	0.00	10.53	0.00	12.12	9.86
Equal	60.00	74.62	76.25	70.00	57.89	80.00	69.70	73.47
More	10.00	6.82	11.25	20.00	21.05	10.00	9.09	8.92
Much more	0.00	3.41	6.25	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	3.76
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Change labor load

	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Has your workload changed or remained the same since Phase 1?								
It has decreased	19.35	10.30	13.45	11.76	8.33	0.00	8.82	10.82
It has become more	38.71	40.96	31.93	35.29	55.56	61.54	41.18	40.36
It has remained unchanged	41.94	48.74	54.62	52.94	36.11	38.46	50.00	48.82
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Contacts friends Phase 1

	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Phase 1: have you heard by phone/video calls/via internet seen relatives/friends?								
Several times a day	37.50	32.80	27.73	29.41	44.44	53.85	42.03	33.93
Once a day	25.00	27.75	26.89	23.53	16.67	15.38	21.74	26.04
A few times a week	15.63	25.92	29.41	41.18	27.78	15.38	18.84	25.62

Relation comparison partner

Relationships with cohabittees today vs. prePhase 1?: Partner	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Not applicable	0.00	8.72	8.60	6.25	11.54	8.33	2.22	7.99
Worse	0.00	7.27	9.68	0.00	11.54	8.33	15.56	8.17
Equal	80.00	65.70	63.44	75.00	57.69	50.00	60.00	64.79
Better	20.00	18.31	18.28	18.75	19.23	33.33	22.22	19.06
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Relation comparison Children

Relationships with cohabittees today vs. prePhase 1?: Child(ren)	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Not applicable	6.25	21.56	22.09	28.57	29.63	16.67	19.05	21.47
Worse	0.00	5.69	3.49	0.00	3.70	0.00	2.38	4.52
Equal	81.25	59.88	62.79	50.00	37.04	58.33	69.05	60.26
Better	12.50	12.87	11.63	21.43	29.63	25.00	9.52	13.75
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Relation comparison Others

Relationships with cohabittees today vs. prePhase 1?: Other people	Current health profession							
	Healthcare assistant	Nurse	Doctor	Midwife	Rehabilitation worker	Radiology Technician	Other	Total
Not applicable	18.75	37.88	71.43	14.29	47.62	50.00	40.63	42.51
Worse	12.50	3.41	2.86	0.00	4.76	0.00	0.00	3.30
Equal	68.75	50.51	24.29	71.43	28.57	12.50	50.00	46.04
Better	0.00	8.19	1.43	14.29	19.05	37.50	9.38	8.15
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Ordinary Least Squares regression model predicting self-reported stress

Covariates	Beta coefficients
Demographic variables	
<i>Gender</i>	

8. URJC, Spain

Questionnaire administered in the citizen interviews (migrants of Latin American or Moroccan origin)

0. INTERVIEW ID NUMBER

1. INTERVIEWEE DATA

- a. GENDER
- b. AGE
- c. COUNTRY OF BIRTH
- d. NATIONALITY
- e. ADMINISTRATIVE STATUS
- f. LENGTH OF STAY IN SPAIN
- g. MARITAL STATUS
- h. LEVEL OF EDUCATION (YEARS OF EDUCATION & LEVEL ATTAINED)
- i. CURRENT EMPLOYMENT STATUS

PREFACE TO THE FOLLOWING QUESTIONS: We are going to ask you some questions about your experience of the COVID crisis. We would like your answers to cover what happened during the lockdown of March-May 2020, but also on the months that followed, both before and after the vaccination campaign started.

Reminder for interviewers: Our hypotheses expect that there could be differences in how the pandemic was experienced in different periods. The points in time that we are taking into consideration are the following:

- *Lockdown à March – June 2020*
- *New normal before the vaccination campaign à June – December 2020*
- *New normal after vaccination campaigns began à January 2021 - today.*

2. HOUSEHOLD DATA

- a. CAN YOU DESCRIBE THE DWELLING WHERE YOU LIVE IN?
 - i. IS THE DWELLING YOU LIVE IN OWNED OR RENTED?
 - ii. COULD YOU DESCRIBE YOUR DWELLING? (SQUARE METERS, NUMBER OF BEDROOMS, BATHROOMS, BALCONIES, ETC.)
 - iii. DO YOU HAVE A FIXED INTERNET CONNECTION?
 - iv. HOW MANY PERSONS USUALLY RESIDE IN THE DWELLING?
 - v. WHAT IS THE KINSHIP RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HOUSEHOLD MEMBERS?
 - vi. WAS YOUR HOUSE PREPARED TO COPE WITH THE PANDEMIC? (THINKING NOT ONLY OF THE LOCKDOWN PERIOD, BUT ALSO OF INDIVIDUAL CONFINEMENTS, TELEWORK, HOMESCHOOLING, ETC.)
- b. HAVE YOU GOT ANY CHILDREN? HOW MANY, IF ANY? DO YOU LIVE WITH THEM OR ARE THERE CHILDREN OR YOUNG PEOPLE OF SCHOOL AGE IN YOUR HOUSEHOLD?
 - i. HAVE THEY BEEN ABLE TO CONTINUE THEIR STUDIES NORMALLY?
- c. ARE YOU OR ANY MEMBERS OF YOUR HOUSEHOLD OF HIGH-RISK REGARDING COVID (ELDERLY, CHRONICALLY ILL, ETC.)?

3. IMPACT OF ANTI-COVID-19 MEASURES ON HOUSEHOLD ECONOMY AND OPINIONS ABOUT THE MEASURES

- a. WHO IS THE MAIN INCOME EARNER IN THE HOUSEHOLD IN WHICH YOU LIVE?
 - i. WHAT IS THE OCCUPATION OF THE MAIN INCOME EARNER IN THE HOUSEHOLD?
 - ii. WHAT KIND OF CONTRACT IS HE/SHE IN?
 - iii. HOW MUCH DO YOU EARN?
- b. ARE THERE OTHER INCOME EARNERS IN THE HOUSEHOLD? OCCUPATION? EARNING?
- c. WHAT WAS THE LEVEL OF HOUSEHOLD INCOME PER MONTH FOR ALL ITEMS BEFORE THE PANDEMIC? (Display a card with monthly household income amounts by brackets)
- d. HOW HAS THE PANDEMIC AFFECTED YOUR HOUSEHOLD INCOME?

- e. WHAT IS THE MEASURE OR MEASURES (HOUSE CONFINEMENT, PERIMETER CLOSURES, LIMITATIONS ON COMMERCIAL ACTIVITY, BAR AND RESTAURANT CAPACITY REDUCTION, ETC.), ADOPTED BY THE GOVERNMENT THAT HAS MOST AFFECTED YOUR HOUSEHOLD ECONOMY AND WHY? [Remind respondents of the different stages of the pandemic if they do not address them naturally].
 - i. IN YOUR OPINION, WERE THESE MEASURES THE RIGHT ONES, OR COULD OTHER MEASURES HAVE BEEN TAKEN THAT WERE LESS DAMAGING TO HOUSEHOLDS' FINANCES? DID YOU FIND THAT THEY HAD IN MIND THE NEEDS OF ORDINARY PEOPLE?
- f. DID YOUR HOUSEHOLD RECEIVE PUBLIC/PRIVATE CASH ASSISTANCE: EDUCATION GRANTS, MINIMUM LIVING INCOME, FOOD VOUCHERS, ETC., BEFORE THE PANDEMIC?
- g. HAVE YOU HAD TO ASK FOR HELP FROM PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS, PRIVATE ORGANISATIONS, FOOD BANKS, FAMILY OR FRIENDS TO MEET HOUSEHOLD EXPENSES? [Remind respondents of the different stages of the pandemic if they do not address them naturally].
 - i. HAS THE AID RECEIVED BEEN SUFFICIENT TO MAKE UP FOR THE LOSS OF INCOME?
 - ii. HAVE YOU, IN YOUR HOUSEHOLD, HAD TO REDUCE THE CONSUMPTION OF SOME GOODS OR SERVICES, POSTPONE PAYING BILLS, NOT ATTEND TO REPAIRS, ETC.?
 - iii. FOR HOW LONG HAVE YOU HAD TO RECEIVE THIS ASSISTANCE? [The idea is for respondents to answer whether they are still receiving this help or whether they stopped receiving it at some point].
- h. HAS YOUR HOUSEHOLD HAD TO PROVIDE ASSISTANCE TO OTHER HOUSEHOLDS OF FRIENDS OR RELATIVES DURING THE PANDEMIC?
- i. DO YOU THINK THAT THE EFFECTS OF THE PANDEMIC WILL, TO SOME EXTENT, CONDITION THE FUTURE OF YOUR HOUSEHOLD?

4. *IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON HOUSEHOLD MEMBERS' HEALTH AND OPINIONS ABOUT PUBLIC HEALTH MEASURES* [Remind respondents of the different stages of the pandemic if they do not address them naturally].

- a. HOW HAS THE ILLNESS AFFECTED THE MEMBERS OF YOUR HOUSEHOLD?
 - i. HAS THE PANDEMIC HAD ANY EFFECT ON THE MENTAL HEALTH OF MEMBERS OF YOUR HOUSEHOLD?
- b. HOW HAS THE DISEASE AFFECTED OTHER FAMILY MEMBERS, CLOSE FRIENDS, ETC.?
- c. DURING THE PANDEMIC HAVE YOU OR ANY OTHER HOUSEHOLD MEMBER NEEDED MEDICAL CARE FOR CAUSES OTHER THAN COVID-19?
- d. HAVE YOU BEEN VACCINATED AGAINST COVID-19? AND OTHER MEMBERS OF YOUR HOUSEHOLD? HOW DID YOU FEEL ABOUT THE VACCINATION?
- e. DO YOU THINK THE PANDEMIC HAS AFFECTED HEALTH SERVICES IN ANY WAY?
- f. IN YOUR HOUSEHOLD, DID YOU HAVE THE RESOURCES TO PAY FOR MASKS, ALCOHOL GELS, GLOVES, SURFACE DISINFECTION PRODUCTS, ETC.?
- g. TO WHAT EXTENT HAVE YOU AND MEMBERS OF YOUR HOUSEHOLD COMPLIED WITH PUBLIC HEALTH MEASURES (SOCIAL DISTANCE, HAND HYGIENE, USE OF MASKS, ETC.) ADOPTED BY THE GOVERNMENT?
- h. WHAT DIFFICULTIES HAVE YOU ENCOUNTERED IN COMPLYING WITH SUCH MEASURES?
- i. WHAT IS YOUR OPINION OF THESE MEASURES, DO YOU THINK THEY ARE ADEQUATE, SUFFICIENT, OR INSUFFICIENT TO PREVENT CONTAGION? WHY?
- j. WHAT HAS BEEN THE IMPACT ON YOU AND THE OTHER MEMBERS OF YOUR HOUSEHOLD OF THE LIMITATION OF THE RIGHT OF ASSEMBLY (VISITING RELATIVES, ATTENDING CEREMONIES, FUNERALS, ETC.)?
- k. WHAT WAS THE IMPACT OF THE CRISIS ON CULTURAL AND RELIGIOUS GATHERINGS THAT YOU USED TO ATTEND?
- l. DID YOU FEEL THAT THE RESTRICTIONS ON THESE GATHERINGS WERE PARTICULARLY TOUGH?
- m. HAVE YOU, ANY OTHER MEMBER OF YOUR HOUSEHOLD, OR RELATIVES BEEN SANCTIONED FOR BYPASSING CONFINEMENT, PERIMETER CLOSURES, NOT WEARING A MASK, ETC.?

- n. HAVE YOU EXPERIENCED AN INCREASE IN PREJUDICES AGAINST YOU? FROM WHOM? HOW? WAS IT CONNECTED TO BREAKING ANTI-COVID RULES?
 - o. HAVE YOU REPRIMANDED ANYONE FOR NOT COMPLYING WITH THE RULES?
5. *INFORMATION ON THE DISEASE AND THE MEASURES TAKEN BY THE AUTHORITIES.* [Remind respondents of the different stages of the pandemic if they do not address them naturally].
- a. TO WHAT EXTENT WAS THE ISSUE OF COVID-19 PRESENT IN YOUR DAILY CONVERSATIONS AT WORK, AT HOME, ETC.? [Remind respondents of the different stages of the pandemic if they do not address them naturally].
 - b. DID YOU FOLLOW GOVERNMENTAL INFORMATION DURING THE PANDEMIC?
 - i. DID YOU FIND IT TRUSTWORTHY?
 - ii. DID YOU FIND IT EASY TO COMPREHEND?
 - iii. CAN YOU THINK OF ANY MEASURE TO IMPROVE THEIR COMMUNICATION, PARTICULARLY TO MIGRANTS?
 - c. WHAT MEDIA DID YOU USE TO INFORM YOURSELF ABOUT THE EVOLUTION OF THE PANDEMIC? [Remind respondents of the different stages of the pandemic if they do not address them naturally].
 - i. IN YOUR OPINION, IS THE INFORMATION ABOUT THE PANDEMIC PUBLISHED IN THE MEDIA ACCURATE AND RELIABLE?
 - d. HOW OFTEN DID YOU CHECK DATA ON THE EVOLUTION OF THE DISEASE (CASES, HOSPITALISATIONS, DEATHS, ETC.)?
 - e. WHAT MEDIA DID YOU USE TO INFORM YOURSELF ABOUT THE MEASURES TAKEN BY THE AUTHORITIES?
 - i. IN YOUR OPINION, IS THE INFORMATION PROVIDED BY THE AUTHORITIES RIGOROUS, RELIABLE AND TRUHFUL?
 - f. HAVE YOU OR ANY OTHER MEMBER OF YOUR HOUSEHOLD RECEIVED FALSE, MISLEADING OR MALICIOUS INFORMATION ABOUT THE DISEASE, THE VACCINES ETC.? COULD YOU GIVE AN EXAMPLE?
6. *WE WOULD LIKE TO ASK ABOUT YOUR OPINION REGARDING THE END OF THE OBLIGATION TO CARRY FACEMASKS. DO YOU THINK IT WILL MAKE A DIFFERENCE IN YOUR LIFE? HAS IT MADE A DIFFERENCE SO FAR?*
7. *WE WOULD LIKE TO THANK YOU FOR YOUR ANSWERS SO FAR. THE INTERVIEW IS ALMOST OVER. FINALLY, OF ALL THE GOVERNMENT MEASURES THAT WERE TAKEN, WHICH ONES DO YOU THINK WORKED BEST?, WHICH ONES HELPED YOU THE MOST?, WHICH ONES CAUSED YOU PROBLEMS? WHICH MEASURES WOULD YOU HAVE DONE DIFFERENTLY?*

Questionnaire administered in the interviews with institutional actors.

This section includes the translated questionnaire administered in the interviews with institutional actors: from decision makers to practitioners and CSOs. This questionnaire is similar to the previous one insofar as it explores the same topics. The main difference is that it shifts the attention from the personal experience to how their organizational activity was affected by COVID19. The original questionnaire is in Spanish.

- 0. INTERVIEW ID NUMBER
- 1. *INTERVIEWEE DATA*
 - a. MALE/FEMALE
 - b. AGE
 - c. CORE TRAINING
 - d. YEARS OF EXPERIENCE AS A PUBLIC MANAGER IN THE CITY OF MADRID

- e. HAS EXPERIENCE/TRAINING IN CRISIS AND EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT
- f. POSITION HELD
 - o HAS HELD THE POSITION SINCE THE BEGINNING OF THE PANDEMY?

2. *DESCRIPTION OF ROLES, RESOURCES AND RELATIONSHIPS FOR PANDEMIC MANAGEMENT*

- a. MAIN FUNCTIONS OF ITS ORGANISATIONAL UNIT LINKED TO COVID CRISIS MANAGEMENT
- b. MAIN RESOURCES (HUMAN, TECHNICAL, ETC) THAT YOUR ORGANISATIONAL UNIT HAS MOBILISED TO DEAL WITH THE PANDEMIC
 - i.CURRENT RESOURCES
 - ii.EXTRAORDINARY RESOURCES
- c. WITH WHOM IT HAS HAD TO COORDINATE/COOPERATE, THROUGH WHICH FORMAL OR INFORMAL MECHANISMS AND FOR WHAT SPECIFIC PURPOSES?
 - i.WITHIN THE MUNICIPAL ADMINISTRATION
 - ii.WITH OTHER ADMINISTRATIVE LEVELS (OTHER CITIES, REGIONAL ADMINISTRATION, NATIONAL ADMINISTRATION, EUROPEAN INSTITUTIONS)
 - iii.WITH SOCIAL ACTORS, INTEREST GROUPS, ASSOCIATIONS, REPRESENTATIVES OF LOCAL COLLECTIVES, ETC.

3. *DECISION-MAKING PROCESS TO ADDRESS THE CORONAVIRUS CRISIS*

- a. DOES YOUR UNIT HAVE A SPECIFIC PLAN FOR DEALING WITH CRISES, DISASTERS AND EMERGENCIES?
- b. WHAT FORMAL MECHANISMS HAVE BEEN USED FOR DECISION-MAKING THROUGHOUT THE PANDEMIC (COMMITTEES, WORKING GROUPS, COORDINATION BODIES, ETC.)?
 - i.STANDARD MECHANISMS
 - ii.EXTRAORDINARY MECHANISMS
- c. HAVE FORMAL PLANS BEEN DEVELOPED IN YOUR UNIT TO DEAL WITH THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE PANDEMIC?
- d. IN YOUR UNIT, HAVE YOU HAD TO RESORT, IN AN EXTRAORDINARY WAY, TO EXPERTS, SPECIALISTS, TECHNICIANS FROM OTHER AREAS, LEVELS OF GOVERNMENT, RESEARCHERS, ETC., IN THE DECISION-MAKING PROCESS?
- e. TO WHAT EXTENT AND BY WHAT MEANS HAS THE PARTICIPATION OF CITIZENS, INTEREST GROUPS, VULNERABLE GROUPS, ETC., BEEN ORGANISED IN DECISION-MAKING TO ADDRESS THE PANDEMIC?

4. *MEASURES ADOPTED AND IMPLEMENTED BY ITS ADMINISTRATIVE UNIT*

- a. MEASURES FOR THE GENERAL POPULATION
- b. MEASURES FOR VULNERABLE GROUPS (PARTICULARLY AFFECTED BY THE SOCIAL, ECONOMIC AND HEALTH CONSEQUENCES OF THE PANDEMIC)
- c. ADAPTATION OF GENERAL MEASURES FOR VULNERABLE GROUPS
- d. SPECIFIC MEASURES/ADAPTATION OF GENERAL MEASURES FOR THE IMMIGRANT POPULATION

5. *COMMUNICATION WITH THE PUBLIC*

- a. WHAT CHANNELS OF COMMUNICATION WITH THE PUBLIC HAVE BEEN USED IN YOUR UNIT?
 - i.PRE-EXISTING CHANNELS,
 - ii.CHANNELS SPECIFICALLY DESIGNED TO ADDRESS COMMUNICATION DURING THE PANDEMIC
- b. HAVE SPECIFIC CHANNELS BEEN PUT IN PLACE TO COMMUNICATE WITH VULNERABLE GROUPS AND WITH THE IMMIGRANT POPULATION?

